

Comparative Nupoid and Ebiroid

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ABSTRACT

Current mainstream classification regards Nupoid as one of the coordinate arms of Benue-Congo, itself a branch of the Niger-Congo language phylum. The languages currently classified as Nupoid are Nupe, Gwari, Gade, and Ebiroid, which includes Ebira and related dialects. This classification is challenged in this study, which critically examines the relationship between Ebiroid (i.e. Ebira Okene, Ebira Kwotto and Etuno) and those languages that are indisputably Nupoid. The aim is therefore to determine whether Ebiroid falls within Nupoid or is an independent and coordinate arm of Benue-Congo.

A lexicostatistic study of the Nupoid languages and Ebiroid varieties was carried out. This entailed the elicitation of data, using a revised version of the Swadesh 100-wordlist and a comparison of lexical items and grammatical morphemes from the languages being compared. It also involves a counting of the lexical items that are cognate between languages. The figures derived from this exercise are converted into percentages of cognation between the languages in question. The higher the cognation percentage, the more related the languages are. However, this was only used to support the application of the comparative method, which remains the most reliable method for establishing genetic relationships and for sub-grouping within larger genetic units. The phonologies and morphologies of the languages help in the reconstruction of the phonology and lexicon of the parent language of the group in question.

Data used in this study were personally elicited from native speakers of the various languages. Only in the case of Gade were data collected from *A Gade-English dictionary*.

This work reveals that Ebiroid, though genetically related to Nupoid, should not be classified as Nupoid. This position is reflected in the cognation percentages recorded between Ebiroid and Nupoid as well as between these two and some other recognised Benue-Congo language groups. Nupoid and Ebiroid were not significantly more related to each other than either is to other Benue-Congo arms such as Edoid, Igboid, and Yoruboid. An examination of sound change and the reconstruction of lexical items not just in Ebiroid but also in Nupoid revealed certain innovations in sound and vocabulary in Ebiroid to the exclusion of Nupoid. This indicates that Ebiroid and Nupoid are different branches of Benue-Congo.

This work is a major contribution to the continuing search for the true internal genetic relationships within Niger-Congo and, especially, within Benue-Congo. It finds that there is a need to revise the internal classification of Benue-Congo. The study proposes a classification of Ebiroid coordinate with Nupoid and other arms within Benue-Congo, presents Proto-Ebiroid phonetics and phonology as well as the first in-depth comparative study of Nupoid. Most importantly, it also presents a reconstruction of Proto-Nupoid phonology and lexicon.

Keywords: Comparative Phonology, Language Classification, Nupoid, Ebiroid, Genetic relationship

Word Count: 445

Dedication

This work is dedicated to Almighty God
who makes all things possible in His own time.
It is also dedicated to my late Father and Father In-Law.

Acknowledgement

Like many of its kind, this work is the product of not very few years and not few minds. Of these people, many impacted more on the intellectual plane while others chose the spiritual as point of interface with me in this work. From both groups of persons, I got my fair share of encouragement, mentoring and support, technically and spiritually. It is with joy that I express my profound gratitude and send Gods blessings to them.

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by O. A. Bankale (Mrs.) in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

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Abbreviations

- PYIG = Proto Yoruba-Isekiri-Igala
- PE = Proto Edoid from Elugbe
- PI = Proto Ijo
- PLN = Proto-Lower Niger
- BCCW = Benue-Congo Comparative Wordlist
- PBC = Proto Benue-Congo
- PBK = Proto Benue-Kwa
- PB = Proto-Bantu
- PS = Proto Sudanic
- PWS = Proto West-Sudanic
- PWN = Proto West Nigritic
- PJ = Proto Jukunoid
- PCJ = Proto Central Jukunoid
- PYK = Proto Yukuben
- Nu = Nupe
- Gw. = Gwari
- Gd. = Gade
- Eb. = Epira
- Id. = Idoma
- (Ik) = Ikom
- Ei. = Eloyi
- Et. = Etulo
- Ar. = Arago
- Ige. = Igede
- Akw. = Akweya
- EdB. = Edo Bini
- Yor. = Yoruba
- Ig. = Igala
- Igb. = Igbo
- Ekp. = Ekpeye

Abbreviations of Authors names used in the study are listed below.

EL for Elugbe
Sh for Shimizu
DeW for De Wolf
Gt for Guthrie
West. for Westermann
Wil. for Williamson

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 THE LANGUAGES, THE SPEAKERS AND THEIR GEOGRAPHIC LOCATION

1.0.1 (The) Nupe

Nupe, also known as Yakpa or Ampeyi, is a Benue-Congo language spoken by a group of people who also call themselves Nupe. They live mainly around the rivers Niger and Kaduna in Kogi and Niger States of Nigeria. In Niger State, they specifically live in Gbako, Lavun, Agaie, Lapai and Mariga Local Government Areas (LGAs). In Kwara State, they live in Patigi LGA, and, in Kogi State, in Edu and Kogi LGAs. In Benue State, they are found in Bassa LGA. The Nupe language is a unifying force between the Nupe particularly because they are not all located in the same territory and they have developed slightly different cultures in their different locations. Moreover, they seem to share a common historical origin, centered on Tsoede, which also keeps them united (Forde 1955).

Tsoede was the grandson of an Igala ruler, the Attah Gara at Idah, whose son had traveled to the Nupe lands, hunting. There he met a widow, who happened to be the daughter of Nupe chief of Nku and by whom he had Tsoede. Tsoede became the first Nupe king, also known as Etsu Nupe. He had established himself at Ega along the Kaduna river on his way back from Idah having been sent there (Idah), as a slave by his mother's brother. The charm and ring he had on, signifying his connection to the throne earned him favour with the Attah. The charm and ring had been given him by his mother, being gifts from his father. He was sent back to Nupe land with riches and various insignia of kingship. He finally settled at Nku and delivered Nupe from Idah as a tributary.

The major dialects of Nupe are NupeTako (Bassa Nge), Dibo (Ganagana), Kakanda (Akanda, Hyabe), Kupa, and Nupe proper (Takpa, Anufe). Nupe proper extends East and West of Bida. The dialects studied here are Nupe proper, spoken in Lafiagi, and Nupe Tako, spoken further down the Niger around Lokoja. History has it that the Nupe Tako also known as the Bassa Nge, are of Nupe origins. They migrated from Nupe due to inter-tribal wars. They are a different race from the Bassa Nkomo also known simply as Bassa and who live around Mt. Pati in Lokoja. The Bassa Nge got their name from the district in which they lived, i.e. the then Kwara District within Kabba Division. In Lokoja both the Bassa Nkomo and the Bassa Nge live in the same area around Mt. Pati and so the mix up in the names and identity particularly that there was an amalgamation in 1918. The two groups are very distinct culturally and socially.

The Lafiagi dialect is chosen to represent Nupe spoken in the heart of Nupe land. The Lokoja dialect is chosen because it serves a dual purpose. The first is that it represents Nupe spoken away from the heartland (i.e. in the south) and, two, it is spoken near Ebara Land. This second purpose is meant to show that differences between Nupe of Lokoja and Ebara are still seen to exist in spite of geographic closeness.

Kawu Ndanusa, a 40-year-old native of Lafiagi and Abaaji James, a 30-year-old, are the informants for the two varieties respectively.

Languages that are geographically close to Nupe are Yoruba (to the West and Southwest), Ebara (to the South), Gwari (to the North and East), and Kambari (to the North and West). The Nupe speaking people are likely to be one million now since Crozier and Blench (1992) estimate the number of speakers as 800,000.

Several works on Nupe exist. They include Bible translations, Primers, Orthography, Dictionary (by A.W. Banfield 1914/16), Grammars (by Banfield and Macintyre (1915), Madugu (1975) and Kawu (1990) are post-graduate theses containing information on Nupe grammar.

1.0.2 (The) Gwari

Gwari is a language spoken by a group of people who live and are known in two distinct communities, the Western and the Eastern. The Western are known as Gwari Yamma while the Eastern are known as Gbagyi. The former, call themselves 'Gbari', while the latter call themselves 'Gbagye'. Other people call them Gwari which we shall adopt here as it is the more widespread and it applies to both groups. Gwari is spoken in about four States and the Federal Capital (FCT) of Nigeria. The States are Kaduna, Kogi, Nassarawa and Niger. The largest Gwari towns are Minna in Niger State, Kaduna in Kaduna State and Abuja in the FCT. Other major towns where Gwari is spoken are Kotangora and Bida in Niger State and Birnin-Gwari, Zaria and Kargako in Kaduna State.

The Western have their main centre in the Paiko-Bosso-Maikonkele sector while the Eastern have their main centre in the Kuta-Fuka sector, all in Niger State. These two communities are found intermingled with, and interspersed by other groups such as the Nupe, the Gade and Hausa speakers. In fact it is believed that most Dibo (a dialect of Nupe) speakers have largely become Gwari speakers.

The Gwari of both sections, i.e. the Eastern and the Western, understand each other, although with some difficulty. The Hausas call the Gbagyi, 'Gwari Matai' and 'Ngenge'. The LGAs where both Gwari Yamma and Gbagyi are mainly found in Niger

State are Chanchaga and Suleija. The Gbagyi are also situated in the Rafi and Shiroro LGAs of the State. Gwari is spoken in the Kachia LGA in Kaduna State; in Nassarawa and Keffi LGAs of Nassarawa State and in the FCT, while the Gwari Yamma are found in Agale and Lapai LGAs in Niger State. Despite the fact that the lexicon of the Gwari Yamma is distinguished from that of the Gbagyi they share cultural traits and a sense of affinity.

The origin of the Gwari is largely dependent on oral tradition. They are said to have come from Bornu during the twelfth century (12th C) Jihad led by the Fulani. The Gwari who claim to be Kanuri (Beri-Beri), were at that time scattered into the then Kano and Zaria provinces from where they moved into other places like today's FCT. Records show however that the Gwari occupied their present locations before the Fulani Jihad which broke up their settlements. They moved massively down south eastwards of the Chadic speaking peoples of the Northern parts of Nigeria breaking up areas occupied by the sub-Bantu inhabitants of the present day Hausa land, i.e. the real Bassa. The Gwari also share a long standing relationship with the Koro of Bornu and the Hausa traditions rank Gbari as one of the then seven non-Hausa States of the Nigerian Sudan. These groups the Hausa called "banza bakwai" and their ancient centres are unknown. Birnin Gwari was founded in 1800 AD by a Bornu Arab who settled first among the Gbari of Kuta. The Gbari are thought to have entered into Koton-Karfi and Nassarawa shortly after they entered Abuja in 1750 AD.

The Eastern Gwari data studied here were provided by Lance Corporal Adamu Jiwabbi, a 40 year-old native of Hulumi in the FCT Garki Municipal Area Council. My informant for Gwari Yamma is Awwal Mohammed, a native of Badeggi, Badeggi Local

Government Area Niger State

The neighbouring languages to Gwari are Hausa (to the North), Nupe (to the West), Epira (to the South), and Yoruba (to the Southwest).

The Gwari are mostly farmers and craftsmen. The women often carry heavy loads on their shoulders. The crops grown include millet, guinea corn, rice and groundnut. Their crafts include mat weaving, smithing and carpentry. The estimated population of the Gwari is 500,000 (Crozier and Blench 1992).

Fragments of the Bible as well as books have been written in Gwari.

1.0.3 (The) Gade

The speakers of Gade are located in the South East of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) in Kuje, Gaube, Kusaki, Kabi and Agwai villages. The Gade also live in Nassarawa in Nassarawa State. They are one people with the same customs.

According to oral tradition, two brothers came from Doma in the then Benue province on a hunting expedition to Southwest Nassarawa. Kafati, the elder brother, settled at Nassarawa while the younger, Kwakwara, moved to Abuja. There he killed a hairless buffalo at a place called Kuzazaje, later known as Kuje. The brothers are believed to have left Idoma about 1750 AD. The name Gade is said to be a word in their language which means a kind of rat which children catch and use as a cure for nose bleeding.

Not much work has been done in Gade. In 1977, Sterk wrote his Ph.D dissertation, *Elements of Gade Grammar and a Gade-English Dictionary*; and in 1978, a paper: 'The noun class system of Gade'.

The Gade are about 80,000 in number (Crozier and Blench 1992).

1.0.4 (The) Ebira

Ebira (Igbirra) is spoken mainly in Koton-Karfi, Adavi, Okehi, Ihima, Okene, Ageva and Ajaokuta LGAs of Kogi State, in Nassarawa LGA of Nassarawa State, and at Igarra in Akoko Edo LGA of Edo State. In Edo State, Ebira speakers who live in Igarra town call their language Etuno. They call themselves Anetuno. Ebira Kwotto is spoken in Koton-Karfi in Kogi State. My informant for the Okene dialect is Mr. Dauda Bello, 44 years old, and a native of Okene. I was also privileged to have access to Professor Ben Elugbe's Ebira Okene data. Mr. A. A. Moses, 52 years, supplied me the Etuno variety. He hails from Igarra, Akoko Edo LGA, in Edo State.

The neighbouring languages to Ebira are Yoruba (to the West), Nupe (to the North), Gwari and Gade (to the North East) and Ogori and Edoid languages (to the South).

The Ebira are mostly farmers and weavers. They often move in search of good soil for farming. The population of the Ebira is about 1,000,000 (Crozier and Blench 1992).

The study of Ebira has not been very extensive. There are Bible translations and some scholarly works such as: A descriptive Study of the Verbal Piece in Ebira, (Adiva 1984), Ebira Orthography (Adiva 1985) and Ladefoged's (1966) 'Igbirra notes and wordlist'. Elugbe (1983) also wrote a seminar paper 'Aspects of Ebira Phonology'

1.1 Previous Classifications

Koelle (1854) was the first to recognise the relationship between Nupe, Gwari, and Ebira (see Fig.1). He called them the 'Niger-Dshadda' Group although he himself had some doubts as to the accuracy of his data, based on the circumstances of his informants as freed slaves. Also, quite some time (close to two centuries) had passed between the time his informants left home and time of collecting data. Koelle wrote (1854: iv):

... we cannot hide from ourselves that Vocabularies of this description i.e. Vocabularies of languages with whose grammar one is not acquainted, and which are usually obtained from ill-informed natives, cannot lay claim to correctness in detail. I am convinced that this Polyglotta contains instances of incorrectness, and actual mistakes.

These languages have since been classified in various ways by different scholars through the use of different methods. Westermann and Bryan (1952) named them 'Nupe group' (see Fig.2). They went a step further than Koelle by presenting some grammatical features of some of the languages and a classification in which Igarra (i.e. Epira) was established as a Dialect Cluster within the group. Nupe and Gwari were also recognised as Dialect Clusters respectively. The dialects of each Unit as listed by Westermann and Bryan (1952: 85/86) are:

Nupe Group:

Nupe Dialect Cluster:

Nupe (Nupe proper)
Ebe (Abewa)
Dibo (called Ganagana by the Hausas)
Bassa-Nge (Ibara)
Kupa (Kupanchi)
Kakanda (called Shabe by the Igarra)

Gbari Dialect Cluster

Gbari (i.e. Gwari) Gyenguen (Matai)
Gbari Yamma of Paiko gan gan)
Gbari Yamma Gayegi
Gbari Kwange)

Igbira Dialect Cluster

Igbira-Panda (also known as Kwotto)
Igbira-Hima (also known as Okene Igbira)
Igbira-Igu (Egu, Ika)

They were known to be quite close to each other in their various cluster units. Gade was not classified until Greenberg (1963) included it in his Kwa, group d: Nupe

Gwari, Gade and Ebira (see Fig.3). Greenberg's 1963 work, although widely accepted as the 'prevailing orthodoxy in the area of African language classification' (Bendor Samuel 1989), has undergone re-examination and modification. He used the mass comparison method, quite different from the old method of classifying languages by types or races used by earlier scholars. He compared several languages and was able to classify them using only linguistic features.

In 1976, Hoffmann excluded Ebira from the Nupe Group. He renamed the Nupe Group Niger-Kaduna (see Fig.4). In 1977, Bennett and Sterk presented a revision of Greenberg's Niger-Congo. They came up with a branching which included what they called Eastern South Central Niger-Congo (ESCNC). This branch included Nupe, Gwari, Gade and Ebira, all subsumed under Niger-Kaduna. This was thus a reversal of Hoffmann's (1976) classification, which excluded Ebira from the Nupe group.

Bennett and Sterk's classification was based on a computer-aided lexicostatistical study and lexical innovation. Their cognate percentage figures reflect Nupe and Gwari as being more closely related to each other than either of them is to Ebira or Gade and this may have influenced their view expressed in the tree diagram (see Fig. 5). Their Niger-Kaduna has an initial three-way split:

- I. Gade
- II. Nupe-Gwari
- III. Igbiroid

The subdivisions of their Nupe-Gwari are Nupoid (i.e. Nupe) and Gwaroid (i.e. Gwari, Ganagana and Kakanda). Their Igbiroid (which I call Ebiroid to avoid confusion) comprises Igbirra, Igarra and Koto. The tree diagram presented by Bennett and Sterk (see Fig. 5) does not reflect the cognate percentages between Ebiroid and other languages outside Niger-Kaduna. It also does not show the correct relationship between

Ebiroid and Gade. Bennett and Sterk's (1977) figures between Ebiroid and other languages apart from those grouped as Niger-Kaduna are presented in this study. For instance, I present their figures between Ebiroid and Idoma as well as Yoruba for easy demonstration of the degree of closeness i) between Ebiroid and the languages classified as Niger-Kaduna by Bennett Sterk (1977) i.e. Gade, Nupe and Gwari, and ii) between Ebiroid and some other branches of Benue-Congo (Williamson 1989) e.g. Igala, Igbo, Degema etc. (see Chapter seven).

Methods applied in this work are the Comparative Method and Lexicostatistics.

The Comparative method according to Campbell (1998:112) is

a method (or set of procedures) which compares forms from related languages, *cognates*, which have descended from a common ancestral language (*the proto-language*), in order to postulate, that is *to reconstruct*, the form in the ancestral language.

This method is known to establish genetic relationship among languages. The languages in a family develop from the same parent i.e. proto-language. The descendants of a proto-language develop as a result of linguistic changes although sometimes the original features of the parent are retained in them.

Reconstruction which is basic to the comparative method involves a recovery of the parent language through a comparison of the daughter languages to determine the inherited features. The features are then used in reconstructing the linguistic traits of the parent language. A phonological study of the languages precedes reconstruction so as to get the sound system.

The steps applied in the reconstructions here after presenting a phonological studies, are

1. assemble the potential cognates particularly the basic vocabulary items, which resist borrowing more than other words in the lexicon. (see Volume 2)
2. establish sound correspondences (see chapters 5 and 6)
3. reconstruct the parent language by applying certain linguistic guidelines such as
 - a. *directionality* of certain sound changes (having considered the phonetic motivation for such a change
 - b. *majority wins* i.e. the sound which shows up more in the correspondences is chosen as the proto-sound. This is hinged on the provision of explanations for the development of other corresponding sounds from it.
 - c. *features held in common are factored in* where no sound meets guideline b. and the reconstructed sound is as close as possible to the phonetic form.
 - d. *economy* i.e. a sound that required the least number of independent changes of a set of alternatives is the one chosen as parent sound (see chapters 5 and 6).
4. check the plausibility of the reconstructed sound from perspective of the overall phonological inventory of the proto-language (see chapters 5 and 6).

The basic assumptions of the comparative method which are actually observable after reconstruction are that

1. the proto-language has no dialects or social variants
2. language splits are sudden
3. there is no subsequent contact among the related languages after the split-up
4. sound change is regular.

The weaknesses of the method are that in reality no language exists without variants and secondly since only material in the related languages is addressed, the method cannot deal with borrowings given assumptions 2 and 3. There is usually contact among languages and splits may not always be sudden. There may be intermediate stages in splits. The linguist is thus saddled with the responsibility of factoring in the possible intermediate stages in the development of the sounds. Basically the method serves the purpose of recovering the parent language which goes a long way in establishing genetic relationship and subgrouping of the larger language units.

Lexicostatistics the other method applied in this study assumes a basic or core vocabulary which is relatively culture-free and which is less susceptible to change as other kinds of vocabulary (see appendix 1 for Swadesh 100 basic vocabulary used in this study). The second assumption is that the rate of retention of the basic vocabulary is constant through time and as such about 81 percent of the vocabulary will be retained over a millennium. The third assumption is that the rate of loss of is also constant, about 14 percent will be lost over a millennium. With this in mind the cognation count will surely give information about subgrouping of related languages.

The method has been criticised in that there can be no absolutely culture free basic vocabulary since some items are actually borrowed for cultural reasons in some languages. For example Campbell (1998:180) cited the case of 'dog' in Pipil (Uto-Aztec). The native term was replaced by the borrowed term from Spanish.

Secondly, there is usually no one-to-one matching between the word-list and a word of each language. E.g. 'I' has several forms in different languages based on the social

status and degree of intimacy. Other languages have no equivalent for the item on the list such that the same item may represent two items on the list. Furthermore a language may have more than one equivalent per item on the list e.g. 'bathe' may mean 'to wash with soap' or 'swim'. Finally, it has been noted that some items tend to be replaced faster than others for cultural reasons e.g. taboo.

The method is however known for providing a fast and easy means for determining subgrouping or internal classification of a language family. It serves as a useful starting point in the classification of languages before the discovery of innovations, which help distinguish different units within language families.

Below are tree diagrams showing classification of Ebiroid by earlier writers.

Fig. 1
Koelle (1854)

Fig. 2
Westermann and Bryan (1952)

Fig. 3
Greenberg (1963)

Fig. 4
Hoffman (1976)

Fig. 5
Bennett and Sterk (1977)

Fig. 6
Williamson (1989)

Fig. 7
Blench (1989)
(slightly reduced here)

Internal Relations of the Nupoid Languages

LANGUAGE MAP OF NUPOID AND EBIROID

GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF NUPOID AND EBIROID SPEAKERS

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 PHONETICS

2.0.1 Introduction

This chapter contains mainly a description of the sounds employed in the different phonological systems within Nupoid and Ebiroid. I present the general articulatory features. Investigation was mainly auditory and so only a general phonetic outline of the sounds is presented.

2.1 Consonants

Consonants are sounds whose articulation involves blockage or near-obstruction of the airstream in the oral cavity. The degree of obstruction differs depending on the classes of sound. Twenty-nine (29) different consonant sounds are attested in Nupoid while twenty-four (24) are found in Ebiroid. The sounds fall into the following classes: Stop, Fricative and Approximant. In both Nupoid and Ebiroid, all the classes have representatives. Four sub-groups are identified under the Stop class: Nasal, Plosive, Implosive and Affricate. Of these, only implosives are not found in Ebiroid. The phonological status of the various sounds in Nupoid and Ebiroid is discussed in Chapters Three and Four respectively.

2.1.1 Stop

Stops are speech sounds whose airstream meets with total obstruction in the oral cavity during their production. Stop articulation involves three phases and oral closure is maintained during the medial phase. The initial phase is the coming together of the articulators while the last phase is the release phase, i.e. separation of the articulators.

2.1.1.1 Nasals

Nasals are produced with total oral closure and the airstream escapes through the nose as a result of velic opening. The airstream is basically pulmonic egressive.

Seven nasals are recorded in Nupoid. They are [m n nh ɲ ɲ* ɲ̃m] i.e. the bilabial, labiodental, alveolar, lenis alveolar palatal, velar, labialised velar and the labial-velar nasal respectively. Of the nasals, only [ɲ̃m] is doubly articulated and it is found only in Gwari between a labial-velar plosive and nasalised vowel.

[n] and [nh] represent a fortis/lenis distinction observed synchronically only in Nupoid and as expected in the production of lenis sounds, articulation of [nh] is not as strong as of the other nasals (see section 2.3).

In Nupoid [nh] is found only in Gwari Yamma and once. Its occurrence is restricted to - C²- position: [gbānhī] 'jaw'. Apart from [ɲ̃m] and [nh], nasals occur freely in Nupoid. No restriction is placed on their distribution in a word. In Gwari Yamma the articulation of [nh] and [r] are almost identical due to the shortness of duration of both articulations. Elugbe's (1989:66) description of the production of the alveolar (central) approximant fits that of [r] here and I quote,

... a token movement of the tip of the tongue towards the teeth ridge...

The articulation of [nh] also involves a short duration. Clements (2000) calls the lenis sounds 'extra-short (tapped) sounds'.

There is an overlap between [l] [n] and [r]. [n] is an allophone of // before nasalised vowels and [l] and [r] are used alternatively in certain environments in Gwari (see section 3.3.1.1). Neither [nh] nor [ɲ̃m] is attested in Ebiroid. Only [m,n,ɲ,ɲ*] and labialised velar [ɲ*] are found in Ebiroid.

2.1.1.2 Plosive

Plosives in Nupoid and Ebiroid fall neatly into four voiceless/voiced pairs: p:b, t:d, k:g and kp:gb. They are bilabial, alveolar, velar and labial-velar respectively. A voiced labial-velar plosive whose production involves suction is observed in Gwari. Hyman and Magaji (1970) had earlier noted a slight implosion with [kp] and [gb] in Gwari. We explain the articulation along Ladefoged's (1964) position that in a number of Nigerian languages, the velaric airstream is used in conjunction with the pulmonic egressive in the production of certain labial-velar plosives. In Ebiroid the labial-velar plosives are produced on the pulmonic egressive airstream.

Examples: Gwari

1. [gbwagmà] 'arm'
[gbwato] 'touch with hand'
[lágbují] 'louse'

Plosives in Nupoid and Ebiroid have palatalised or labialised counterparts depending on the nature of the following vowel. Where the vowel is front particularly [i] or [ɪ], the plosive is palatalised. It is labialised where the adjacent vowel is back, particularly [u] or [ʊ].

2.1.1.3 Implosive

The only implosive found in Nupoid is the voiced bilabial implosive [ɓ] in Gwari and Gwari Yamma. It is produced on the glottalic ingressive plus pulmonic ingressive airstreams. No voiceless counterpart is attested in Nupoid. Also no implosive is attested in Ebiroid.

2.1.1.4 Affricate

Two pairs of voiceless/voiced affricates are found in Nupoid. The voiceless are

[ts], a voiceless alveolar affricate and [tʃ], a voiceless palato-alveolar affricate. The voiced are [dz], a voiced palatal affricate and [dʒ], a voiced palato-alveolar affricate. They are single consonant sounds and the manner of air release is fricative, i.e. with hissing noise. In Ebiroid, only the palato-alveolar affricates [tʃ] and [dʒ] occur.

2.1.2 Fricative

Six fricatives produced on the pulmonic egressive airstream are attested in Nupoid and Ebiroid respectively. They make up three sets of voiceless/voiced pairs. They are produced at the labiodental, alveolar, palato-alveolar and glottal places of articulation:

f:v	labiodental
s:z	alveolar
ʃ:ʒ	palato-alveolar
-:h	glottal

The glottal fricative, [h] seldom occurs in Nupoid. As in Nupoid, all listed fricative sounds are attested in Ebiroid. The fricative inventory varies in Ebiroid i.e. not all the fricatives are attested in each Ebiroid language. In Nupoid the alveolar fricatives are often realised as their palato-alveolar counterparts due to palatalisation.

2.1.3 Approximants

Four approximants: [r | j] and [w] produced on the pulmonic egressive airstream are attested in both Nupoid and Ebiroid. They are alveolar, palatal and labial-velar respectively. [r] and [nh] in Gwari and Gwari Yamma sound much alike before significantly nasalised [i] (see 2.1.1.1).

2.2 CN sequences / Nasal Release

Nasal release of plosives is observed in Nupoid, precisely in Gwari and Gwari Yamma. They are transcribed as CN sequences but are interpreted as phonetically

single but complex consonant sounds having both oral and nasal features. The "oral closure for the first stop is maintained through the closure phase of the second" such that only a lowering of the velum allows the compressed air to escape. Oral closure for the two stops is achieved once. They are not instances of a consonant cluster. The consonant is an oral stop-plus-nasal functioning as a single consonant with complex nasal plosion. CN sequences were also noticed by Hyman and Magaji (1970). Examples of CN sequences cited from Hyman and Magaji (1970:14) are presented in 2. below.

Hyman and Magaji (1970: 14)

- | | | |
|----|-------------------|-------------------|
| 2. | p ^m i | 'to wait for' |
| | b ^m a | 'to break' |
| | ot ⁿ a | 'last, next year' |
| | k ⁿ i | 'to select' |

This study agrees with Hyman and Magaji (1970) that only plosives are attested in the CN sequences. Example 3 shows nasal release in Nupoid. My transcription differs from that of Hyman and Magaji presented in example 2. in that I give equal prominence to the two parts i.e. CN as against their Cⁿ which suggests partial rather than complete nasal plosion.

3. Gwari

- | | | | | | | |
|----|---|----|---|---|----|----------|
| a. | V | C | V | C | V | |
| | a | kŋ | ɪ | | | 'ground' |
| | | tn | | ū | tn | ū |
| | | | | | | 'work' |

b. Gwari Yamma

- | | | | | | | |
|--|---|----|---|----|---|---------|
| | V | C | V | C | V | |
| | | tn | ū | bw | à | 'ear' |
| | e | gŋ | ɪ | | | 'thigh' |

c.

Gwari CVCV		Gwari-Yamma CVCV	Gloss
[nàkpɔ̃mí]	'leopard'	[ɛkɔ̃í]	'needle'
[kɔ̃í]	'to choose'	[okɔ̃á]	'thorn'
[kɔ̃á]	'to fry'	[kɔ̃á]	'to fry'
[ńtní]	'five'	[ɔ̃dná]	'river'
[gɔ̃pí]	'mortar'	[gɔ̃pí]	'mortar'

Example 3. shows that nasal release is usually homorganic with the preceding plosive. The only seeming exceptions are [gbadma] 'banana' and [wagmà] 'arm' where the release is not homorganic with the place of articulation of the preceding plosive. These are considered indicators of a *CVNV sequence developing into CNV through loss of the first vowel (see section 5.2.2). The nasal plosion is homorganic where nasality spreads from the N to the preceding consonant.

In Ebiroid the situation is different. There are no nasally released consonants and nasals are usually phonemic.

2.3 Lenis/Fortis

Lenis sounds are those whose production is of a weak articulation. The phonetic correlates of lenisness are

- i) reduction in duration of articulation as noted by Hombert and Elugbe (1975) working on Ghotuo: [m]:[mh], [n]:[nh] and [l]:[lh]. The lenis sound is indicated by addition of symbol [h] to the main symbol. This does not mean we are dealing with two sounds rather one e.g. [n], fortis alveolar nasal plosive: [nh], lenis alveolar nasal plosive.

- ii) the degree of muscular tension from a neutral specification of moderate degree of muscular tension suggested by Laver (1994:416/7). This results in less articulatory effort, less sub-glottal pressure as well as shortness in the duration of articulation.

Fortis sounds on the other hand are those whose articulations are strong or better still the opposite of lenisness. Synchronic evidence of these features is observed in Nupoid in the alveolar nasal plosives.

2.4 Vowels

Vowels are speech sounds having little or no obstruction in the oral cavity. They are produced on the pulmonic egressive airstream in Nupoid and Ebiroid. They are differentiated basically in terms of tongue height, backness in the mouth and roundedness of the lips.

Ten vowels are attested in Nupoid and in Ebiroid. They are [i e ε ə a ɔ o u]. Basically four levels of tongue height are observed in all (see 4. below). Vowels [i] and [u] are higher than [e] and [o]. All the back vowels are more rounded than the front. They are nasalised in the environment of nasal consonants although they sometimes occur significantly nasalised. Unlike in Nupoid where all the ten vowels are distinguished in one language: Gade, the highest number of vowels distinguished by any language in Ebiroid is nine. In all, the least number of vowels distinguished is seven as in Nupe. A nine vowel system usually has [i e ε ə a ɔ o u u] with [ə] and [a] occurring as alternates in the vowel harmony systems, e.g. in Gwari and Gwari Yamma. A seven vowel system has [i e ε ə ɔ o u] which may manifest five phonetically as in Nupe and Nupe Tako. The five vowels are [i e ə o u]. [ε] and [ə] merge with [a]

phonetically.

4. Vowel Inventory

i u
i u
e o
ɛ ɔ
 ɔ
 a

2.5 Vowel Harmony

The vowels are placed in subsets determined on the basis of Advanced Tongue Root, a phonetic feature characterising an expanded 'front-to-back' diameter of the pharynx'.

The vowel sets are

+ATR		-ATR	
i	u	i	u
e	o	ɛ	ɔ
ə		a	

In cases where [ə] is not attested, [a] is usually neutral to both sets and this means that it can co-occur with vowels of both sets.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 PHONOLOGIES OF NUPOID LANGUAGES

3.0.1 Introduction

The major phonological systems of Nupoid Languages are presented in the following sections. Nupe phonology is presented first being the language after which the term Nupoid is coined with the suffix -oid.

Nupe Tako (Bassa Nge) phonology is presented next being the closest to Nupe proper genetically. After Nupe Tako, I present Gwari followed by Gwari Yamma and finally Gade, the most distant from Nupe proper within the group. The phonologies of the Ebiroid languages are presented in the next chapter because they are considered different from Nupoid.

The descriptive method is employed in the phonological analysis of the languages. Suspicious pairs of sound are examined and those in complementary distribution are assigned to the same phoneme. Examples showing the environment where each allophone is found are also presented. Apart from allophones of differing phonetic shape with the phonemes, there are those of similar phonetic shape with the phonemes in environments different from those specified for allophones of differing phonetic shape.

3.1 NUPE

3.1.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic Consonant Inventory

m	n	ɲ	ŋ				
p b	t d		k g	kp	gb		
	ts dz						
f v	s z					h	
	r						
	l	j			w		

3.1.1.1 Notes on consonants

As mentioned in Chapter Two, the consonant sounds of Nupoid fall into three classes: Stop, Fricative and Approximant. Nupe has nasals, plosives, affricates in the stop class. Example 1. shows that fricatives and approximants also exist in Nupe. The allophones of the consonant phonemes are presented in sections 3.1.1.1.1- 3.1.1.1.5 where phonological processes observed in Nupe are discussed.

3.1.1.1.1 Palatalisation

Stops and fricatives are palatalised before close and close mid front vowels. The process may involve change of sound class as in /ts/, /dz/, /s/ and /z/ developing allophones [tʃ], [dʒ], [ʃ] and [ʒ] respectively or it may simply involve secondary articulation whereby C becomes [C^ɹ]. As indicated in 3.1.1.1 the phonemes have non-palatalised allophones elsewhere.

(2)	/et̩/	[et ^ɹ]	'head'			
	/ge/	[g ^ɹ e]	'be good'			
	/ts̩gb̩/	[tʃɪgb̩]	'tree'	cf. /tsu/	[tsu]	'die'
	/dzika/	[dʒika]	'bag'	cf. /dzukó/	[dzuk ^w ó]	'market'
	/se/	[ʃe]	'be full'	cf. /só/	[só]	'bury'
	/ezi/	[eʒi]	'town'	cf. /ezà/	[ezà]	'person'

3.1.1.1.2 Labialisation

Labialisation occurs before close/close mid back rounded vowels in Nupe as in example 3, i.e. C becomes [C^w]. The process is not phonemic and so does not affect the word meaning. The phonemes have non-labialised allophones elsewhere.

(3)	/guru/	[g ^w uru]	'horn'			
	/egò/	[eg ^w ó]	'grass'	cf. /ega/	[ega]	'guest (stranger)'

/kù/	[k ^w ù]	'sell'	cf. /kā/	[kā]	'fry'
/jèkò/	[jèk ^w ò]	'cold'			
/édo/	[éd ^w o]	'mud'	cf. /edá/	[edá]	'shoe'
/ètò/	[èt ^w ò]	'bush'			
/tū/	[t ^w ū]	'vomit'	cf. /aràta/	[aràta]	'fifty'
/tsu/	[ts ^w u]	'die'			
/etsɔ/	[ets ^w a]	'moon'	cf. /tsábi/	[tsábi]	'defecate'

3.1.1.1.3 Nasalisation

Significantly nasalised vowels are found in Nupe and they initiate nasalisation of /l/, /j/ and /w/ to produce [ɺ] [ɺ̃] [ɺ̃^w] respectively. Elsewhere /l/, /j/ and /w/ are [l], [j] and [w] respectively.

(4)	/lù/	[ɺù]	'hoe (v.)'	cf. /lu/	[lu]	'weave (cloth)'
	/jīmi/	[jīmī]	'wife'	cf. /ji/	[ji]	'steal'
	/lūwā/	[ɺūwā]	'water'	cf. /wu/	[wu]	'beat (person)'
	/èmi/	[èmī]	'compound'			

3.1.1.1.4 Nasal Release

There are no instances of nasal release in Nupe proper.

3.1.1.1.5 Glide Formation

Glide formation is not observed in Nupe proper since vowel clusters are not observed.

3.1.2 Vowels

/i e ɛ a ɔ o u/ (oral) and /ĩ ǎ ũ/ (nasalised) are the Nupe proper vowels. The oral vowels are realised as five: [i e a o u]. The contrast between /ɛ l, lɔ/ and /a/ is neutralised and they are realised as [a]. (Hyman (1970) refers to this process as Absolute Neutralisation i.e. AN). Example (6) demonstrates the presence of /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ in Nupe (cf. example (5)).

(5)	(Hyman 1970)	
	Yoruba	Nupe Proper

kèkè	'bicycle'	k'ák'á	/C _ɛ C _ɛ /
kóbò	'penny'	k ^w áb ^w à	/C _ɔ C _ɔ /
tɔɛ	'to give a gift'	t ^w ar'á	/C _ɔ C _ɛ /

(6)	Nupe Tako		Nupe proper
	/azɛ/ [aʒɛ̃]	'blood'	/egè/ [eg'jà]
	/agɔ/ [ag ^w ɔ]	'hand'	/egɔ/ [eg ^w a]
	/etsɔ/ [etsɔ]	'moon'	/etsɔ/ [ets ^w a]

The analysis is further supported by the fact that only close / close mid front unrounded vowels cause palatalisation and only close / close mid back rounded vowels cause labialisation of preceding consonants in Nupe Proper. Words with nasalised vowels are in example (7).

(7)	/ègū/	'buttocks'	/ekā/	'thorn'
	/dukū/	'water pot'	/ekī/	'needle'
	/esā/	'salts'	/fī/	'drink'

(8) **Phonemic Vowel Inventory**

oral		nasalised	
i	u	ī	ū
e	o		
ɛ	ɔ		
	a		ā

3.1.3 Syllable Structure

In Nupe proper, (C)V(C) is the phonetic syllable structure. The C can only be a consonant which may be palatalised or labialised depending on the nature of the following vowel (see 3.1.1.1.1 and 3.1.1.1.2).

The V, is either a vowel (oral or nasalised) or a syllabic nasal: m̩, n̩ and ŋ̩. A homorganic nasal surfaces between a significantly nasalised vowel and a consonant within the word to derive (C)V̄N̄CV where the N is actually a nasal consonant i.e. CV̄CCV.

The different forms of (C) V (C) in Nupe proper are presented in example no. (9).

(9) a.	VCV	VCV		
	/ejé/	[ejé]		'eye'
	/emí/	[emí]		'oil'
	/ñlǎ/	[ñnǎ]		'mother'
b.	CVCV	CVCV		
	/tukpa/	[tukpa]		'ear'
	/kpomi/	[kpomí]		'okro'
c.	CVCV(CV)	CVCCV(CV)		
	/lāgi/	[nāng ^ɔ i]		'goat'
	/gbǎfèrè/	[gbǎmfèrè]		'hamarttan'
	/kīgbàgbà/	[kīŋmgbàgbà]		'sheep'
d.	V-CV	V-C^ɪV	V-C^ɪV	
	/e-gè/	e-g ^ɪ ε	[e-g ^ɪ à]	'blood'
		Palatalisation	AN	
	/egi/	eg ^ɪ i	[e-g ^ɪ i]	'child'
	/ege/	e-g ^ɪ e	[e-g ^ɪ e]	'wine'
		Palatalisation		
e.	V-CV	V-C^wV	V-C^wV	
	/egɔ/	e-g ^w ɔ	[eg ^w a]	'hand'
	/etsɔ/	e-ts ^w ɔ	[ets ^w a]	'moon'
		Labialisation	AN	
	/ego/	e-g ^w o	[eg ^w o]	'grass'
	/kú/	k ^w ú	[k ^w ú]	'sell'
	Labialisation			

3.1.4 Vowel Harmony

The fact that only five oral vowels are realised phonetically automatically rules out the presence of vowel harmony in Nupe proper. Phonemically the language has seven vowels five of which are [+ATR] and three of which are

[-ATR]: /ɛ/, /ɔ/ and [a]. Vowels /ɛ/ and /ɔ/ are showed to have merged with /a/ since the

contrast between them is neutralised at the phonetic level. Properly the prefixes of such words should have been [-ATR]. What one observes is that such words have either e- or i- as prefix i.e. [+ATR] vowels. It follows then that the underlying [-ATR] prefixes of such words have merged with these two [+ATR] vowels. (In section 3.1.5 it is noted that only [e] and [i] occur as noun prefixes in Nupe proper.) Some cognate Yoruba items are cited in (10) to support the fact that there have been vowel mergers.

(10)	Nupe proper		Yoruba
	eg ^l ε [eg ^l à]	'blood'	[èdʒè]
	eg ^w ɔ [eg ^w a]	'hand'	[ɔwó]

Yoruba stem vowel /ε/ has prefix /ε/ with the same tongue root, but Nupe proper stem vowel /ε/ has prefix /e/ with a different tongue root.

3.1.5 Morphology

Words in Nupe proper may be monosyllabic, disyllabic or even trisyllabic. The stems often have a CV structure with prefix vowels. Verbs are basically of the CV(CV) structure. Nasals sometimes occur as prefixes and where the prefix vowel is significantly nasalised, a homorganic nasal is inserted between the prefix and the following consonant (see section 3.1.3). It is instructive to note that only e- and i- occur as noun prefixes and that there are many more occurrences of e- than of i- yet they are not inflected to show pluralisation nor do they indicate noun classes. Plurals are formed in Nupe proper through suffixation of -ʒi to the noun. The fact that the prefix is often e- suggests that the prefix has a specific shape; the only instances of i- observed are presented in (11) a. (11) b shows syllabic nasals as np.

(11)	a.	/i-kā/	[i-kā]	'tooth'
		/i-kā/	[i-kā]	'fish'
		/i-gídi/	[i-gídi]	'sun'

b.	/ñ-dátjé/	[ñ-dátjé]	'hunter'
	/ñ-dǎ/	[ñ-ɖa]	'father'
	/ñ-nǎ/	[ñ-nǎ]	'mother'
c.	/egi/	[eg ^h i]	'child'
	/egizi/	[eg ^h iʒi]	'children'
	/eti/	[et ^h i]	'head'
	/etizi/	[et ^h iʒi]	'heads'

3.1.6 Tone

Three tonemes are attested in Nupe proper. They are high / ˀ / = [ˀ], mid / ˁ / = [ˁ] and low / ˁ̄ / = [ˁ̄]. Each has an allotone: high [ˀ̄], mid [ˁ̄] and low [ˁ̄̄], respectively. Other tones observed in Nupe are the low rising [ˁ̄̄̄] and the high falling tone [ˀ̄̄̄]. The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

(12)	/gírá/	'hawk'
	/ewa/	'snake'
	/kàsà/	'crocodile'
	/efú /	'bee'
	/ezà/	'person'
	/díní/	'housefly'
	/gùlu/	'vulture'
	/tsígbà/	'tree'
	/kána/	'monkey'
	/ñnǎ/	'mother'
	/ñdǎ/	'father'
	/nímâ/	'mother's brother'
	/yéle/	'in-law'

3.2 Nupe Tako (Bassa Nge)

3.2.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic consonant inventory

m n ŋ
 p b t d k g kp gb
 ts dz
 f v s z
 r
 l j w

3.2.1.1 Notes on Consonants

The consonant inventory shows that Nupe Tako like Nupe proper has nasals, plosives, affricates, fricatives and approximants. Allophones of phonemes are presented in sections 3.2.1.1.1- 3.2.1.1.5. Apart from such allophones each consonant phoneme has an allophone of the same phonetic shape as itself elsewhere.

3.2.1.1.1 Palatalisation

[j] and [ʒ] are allophones of /s/ and /z/ respectively and [tʃ] and [dʒ] are allophones of /k/ and /g/ respectively before close front vowels through palatalisation. One observes a change of place of articulation from alveolar and velar to palatal in the development of the allophones.

(2)	/si/	[ʃi]	'buy'
	/rɪzɪja/	[rɪʒɪja]	'well'
	/azɛ/	[aʒɛ]	'blood'
	/àki/	[àtʃi]	'needle'
	/bàgi/	[bàdʒi]	'man'

3.2.1.1.2 Labialisation

Consonants are labialised before close and close mid back rounded vowels. The process is not observed with fricatives and approximants. It is observed more with the velar plosives.

(3)	/kú/	[kʷú]	'sell'
	/ígù/	[ígʷù]	'mud'

/zikò/	[ʒik ^w ò]	'black'
/àtù/	[àt ^w ù]	'hat/cap'
/èdù/	[èd ^w ù]	'sea'
/etsu/	[ets ^w u]	'chief'

3.2.1.1.3 Nasalisation

Consonants are nasalised before phonemically nasalised vowels thereby /l/ is [ɺ], /j/ is [j̃] and /w/ is [w̃].

(4) /lù/	[ɺù]	'extinguish'
/jì/	[j̃ìkɔ]	'fish'
/lùwɔ̃/	[ɺùw̃ɔ̃]	'water'
/gòmáɔ̃/	[gòmáɔ̃]	'lies'
/wù/	[w̃ù]	'swell (of boil)'

3.2.1.1.4 Nasal Release

Nasal release is not observed in Nupe Tako.

3.2.1.1.5 Glide Formation

Glide formation is not observed in Nupe proper since vowel clusters are not observed.

3.2.2 Vowels

Nupe Tako has both oral and nasalised vowels. The oral are /i e ε a ɔ o u/ and the nasalised are /ĩ ē ā ɔ̃ õ ũ/. Only /ē/ is not attested and [ē] and [õ] each occur only once in my data. They occur in the words 'dry season' and 'charcoal' respectively. Some Nupe Tako words with significantly nasalised vowels are in (5).

(5) /aĩ/	[aĩ]	'hair'
/ēkéré/	[ēkéré]	'dry season'
/āgbá/	[āŋmgbá]	'jaw'
/aɔ̃/	[aɔ̃]	'goat'
/zòkara/	[zòŋkara]	'charcoal'

/tʊ / [tʊ] 'work'

(6) **Phonemic Vowel Inventory**

oral		nasalised	
i	u	ĩ	ũ
e	o	ẽ	õ
ɛ	ɔ		õ̃
	a		ã

The fact that [ẽ] is unattested in Nupe Tako suggests that the contrast between /e/ and /a/ was neutralised before nasalisation.

3.2.3 Syllable Structure

The syllable structure of Nupe Tako is (C)V(C). The V is a vowel (oral or nasalised) or syllabic nasal and the C, a consonant. The C is labialised: [C^w] before close back rounded vowel. Example 7 shows the possible combinations of the syllable structure. As observed in Nupe proper, (see section 3.2.3), a homorganic nasal is realised between a significantly nasalised vowel and a following non-nasal consonant thus creating a (C)ṼCCV pattern

(7) a. /{(V)CV(C(V))}(C)/ [VCV(V)(C)]

/ipà/	[ipà]	'skin'
/kíngl/	[tʃíndʒi]	'small'
/kám̃/	[kám̃]	'farm'
/àkpɔ̃m/	[àkpɔ̃m]	'okro'
/gɔ̃mgɔ̃m/	[gɔ̃mgɔ̃m]	'wall of house'
/tsam/	[tsam]	'greet (salute)'

b. /CVCV(C)/ [CV CV(C)]

/lèkim̃/	[lètʃim̃]	'fall'
/jàzè/	[jàzè]	'reply'
/bitsi/	[bitsi]	'run'

c.	<i>/(CV)(C)V̄(C)CV(CV)/</i>	<i>[CV̄CCV(CV)]</i>	
	/jěpà/	[jěmpà]	'compound'
	/āgúlú/	[āŋgúlú]	'vulture'
	/jǒkpa/	[jǒŋkpa]	'iron (metal)'
	/é-kéré/	[éŋk'éré]	'dry season'

d.	<i>N-CV/</i>	<i>[V-C^hV]</i>	<i>V-C^hV</i>
	/idl/	[id ^h l]	'river'
	/kpl/	[kp ^h l]	'learn'
	/dilǒ/	[d ^h lǒ]	'burn (tr.)'

e.	<i>N-CV/</i>	<i>[V-C^wV]</i>	
	/gum/	[g ^w um]	'basket'
	/iku/	[ik ^w u]	'war'
	/adokò/	[ad ^w ok ^w ò]	'horse'

3.2.4 Vowel Harmony

Nupe tako has seven oral vowels. Four are of Advanced Tongue Root [+ATR] and three are of [-ATR].

+ATR		-ATR	
i	u	ɛ	ɔ
e	o		
		(a)	

Nupe Tako simply manifests vestiges of vowel harmony because [ɛ] is attested in only two words [azè] 'blood' and [āgèdè] 'banana' and [ɔ] co-occurs with vowels of both sets except [e] (see (8)a). Vowel [a] is neutral to both sets and so can co-occur with all the vowels as observable in (8)b.

(8)	a. set I	b. set II
	[azo] 'fat'	[igɔ] 'word'
	[ibá] 'husband'	[inǒwú] 'smoke'
	[eja] 'buffalo'	[nǒvó] 'refuse'
	[g ^w úba] 'two'	[jǐkɔ] 'fish'
	[anǐ] 'song'	[ák ^w úsɔ] 'rat'

[atsɔ]	'moon'
[agbá]	'axe'
[adʒɛ]	'blood'

3.2.5 Morphology

Words in Nupe Tako are composed of V and CV syllable types. The number of syllables in a word ranges from one to four basically of the combination (V)CVCV. As in Nupe proper, nouns in Nupe Tako often have a V-prefix although there are some with zero prefix i.e. they begin with consonants. Verbs are basically of the CV(CV) structure. In the case of nouns, nasals like vowels occur as initial vowels and when they do they are homorganic with the following consonant sound.

Nupe Tako noun initial vowels are i-, e- and a- (both oral and nasalised), although the nasalised are rare. Syllabic nasals are occurring in the same noun initial positions are ŋ, m̩.

(9)	[n̩n̩á]	'father'
	[m̩m̩ô]	'mother's brother'
	[h̩d̩étsé]	'hunter'
	[nz̩ádʒi]	'woman'

As observed in Nupe proper, (see section 3.2.3), a homorganic nasal is realised between a significantly nasalised vowel and a following non-nasal consonant thus creating a (C)V̩CCV pattern. The prefix vowels are not inflected for pluralisation; rather a suffix -ʒi is attached to the stem.

(10)	/igi/	[idʒi]	'child'
	/igizi/	[idʒiʒi]	'children'
	/iti/	[iti]	'head'
	/itizi/	[itiʒi]	'heads'

3.2.6 Tone

Three tonemes are attested in Nupe Tako. They are high / ˥ /, mid / ˧ / and low / ˩ /. Each has an allotone: high [˥˥], mid [˧˧] and low [˩˩], respectively. A low rising [˩˥] and a high falling tone [˥˩] are also found in Nupe Tako. The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

(11)	[kpákó]	'two hundred'
	[gbèrè]	'root'
	[inō]	'fire'
	[àgbɔ]	'rope'
	[èdé]	'cloth (material)'
	[h̄dá]	'father'
	[h̄nǒ]	'mother'
	[m̄m̄ô]	'mother's brother'
	[jèlè]	'in-law'

3.3 Gwari

3.3.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic Consonant Inventory

	m		n	ɲ	ŋ		
p	b		t	d	k	g	kp gb
	β						
		f	v	s	z	ʃ	ʒ
				l			
				r		j	w

3.3.1.1 Notes on Consonants

The consonant sound classes attested in Gwari are implosive, nasal, plosive, fricative and approximant. Phonemic overlapping is observed since nasals are derived as allophones of oral approximants through nasalisation.

Hyman and Mogaji (1970) observed an alternation between Gwari /r/ and ///. The speakers according to them substitute [l] or [g] for /r/ in the Hausa borrowings as follows: [l] for [r] before [a, o, u] and [g] for [r] before [i, e]. (In this study [g] is palatalised [gʲ] (see 3.3.1.1.1)).

Hyman and Magaji (1970: 12)

(2) Hausa	Gwari	Gloss
asiri	asiri ~ asigji	'secret'
rogo	rógo ~ lógo	'cassava'

This suggests that the contrast between /r/ and /g/ before [i] and [e] as well as that between /r/ and // before [a], [o] and [u] have been neutralised. The correspondence between [r] and [g] in Gwari and Gwari Yamma in 'sleep v.' also confirms relationship between the two sounds.

3. Gwari	Gwari Yamma	Gloss
[ŋʷāgʲe]	[jerʲe]	'sleep (v.)'

3.3.1.1.1 Palatalisation

Consonants are palatalised before close and close mid front vowels. Fricatives and the palatal approximant do not undergo palatalisation as seen in 3b. /t/ and /d/ thereby are [tʲ] and [dʲ] and [t]/[d] elsewhere respectively.

(4) a.	/àgbɛgè/	[àgbʲɛgʲè]	'root'
	/kāwí/	[kŋāwʲí]	'arrow'
	/ewé/	[ewʲé]	'eye'
	/áwí /	[əwʲí]	'guinea worm'
	/abe/	[abʲe]	'fat'
	/gè/	[gʲè]	'see'
	/tí/	[tʲí]	'sew'
	/dì/	[dʲí]	'carve (wood)'
b.	/sɪ/	[sɪ]	'buy'
	/fɪ/	[fɪ]	'sweep'
	/ʃɪ/	[ʃɪ]	'hold in hand'
	/əvɪ /	[əvɪ]	'thief'

/táj/	[táj]	'bow(weapon)'
/áj/	[áj]	'song'

3.3.1.1.2 Labialisation

Plosives, are labialised before close back rounded vowel whereas fricatives and approximants are not labialised as observed in (5) b.

(5) a.	/ogu/	[og ^w u]	'fight'
	/go/	[g ^w o]	'grind'
	/lākó/	[nāk ^w ó]	'cow'
	/bòkù/	[b ^w òkɛ̀ù]	'back'
	/búsi/	[b ^w úsi]	'stick'
	/pusé/	[p ^w usé]	'chicken'
b.	/súkó/	[súk ^w ó]	'night'
	/zo/	[zo]	'finish'
	/sàkpejé/	[sàɛ̀kpejé]	'salt'
	/sūkà/	[sūɛ̀kɛ̀à]	'iron (metal)'
	/awú/	[awú]	'smoke'

3.3.1.1.3 Nasalisation

//, /j/ and /w/ are nasalised before significantly nasalised vowels. //, /j/ and /w/ thus have allophones [n], [ɲ] and [ŋ^w] respectively in such environments and [l], [j] and [w] respectively elsewhere.

(6)	/lāko/	[nāɛ̀k ^w ó]	'cow'
	/əlá/	[əná]	'fire'
	/áj/	[áj]	'song'
	/wā/	[ŋ ^w ā]	'catch'
	/lūwā/	[nūɛ̀ɛ̀ā]	'water'

3.3.1.1.4 Nasal Release

Nasal release of plosives before nasalised vowels is attested in Gwari. The consonant-plus-nasal (CN) sequences are instances of plosives that are nasally

released. The plosion is often homorganic with the plosive. There are only a few exceptions as in example (7) b.

- (7) a. [tn̩tn̩] 'work'
 [ɛdn̩] 'fear'
 [ɛkɲ̩] 'sheep'
 [labm̩] 'dawn'
- b. [gbàdm̩] 'banana'
 [gbwàgm̩] 'arm'

3.3.1.1.5 Glide formation

[j] and [u]/[ɔ] preceded by a consonant and followed by an unidentical vowel become [j] and [w] respectively in Gwari. The tone is transferred unto the following vowel.

- (8) a. /wóʃiā/ [wóʃjā] 'heavy'
 /ʃiégu/ [ʃjég^wu] 'turn round (intr.)'
 /ʃié/ [ʃjé] 'shoot'
- b. /àbùàdà/ [àbwàdà] 'shoe'
 /òbùà/ [òbwà] 'nose'
 /obue/ [obwe] 'calabash'
 /zàmui/ [zámwi] 'forget'
 /amúí/ [amwi] 'earth (soil)'
 /ko + anī/ [kwapī] 'sing'
 'sing' 'song'

3.3.2 Vowel

Gwari has both oral and significantly nasalised vowels: oral /i e ɛ ə a ɔ o u u/; nasal /ī ā ū/.

(9) Phonemic Vowel Inventory

Oral		nasalised
i	u	ĩ ã
	u	
e	o	
ɛ	ɔ	
	ə	
a		ã

The occurrence of [u], [ɔ] and [ɛ] is very limited in Gwari. In my data [u] is attested only twice ([ùb^wà] 'nose' and [uzu] 'beans'), [ɔ] once ([ɔgbɪmã] 'rain') and [ɛ] very few times. This indicates that the vowel system is undergoing reduction. /ə/ as stem vowel is found in (10) d although it occurs more often as a noun-prefix in Gwari (see example (10)c).

(10) a. Oral vowels

[bi]	'bury'
[fé]	'throw'
[zè]	'to pour'
[àpà]	'skin'
[zo]	'finish'
[lú]	'to beat person'
[ùbwá]	'nose'

b. Nasalised vowels

[ɔgbɪmã]	'rain'
[kɪĩ]	'to choose'
[gɪũ]	'to climb'
[afɪɪ ^w ã]	'tree'

c. /əlá/	[əná]	'fire'
/àpà/	[àpà]	'skin'
/əkã/	[əkɪã]	'thorn'
/ágbé/	[ágbê]	'mouth'

d.	/kəpú/	[kəp ^u ú]	'navel'
	/pàte/	[pətʃe]	'mat'
	/obue/	[obwe]	'calabash'

Other vowels and syllabic nasals found in noun prefix position in Gwari are /a ɔ
 ɔ u e m̩ n̩/.

Examples of syllabic nasal prefixes in Gwari are presented in example (10)e.

e.	[m̩-bà]	'two'
	[n̩-lá]	'three'
	[ŋ̩-ɲí]	'four'

3.3.3 Syllable Structure

The phonetic syllable structure observed in Gwari is (C)V. Phonemically this is simplified as V and CV. The V may be nasalised or be a syllabic nasals. The C may be palatalised [C^j], labialised [C^w] or nasally released (CN). Nasal release of consonants occurs before nasalised vowels provided the C is a plosive (see example (11) b). Fricatives and approximants are not nasally released (see examples (11) a and (11) d). A homorganic nasal is inserted between a nasalised vowel and a following plosive (see (11)c). A V becomes a C when /i/ or /u,u/ preceded by a consonant occurs before an unidentical vowel. The vowel undergoes glide formation. /i/ becomes [j] while /u,u/ become [w] (see example (11)g).

(11) a.	/ (V)CV /	[(V)CV]	gloss
	/odú/	[odú]	'heart'
	/əpà /	[əpà]	'skin'
	/uzu/	[uzu]	'beans'
	/wo/	[wo]	'hear'
	/sì/	[sì]	'buy'
	/ntá/	[ntá]	'three'

b.	/ (V)CṼ /	[(V)CNṼ]	
	/ə kā /	[əkŋā]	'thorn'
	/ətú/	[ətɲú]	'ashes'
	/bā/	[bmā]	'to pierce'
	/əgbā/	[əgbŋmā]	'rain'
	/labī/	[labmī]	'dawn'
c.	/ (V)CṼ +CV /	[(V)CṼC CV]	
	/sàkpejé/	[sàŋkpejé]	'salt'
	/jàgbà/	[jàŋgbà]	'pepper'
	/jàkNú/	[jàŋkŋû]	'room'
d.	/ (V)CṼ /	[(V)CṼ (CṼ)]	
	/fi/	[fi]	'sweep'
	/sījī/	[sīŋi]	'drink'
	/afīwá/	[afīŋ ^w á]	'tree'
	/əmī/	[ə ^m ī̄]	'oil'
	/jī/	[ŋī]	'dig'
	/wā/	[ŋ ^w ā]	'catch'
e.	/NCV/	[(V)C^jV]	
	/e-wé/	[ew ^j é]	'eye'
	/á-wí/	[áw ^j í]	'guinea corn'
	/a-be/	[ab ^j e]	'fat'
	/bàgè/	[bàg ^j è]	'neck'
f.	/NCV/	[(V)C^wV]	
	/go/	[g ^w o]	'grind'
	/ogu/	[og ^w u]	'fight'
	/túkó/	[túk ^w ó]	'head'
g.	/NCVV/	[VCCV]	
	/obuə/	[obwə]	'calabash'
	/obúá/	[obwá]	'hand'
	/àbùàdà/	[àbwàdà]	'shoe'
	/əpíá/	[əpjá]	'moon'
	/mbia/	[mbjā]	'to be good'

3.3.4 Vowel Harmony

In Gwari vowels of the same type of tongue root co-occur in a word thereby creating harmony. Two sets of [-ATR] and [+ATR] are thereby established (see section 2.5). Vowel [ɪ] is not attested in Gwari. [a] is enclosed in parentheses because it co-occurs with vowels of both sets (see 13a).

+ATR	-ATR
i u	u
e o	ɛ ɔ
ɔ	(a)

(12)	+ATR	-ATR
	[owa] 'snake'	[uzu] 'beans'
	[àjì] 'needle'	[úf̃ a] 'farm'
	[túk*ó] 'head'	[bɛ́bɛ́] 'breast'
	[busi] 'to run'	[dagba] 'elephant'
	[yeʒi] 'to gather'	[ɔgbɪmā] 'rain'
	[ɔjé] 'year'	[zɛ́] 'pour'

There are fewer occurrences of the [-ATR] vowels suggesting that vowel harmony is gradually fading out in Gwari. In fact the only phonetic occurrence of [ɔ] in our data is found in prefix position in 'rain'.

3.3.5 Morphology

Gwari stems are made up of V and CV syllables. Nouns generally have a (V)CVCV while verbs have CV(CV) structure. Pluralisation is indicated by inflection in the prefix vowel (see example (13) a). Some lower numerals have syllabic nasals as prefixes e.g. n- and m- (see (13) b). As observed in example (13) c, some nouns are actually combinations of other words resulting in the loss or modification of some prefixes.

(13)	a.	/eḃi/		'child'
		/aḃi/		'children'
		/musu/		'cat'
		/amusu/		'cats'
		/jākū/		'house'
		/api/		'houses'
	b.	[m̀bà]		'two'
		[̀ntá]		'three'
		[̀n̄ī]		'four'
		[̀ntn̄ī]		'five'
	c.	[túk ^w ó] + [èji]		[túk ^w òŋi]
		head	hair	'hair (head)'
		[obwá + ásê]		[bwáse]
		'hand' 'wind'		'wing'
		[̀ntn̄ī + m̀bà]		[tnābà]
		'five' 'two'		'seven'

3.3.6 Tone

There are three basic tonemes in Gwari: High /´ / = [ˊ], mid / ˘ / = [˘], low / ˋ / = [ˋ]. There are gliding tones too: High-Falling [ˊˋ] mid-falling [˘ˋ] and low falling [ˋˋ].

The falling tones occur in word final positions and are derived from the combination of two separate level tones. The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

(14)	/ágbè/	[ágb ^ˊ è]	'mouth'
	/fígbé/	[fígb ^ˊ é]	'charm (medicine)'
	/əbe /	[əbe]	'knife'
	/gbégbè/	[gb ^ˊ égb ^ˊ è]	'grass'
	/jàwì/	[jàw ^ˊ ì]	'maize'
	/ḃe/	[ḃe]	'to come'
	/ji/	[ji]	'to call'
	/pa/	[pa]	'to think'
	/aǰíwâ /	[aǰíŋ ^w â]	'tree'
	/áwì/	[áw ^ˊ ì]	'guinea corn'
	/asúkNú/	[asúkŋú]	'bone'

3.4 GWARI YAMMA

3.4.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic Consonant Inventory

	m	n		ɲ	ŋ			
p	b	t	d		k	g	kp	gb
	β							
				tʃ	dʒ			
	f	v	s	z	ʃ	ʒ		
				l				
				r	j			w

3.4.1.1 Notes on Consonants

As in Gwari, consonant sound classes attested in Gwari Yamma are implosive, nasal, plosive fricative and approximant. Phonemic overlapping is observed when nasals are derived as allophones of oral approximants through nasalisation. Each phoneme has at least one allophone of similar phonetic shape as itself. Apart from palatalisation and labialisation, glide formation is also evident in the language.

3.4.1.1.1 Palatalisation

Consonants are palatalised before close/ close mid front vowels. Fricatives and the palatal approximants do not undergo palatalisation.

(2)	/aβi/	[aβ ^j i]	'children'
	/ede/	[ed ^j e]	'wine'
	/oti/	[ot ^j i]	'yam'
	/òwì/	[òw ^j i]	'guinea corn'
	/funté/	[funt ^j é]	'leaf'
	/majì/	[maj ^j i]	'spear'

3.4.1.1.2 Labialisation

Plosives are labialised before close/close mid back rounded vowels.

(3)	/zùgò/	[zùg ^w ò]	'hoe'
-----	--------	----------------------	-------

/ʃugó/	[ʃug ^w ó]	'sea'
/lūbo/	[nūb ^w o]	'stomach (internal)'
/dogò/	[dog ^w ò]	'horse'
/tʃuwū/	[tʃuŋ ^w ū]	'bone'
/tʃóŋgó/	[tʃóŋg ^w ó]	'night'

3.4.1.1.3 Nasalisation

/l/, /j/ and /w/ become [ɺ], [ɺ], and [ɺ^w] respectively before nasalised vowels but maintain their various shapes elsewhere.

(4)	/wūfu/	[ɺ ^w ūfu]	'cotton'
	/əlá/	[əɺá]	'fire'
	/líí/	[ɺíí]	'day'
	/jì/	[ɺì]	'dig'

3.4.1.1.4 Nasal Release

Plosives are nasally released before nasalised vowels and the plosion is often homorganic with the plosive. The exception in 'arm' (see (5) b. is explained in sections 2.2 and 5.2.2).

(5)	a.	/ə̀dā/	[ə̀ɺnā]	'river'
		/tūtú/	[tnūt ⁿ ú]	'send'
		/kú/	[kɺú]	'sell'
		/gíjí/	[gɺjí]	'mortar'
	b.	/wagmà/	[wagmā]	'arm'

3.4.1.1.5 Glide Formation

[i] and [u] become [j] and [w] respectively when followed by an unidentical vowel and is itself preceded by a consonant. This position is adopted since no consonant clusters are observed in the syllable structure (see section 3.4.3) whereby /opja/ [opja] 'moon' would be unacceptable.

(6)	a.	/ntʃiá/	[ntʃjá]	'three'
		/jaʃia/	[jaʃia]	'iron (metal)'
		/opiá/	[opjá]	'moon'
		/ewié/	[ewjé]	'eye'
		/edie/	[edje]	'cloth'
		/zèfio/	[zèfjo]	'pour'
		/dʒàbiù/	[dʒàbjù]	'bush'
	b.	/tobúá/	[tobwá]	'touch with hand'
		/zagúé/	[zagwé]	'old person'
		/əbue/	[əbwe]	'calabash'

3.4.2 Vowels

The vowels of Gwari Yamma are eight: [i e ε ə a ɔ o u]. The significantly nasalised one are [ĩ ũ ā].

(7) Phonemic Vowel Inventory

oral		nasalised	
i	u	ĩ	ũ
e	o		
ε	ɔ		
	ə		
	a		ā

The vowels are presented in (8).

(8)	[bí]	'to bury'
	[mùké]	'dry season'
	[ló]	'to go'
	[ɔmí]	'oil'
	[pa]	'to tie rope'
	[ékɪĩ]	'needle'
	[tnũtnũ]	'to send'
	[okɪá]	'thorn'
	[ɪĩ]	'to dig'
	[ədnà]	'river'

3.4.3 Syllable Structure

Gwari Yamma basically shares similar syllable structure with Gwari: a (C)V(C) whose vowel may or may not be nasalised or be a syllabic nasal and a consonant C which may be nasally released before nasalised vowels, if plosive. If the C is a fricative or an approximant, a homorganic nasal is inserted between the nasalised vowel and a following plosive. The fricative and approximant are not nasally released. Plosives, as already observed, also undergo palatalisation and labialisation before close front and close back rounded vowels respectively (see 3.4.1.1.1 and 3.4.1.1.2). There is glide formation when [i] or [u]/[ʊ] occurs before an unidentical back vowel (see 3.4.1.1.5).

Below are examples of the different forms of the syllable structure.

(9)	a.	<i>N-CV(V)(CV)</i>	<i>[V-CV(V)(CV)]</i>	
		/otʃi/	[otʃi]	'millet'
		/wu/	[wu]	'kill'
		/lo/	[l ^w o]	'to go'
		/m̀bà/	[m̀bà]	'two'
		/tʃóŋgó /	[tʃóŋg ^w ó]	'night'
		/gbà̀nti/	[gbà̀nti]	'banana'
		/ténti/	[ténti]	'tail'
		/bóúfè/	[bóúfè]	'hunter'
		/tnáábà/	[tnáábà]	'seven'
	b.	<i>[(V)-CṼ]</i>	<i>[(V)-CNṼ]</i>	
		/gīgo/	[gŋīg ^w o]	'market'
		/àdā/	[àdnà]	'river'
		/tūtū/	[tnūt ^w nú]	'send'
		/kī/	[kŋī]	'to make hair'
		/làbí/	[labmí]	'bad'
	c.	<i>[(V)-CṼ +CV]</i>	<i>[(V)-CṼC CV]</i>	
		/mīta/	[mīnta]	'tongue'
		/bòzūgò/	[bòzūŋg ^w ó]	'thigh'
		/osūgu/	[osūŋg ^w u]	'to fight'
		/gbārí/	[gbŋmārí]	'one'

	/gbāwù/	[gb̄m̄āŋ ^w ù]	'axe'
	/kārí/	[k̄r̄í]	'red'
d.	/ (V)-CV /	/ [(V)-C ^J V]	
	/òwí /	[òw ^J í]	'guinea corn'
	/ede/	[ed ^J e]	'wine'
	/égá/	[eg ^J â]	'blood'
	/otí/	[ot ^J í]	'yam'
e.	/ (V)-CV /	/ [(V)C ^w V]	
	/polo/	[p ^w olo]	'hat'
	/kpagu/	[kpag ^w u]	'tortoise'
	/vojí/	[v ^w ojí]	'follow'
	/òbují/	[òb ^w ují]	'back'
f.	/ CVCVV /	/ [CVCCV]	
	/bàrié/	[bàrjé]	'cat'
	/ntjía/	[ntjjá]	'three'
	/wiàŋgo/	[wjàŋg ^w ó]	'sun'
	/tjimua/	[tjímwa]	'tree'
	/bùbúí/	[bùbwí]	'white'
	/zagúé/	[zagwé]	'old person'
	/buarídžè/	[bwarídžè]	'right side'

3.4.4 Vowel Harmony

As in Gwari, vowel harmony is not very pervasive in Gwari Yamma although the vowel are of both [+] and [-] Advanced Tongue Root (ATR).

+ATR		-ATR	
i	u		
e	o	ɛ	ɔ
(ə)		(a)	

[ə] and [a] are enclosed in brackets because they co-occur with vowels of both sets.

There are not too many instances of [-ATR] vowels in my data and in fact [ɔ] occurs only in noun prefix positions in words which have [i] as stem vowel. Example

(10) a. and b. shows that Gwari Yamma only shows vestiges of vowel harmony.

(10) a.	[ɔp ^ɔ i]	'house'	b.	[dʒɛ̄ʃɛŋ ^w ɔ]	'cooking pot'
	[ɔt ^ɔ i]	'yam'		[ɛkŋɪ]	'needle'
	[ɔmi]	'oil'		[ose]	'wind'

3.4.5 Morphology

In Gwari Yamma nouns are of both V-CV and CVCV structures. This means that there are prefix vowels in the language. Gwari and Gwari Yamma prefix vowels are /e ε ɔ o a/ and some lower numerals have syllabic nasals as prefixes e.g. m̩- and ŋ̩-. These are homorganic with the following consonant (see (11) a). Prefix alternation is observed in the formation of the plural of the word 'child' (see (11) b.).

11. a.	/m̩bà/	'two'
	/ŋ̩tʃiá/	'three' —
b.	/eʃi/	'child'
	/aʃi/	'children'

3.4.6 Tone

The three basic tonemes of Gwari Yamma are High /´/ = [ˊ], Mid / ˊ / = [ˊ] low / ˋ / = [ˋ] exemplified in (12)a. Other tones are gliding and are derived from combination of two level tonemes. They are the mid-rising [ˊˊ] and mid-falling [ˋˋ] tones (see—example (12)b). The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

(12) a.	[kŋɔ̄]	[ˊˊ]	'to sell'
	[kŋá]	[ˋ]	'to fry'
	[bà]	[ˋ]	'to count'
b.	[máǵ'e´]	[ˊˊ]	'to sow (seeds in holes)'
	[dàza]	[ˋˋ]	'to walk'

[mija:]	[—]	'mother'
[wákà:jà]	[—]	'to fall'

3.5 Gade

3.5.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic consonant inventory

	m		n	j		ŋ			
p	b		t	d		k	g	kp	gb
			ts						
	f	v	s	z					
				r					
					j				w

3.5.1.1 Notes on consonants

Gade consonant sound classes are nasal, plosive, affricate, fricative and approximant. Each phoneme in Gade has at least one allophone of similar phonetic shape as itself. Apart from palatalisation and labialisation, glide formation is also evident in the language.

Nasalisation is predictable in Gade and as such not distinctive.

3.5.1.1.1 Palatalisation

Consonants are palatalised before front vowels and as such /ts/, /s/ and /z/ are [tʃ], [ʃ] and [z] respectively. They are [ts], [s] and [z] respectively elsewhere.

(2)	/zimu/	[zimŋ]	'dance'
	/ùpisi/	[ùpʃiʃ]	'he goat'
	/tsi /	[tʃi]	'to die'
	/kike/	[kʃikʃɛ]	'saliva'
	/tsé/	[tʃé]	'throw'

3.5.1.1.2 Labialisation

Consonants are labialised before back rounded vowels in Gade.

(3)	/gigó/	[gʃigʷó]	'stomach'
-----	--------	----------	-----------

/gùg'é/	[g ^w ùg ^j é]	'cloth'
/ábò/	[áb ^w ò]	'be rotten'
/ìbékò/	[ìbék ^w ò]	'seed'
/ukò/	[uk ^w ò]	'stone'
/rùgù/	[rùg ^w ù]	'mountain'

3.5.1.1.3 Nasalisation

Nasalisation is predictable in Gade. Vowels are nasalised after nasal consonants.

(4)	/múnì/	[múnì̃]	'sallow'
	/mɔ́/	[m ^w ɔ́]	'give birth'
	/ìnɔ́/	[ìnɔ́̃]	'four'
	/fúné/	[fúné̃]	'cow'
	/baná/	[banā̃]	'untie'
	/ɲíɲì/	[ɲíɲì̃]	'wash things'
	/mé/	[mé̃]	'build'

3.5.1.1.4 Nasal Release

Nasal release is not evident in Gade.

3.5.1.1.5 Glide formation

[i] and [u] become [j] and [w] respectively when followed by an unidentical vowel and is itself preceded by a consonant.

(5)	/ùpɪa/	[ùpja]	'moon'
	/bɪá /	[bjá]	'blow with mouth'
	/fua/	[fwa]	'stink'

3.5.2 Vowels

Gade has a ten vowels: [i ɪ e ɛ ə a ɔ o u, u]. These vowels except [ə] and [o] have nasalised counterparts in the environment of nasal consonants. [ə̃] is not attested in Gade because it occurs only with consonant [g] and [r] in prefix positions and so does

not undergo nasalisation.

(6) **Phonemic Vowel Inventory**

a.
oral

i	u
ɪ	ʊ
e	o
ɛ	ɔ
	ə
	a

b.
nasalised

ĩ	ũ
ĩ̃	ũ̃
ẽ	
ē	õ
	ə̃
	ã

(7) a. Oral vowels

/sɪ/	'to buy'
/kpu/	'to dig'
/tiji/	'hair'
/pu/	'to bury'
/pe/	'to surpass'
/gɛti/	'iron (metal)'
/sɛ/	'to pour'
/sa/	'to tear'
/kɔ/	'to sew'
/go/	'to climb'

b. Nasalised Vowels

[ɪĩnɛnĩ]	'woman'
[unõ]	'farm'
[iɲẽ]	'soup'
[ɔbanã]	'husband'
[zimũ]	'dance'
[mũnĩ]	'swallow'

3.5.3 Syllable Structure

The syllable structure of Gade is: CV. The V may be a vowel or syllabic nasal and the C, a consonant may be palatalised [C^jV] or labialised [C^wV]. A vowel may undergo class change through glide formation by becoming an approximant. i.e. CVV becomes CjV or CwV depending on the nature of the first vowel. [i]/[ɪ] become [j] and [u]/[ʊ] become [w] when followed by an unidentical vowel in a word and is preceded by a

consonant.

Examples

(8)	a.	V / CV		
		/ije/	[ije]	'heart'
		/gànú/	[gànù]	'mouth'
		/tsi /	[tʃi]	'to die'
	b.	/(V)-CV/	[(V)-C^hV]	
		/dèhndè/	[dèhnd ^h e]	'to sit down'
		/m̀pè/	[m̀p ^h è]	'millet'
		/ké/	[k ^h é]	'to pierce'
		/kénè/	[k ^h énè]	'to fry'
	c.	/(V)-CV/	[(V)-C^wV]	
		/gigó/	[g ^h ig ^w ó]	'stomach'
		/kapu/	[kap ^w u]	'bag'
		/kúpómpo/	[k ^w úp ^w ómp ^w o]	'navel'

3.5.4 Vowel Harmony

The vowels of Gade fall neatly into two harmonising sets based on Advanced Tongue Root (ATR).

+ ATR		- ATR	
i	u	ɪ	ʊ
e	o	ɛ	ɔ
ə		a	

Only members of each set can co-occur in a morpheme or word. Singular and plural noun prefixes harmonise with the stem vowel if the latter is produced with advanced tongue root.

(9)	a.	/jeje/	'to be good'	b.	/gúkíkù/	'bone'
		/zìré/	'white'		/ùzɔ /	'water'
		/kùrí/	'fifty'		/úkátsí/	'salt'
		/bàjí/	'blood'		/k ^h ík ^h ɛ/	'saliva'

3.5.5 Morphology

Nouns in Gade often begin with CV- noun prefixes although there are some with V- prefixes. The consonant in such CV- prefixes is g- or r- (cf. the prefixes in Ebiroid). Only in the plural form does the prefix tɪ- surface in 'cotton'. The noun prefixes actually fall into noun classes and the prefix vowel harmonises with that of the stem in terms of advanced tongue root. When the stem vowel is [-ATR], the noun class prefix does not harmonise with the stem vowel. Noun prefix thus performs grammatical function through plural formation. Verbs stems are often of CV(CV) structure.

Examples

(10) a.	np-stem	gloss		
	[gútap ^w ú]	'ear'		
	[r̄j̄i]	'tooth'		
	[gànu]	'mouth'		
	[guk ^j ik ^w ù]	'bone'		
	[gùfé]	'leaf'		
	[r̄ɜ̀è]	'egg'		
b.	singular			plural
	/gù-/	[gù-bo]	'hand'	/ɪ-/ [i-bo]
	/gù-/	[gù-tu]	mortar	/ɪ-/ [i-tu]
	/ù-/	[ù-piʃi]	'he goat'	/ɪ-/ [i-piʃi]
	/u-/	[u-bek ^w ɔ]	'seed'	/ɪ-/ [i-bek ^w ɔ]
	/gu-/	[gu-gɪ]	'thigh'	/a-/ [à-gɪ]
	/ù-/	[ù-je]	'year'	/ɪ-/ [i-je]
	/ù-/	[ù-zɔ]	'water'	/ɪ-/ [i-zɔ]
	/gè-/	[gè-jè]	'cotton'	/tɪ-/ [tɪ-jè]
	/gi/	[gizɛ]	'yam'	/N-/ [n̄zɛ]
	/ɪ-/	[ɪjɛjɛ]	'mosquito'	/ɪ-/ [i-jɛjɛ]
	/kɪkɪɪ/	[kɪkɪɪ]	'dry'	...
	/tsɛɪ/	[tsɛɪ]	'six'	...

Sterk (1978:43) noted about Gade that:

A general rule of vowel assimilation states, moreover, that whenever a non-expanded vowel (for example, in a prefix) is associated with an expanded vowel (for example, in a noun stem), the non expanded vowel becomes expanded.

(The reverse is not true, expanded vowels never become non-expanded).

This means that in Gade, the shape of noun prefix vowel is determined by the shape of the noun stem vowel if the stem vowel is [+ATR] (see 10 b).

3.5.6 Tone

The main tonemes in Gade are High / ˈ / = [ˊ], mid / ˌ / = [ˋ], and low / ˒ / = [ˑ].

Gliding tones are also attested in Gade. They are derived through the combination of two level tones. The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

(11)	/sú/	[sú]	'to take (one thing)'
	/sɔ/	[sɔ]	'to roast'
	/gù/	[gù]	'to close'
	/ùróòrò/	[ùrórò]	'man'
	/úgèèza/	[úgèza]	'needle'

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 Phonologies of Ebiroid Languages

4.0.1 Introduction

In this chapter Ebiroid languages are presented in an order starting from south to North. Etunọ (Igarra), being the most southerly is presented first. Next, I present Ebira Okene which is spoken in the area just above Igarra land and finally, I present Ebira Kwotto which is spoken north of Ebira Okene land.

4.1 Etunọ

4.1.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic Consonants Inventory

m n ɲ ŋ
p b t d k g h
 f v s z ʃ
 r j w

4.1.1.1 Notes on Consonants

As indicated in Chapter Two, consonant sounds of Ebiroid fall into three classes: Stop, Fricative and Approximant. Nasals, plosives and affricates make up the stop class. The fricatives and approximants of Etunọ are presented in 1. Sections 4.1.1.1.1-4.1.1.1.5 show the different allophones of the consonant phonemes under different phonological conditions. Examples in support of each process are also presented. Apart from the allophones mentioned in the sections each phoneme has an allophone of similar shape as itself elsewhere.

4.1.1.1.1 Palatalisation

/k/, /g/ are [tʃ] and [dʒ] before close front vowels [i] and [ɪ] through palatalisation.

These phonemes occur as [k] and [g] elsewhere. i.e. [k] and [g] never occur before [i] and [ɪ] phonetically (except in [àkíkórí] 'snail'). Also [tʃ] and [dʒ] never occur before back vowels (except in the case of 'black' and 'bone'). The sounds thus exhibit some special relationship before [i] and [ɪ].

(2)	/kí/	[tʃí]	'descend'	
	/òkí/	[òtʃɪ]	'tree'	
	/ogigi/	[ódʒódʒi]	'black'	cf. Ebira Kwotto [odʒi] 'black'
	/ògi/	[òdʒɪ]	'cooking pot'	
	/gi + atɛ/	[dʒàtɛ]	'spit'	
	'spit' + 'saliva'			
	/apiné/	[ap ^ɰ inɛ]	'lies'	
	/atító/	[at ^ɰ ító]	'ashes'	
	/òkí + uku/	[òtʃuku]	'bone'	cf. [òtʃɪ] 'tree'
	/àkíkórí/	[àkíkórí]	'snail'	

4.1.1.1.2 Labialisation

Plosives are phonetically labialised before close/ close mid back rounded vowels. Labialisation is therefore not significant in the language. [ŋ^w], a voiced labialised velar nasal is an allophone of /ŋ/ before [u].

(3)	/ŋunó/	[ŋ ^w unó]	'enter'
	/ireŋú/	[ireŋ ^w ú]	'room'
	/èdùdù/	[èd ^w ùd ^w ù]	dust'
	/iretaku/	[iretak ^w u]	'grinding stone'

4.1.1.1.3 Nasalisation

Nasalisation is predictable in Etuno since vowels become nasalised after nasal consonants.

(4)	/ɛpi/	[ɛpĩ]	'water'
	/ɛna/	[ɛnã]	'four'

/muné/[mōnē]	'swallow'
/ná/ [ná]	'sell'
/apí/ [apí]	tooth
/iné/ [inē]	'belly (external)'

4.1.1.1.4 Nasal Release

Nasal release is not attested in Eṭuṇo.

4.1.1.1.5 Glide Formation

[i]/[i] becomes [j] and [u]/[u] becomes [w] between a consonant and an unidentical vowel respectively. The process occurs both within and across morpheme boundary before non palatalised segments.

(5) /ɔpia/	[ɔpja]	'matchet'
/ozí + ɔzókú/	[ozjɔzókú]	'elder brother'
'child' + 'old person'		
/aṅuḗ/	[aṅwḗ]	'palm oil'
/àṅuàfi/	[àṅwàfi]	'fear'
/ku + été/	[kwété]	'kneel'
'grind' + 'ground'		
/ṅu + emi/	[ṅwēmī]	'defecate'
'pass' + 'feaces'		

4.1.2 Vowels

Eṭuṇo vowel phonemes are /i ɪ e ε a ɔ o u u/. Each vowel has a nasalised counterpart after a nasal consonant as well as one of similar shape as itself, elsewhere. [ē] and [ō] are not common.

(6) Phonemic Vowel Inventory

i	u
ɪ	ʊ
e	o
ε	ɔ
ə	
a	

Example (7) shows instances of the vowels of Eṭuṇo .

(7) a.	/asi/	[asi]	'wind'
	/fù/	[fù]	'lie down'
	/súnè/	[súnè]	'weep(cry)'
	/ma/	[mā]	'give birth'
	/rɛfá/	[rɛfá]	'name'
	/irezì/	[irezì]	'dog'
	/òzè/	[òzè]	'door(way)'
	/ɔnɔ́rú/	[ɔnɔ́rú]	'man'
	/muné/	[mūnè]	'swallow'
	/oomu/	[oomū]	'tail'
	/unomi/	[unōmī]	'bird'
	/ɲunó/	[ɲ ^w ūnō]	'enter'

Vowel clusters are not very common in Eṭuṇo. Those attested are presented in

(5) b.

b.	/ɛ̀ɛ̀-ʃí/	'five'
	/owei/	'small'
	/àufɛ́/	'chicken'
	/òózí/	'darkness'

4.1.3 Syllable Structure

(C)V(C) syllable structure is observed in Eṭuṇo. V represents a vowel or a syllabic nasal while C, a consonant. The C is palatalised before close front vowels (see 4.1.1.1.1). /ɲ/ is labialised before a close back vowel (see (3)). The vowel may change into a glide through glide formation i.e. /CVV/ becomes [CCV].

(8) a.	/V-CV/ [V-CV]
	ira 'fire
	u-bó 'arm
	e-ji 'eye'
	a-ɲí 'tooth'

- b. (V)CVVCV
l-dí-tj-k"ù 'knee'
- c. (V)CVC(V)
à-da-m (i) 'father/my father'

4.1.4 Vowel Harmony

Vowels harmony is observed in Ètuno. The vowels into fall into two sets of [+] and [-] Advanced Tongue Root [ATR] feature. The [+ATR] (Set I) vowels are [i,u,e,o] and the [-ATR] (Set II) vowels are [ɪ,u,ɛ,ɔ,a]. Vowel [a] co-occurs with both sets and as such is neutral to both sets. Example (9) shows vowel harmony in the language.

(9) a.	Set I		b.	Set II	
	usí	'thigh'		̀resu	'head'
	ínê	'mortar'		uvó	'hand'
	vòjì	'to reply'		asísé	'feather'
	irenū	'mouth'		atító	'ashes'
	òhè	'fat'		ufé	'moon'
	ùgùfá	'bark of tree'		òvá	'husband'
	arejí	'smoke'		ǰáǰí	'forget'

4.1.5 Morphology

Nouns stems in Ètuno sometimes begin with a V(C)V- prefix and they have a CVVCV stem. The prefix consonant is usually [r], and the pre CV prefix vowels is [ɪ] or [i]. Verbs have a CVVCV structure. Number is indicated in the prefix of human nouns (see example (10) c). The fact that the prefix is sometimes just a V- indicates that it has undergone reduction i.e. VCV- → CV- → V- in such instances.

(10) a.	Nouns	
	̀rá-fu	'night'
	ire-ǰí	'house'
	ɔ-lǰí	'tree'

- a-ví 'leaf'
- b. **Verbs**
 dʒi 'to jump'
 ʃrã 'to fly'
 tʃire 'put on (clothes)'
 wãrà 'fry'
- c. **singular plural**
 /anɔrú/ 'man' [anɔrú] 'men'
 /ozí/ 'child' [ezí] 'children'

Combinations of morphemes to form new words generate surface forms which seem to violate the vowel harmony principle. The reason is that each of the combined morphemes maintains its vowel harmony structure. Examples are presented in example

(11).

- (11) [èèfí + ènã] [ʃínnã]
 'five' 'four' 'nine'
 [èú + rV + èva] [èúréva]
 'ten' + morph + 'two' 'twelve'
 [èú + rV + ihíntà] [èúríhíntà]
 'ten' + morph + 'eight' 'eighteen'

4.1.6 Tone

The tonemes attested in Ètunɔ are high / ˀ / = [ˀ], mid / ˁ / = [ˁ] and low / ˂ / = [˂]. Downdrift is observed in Ètunɔ. Identical tones are lowered throughout the word (see example (12) c). The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

- (12) a. [fú] [ˀ] 'cook'
 [mí] [ˀ] 'extinguish'
 [ní] [ˁ] 'choose'
 [ne] [ˁ] 'throw'
 [vã] [˂] 'pour'
 [fù] [˂] 'roast'
- b. [zózã] [ˀ ˂] 'good'

[ètá] [_ _] 'three'
 [ozí] [_ _] 'child'

- c. [uvɔ́rɪ] [_ _ _] 'right (side)'
 [adʒɛ] [_ _] 'egg'
 [írèfù] [_ _ _] 'sea'
 [òpànè] [_ _ _] 'horn'
 [asísé] [_ _ _] 'feather'
 [óbá] [_ _] 'compound'

4.2 Ebira Okene

4.2.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic Consonant Inventory

	m		n		ɲ		ŋ	
p	b	t	d		k		g	
		s	z					h
			r		j			w

4.2.1.1 Notes on Consonants

Ebira Okene like Eṭuṇo has nasals, plosives and affricates in the stop class. Fricatives and approximants are also attested in Eṭuṇo. Allophones of the consonant phonemes under the different phonological environment are presented in sections 4.2.1.1.1- 4.2.1.1.4 where phonological processes in Eṭuṇo are discussed. Examples supporting each process are presented accordingly. Also each phoneme has an allophone of similar shape as itself elsewhere.

4.2.1.1.1 Palatalisation

/s/ is [ʃ], /z/ is [ʒ], /k/ is [tʃ] and /g/ is [dʒ] before [i]/[ɪ] through palatalisation. [sʃ] and [zʒ] are in free variation with [ʃ] and [ʒ] respectively. I consider [sʃ] and [zʒ] as intermediate stage between the underlying form and the palatalised form. /k/ and /g/

are [k] and [g] elsewhere. i.e. [k] and [g] never occur before [i]/[ɪ] and [e] phonetically.

- (2) /ozi + ɔnɔrú/ [ɔzjɔnɔ́rú] ~ [ɔzɔ́nɔ́rú] 'son'
 'child' + 'male'
 /ozi + ɔné/ [ɔzjɔ́nɛ́é] ~ [ɔzɔ́nɛ́é] 'daughter'
 'child' + 'female'

(3) Within the morpheme boundary

- a. /ki/ [tʃi] 'descend'
 /ɔkí/ [ɔtʃí] 'stick/tree'
 /eke/ [etʃe] 'wine'
 /ugi/ [udʒi] 'basket'

Across morpheme boundary

- b. /si + anɔ́/ [ʃã́nɔ́] 'look for salt'
 'look for' + 'salt'
 sí + Olu [ʃɔlu] 'pay Olu'
 'pay' + 'Olu'
 ozi + ɔ́tárú [ɔzjɔ́tárú] ~ [ɔzɔ́tárú] 'Otaru's child'
 'child' + 'Òtárú'

4.2.1.1.2 Labialisation

Consonants are also labialised before close back rounded vowels although this process is not significant. [ŋ^w], a voiced labialised velar nasal is an allophone of /ŋ/ before [u].

- (4) /ŋú/ [ŋ^wú] 'enter'
 /gù/ [g^wù] 'plant (tubers)'
 /òmù/ [òm^wù] 'tail'

4.2.1.1.3 Nasalisation

Nasalisation is not phonemic. Vowels are nasalised after nasal consonants. The only instance of progressive nasalisation is in the word 'knee'. There are no nasally released consonants.

- (5) /inomi/ [inõmĩ] 'bird'
 /èèna/ [èèñǎ] 'four'

/mú/	[mú]	'swallow'
/ldùŋkù/	[ldùŋkù]	'knee'
/ɔ̀vɛnɛ́/	[ɔ̀vɛnɛ́]	'mat'
/ɔ̀jɪ́/	[ɔ̀jɪ́]	'mother'
/nɛ́/	[nɛ́]	'to throw'
/ɔ̀nɔ̀rú/	[ɔ̀nɔ̀rú]	'man'
/oomu/	[oomú]	'tail'
/ɛɛhi + nV + ɔ̀ɔ̀jɪ́/	[ihínɔ̀jɪ́]	'six'
'five' 'plus' 'one'		

4.2.1.1.4 Nasal Release

No consonant is nasally released in Ebirá Okene.

4.2.1.1.5 Glide Formation

[i]/[i] becomes [j] and [u] / [u] becomes [w] between a consonant and an unidentical vowel respectively. The process occurs either within or across morpheme boundary.

(6)a. Within morpheme boundary

/ihíáma/	[ihjá má]	'louse, lice'
/híɛdu/	[hjíɛdu]	'fall'
/u-huɛ́/	[uhwɛ́]	'moon'
/aŋúɛ́/	[aŋwɛ́]	'oil palm'
/zùè/	[zwè]	'to run'

b. Across morpheme boundary

i. /í/ /í/	[j]	
/hí+anɔ́/	[hjanɔ́]	'buy salt'
'buy' + 'salt'		
/hí + ezi/	[hjízi]	'call children'
'call' + 'children'		
/ozí + ɔ̀nɔ̀rú /	[ozjɔ̀nɔ̀rú]	'son'
'child' 'man'		
/ozí + ɔ̀nɛ́ /	[ozjɔ̀nɛ́]	'daughter'
'child' 'female'		
ii. /u/ /u/	[w]	
/ku + ɛtɛ/	[kwɛtɛ]	'kneel'
'greet' + 'ground'		

/tu + àzà/	[twàzà]	'beat people'
	'beat' + 'people'	
/du + òzà /	[dwòzà]	'chase person'
	'chase'+ person	

4.2.2 Vowels

Vowel phonemes of Epira Okene are nine: /i, ɪ, e, ɛ, a, ɔ, o, u, u/. Each has an oral and nasalised allophone. The nasalised ones occur after nasal consonants. The vowel system inventory is presented in (7) and examples in (8).

(7) Phonemic Oral Vowel Inventory

Front	Back
i	u
ɪ	ʊ
e	o
ɛ	ɔ
a	

(8) /epi/	[epi]	'water'
/òjɪ/	[òjɪ]	'mother'
/ne/	[nē]	'to throw'
/ɪnɛ/	[ɪnɛ̃]	'stomach'
/èèna/	[èènā]	'four'
/ɔnɔ́/	[ɔnɔ́]	'man'
/mu/	[mū]	'swallow'
/oomu/	[oomū]	'tail'
/onobó/	[onōbó]	'old person'
/inomi/	[inōmī]	'bird'

4.2.3 Syllable Structure

The syllable structure of Epira Okene is (C)V(C). The V is either a vowel or syllabic nasal and the C is a consonant which may be palatalised if the following vowel is i/i. [ɲ] is however never palatalised. Elugbe's recognition of glide formation in Epira Okene, rather than Adivé's distinctive palatalisation and labialisation, in his review of the

Verbal Piece in Ebirá (Elugbe: 1991) is upheld here. [i]/[ɪ] and [u]/[ʊ] become [j] and [w] respectively before an unidentical vowel. A /CVV/ thus becomes [CCV] through glide formation. A syllabic nasal is always homorganic with the following consonant. CVC occurs when the final vowel is lost as in (9) c.

- (9) **V**
- a. é-u 'snake'
 è-ú 'ten'
 e-ɪ 'hair'
 e-í 'eye'
- b. **(V)-CV**
 hú 'to drink'
 sí 'to like'
 kú 'gather (things)'
 ɲū 'enter'
 à-dá 'father'
 ð-ɲí 'mother'
 ɔ-ɔ-ɲɪ 'one'
- c. **(V)-(C)VVCV**
 à-tà-á-hù 'uncle'
 i-dú-ɲ-kú 'knee'
 i-kà-ɲ-gà 'well'
 ɪ-hí-ń-ta 'eight'
 e-hí-m-bà 'seven'
 à-m-pò 'bag'
 è-è-tá/ 'three'
- d. **CVC(V)**
 dàn 'build'
 tuh(i) 'pound in mortar'
- e. **CVV CCV**
 /zuè/ [zwè] 'to run'
 /ósue/ [óswe] 'water spring near a hill'
 /èhue/ [èhwe] 'pieces of dried yam'

/ŋwe/	[ŋwē]	'to spin cotton wool'
/ihje/	[ihje]	'teeth ridge, alveolar'
/hiáma/	[ihjámā]	'louse, lice'
/òháma/	[òhámā]	'an imitator'

Vowel clusters are attested in Epira Okene. They sometimes arise from loss of consonant intervocalically. This brings about juxtaposition of unidentical vowels which eventually become geminate through assimilation (see (10) a). Italicised words in (10) a. are taken from Adiva (1989:19) and expanded to show development of the vowel clusters. Vowel clusters in (10)b. cannot be traced to any lost consonant.

Epira Okene (Adiva 1989:19) expanded)

(10) a.	<i>lirehí/</i>	→	iehí	→	[eehí]	'house'
	<i>làwùrú/</i>	→	àùrú	→	[ààrú]	'gown'
	<i>làvábá/</i>	→	ààbá	→	[ààbá]	'all'
b.	/aá-hí/		'nose'			
	/èè-tá/		'three'			
	/èè-hí/		'five'			

4.2.4 Vowel Harmony

Epira Okene vowels fall into two harmonising sets based on Advanced Tongue Root [ATR] feature. The [+ATR] (Set I) vowels are [i,u,e,o] and the [-ATR] (Set II) vowels are [ɪ,ʊ,ɛ,ɔ,a]. [a] is neutral to both sets. As stem vowel [a] does not take an [o] or [u] prefix. Example (11) shows that vowels of a set co-occur in a word.

(11) a.	Set I		b.	Set II	
	usí	'thigh'		iresú	'head'
	inē	'mortar'		uvó	'hand'
	vóhi	'to reply'		asise	'feather'
	irenū	'mouth'		átito	'ashes'
	òhè	'fat'		uhué	'moon'
	ùgùhá	'bark of tree'		òvá	'husband'
	áréji	'smoke'		òò rí	'he ate'
	hjajé	'forget'			
	òò re	'he saw'			

4.2.5 Morphology

Nouns in Epira Okene sometimes begin with a (V)(C)V prefix and they have CV(CV) stem. Verbs are however of the CV(CV) structure. The prefix consonant is usually [r] and the pre CV-prefix vowel usually vowel [i] or [ɪ]. Pluralisation is sometimes indicated in the prefix vowel of nouns referring to human beings (see example (12) a. and (12) d.). The alternation in plural seems to be informed by vowel harmony seeing the prefix vowel is of the same set with the stem vowel.

(12) a. Adiva (1989:102)

Singular		Plural	
òzà	'a person'	àzà	'people'
oṇẹ́	'a woman'	aneé	'women'
oṇoṛú	'a man'	anonú	'men'
òzoḡa	'a visitor'	àzoḡa	'visitors'
ozí	'child'	ezi	'children'
òsé	'wife'	èsé	'wives'

b. **Nouns (V)(C)V-CV**

ìrà-rè	'tongue'
ire-va'	'breast'
ò-pà	'arrow'

c. **Verbs CVCV**

vé	'come'
kósè	'learn'
tùrà	'pull'

Singular		Plural	
ozí	'child'	ezi	
òzà	'person'	àzà	
o-nõrú	'man'	a-nõrú	

The fact that the prefix is sometimes just a V- indicates that it has undergone reduction

i.e. CVC- → CV- → V- in such instances

New words and meanings are sometimes derived through combination of morphemes. Each morpheme maintains its vowel harmony structure regardless of its merger with another morpheme containing vowels of a different type of tongue root. Also higher numerals are derived from the lower ones (see (13) b.).

- | | | | |
|---------|--|---|----------------------------|
| (13) a. | /ètʃè + ɔmɔ/
'alcohol' + 'drink (n.)' | → | [ètʃómɔ̄]
'wine' |
| | /ògèdè + oweji/
'plantain' + 'short of stick' | → | [ògèdówéī]
'banana' |
| | /ozí + ɔné/
'child' + 'female' | → | [oʒɔnēé̄]
'daughter' |
| b. | /εεhí + nV òòjɪ/
'five' + plus + 'one' | → | [εεhínójɪ̄]
'six' |
| | /εεhí + nV èba/
'five' + plus + 'two' | → | [ihím̀bà̄]
'seven' |
| | /εεhí + nV èta/
'five' + plus + 'three' | → | [ihíntā]
'eight' |
| | /èú + rV + èva/
'ten' + plus + 'two' | → | [èúrévā]
'twelve' |
| | /èú + rV + ìhíntà/
'ten' + plus + 'eight' | → | [èúríhíntà̄]
'eighteen' |

4.2.6 Tone

The tonemes attested in Epira Okene are high / ˈ / = [ˊ], mid / ˌ / = [ˋ] and low / ˉ / = [ˉ]. Downdrift is observed in Okene. Consecutive identical tones are lowered through the word (see example 14c). The mid tone is left unmarked for typographical convenience.

- | | | | |
|---------|------|-------|------------------|
| (14) a. | [hú] | [ˊ] | 'beat (drum)' |
| | [ji] | [ˊ] | 'steal' |
| | [re] | [ˋ] | 'see' |
| | [ne] | [ˋ] | 'bury' |
| | [vá] | [ˉ] | 'pour' |
| | [gù] | [ˉ] | 'plant (tubers)' |

b.	[hèré]	[	'vomit (v.)'
	[héhè]	[	'defecate'
	[ozí]	[	'child'
	[étʃúkà]	[	'cassava'
c	[unókò]	[	'cooking pot'
	[aremí]	[	'charcoal'
	[ákòkò]	[	'pepper'
	[ùvèně]	[	'mat'
	[íràrè]	[	'tongue'
	[íràgà]	[	'axe'
	[étʃúku]	[	'bone'
	[úpéjù]	[	'skin'

4.3 Ebira Kwotto

4.3.1 Consonants

(1) Phonemic Consonant Inventory

	m	n		ɲ		ŋ			
p	b	t	d		k	g	kp	gb	
		s	z		ʃ				h
			r						
			l		j			w	

4.3.1.1 Notes on Consonants

Consonants of Ebira Kwotto are presented in 1. Each phoneme has an allophone of similar shape as itself in environment other than those found in the different phonological processes discussed in sections 4.3.1.1.1- 4.3.1.1.5.

4.3.1.1.1 Palatalisation

Palatalisation in Ebira Kwotto creates allophones [tʃ] and [dʒ] for /k/ and /g/ respectively before [i]/[ɪ] and [e]. i.e. [k] and [g] never occur before these close/mid close vowels.

(2)	/ugi/	[udʒi]	'basket'
	/ki/	[tʃi]	'descend'
	/eke/	[etʃe]	'wine'

4.3.1.1.2 Labialisation

Plosives are labialised before back rounded vowels. This process is not phonological. [ŋ^w], a voiced labialised velar nasal is an allophone of /ŋ/ before [u].

(3)	/ŋuné/	[ŋ ^w uné]	'enter'
	/okú/	[ok ^w ú]	'corpse'
	/dùsè/	[d ^w ùsè]	'walk'
	/kó/	[k ^w ó]	'greet (salute)'
	/εŋú/	[εŋ ^w ú]	'body'

4.3.1.1.3 Nasalisation

In Epira Kwotto nasalisation is predictable. It occurs after nasal segments.

(4)	/epi/	[epĩ]	'water'
	/εna/	[ɛnā]	'four'
	/muné/	[mūnɛ́]	'enter'
	/ihínɔŋi/	[ihínɔŋĩ]	'six'

4.3.1.1.4 Nasal Release

Nasal release is not evident in Epira Kwotto as is the case in Ebiroid.

4.3.1.1.5 Glide Formation

(5)	Within the morpheme		
a.	/áŋuɛ́/	[áŋwɛ́]	'oil palm'
	/uhuɛ́/	[uhwɛ́]	'sun'
	/bahɔ́/	[bahjɔ́]	'pour'
b.	Across morpheme boundary		
	//hu + èrɛ́//	[hwèrɛ́]	'vomit'
	/ŋu + emí/	[ŋwemí]	'defecate'
	'pass' + 'feaces'		
	/ku + été/	[kwété]	'kneel'
	'greet' + 'ground'		
	ozí + ɔŋijé	[ozjɔŋijé]	'daughter'

'child' + 'female'

4.3.2 Vowels

Oral vowel phonemes of Ebira Kwotto are /i, ɪ, e, ɛ, a, ɔ, o, u, u/. There are no nasal vowel phonemes in Ebira Kwotto as in all Ebiroid. The nasalised counterparts occur after nasal consonants. [ẽ] and [õ] hardly occur. Example 7. shows the various vowels.

(6) Phonemic Vowel Inventory

Front	Back
i	u
ɪ	ʊ
e	o
ɛ	ɔ
ə	
a	

(7) /epi/	[epī]	'water'
/ɔpi/	[ɔpī]	'mother'
/ne/	[nē]	'to throw'
/aŋúé/	[aŋwé]	'oil palm'
/ɛna/	[ɛnā]	'four'
/ɔnɔrú/	[ɔnɔrú]	'man'
/muné/	[mūnē]	'enter'
/oomu/	[oomū]	'tail'
/inomi/	[inõmī]	'bird'
/atító/	[atító]	'ashes'

4.3.3 Syllable Structure

Ebira kwotto has a similar syllable structure as Ebira Okene: (C)V(C). The V is either a vowel or a syllabic nasal while the C is a consonant which may be palatalised before a front vowel. Glide formation is also observed in Ebira Kwotto. [i]/ [ɪ] and [u]/ [ʊ] become [j] and [w] respectively before another vowel. A /CVV/ thus becomes [CCV].

- (8) **V-CV**
- a. á-ŋí 'tooth'
 e-ji 'eye'
 ò-mù 'tail'
- b. **(V)(C)VCV**
 i-dí-ŋ-kù 'knee'
 é-ń-sé 'iron (metal)'
- c. **VCVV** **VCCV**
 /áŋuél/ [áŋwé] 'oil palm'
 /uhuél/ [uhwé] 'sun'

4.3.4 Vowel Harmony

Two sets of vowels based on the Advanced Tongue Root [ATR] feature are found in Epira Kwotto. The [+ATR] (Set I) vowels are [i u e o] and the [-ATR] (Set II) vowels are [ɪ ʊ ɛ ɔ a]. Vowel [a] is neutral to both sets and so co-occurs with all the vowels. It is however not seen to co-occur as stem vowel with either [o] or [u] as prefix vowel. Below are some examples of nouns and verbal constructions which showing vowel harmony in Epira Kwotto.

- (9) a. **Set I**
 bòhi 'to reply'
 òhè 'fat'
 igùhá 'bark of tree'
 iréjɪ 'smoke'
 iréfù 'sea'
 oò re 'he saw'
- b. **Set II**
 irésú 'head'
 uvó 'hand'
 asísé 'feather'
 atító 'ashes'
 uhwé 'moon'

àbá	'husband'
ò ò rí	'he ate'

4.3.5 Morphology

Nouns in Epira Kwotto often begin with a V(CV) prefix and they have CVCV stem. Verbs are however of the CVCV structure as observable in the examples below. The noun prefix consonant is usually [r] and the pre CV-prefix vowel usually vowel [i] or [ɪ]. Pluralisation is sometimes indicated in the noun prefix and other times by a suffix (see (10) c.). The fact that the prefix is sometimes the CVC- in such instances has undergone reduction i.e. CVC- → CV- → V-.

(10) Nouns

a.	ìràrè	'tongue'
	ìrebá	'breast'
	òkpà	'arrow'
	orihí	'rain'
b.	Verbs	
	bé	'come'
	kóse	'learn'
	tùrà	'pull'
c.	singular	plural
	/ònrú/	[anòrú] 'men'
	/ozí/	[ozíní] 'children'

In words derived through combination of morphemes each morpheme maintains its own vowel harmony structure. In Epira Kwotto too as in other Epiroid languages, higher numerals are derived from the lower ones (see (10)e).

d.	oʃi + nɔʃi	→	[òʃínóʃi]
	'king' of 'sun' (the greatest?)		'king'
	ɔtɛ + ngi + ira	→	[ɔtɛndʒira]
	'fire'		'hat/cap'
	èʃi + ɔmɔ	→	[èʃɔmɔ]
	'water' 'drink'		'palm wine'

	ozí + onijé	→	[ozjónijé]
	'child' + 'female'		'daughter'
e.	εεhí + nV + òòrɪ	→	[εεhínóɪɪ]
	'five' + plus + 'one'		'six'
	εεhí + nV + èba	→	[ihímɓà]
	'five' + plus + 'two'		'seven'
	εεhí + nV + ènà	→	[ihíhà]
	'five' + plus + 'four'		'nine'
	èú + rV + èba	→	[èúrèba]
	'ten' + plus + 'two'		'twelve'
	èú + rV + ihíntà	→	[èúríhìntà]
	'ten' + plus + 'eight'		'eighteen'
	òhu + rV + èba	→	[òhurèba]
	'twenty' plus 'two'		'twenty-two'

4.3.6 Tone

The tonemes attested in Epira Kwotto are high / ˈ / = [ˉ], mid / ˨ / = [ˊ] and low / ˧ / = [˘]. Downdrift is observed in Epira Kwotto. Identical tones are lowered throughout the word (see example (11)c).

(11)a	[tú]	[ˉ]	'pound (in mortar)'
	[zá]	[ˊ]	'catch'
	[wɔ]	[ˊ]	'kill'
	[ne]	[ˊ]	'throw'
	[bà]	[ˊ]	'pour'
	[kù]	[˘]	'grind'
b.	[húrè]	[ˉ ˊ]	'choose'
	[diné]	[ˊ ˉ]	'stand'
	[ozí]	[ˉ ˉ]	'child'
	[etʃúkà]	[ˉ ˉ ˊ]	'cassava'
c.	[keke]	[ˊ ˊ]	'small'
	[eja]	[ˊ ˊ]	'buffalo'
	[itútú]	[ˊ ˊ ˊ]	'rubbish heap'
	[irárè]	[ˊ ˊ ˊ]	'tongue'
	[asísé]	[ˉ ˉ ˉ]	'feather'
	[éńsé]	[ˉ ˉ ˉ]	'iron (metal)'

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 COMPARATIVE NUPOID PHONOLOGY

5.0.1 Introduction

This chapter contains Proto-Nupoid (PN) consonant and vowel reconstructions.

The reconstructions are made following an examination of the phonetic sound correspondences drawn from the various speech forms. Sounds are reconstructed on the basis of phonetic plausibility governed by principles of sound change. Each corresponding sounds is considered as a potential Proto- sound however my choice is determined the most widespread sound or by the phonetic plausibility of deriving the majority of corresponding sounds from one of them provided it has not been reconstructed earlier. Sometimes, where this is not possible, a lenis segment is reconstructed to account for a set of varied correspondences. I try to provide explanations to account for the development of each sound from the reconstructed one where the corresponding sounds are varied.

The correspondence sets (c.s.) are of two types: those that have identical phonetic shape and those with unidentical phonetic shape. In examining the former, no assumption is made concerning a sound shift that has occurred, whereas, in the latter, assumptions that some sound shift has taken place are made. Again, the factors responsible for such sound shifts are considered before reconstruction is made (e.g. the effect of vowels in the environment). Where there is no evidence from vowel environment, reconstruction is made on the basis of other phonological processes that may have occurred such as weakening, elision, etc. The overall pattern of the phonetic

sound inventory as well as reconstructions in other branches of Benue-Congo is considered to determine the possible phonetic shape of the Proto-sound.

The correspondence sets (c.s.) are presented only in phonetic form for easy understanding especially because

- (i) it is the phonetic shapes that are considered in reconstructions, and
- (ii) each language has its own phonemic structure different from those of other languages. Presentation of sounds in phonemic form may affect uniformity of cognate sounds and as such reconstruction will be difficult.

Comparative series (C.S.) and reconstructed sounds are presented. The latter are indicated by an asterisk: *. Relevant C.S.'s are also listed along with the c.s. and reconstructions. The possible line of development of reflexes from the reconstructed sounds is discussed in section 5.6. Furthermore the phonetic environment excluded by the correspondence sets (c.s.) is also indicated. Non-cognate sounds are represented by a dash in parentheses.

For ease of reference in section 5.6, the languages are indicated by the following numbers:

1. Nupe
2. Nupe Tako
3. Gwari
4. Gwari Yamma
5. Gade

In section 5.5 the relevant PN reconstructed items from which correspondence sets are established for reconstructing PN consonants are cited here from Volume Two for easy and quick reference. This is why the numbering is not serial here unlike in Volume Two. The PEB reconstructions for each item are also presented to show the

extent of cognation with PN.

5.1 PN Consonants

(1) Phonetic Inventory of PN Consonants

	Bilabial	Labio-dental	Alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Labial-velar
Nasal	m		n	ɲ		
Lenis			nh			
Nasal Plosive	p	b	t	d	c	k g kp gb
Lenis Plosive	ph	bh			kh gh	gbh
Implosive	ɓ					
Affricate			ts			
Fricative		f	s z			
Central Approximant				j		w
Lateral Approximant			l			wh
Lenis Approximant			lh			

5.1.1 Notes on PN Consonants

Nasals, plosives, implosives and affricates within the class of sounds referred to as Stop are reconstructed in PN. The nasal and plosive sub-classes have lenis sounds as seen in 1. Fricatives and approximants are also reconstructed in PN. Sound changes observed in the development of reflexes undergo palatalisation, affrication, deaffrication, spirantisation (fricativisation), hardening and even weakening sometimes. See the sections below for comments on each process.

Lenisness is reconstructed even though there is only one synchronic evidence of it in Nupoid – [nh], a lenis voiced alveolar nasal found in Gwari Yamma in the item [gbānhi] 'jaw'. A lenis consonant is considered a weak segment whose nature is prone

to various changes. Elugbe (1989:109) described weakening as "a movement along the stricture scale" from complete closure to open approximation. According to him, it is "a process in which a stop becomes a fricative, then an approximant, and finally, a zero." Lenis consonants are reconstructed based on the nature of their reflexes which range from non-lenis plosives to affricates, fricatives and approximants. The lenis sounds sometimes have zero reflexes suggesting that PN consonant system has undergone reduction in Nupoid.

5.1.1.1 Nasals

*m : --
 *n : *nh
 *ɲ

Reconstructed PN nasals are *m, *n, *ɲ, produced at the bilabial, alveolar and palatal places of articulation respectively. The only lenis nasal is [nh] restricted to the C2 position.

Overlapping is observed in the development of reflexes of the nasals e.g. Nupoid [ɲ] has three sources while [ŋ] has two sources. The former develops from *ɲ, *m and *n. The latter from *w and *kh (see Tables 1-5).

5.1.1.2 Plosives

*p : *b *t : *d *c : - *k : *g *kp : *gb
 *ph : *bh - : - - : - *kh : *gh - : *gbh

Pairs of voiceless and voiced lenis/non-lenis plosives are reconstructed at three different places of articulation in PN. They are bilabial, alveolar and velar places. A voiced lenis labial-velar and a voiceless palatal plosive are also reconstructed. There are therefore six gaps in the series: the voiceless and voiced lenis alveolar plosive, the

voiced palatal plosive and the lenis pair of the palatal plosive and the voiceless lenis labial-velar plosive.

5.1.1.3 Implosive

*ɓ

Implosion is described as stop plus suction by Elugbe (1989) and this feature is evident in Proto-Nupoid in the bilabial implosive *ɓ. Synchronic evidence for implosion exists in Gwari and Gwari Yamma. The suction feature is observed to have been lost in Nupe, Nupe Tako and Gade as they all have reflex [b], a plosive of the PN implosive *ɓ. There is therefore a merger between the implosive and plosive since the contrast established at the Proto level is no longer evident in the languages that have lost it.

5.1.1.4 Affricates Versus Fricatives

*ts : -
*f : - *s : *z

*ts, a voiceless alveolar affricate, *f, a voiceless labiodental fricative, *s, a voiceless alveolar fricative and *z, a voiced alveolar fricatives have been reconstructed for PN. Synchronic evidence for their reconstruction can be found in Tables 1, 2 and 3. One major observation is that the affricate has alveolar plosive reflexes suggestive of some merger with the plosive counterpart. No voiced counterpart of *ts and *f is reconstructed in PN. Synchronic [v] is actually a reflex of *bh. No item showing synchronic [dz] is found to be cognate in Nupoid.

5.1.1.5 Approximants

*j
*l : *lh
*w : *wh

Reconstructed approximant sounds are centrally produced alveolar approximant.

palatal approximant, lenis / non-lenis laterally produced alveolar approximant and lenis/non-lenis labial-velar approximant. Synchronic evidence for the reconstruction of the non-lenis approximant can be seen in Tables 2, 3, and 5. One observes that [*r] is the only approximant that is not reconstructed although it occurs as reflexes of many reconstructed sounds: *bh, *nh, *lh and *l.

5.2 Development of Consonants from PN

The changes observed in the development of the reflexes from the Proto level appear to have arisen from different processes such as palatalisation, nasalisation, affrication, deaffrication, spirantisation (fricativisation), hardening and even weakening.

5.2.1 Palatalisation

At the synchronic level this phonological process is very pervasive in Nupoid. *c before front vowels developed alveolar and palato-alveolar reflexes in most of the languages suggesting fronting of the sound. The bilabial nasal developed palatal counterpart (see c.s. 2).

5.2.2 Nasalisation

Nasalisation in Nupoid can be traced to *CVNV structures as such there are no nasalised phonemes in PN (see (2)). Nasalisation is predictable in the development of the nasalised segments and therefore not significant. Vowels are nasalised in the environment of nasal segments. Nasal release is not reconstructed in PN.

(2) *CVNV > (i) CNV > C $\bar{V}$ (loss of V¹)

(ii) CVN > C $\bar{V}$ (loss of V²)

(2i) involves deletion of the first vowel and then that of the second consonant i.e.

N immediately the V² has undergone nasalization by the preceding N. (2ii) involves deletion of the first vowel V² resulting in CN sequence.

Nasalisation in Nupoid thus developed from the C² in *CVNV structures but the process is along different lines in the languages. In Nupe and Nupe Tako *CV¹NV² > C¹V¹N > C¹V̄¹. This results in significant vowel nasalisation where the C¹ is non-nasal. In Gwari and Gwari Yamma, *C¹V¹NV² > C¹NV² or C¹V̄² (see section 2.1.1.1). When CNV is realised, C¹ is nasally released provided it is a plosive and the spread of nasalisation is towards the C¹. Where the spread does not take place then there is no homorganicity as in Gwari Yamma [gbadma] 'banana' and [wagmà] 'hand'. If the C¹ is a fricative or an approximant, nasalisation spreads to the V² and the C² (i.e. N) is deleted. Synchronic evidence of this C² in Nupoid is demonstrated in 3a-c and 4a-c. In Gade the V² and the C² are both deleted i.e. *CVNV > CV. (CVN is found Gwari and Gwari Yamma in 'leaf'.)

- (3) *CVNV >
- i. CVNV
 - ii. CNV
 - iii. CV

a. PN *CV-f a n i-

	CVNV / CVN	/ CV ₀₀	
Nupe	f i n ī		'leaf'
Nupe Tako	f i n i		
Gwari		f i n tolo	
Gwari Yamma		f u n t̄ ¹ e	
Gade			g u f ε

b. PN *V-kp o m i

	CVNV	/ CNV	
Nupe	kpomī		'okro'
Nupe Tako	kpomī		
Gwari	a-	kp̄ɪ̄m̄ ī	
Gwari Yamma	o-	kp̄ɪ̄m̄ ī	
Gade			(rɪ-kwoibi)

c.	PE *V-dinā				
		CVNV	/ CNV	/CV ₀₀	
Nupe		dinā			'burn'
Nupe Tako		dinā			
Gwari			dnadna		
Gwari Yamma		(a-gina)			
Gade				du	

(4) *CVNV > i) C $\bar{V}$
ii) CNV

a.	PN *V-tuNu				
		i) C $\bar{V}$	ii) CNV		
Nupe	e-	tū			'work'
Nupe Tako	i-	tū			
Gwari			t nut nu		
Gwari Yamma			t nut nu		
Gade		(gatimε)			

b.	PN *tutuNuti				
		i) C $\bar{V}N$	ii) CNV		
Nupe		tu tū n ti			'rubbish heap'
Nupe Tako		tu. t i m pti			
Gwari	(fīdakulu)				
Gwari Yamma			t nut nū		
Gade	(igin baaʒi)				

c.	PN *gəN				
		i) C $\bar{V}$	ii) CNV		
Nupe		g ā			'divide (share out)'
Nupe Tako		g ɔ			
Gwari			g ŋ ā		
Gwari Yamma			g ŋ ā		
Gade	(za)				

The CVNC forms in Nupe and Nupe Tako as in 'rubbish heap' is not widespread.

5.2.3 Affrication / Deaffrication

Affrication is the process whereby a sound becomes an affricate and deaffrication is the process whereby an affricate becomes fricative. These are observed

in the development of reflexes from PN *p > ts (c.s.5); *t > ts,tʃ (c.s. 14); *z > dʒ (c.s. 24).
 *k > ts,tʃ (c.s. 34). In c.s. 28 we see a case of deaffrication of *ts to ʃ and t.

5.2.4 Spirantisation (Fricativisation)

Spirantisation, a process whereby stops become fricatives is observed in the development of reflexes from PN e.g. *t > s,ʃ (c.s. 14); *d > ʒ (c.s. 17); *k > s (c.s. 34).

5.2.5 Hardening

Hardening, a process whereby a sound derived from an original one as a result of sound changes is of a stronger articulation than the original is observed in the development of reflexes in the daughter languages. For example implosive becomes plosive; lenis sounds become hardened to non-lenis counterparts e.g. *nh > n (c.s. 21), *lh > l (c.s. 26), *gbh > gb (c.s. 43/44).

5.2.6 Weakening

Weakening is process whereby a sound of sound changes is of a weaker articulation is derived from a stronger original one. This is observed in the development of reflexes in the daughter languages. *kh > ø (c.s. 36). Affrication and spirantisation are examples of the weakening process.

5.3 Tables showing PN consonants and their reflexes

Table 1 Labials

PN	*b	*p	*b	*f	*ph	*bh	*m
Nupe	b	p/b/m/ts	b	f	f	v/r	m/ɲ
Nupe Tako	b	p/b	b	f	f	v/r	m/ɲ
Gwari	β	p	b/m	f	f,s	b	m
Gwari Yamma	β/b	p	b/m	f	f,s	b	m
Gade	b	p	b/m	f	f	v/r	m

	*n	*nh	*t	*d	*ts	*s	*z	*l	*lh
PN	n	nh	t	d	ts	s	z	l	lh
Nupe	n	n	t/ts/tʃ/tn	d/dʒ/gʒ	ts	s/ʃ	z/ʒ/dʒ	l	l/w
Nupe Tako	n	n	t/ts	d/ʒ	ts/s	s/ʃ	z/ʒ	l	l
Gwari	n/p/ŋ ^w	(-)	t/tn/tʃ/ʃ/s	d/dn/dʒ	tn/ts	s/ʃ	z/ʒ	l	l
Gwari Y.	n/p	r	t/tn/tʃ/tʒ	d/dn/dʒ	tʃ/kŋ	s	z/dʒ/ʒ	l	ŋ ^w /l/ʃ
Gade	n/p	(-)	t/tʃ	d/ʒ/gʒ	t/tʃ	s	z/ʒ	n/r	r

	*c	*ɲ	*j
PN		ɲ	j
Nupe	tʃ	j/ɲ	j
Nupe Tako	ts	j	j
Gwari	ʃ	ɲ	j
Gwari Y.	ʃ/tʃ/t	ɲ/ʒ	j/ʒ
Gade	ʃ/tʃ/kʒ	j/ɲ	j

	*k	*g	*kh	*gh
PN	k	g	kh	gh
Nupe	g/k/ts/tʃ	g/gʒ	ø	w/v
Nupe Tako	g/k/tʃ/s	g/dʒ/ʒ	ø	w/v
Gwari	g/k/kŋ/s	g/gŋ/p/gʒ	kŋ	w
Gwari Yamma	g/k/kŋ/t/tʃ	g/gŋ/m	ŋ ^w	gŋ
Gade	k/kʒ/w/tʃ	g	k	g

	*kp	*gb	*gbh	*w	*wh
PN	kp	gb	gbh	w	wh
Nupe	kp	gb	gb/g/b/gʒ	w/ŋ ^w	j
Nupe Tako	kp	gb/g	gb/g/b/dʒ	w/ŋ ^w	j
Gwari	k/kpŋm	gb/b	ŋ ^w /b/gb/b/bʒ	wʒ/w/ŋ ^w	wʒ
Gwari Yamma.	k/kpŋm	gb/w	ŋ ^w /b/w/gb/b/bʒ	wʒ/w/ŋ ^w /m	wʒ
Gade	kp	gb/b	b/ʃ	w/m/b/g	--

5.4 Correspondence Sets and Development of Consonants from PN to Nupoid

5.4.1 Labials

c.s. 1 PN *m

	1	2	3	4	5
C.S. 90	m~(-)	~	m	~	m~(-)
C.S. 1	m	~	m	~	m~m
C.S. 91	m	~	m	~	m~(-)
C.S. 92/93	m	~	m	~	(-)~(-)~m

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape therefore *m, a voiced bilabial nasal is reconstructed. This reconstruction excludes the environment before nasalised vowels.

c.s. 2 PN *m /-T

1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 2 p ~ p ~ m ~ m ~ m

[p] in 1 and 2 are instances of palatalised *m before [T]. In 3 and 4 [m] is nasally released and since it is already a nasal, the reflex [m] is realised. In 5 nasalisation is not significant. Evidence outside Nupoid supports the reconstruction here since only one item is cited.

c.s. 3. PN *p

1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 3 p ~ p ~ p ~ p ~ p
C.S. 85 p ~ p ~ p ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 84 p ~ p ~ p ~ p ~ (-)
C.S. 232 p ~ p ~ p ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 4 p ~ p ~ p ~ p ~ (-)

This c.s. excludes the environment before -i, -ia and -ie discussed in C.S. 5, 6 and 7 respectively. *p, a voiceless bilabial plosive has developed regularly into p in all the language.

c.s. 4. PN *p /-i

1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 5 b ~ b ~ p ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 6 b ~ b ~ p ~ p ~ (-)

The reflexes are varied. *p is voiced between vowels in 2 and initial position tends to accentuate voicing. Note that [i] is [u] in 3 and 4 after labial sounds.

c.s. 5. PN *p /-iV

1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 7 ts ~ ts ~ p ~ p ~ p
C.S. 67 (-) ~ (-) ~ p ~ p ~ ts

*p is affricated to [ts] in 1, 2 and 5 before i.

c.s. 6 PN *b

1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
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C.S. 11	b ~ b ~ b ~ b ~ (-)
C.S. 13	b ~ b ~ b ~ b ~ v
C.S. 9	b ~ b ~ (-) ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 10	b ~ b ~ b ~ b ~ b
C.S. 87	b ~ b ~ b ~ b ~ (-)
C.S. 86	b ~ b ~ b ~ b ~ b

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape therefore *b, a voiced bilabial plosive is reconstructed. I have no explanation for the development of [v] before [a] in 5 (C.S. 13). Note that stops do weaken to fricative as in Edoid. PE *bi 'be black' > visina in Uhami. Also PE *p became [f] in almost every arm of Edoid. E.g. PE *puNa 'be white' > fu (Degema), fuafu (Okpe), fua (Auchi), fufu (Uhami).

c.s. 7 PN *b / T?

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 16	b ~ b ~ m ~ m ~ m

The reconstruction here is tentative since only one item is cited. The alternatives are *b and *m. *b is reconstructed here since *m has been reconstructed in c.s. 1. *b is believed to have had a nasally released reflex: [bm] in 3 and 4 which developed from a *CVNV. Loss of [b] in [bm] results in [m], i.e. the nasal articulation in 3 and 4. In 5 [b] was simply nasalised before the close front vowel. Reconstruction of *bm suggests nasal plosion at the Proto-level whereas the present reconstruction explains plosion from a *CVNV.

c.s. 8 PN *bh

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 12	v ~ v ~ b ~ b ~ v
C.S. 144	r ~ r ~ b ~ b ~ (-)
C.S. 165	(-) ~ (-) ~ b ~ b ~ r

The alternatives are [b], [p] and [r]. *bh, a voiced lenis bilabial plosive is reconstructed to account for the varied reflexes since lenis sounds are generally weak and therefore prone to change. Also it is phonetically implausible for *r or *v to develop

a stop i.e. [b]. *b has been justifiably reconstructed in c.s. 7.

c.s. 9 PN *b

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 238	(-)~(-) ~ b ~ b ~ b
C.S. 14	b ~ b ~ b ~ b ~ b
C.S. 15	b ~ b ~ b ~ (3) ~ b
C.S. 89	b ~ (-) ~ b ~ (-) ~ (tʃ)

Alternatives are [β] and [b]. *b has been justifiably reconstructed in C.S. 7. *b, a voiced bilabial implosive is therefore reconstructed. Development of [b] in 1, 2 and 5 are instances of *b that has lost suction.

c.s. 10 PN *f

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 18	f ~ f ~ f ~ f ~ (-)
C.S. 19	f ~ f ~ f ~ f ~ f
C.S. 17	f ~ f ~ f ~ f ~ f
C.S. 229	f ~ f ~ (-) ~ f ~ f

*f, a voiceless labiodental fricative is reconstructed since the c.s. is of identical phonetic shape.

c.s. 11 PN *ph

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 20	f ~ f ~ s ~ s ~ (-)
C.S. 237	f ~ f ~ s ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 21	f ~ f ~ s ~ s ~ f
C.S. 37	(-)~(-) ~ s ~ s ~ f
C.S. 22	f ~ f ~ s ~ s ~ (-)
C.S. 237	f ~ f ~ s ~ (-)~ (-)

[f] and [s] and they are the alternatives. Neither is however reconstructed because *f has been reconstructed in c.s. 10 and *s in c.s. 22. *ph, a voiceless lenis bilabial plosive is therefore reconstructed. *ph is spirantised to [f], a voiceless labiodental fricative in 1, 2 and 5 and to [s], a voiceless alveolar fricative as observed in 3 and 4.

5.4.2 Alveolars

c.s. 12 PN *t

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 27	t~	t~	t~	t~	(-)
C.S. 96	t~	t~	t~	t~	t
C.S. 97	t~	t~	t~	t~	(-)
C.S. 228	t~	t~	(-)	(-)	t

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape therefore *t, a voiceless alveolar plosive is reconstructed. This c.s. excludes the environment before *-VN as found in c.s. 13 and before -iV as in c.s. 14 where *t is [tʃ] in 4 (C.S.29) due to a following vowel [i] not attested in the other languages.

c.s. 13 PN *t/-V̄

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 23	t~	t~	tn~	tn~	t
C.S. 24	t~	t~	tn~	tn~	(n)
C.S. 25	t~	t~	(-)	tn~	(-)
C.S. 26	t~	t~	tn~	tn~	t
C.S. 98	t~	t~	tn~	tn~	(-)

*t and *tn are the alternatives here. *t, reconstructed in c.s. 12 is again reconstructed but under a different environment i.e. -V̄. In 3 and 4 [tn] is [t] nasally released which is derived from *CVNV. Reconstruction of *tn suggests nasal plosion at the Proto-level whereas the present reconstruction explains plosion from a *CVNV. This c.s. excludes the environment before -iV as in c.s. 14.

c.s. 14 PN *t/iV

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S.36	ts~	ts~	(-)	tʃ~	t
C.S. 38	ts~	ts~	(-)	tʃ~	tʃ
C.S. 126	ts~	ts~	ts~	tʃ~	(-)
C.S. 125	ts~	ts~	tn~	(-)	t
C.S. 106	(-)	(-)	tʃ~	tʃ~	t

C.S. 129 tʃ ~ ts ~ s ~ t ~ (-)

C.S. 130 tʃ ~ ts ~ ʃʲ ~ tʲ ~ (-)

There is affrication and spirantisation of *t to [tʃ], [tʃʲ] and [ʃ] before [i]; [ts] in 1 before [i] followed by [u] and [tʃʲ] before [i] followed by another vowel. But for C.S. 38, [t] is retained in 5. [ts] is always reflex in 2 while any of the reflexes occur 3 and 4.

c.s. 15 PN *d

	1~	2	~3	~4	~5
C.S. 30	d	~d	~d	~d	~d
C.S. 31	d	~d	~d	~d	~d
C.S. 32	d	~d	~d	~d	~d
C.S. 100	d	~(-)	~d	~d	~d
C.S. 101	d	~d	~(b)	~d	~(-)
C.S. 113	d	~d	~d	~d	~(-)
C.S. 104	d	~d	~(-)	~d	~(-)
C.S. 110	d	~d	~d	~(-)	~(-)

*d, a voiceless alveolar plosive is reconstructed since the c.s. is of identical phonetic shape. This c.s. excludes the environment before -VN (see c.s. 16) or before /ie (see c.s. 17).

c.s. 16 PN *d /-V̄

	1~	2	~3	~4	~5
C.S. 103	d	~d	~dn	~dn	~(-)
C.S. 107	d	~d	~dn	~(-)	~d
C.S. 124	d	~d	~d	~dn	~(-)

*d and *dn are the alternatives here. *d, reconstructed in c.s. 15 is again reconstructed but under a different environment i.e. -V̄. In 3 and 4 [dn] is [d] nasally released, derived from *CVNV. Reconstruction of *dn suggests nasal plosion at the Proto-level whereas the present reconstruction explains plosion from a *CVNV.

c.s. 17PN *d /-ie

1~ 2 ~3 ~4 ~5

C.S. 160	$d_3 \sim 3 \sim (-) \sim d^j \sim (-)$
C.S. 64	$g^j \sim 3 \sim d_3 \sim d^j \sim 3$

*d, is palatalised to [d^j], affricated to [d₃] and spirantised to [ʒ]. Affrication and spirantisation are here accompanied by palatalisation resulting in change of place of articulation from alveolar to palatal. (cf. c.s. 14).

c.s. 18PN *n

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 115	n ~ n ~ n ~ n ~ (-)
C.S. 82	n ~ n ~ n ~ n ~ (-)
C.S. 33	n ~ n ~ n ~ n ~ (-)
C.S. 116	n ~ n ~ n ~ n ~ (-)
C.S. 119	n ~ n ~ n ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 121	n ~ n ~ (-) ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 118	n ~ n ~ n ~ n ~ (-)
C.S. 117	n ~ n ~ n ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 217	n ~ n ~ (-) ~ (-) ~ (-)

This c.s. excludes the environment before [ɾ] c.s. 19 and before ũ (c.s. 20).

Here the c.s. are of identical phonetic shape and as such *n, a voiced alveolar nasal is reconstructed.

c.s. 19 PN *n /-iaN

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 35	n ~ n ~ ɲ ~ ɲ ~ n
C.S. 122	n ~ n ~ ɲ ~ ɲ ~ ɲ
C.S. 123	n ~ n ~ ɲ ~ ɲ ~ j

*n, is palatalised to [ɲ] resulting in change of place of articulation 3, 4 and sometimes in 5. [j] in 5 can only be explained through sporadic loss of nasalisation. The alternative *ɲ, has been reconstructed (c.s. 30) and development of [n] (C.S. 35) from *ɲ before [i] is almost impossible except in a situation where [ɲi] coalesces into [n]. The attested sound is however not a syllabic nasal in this case.

c.s. 20 PN *n/-u

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 157	n ~ n ~ ŋ*~(-)~(-)

Alternatives for reconstruction are *n and *ŋ*. [ŋ*] in 3 is labialised [n] therefore *n is reconstructed. An *ŋ* developing [n] in 1 and 2 is most unnatural especially before [u], a back rounded vowel.

c.s. 21 PN *nh /-iaN

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 34	n ~ n ~ (-) ~ r ~ (-)

This reconstruction is tentative pending availability of more data. Only once do I find synchronic evidence of *nh in Nupoid. This is in 4 [gbānhī] 'jaw'. *nh is reconstructed here to account for the varied reflexes: [n] and [r]. Being a lenis sound, *nh is further weakened to an approximant [r] in 4.

c.s. 22 PN *s

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 45	ʃ~ ʃ ~ s ~ s ~ s
C.S. 139	s ~ s ~ ʃ ~ (-) ~ s
C.S. 138	s ~ s ~ s ~ (-) ~ (-)

*s is reconstructed here since [ʃ], one of the reflexes is palatalised in 1 and 2.

c.s. 23 PN *z

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 46	z ~ z ~ z ~ z ~ (-)
C.S. 143	z ~ z ~ z ~ z ~ (-)
C.S. 47	z ~ z ~ z ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 140	z ~ z ~ (-) ~ z ~ (-)

*z is reconstructed because the c.s. is of identical phonetic shape. This c.s. excludes the environment before i found in c.s. 24.

c.s. 24 PN *z /-i

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 52	ʒ ~ ʒ ~ ʒ ~ dʒ ~ (-)

C.S. 161	3 ~ 3 ~ 3 ~ 3 ~ (-)
C.S. 162	3 ~ 3 ~ 3 ~ d ₃ ~ (-)
C.S. 158	d ₃ ~ 3 ~ 3 ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 109	(-) ~ (-) ~ z ~ z ~ 3
C.S. 51	3 ~ 3 ~ 3 ~ 3 ~ 3

*z is affricated to [d₃] and spirantised to [ʒ]. Although [ʒ] has wider incidence and as such this shape could have been reconstructed, we reconstruct *z from which all the alternatives can develop in the given environment. [z] in C.S. 109 is actually before [u] where [i] changed to [u] having assimilated features of the labial consonant in the environment.

c.s. 25 PN *l

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 147	l ~ l ~ l ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 149	l ~ (-) ~ l ~ (-) ~ (s)
C.S. 148	l ~ (-) ~ l ~ l ~ (-)
C.S. 146	l ~ l ~ l ~ l ~ n
C.S. 151	l ~ l ~ (-) ~ (-) ~ n
C.S. 154	l ~ l ~ l ~ l ~ r

The c.s. is mainly of identical phonetic shape therefore *l is reconstructed. In 5, [r] is in free variation with [l].

c.s. 26 PN *lh

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 152	l ~ l ~ (-) ~ j ~ (-)
C.S. 48	l ~ l ~ l ~ η ^w ~ (-)
C.S. 153	w ~ l ~ l ~ l ~ r

*lh, a lenis alveolar approximant is reconstructed here to account for the differences in the c.s.. [r] is in free variation with [l] in 5. *lh is chosen over *w (η^w) and [l] because it is a weak segment and can easily develop into [w] in 1 (C.S. 153) or into [j] in 4 (C.S. 152).

5.4.3 Palatals

c.s. 27 PN *c

	1	2	3	4	5
C.S. 40	tʃ	ts	ʃ	ʃ	ʃ
C.S. 42	tʃ	ts	s	t	(-)
C.S. 41	tʃ	ts	ʃ	tʃ	k
C.S. 127	tʃ	ts	ʃ	tʃ	(-)
C.S. 44	tʃ	ts	ʃ	tʃ	tʃ
C.S. 128	tʃ	ts	ʃ	(-)	(-)

In this c.s. the correspondences are of regular phonetic shape in most of the languages. We reconstruct *c, a voiceless palatal plosive to account for all the varied shapes. *c is fronted to palato-alveolar place and is affricated in 1; fronted to alveolar place and is affricated in 2; fronted to alveolar/palato-alveolar place and spirantised in 3; fronted to alveolar/palato-alveolar place, affricated and spirantised in 4 and in 5 it is fronted to palato-alveolar place, affricated and also spirantised to [ʃ]. I have no explanation for the presence of [k] in 5 (C.S. 41), however *c serves as a mid point between stricture point for [ts] and [k] along the roof of the mouth. Also *ts and *k have been reconstructed in c.s. 28 and 31 respectively and so cannot be reconstructed here again.

c.s. 28 PN *ts

	1	2	3	4	5
C.S. 132	ʃ	ts	(-)	(-)	(-)
C.S. 43	ʃ	ts	ʃ	tʃ	tʃ
C.S. 131	ʃ	ts	(-)	ʃ	(-)
C.S. 99	t	t	kʲ	kʲ	(-)

This c.s. differs from c.s. 27 only in the fact that spirantisation, not affrication has taken place in 1. *ts is reconstructed here to match *c in c.s. 27 since both have stop elements and have alveolar and palato-alveolar reflexes. In 4 and 5 *ts is spirantised

and palatalised simultaneously as observed in the change of manner (to fricative) and place of articulation (to palatal) (see C.S.43). These processes are blocked when nasalisation has taken place (see C.S.99). *t and *k, the alternatives to *ts have been reconstructed elsewhere (c.s. 12 and 31) and as such cannot be reconstructed here again. *ts is considered to be the lenis of *c for which there is no voiced counterpart in the overall inventory of consonant sounds in PN.

c.s. 29 PN *j

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 170	j~	j~	j~	3~	(-)
C.S. 54	j~	j~	j~	j~	(-)
C.S. 163	j~	j~	j~	(-)	j~
C.S. 218	(-)	(-)	j~	(-)	j~
C.S. 164	(-)	(-)	j~	j~	j~
C.S. 55	j~	j~	j~	(-)	(-)
C.S. 168	j~	j~	j~	j~	(-)
C.S. 53	j~	j~	j~	j~	j~

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape therefore *j is reconstructed. [ʒ] in C.S. 170 is considered to be a sporadic development in 4. This c.s. excludes the environment before nasalised vowels as observed in c.s. 31 where [ɲ] is realised phonetically.

c.s. 30 PN *ɲ

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 176	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	(-)
C.S. 175	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~
C.S. 62	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~
C.S. 63	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~	(-)
C.S. 174	ɲ~	ɲ~	(-)	(-)	(-)
C.S. 61	ɲ~	ɲ~	(-)	(-)	(-)

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape therefore *ɲ is reconstructed here.

c.s. 31 PN *ɲ

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 59.	j~	j~	ɲ~	(-)~	(-)~
C.S. 58	ɲ~	j~	ɲ~	ɲ~	-j
C.S. 60	j~	j~	ɲ~	ɲ~	ɲ~

*ɲ is reconstructed here because nasalisation in PN is predictable. It is therefore not a case of nasalisation of *j before a significantly nasalised vowel. I postulate sporadic loss of nasalisation in those languages where [j] is attested because *ɲ has developed regularly in all the languages in c.s.30.

5.4.4 Velars

c.s. 32 PN *k

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 185	k~	k~	k~	k~	(-)~
C.S. 186	k~	k~	(-)~	k~	(-)~
C.S. 66	k~	k~	k~	k~	(-)~
C.S. 80	(-)~	(-)~	k~	k~	k~
C.S. 184	k~	k~	k~	k~	k~
C.S. 180	k~	k~	(-)~	k~	(-)~
C.S. 28	k~	k~	k~	k~	k~

This c.s. excludes the environment before nasalised segment as found in c.s. 33. In this c.s., *k is reconstructed because all the languages have developed [k] as reflexes.

c.s. 33 PN *k/-V̄

	1~	2~	3~	4~	5
C.S. 179	k~	k~	kɳ~	kɳ~	(-)~
C.S. 183.	k~	k~	kɳ~	kɳ~	(-)~
C.S. 181	k~	k~	kɳ~	(-)~	k~
C.S. 182	k~	k~	kɳ~	kɳ~	k~

This c.s. excludes the environment before nasalised [ɪ] as found in c.s. 34. *k is [kɳ], a nasally released voiceless velar plosive before nasalised segment. *k and *kɳ are

the alternatives here. *k, reconstructed in c.s. 32 is again reconstructed but under a different environment i.e. -V̄. In 3 and 4 [kŋ] is [k] nasally released, derived from *CVNV. Reconstruction of *kŋ suggests nasal plosion at the Proto-level whereas the present reconstruction explains plosion from *CVNV.

c.s. 34 PN *k/-iN

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 242	tʃ ~ s ~ kŋ ~ t ~ kʲ
C.S. 187	k ~ tʃ ~ kŋ ~ kŋ ~ (-)
C.S. 189	k ~ tʃ ~ tʃ ~ kŋ ~ (-)
C.S. 188	k ~ tʃ ~ tʃ ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 65	k ~ k ~ (-) ~ tʃ ~ tʃ
C.S. 39	ts ~ s ~ s ~ tʃ ~ kʲ

*k is fronted and affricated in this c.s. These processes are blocked where nasalization has occurred. In 5 *k is sometimes just palatalised. *k is reconstructed here since the various reflexes are easily explained in environment. [s] is an instance if spirantised *k.

c.s. 35 PN *k

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 69	g ~ g ~ g ~ g ~ k
C.S. 195	g ~ g ~ (-) ~ (-) ~ k

The alternatives are *k and *g. Although there are many more occurrences of [g] than of [k], *k is reconstructed because of the directionality or naturalness of certain sound changes such as voiceless sounds becoming voiced intervocalically, consonants becoming palatalised before front vowels than the reverse (C.S. 195). *k is therefore assumed to have undergone voicing intervocalically in 1 and 2 in C.S. 69 *k occurs in word initial position, one which facilitates voicing.

c.s.36 PN *kh

	1- 2 - 3 - 4 - 5
C.S. 208	σ - σ - kŋ - ŋ ^h - k

*kh is reconstructed because of the varied reflexes. *kh is nasally released and undergoes a change to [w] phonetically realised as [ŋ^h]. In 5 it is hardened to [k].

c.s. 37 PN *g

	1- 2 - 3 - 4 - 5
C.S. 226	(-) ~(-) ~ g ~ g ~ g
C.S. 239	g ~ g ~ (-) ~(-) ~ g
C.S. 197	g ~ g ~ (-) ~(-) ~ (-)
C.S. 193	g ~ g ~ (-) ~(-) ~ g

*g is reconstructed here since the reflexes are of identical phonetic shape. It excludes the environment before $\bar{V}$ as in c.s. 38 and before i(V) as in c.s. 39.

c.s. 38 PN *g/- $\bar{V}$

	1- 2 - 3 - 4 - 5
C.S. 191	g ~g ~ g ~ gŋ ~ g
C.S. 196	g ~g ~ gŋ ~(-)~(-)
C.S. 68	g ~g ~ gŋ ~(-) ~(-)
C.S. 137	(-)~(-) ~ gŋ ~gŋ ~ g
C.S. 202	g~ g ~ ɲ ~ m ~(-)
C.S. 212	g ~g ~ ɲ ~ (-) ~(-)

*g is nasally released in 3 and 4. It is palatalised as [ɲ] after being nasally released and fronted to [m] in 4 (C.S. 202). Reconstructed *g here is under a different environment i.e. - $\bar{V}$. In 3 and 4 [gŋ] is [g] nasally released, derived from *CVNV. Reconstruction of *gŋ suggests nasal plosion at the Proto-level whereas the present reconstruction explains plosion from a *CVNV. It excludes the environment discussed in c.s. 39.

c.s. 39 PN *g /-i(V)

	1- 2 - 3 - 4 - 5
C.S. 198	g ~dʒ ~g ^j ~g~(-) 'eat'
C.S. 201	g ^j ~ʒ~(-)~g ^j ~(-) 'blood'

*g is reconstructed again here since the various reflexes can be explained in the

prevalent environment i.e. before [i]. The corresponding sounds: [dʒ], a voiced palato-alveolar affricate, [ʒ], a voiced palato-alveolar fricative and [gʲ], a palatalised voiced velar plosive all appear to have developed from *g before [i], the processes being affrication, spirantisation and palatalisation respectively.

c.s. 40 PN *gh

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 82	w ~ w ~ (-) ~ gɾj ~ (-)
C.S. 121	v ~ v ~ w ~ (-) ~ (-)

A lenis parent is reconstructed here because of the varied reflexes: [v], [w] and [gɾj]. *gh developed into [v] and [w] and is hardened to [g] which is nasally released.

5.4.5 Labial-velar

c.s. 41 PN *kp

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 203	kp ~ kp ~ (-) ~ kp ~ (-)
C.S. 204	kp ~ kp ~ kp ~ kp ~ kp
C.S. 205	kp ~ kp ~ kp ~ (-) ~ (-)

*kp is reconstructed since the c.s. is of identical phonetic shape.

c.s. 42 PN *kp

	1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 71	kp ~ kp ~ k ~ k ~ kp
C.S. 72	kp ~ kp ~ kp̄j̄m̄ ~ kp̄j̄m̄ ~ (-)

*kp reconstructed is nasally released as [kp̄j̄m̄] in 3 and 4 (C.S. 72). It is simplified to [k] in 3 and 4 (C.S. 71) where the labial element is dropped. This is considered a sporadic development since the process is not observed with [kp] elsewhere. A similar weakening of the articulation from double to single place is observed in [gbh] (see c.s. 45 and 46)

c.s. 43 PN *gb

1 ~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5

C.S. 73.	gb~gb ~ gb ~ gb ~ gb
C.S. 210	gb~gb ~ (-) ~ (-) ~ gb
C.S. 208	gb~gb ~ gb ~ gb ~ gb

*gb, voiced labial-velar plosive is reconstructed given that there is no change in the developments.

c.s. 44 PN *gbh

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 74	g ~ g ~ b ~ b ~ (-)
C.S. 75	g ~ g ~ b ~ b ~ (-)
C.S. 194	g ~ g ~ gb ~ (-) ~ (-)
C.S. 76	g ~ g ~ b ~ w ~ b
C.S. 199	g ~ d ₃ ~ b ~ b ~ b

*gbh is also reconstructed here since it has varied reflexes: [gb] [g],[b],[w],[d₃] and [b] and obviously has all the features found in the reflexes i.e. plosion, labial and velar places of articulation. Lenis feature is reconstructed here to account for the development of the affricate and implosive reflexes. *gbh loses either its labial or velar / lenis feature. The labial in 1 and 2, the velar in 3, 4 and 5. In C.S. 199, [d₃] is palatalised /g/ in 2.

C.S. 88 gb ~g ~ b ~w ~ b

A similar process is observed in C.S. 88 where the velar feature is lost in 2, 3, and 4 and the labial feature is lost in 5. In 1 only is loss of suction is found.

c.s. 45 PN*gbh?

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 216	gb~gb~(-)~w ~ (-)

The alternatives here are [gb] and [w]. *gb has been reconstructed in c.s. 43 and *w in c.s. 47/48. The reconstruction is tentative since only one item supports it. Secondly, a lenis segment it is reconstructed to account for the hardened to [gb] in 1 and 2 and weakening to [w] in 3 and 4.

c.s. 46 PN *gbh /-i(V)

	1	2	3	4	5
C.S. 215	g ^j	~ gb	~ b ^j	~ b ^j	~ j
C.S. 214	gb/b	~ b	~ (-)	~ b ^j	~ (-)
C.S. 213	gb	~ b	~ b	~ b	~ (-)
C.S. 233	b	~ b	~ gb	~ (-)	~ (-)

*gbh here loses its velar and lenis elements possibly as a result of the following vowel which palatalises reflex as observed in 1,3, and 4. Reflex [j] is explained as the palatal off glide which is retained when [gbh] is lost in 5 (C.S. 215).

c.s. 47 PN* w

	1	2	3	4	5
C.S. 172	w	~ w	~ w ^j	~ w ^j	~ (-)
C.S. 81	w	~ w	~ w	~ w	~ w
C.S. 78	w	~ w	~ w	~ w	~ w
C.S. 77	w	~ w	~ w	~ w	~ w
C.S. 79	w	~ w	~ w	~ w	~ (-)
C.S. 217	w	~ w	~ w	~ w	~ m
C.S. 219	w	~ w	~ w	~ w	~ b

This c.s. excludes the environment before a nasal segment (c.s. 49). *w is reconstructed as the c.s. is of identical phonetic shape. [w^j] is palatalised *w (C.S. 172). [b] in 5 (C.S. 219) is introduced to strengthen [w] before a close rounded vowel.

c.s. 48 PN *w /-V̄

	1	2	3	4	5
C.S. 220	w	~ w	~ (-)	~ (-)	~ g
C.S. 231	ŋ ^w	~ (-)	~ (-)	~ m	~ (-)
C.S. 221	ŋ ^w	~ ŋ ^w	~ ŋ ^w	~ ŋ ^w	~ m

*w is reconstructed here and considered nasalised as [ŋ^w] before V̄. [m] in 4 (C.S. 221) and 5 (C.S. 231) is nasalised *w which has lost its velar element and so surfaces as a bilabial nasal before V̄. [g] may also have been introduced in 5 (C.S. 220) to strengthen the [w].

c.s. 49 PN *wh

	1~ 2 ~ 3 ~ 4 ~ 5
C.S. 57	j ~j ~ w ^J ~w ^J ~(-)
C.S. 56	j ~j ~ w ^J ~w ^J ~(-)
C.S. 171	j ~j ~ w ^J ~ w ^J ~(-)

*wh, a lenis labial-velar approximant is reconstructed here since it is unlikely to have [w^J] develop from *j before front vowels. *wh hardened to [w] which is palatalised. [j] in 1 and 2 is assumed to be the palatal off glide through loss of the [w].

5.5 PN Reconstructions

The numbering here is not serial because items have been selected from Volume Two where the numbering is serial. The stem initial consonants are considered in the ordering of the reconstructed items. Those with labial sounds are listed first followed by those with alveolar sounds, the palatal, the velar and finally the labial-velar sounds.

5.5.1 Labial

C.S. 90

	PN *ə-mɪ		'oil'
1.	Nupe	e-mí	
2.	Nupe Tako	(inzini)	
3.	Gwari	ə-mí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɔ-mí	
5.	Gade	(bà-nɪ)	
	PEB *a-ŋ ^w ɛ		'oil'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ŋ ^w ɛ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ŋ ^w ɛ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ŋ ^w ɛ	

PE. A-bhidhi (l-) 'oil' (EL. C.S. 8)

C.S. 2

	PN *miNi		'swallow'
1.	Nupe	jī	/ji/
2.	Nupe Tako	jī	/ji/

- | | | |
|----|-------------|------|
| 3. | Gwari | mí |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | mí |
| 5. | Gade | munɪ |

PEB *mune

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | mú |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | múnè |
| 8. | Ètúnọ (Igarra) | múné |

'swallow'

PE *dh i.e. C' of the item has reflex [m] in Ghotuo 'take': mu 'take'+ lɦɦɦ 'swallow' and it is obviously cognate with not just PN and PEB but with all other reconstructions presented below.

PYIG. m'i 'swallow' (AK. C.S. 61)

PE. dhɔNɪ 'swallow' (EL. C.S. 67) cf. Ebira Okene [dɔ] 'take' / [si] 'take'

PB. -min- 'swallow' (Gt. C.S. 1311)

PBK. mh-dh 'swallow' (PBK. 36)

PI. mènì 'swallow' (PBK. 36)

C.S. 1

PN *mɔ

'give birth'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------------------|----------------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | ma | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | mɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | bimá | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | mabí | < ma + efi
bear + child |
| 5. | Gade | m ^w ɔ | |

PEB *ma

'give birth'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|----------------------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | muzi | < ma + ozi
bear + child |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | mozi | < ma + ozi
bear + child |
| 8. | Ètúnọ (Igarra) | ma | |

PYIG. bi 'give birth' (AK. C.S. 1)

cf. Yoruba bimɔ 'give birth (to a child)'

PE. ɓia 'give birth, bear (child)' (EL. C.S. 15)

PB. biád 'bear child' (Gt. C.S. 136)

Two morphemes are observed in the 3 and 4: [ebi] 'child' and [ma] 'to bear'. In the combined forms the verbal morpheme comes after the noun 'child' in 3. Akinkugbe (1978) noted that the PYIG noun [ɔmɔ] is a deverbal noun which verb stems no longer exist having observed the Tiv and Kambari cognate verb stems:

Tiv. māl 'offspring' < māl 'give birth to, beget' (Hoffmann)

C. Kambari mà(tsā) 'bear (child, fruit), beget' (Hoffmann)

A similar situation is evident in Gwari. *ma is reconstructed in PEB as evident in 9 since 7 and 8 forms are derived from two morphemes.

C.S. 91

	PN *mætɪəN		'laugh v.'
1.	Nupe	mátsa	
2.	Nupe Tako	mótsɔ	
3.	Gwari	masā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	matsā	
5.	Gade	(tʃɪ tùm*ɔ)	

	PEB *ɲɪ (rdl.)		'laugh v.'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɲíɲí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɲúɲí	
8.	Ètunɔ (Igarra)	ɲúɲí	

PYIG rí /lɪ 'laugh' (AK. C.S. 172)

PE. ghɪə (gbəi?) (EL. C.S. 92)

C.S. 93

	PN *mɛNdɛN		'hunger n.'
1.	Nupe	mādā	
2.	Nupe Tako	mɔdɔ	
3.	Gwari	(mĩ kɛŋŋ)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(mĩ ŋwú)	
5.	Gade	ɲi-mé	

PEB *u- ŋwɛ 'hunger (n.)'

- | | | |
|----|-----------------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-ŋwe |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-ŋwe |
| 8. | Etunṣo (Igarra) | u-ŋwe |

PYIG. e-bi 'hunger' (AK. C.S. 3)

C.S. 92

		PN *mɔ	
			'sweet, (tasty)'
1.	Nupe	mā	
2.	Nupe Tako	mɔ	
3.	Gwari	(ndá)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(dá)	
5.	Gade	munu	
		PEB *jine	
			'sweet (tasty)'
6.	Ebira Okene	hiné	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hiné	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	jine	

C.S. 3

		PN *ɔ-pa	
			'skin'
1.	Nupe	e-pa	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-pa	
3.	Gwari	ɔ-pa	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-pa	
5.	Gade	gù-pùtá	
		PEB *u-kpa	
			'skin'
6.	Ebira Okene	ú-péŋ*ù	< upa + eŋu skin + body or 'hide of body'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-kpáhá	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	u-pá	

The form in 6 is contracted from [u-pa] 'skin' and [eŋu] 'body' (C.S. 119)

PYIG. a-g'ɔ 'skin, hide' (AK. C.S. 329)

PE. U-phɪNa (I-) 'skin' (EL. C.S. 178)

cf. Ghotuo a) /yofíá/ 'skin (of fruit, etc.) is a development from PE 'skin' in the preceding line.

b) /é-kpà/ 'skin, bag'

C.S. 85

		PN *pa	
			'remember'
1.	Nupe	pa	

- | | | |
|----|-------------|-------------|
| 2. | Nupe Tako | pa |
| 3. | Gwari | pá |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (mukpéyelo) |
| 5. | Gade | (tē) |

PEB *tamaji

- | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | támái |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | támaji |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | támái |

'remember'

C.S. 84

PN *pa

- | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | pa |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | pa |
| 3. | Gwari | pa |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | pa |
| 5. | Gade | (k ^j ε) |

'to tie (rope)'

PEB *su

- | | | |
|----|----------------|----|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | sú |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | sú |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | sú |

'to tie (rope)'

PYIG so 'tie (rope, animal etc) (AK. C.S. 136)

PE fadhı 'tie (bundle); make (rope) (EL. C.S. 77)

C.S. 232

PN* pati

- | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | páti |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | páti |
| 3. | Gwari | (opé) |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (kukù) |
| 5. | Gade | (rùgwò) |

'mountain'

PEB *a-tabá

- | | | |
|----|----------------|-----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ataba |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | àtàbà |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | (iresúfá) |

'mountain'

C.S. 4

PN *po

- | | | |
|----|-----------|----|
| 1. | Nupe | po |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | po |

'roast'

3.	Gwari	pó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	pó	
5.	Gade	(sɔ)	
	PEB *fu		'roast'
6.	Ebira Okene	hũ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hũ	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	fù	

PYIG. sũ 'roast (in fire)' (AK. C.S. 143)
 PE. ɓN 'roast' (EL. C.S. 183)

C.S. 5

	PN *pitia		'leg'
1.	Nupe	bitʃi	
2.	Nupe Tako	bitsi	
3.	Gwari	_____	
4.	Gwari Yamma	-putà	
5.	Gade	(gĩ-né)	
	PEB *a-fu		'leg'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-hũ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-hũ	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	a-fù	

PYIG. ɔ-sē (ε-) 'foot, leg' (AK. C.S. 40)
 Ilaje ε-he 'foot, leg' cf. Ebira Okene and Kwotto forms.
 Ijumu ɔ-hi 'foot, leg' " " " " " " " "

C.S. 6

	PN *pitie		'chicken (domestic fowl)'
1.	Nupe	bife	
2.	Nupe Tako	(a)-bitse	
3.	Gwari	pusé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	pusé (lug ^{wé})	
5.	Gade	(gù-tenè)	
	PEB *V-ʃiue		'chicken (domestic fowl)'
6.	Ebira Okene	á-ɔhwé	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-úhè	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	à-ufé	

The vowel cluster situation noticeable in the PEB forms are derived from reduction of the reduplicated stems as observable in 7. in C.S. 11 The Cⁱ of the reduplicated stem is deleted thus generating the vowel cluster (cf. Edoid)

PYIG. a-diwe 'chicken, fowl' (AK. C.S. 45)

PE. O- khokho (I-) 'chicken (domestic fowl)' (EL. C.S. 122)

C.S. 7

PN *ɔ-pja		
1.	Nupe	e-ts ^w a
2.	Nupe Tako	a-tso
3.	Gwari	ɔ-pja
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-pja
5.	Gade	ù-pja

'moon'

PEB *u-fue		
6.	Ebira Okene	u-hwé
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-h ^w é the
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-fe

'moon'

PYIG. -cù kpá 'moon' (AK. C.S. 237a)

Yoruba o-ju kpa 'moon'

Igala u-pja 'moon'

C.S. 67

PN *pia		
1.	Nupe	(kã)
2.	Nupe Tako	(ko)
3.	Gwari	pí (ja)
4.	Gwari Yamma	pí
5.	Gade	tse

'wring (clothes)'

PEB *kama		
6.	Ebira Okene	kámã
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(pìri)
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kámã

'wring (clothes)'

PYIG. fū 'wring (clothes), squeeze' (AK. C.S. 73)

PE. mi 'wring (clothes)' (EL. C.S. 144)

C.S. 9

PN *e-bi		
1.	Nupe	e-bi

'kolanut'

2.	Nupe Tako	e-bi	
3.	Gwari	(g ^w órò)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(g ^w órò)	
5.	Gade	(górò)	
		PEB *irɛ-bu	'kolanut'
6.	Ebira Okene	irɛ-vu	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(oó-bi)	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	irɛ-vu	

The forms in 3-5 are borrowed from Hausa. The forms in 1 and 2 are cognate with PEB cf. Yoruba o-bi 'kolanut' and the PEB forms.

C.S. 10

		PN *V-ba-		'husband'
1.	Nupe	è-ba		
2.	Nupe Tako	i-bá		
3.	Gwari	ɔ-bá		
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-bá		
5.	Gade	ù-bana		
		PEB *ɔ-ba		'husband'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-vá		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-bá		
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-vá		

PYIG. ɔ-kɔ 'husband (male)' (AK. C.S. 283)

PE. O-chi (I-) 'man, male' (EL. C.S. 44)

C.S. 11

		PN * bu-		'be white'
1.	Nupe	bókù		
2.	Nupe Tako	bókù		
3.	Gwari	bùibùí < bu (+i)		
4.	Gwari Yamma	bùb ^w i < bu (+i)		
5.	Gade	(zírè)		
		PEB *ɔ-bu		'be white'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-vúɔvu ɔ-vu + (ɔvu)		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔɔ-bu		
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-vuɔvu ɔ-vu + (ɔvu)		

A suffix -i often occurs in 3 and 4 after the stem.

PYIG.	-fù	'be white (rdl.)'	(AK. C.S. 74)
PE.	puNa	'be white'	(EL. C.S. 173)
PWS.	pù-	'weiss'	(West. P. 279; Yor. And Okp.)

C.S. 13

PN *gu-ba			'two'
1.	Nupe	gubà	
2.	Nupe Tako	gubà	
3.	Gwari	m-bà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	m-bà	
5.	Gade	i-va	
PEB *e-ba			'two'
6.	Ebira Okene	è:va	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-ba	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	è-va	

PYIG.	è-ji	'two'	(AK. C.S. 239)
PE.	i-va	'two'	(EL. C.S. 194)
PWS.	-gi (-gi)	'zwei'	(West. p. 221; Yor. Ig.)

1 and 2 have a CV prefix 'gu-' while 3 and 4 each have a syllabic nasal [m] a prefix. A CV-prefix is therefore reconstructed to show its existence in PN.

C.S. 87

PN *ba			'count'
1.	Nupe	bà	
2.	Nupe Tako	bà	
3.	Gwari	bà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bà	
5.	Gade	(zà)	
PEB *-ka			'count'
6.	Ebira Okene	kà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(zi)kà	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	kã	

The PEB stem *ka, is related to the PYIG stem for 'count' and 'recount'

PYIG ka 'count' (AK. C.S. 275)
 cf. kà 'recount, tell, say, gossip' (AK. C.S. 276)
 PWS. bà, bàl- 'sahien' (West. p. 204)?

C.S. 86

	PN *a-biə		'knife'
1.	Nupe	e-bi	
2.	Nupe Tako	è-bi	
3.	Gwari	a-be	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-be	
5.	Gade	u-ba	
	PEB *u-fuə		'knife'
6.	Ebira Okene	ù-h"ə	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-hə	
8.	Ètunə (Igarra)	ù-fə	

PYIG. ʒ-bɛ 'knife' (AK. C.S. 6a)

C.S. 16

	PN *CV-biNi-		'feaces'
1.	Nupe	e-bi	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-bi	
3.	Gwari	a-mʲi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-mʲi	
5.	Gade	ti-mi	
	PEB *e-mi		'feaces'
6.	Ebira Okene	(è-hè)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-mī	
8.	Ètunə (Igarra)	e-mī	

The form in 6 [èhè] is considered an innovation (cf. [èheɹi] 'urine', [eɹi] 'water') since the other form for 'feaces', [emi] is cognate with PYIG and PWS.

cf Cama, a-bi, bi 'excrement' (Maddieson 1974)
 PYIG. V-b'V > PYOR i-wī 'feaces, excrement' (AK. C.S. 51)
 PWS. (m)-bi, (m)-bin - 'kot' (West. p. 209; Yor.)
 Pl. bini 'defecate, buttocks' (PBK11)

PB. -b['excreta'	(Gl. C.S. 135)
pBC. -biŋ (a-) 'excrements'	(DeW. p. 59)
PE. A-phɛNi 'urine'	(AK. C.S. 177)

C.S. 50

	PN *		'dog'
1.	Nupe	(e-ŋigi)	
2.	Nupe Tako	(i-ŋi)	
3.	Gwari	à-muí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-mui	
5.	Gade	(gɔ-biki)	
	PEB *ire-zi		'dog'
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-zi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(a-bjá)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ire-zi	

The Ebira Kwotto form [abjá] is suspected to be cognate with Yoruba [adʒá]

'dog'. This implies that two forms for 'dog' exist side by side in Ebiroid as in PN.

PE A-bhua 'dog' (EL. C.S. 12)

C.S. 12

	PN *(a)-buo		'be rotten'
1.	Nupe	vò	
2.	Nupe Tako	vò	
3.	Gwari	b*ò	
4.	Gwari Yamma	à-b*ò	
5.	Gade	vù	
	PEB *bu		'be rotten'
6.	Ebira Okene	vù	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	bù	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	vù	

PYIG. bu 'become mouldy, rotten'	(AK. p.s 20)
PI. buru 'become rotten'	(Wil.)
PB. -bòd- 'become rotten'	(Gl. C.S. 153)
PE. vuaNi 'stink'	(EL. C.S. 201)
PWS. buó 'faulen'	(West. p.213)

C.S. 144

	PN *(e)-bhu-		'dust'
1.	Nupe	ruŋmgbá	
2.	Nupe Tako	è-rúŋmgbá	
3.	Gwari	a-bútukú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bùrekete	
5.	Gade	(gu-riri)	
	PEB *e-dudu		'dust'
6.	Ebira Okene	è-dúdù	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(è-bútù)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	è-dúdù	

PE. -fu- 'sand, dust' (EL. C.S. 19)

C.S. 165

	PN *V-bhua		'nose'
1.	Nupe	(è-jè)	
2.	Nupe Tako	(i-jè)	
3.	Gwari	ù-bwà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-bwa	
5.	Gade	gu-rúfè	
	PEB *a-ji		'nose'
6.	Ebira Okene	ǎ-h'j ₁	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-h ₁	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	à-fíj ₁	

PYIG. i-ŋmu

'nose'

(AK. C.S. 369)

PE. I-chuaNi; -chuveNi (A-)

'nose'

(EL. C.S.49)

PS. b̥u

'Loch, Nasenloch'

(West. p. 123no. 62; Yor.)

PWS. -nwu- (ta), -nyu- (ta)

'Nase'

(West. pp. 272-3; Yor. and Ig.)

PLN. i-mi

'nose'

(Wil.)

C.S. 238

	PN *bi6i		'small'
1.	Nupe	(gbàgbà)	
2.	Nupe Tako	(tʃíndʒi)	
3.	Gwari	bi6i	
4.	Gwari Yamma	biri	
5.	Gade	bibi	
	PEB *kiiki		'small'

- | | |
|-------------------|------|
| 6. Ebira Okene | kiki |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | --- |
| 8. Etuno (Igarra) | --- |

C.S. 14

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|-----------|
| | PN *ri-be | | 'breasts' |
| 1. | Nupe | e-be | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | i-be | |
| 3. | Gwari | bebe | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bebe | |
| 5. | Gade | ri-batu | |

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|-----------|
| | PEB *ire-ba | | 'breasts' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ire-va | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ire-ba | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ire-va | |

PYIG. e-na /e-ya/ 'breast' (AK. C.S. 270)

C.S. 15

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-----|--------|
| | PN *6e | | 'come' |
| 1. | Nupe | be | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | be | |
| 3. | Gwari | be | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (3) | |
| 5. | Gade | be | |

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|--------|
| | PEB *be | | 'come' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ve | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | be | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ve | |

cf. Ghotuo vare 'come'

PYIG b'a 'come' (AK. C.S. 29)

cf. Tiv va 'come' (Arm. b)

Cama. ba /ba/ 'come' (Maddieson, 1974)

PLN. bia 'come' (Wil. 2)

PVP. b'a 'come' (St. p.5)

PWS. bia, ba 'kommen' (West. p. 209; Yor. n.c.)

C.S. 89

- | | | | |
|----|--------|----|-------------------------|
| | PN *6a | | 'break (pot, calabash)' |
| 1. | Nupe | ba | |

2.	Nupe Tako	(là)	
3.	Gwari	bája	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(tʃíkà)	
	PEB *tiaka		'break (pot, calabash)'
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃàkà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃàkà	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	sàkà	

Cf. Yoruba là 'split'

PYIG. f5 'break (pot, calabash etc.)' (AK. C.S. 67)

C.S. 18

	PN *fiN-		'sweep'
1.	Nupe	fī	
2.	Nupe Tako	fī	
3.	Gwari	fī	
4.	Gwari Yamma	fībà	
5.	Gade	(kʷu)	
	PEB *ʃi		'sweep'
6.	Ebira Okene	hī	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hī	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	ʃi	

PYIG. gbá 'sweep' (AK. C.S. 357)

PWS. kùà, kùàlì 'fegen, bursten' (West. p. 241)

C.S. 19

	PN *CV -fiNit-		'leaf'
1.	Nupe	finī ~ (fere)	
2.	Nupe Tako	finī	
3.	Gwari	fintolo	
4.	Gwari Yamma	fünt.¹e	
5.	Gade	gu-fe	
	PEB *a-bi		'leaf'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-vi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(a-surukpá)	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	a-vi'	

PYIG e-we (i-) 'leaf' (AK. C.S. 41)
 PE U-fu 'leaf' (EL. C.S. 16)

C.S. 17

	PN *fu		'fly'
1.	Nupe	fù	
2.	Nupe Tako	fù	
3.	Gwari	(ja)fù	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(wata)fù	
5.	Gade	furu	
	PEB *jira	.	'fly'
6.	Ebira Okene	hirà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hirà	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	jirà	

PYIG fò 'fly, jump' (AK. C.S. 70) cf. Yor. sira 'hurry up'
 PS. pl. 'fliegen' (West. p. 180 no. 264a; Yor. p.c.)

C.S. 229

	PN *fu		'jump'
1.	Nupe	fù	
2.	Nupe Tako	fù	
3.	Gwari	(jàgà)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(wátafù)	
5.	Gade	furu	
	PEB *dʒi		'jump'
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒiriga	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	---	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	dʒi	

C.S. 237

	PN *fedu		'sit down'
1.	Nupe	fédù	
2.	Nupe Tako	fédù	
3.	Gwari	àsàsè	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(jà`so)	
5.	Gade	(dèndè)	
	PEB *jatu		'sit down'
6.	Ebira Okene	jaátù	

7. Ebira Kwotto jatù
8. Etunọ (Igarra) já:tò

C.S. 20

	PN *phiNi		'drink'
1.	Nupe	fi	
2.	Nupe Tako	fi	
3.	Gwari	si(ji)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	si	
5.	Gade	(wu)	
	PEB *fu		'drink'
6.	Ebira Okene	hú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	fú	

PYIG. ɲmū 'drink' (AK. C.S. 370)

PYIS. mu 'drink' (AK. C.S. 370)

PE. ɗa 'to drink (alcohol)' (EL. C.S. 72)

A-yen 'drink (alcoholic)' (EL. C.S. 205)

yɔNu drink '(water)' (EL. C.S. 207)

PB. -mú- 'drink' (Gt. C.S. 1332)

PWS. ni,nu,niu,niua 'trinken' (West. p. 269)

C.S. 21

	PN *-phe		'wind'
1.	Nupe	e-fè	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-fè	
3.	Gwari	ó-sé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-se	
5.	Gade	a-fu	
	PEB *a-fe		'wind'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-hi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-si ~ (afi)	

PYIG. V-fu 'wind' (AK. C.S. 71)

PE. O-fedh- 'wind' (EL. C.S. 78)

PB. -pèèpè 'wind' (Gt. C.S. 1491)

-pépò 'wind' (Gt. C.S. 1493)

PWS. -pap-, -pep- 'wind' (West. p. 274, Yor.)
 Pl. e-féfu 'wind' (Wil.)

C.S. 22

PN * -phu

'bee'

1. Nupe e-fú
2. Nupe Tako è-fú
3. Gwari ð-su
4. Gwari Yamma ð-su
5. Gade (fité)

PEB *e-fu

'bee'

6. Ebira Okene e-hú
7. Ebira Kwotto e-hú
8. Ètunọ (Igarra) e-fú

PYIS. oñi /oyi/ 'bee' (AK. C.S. 264)

PB. -júki, -júkì 'bee, honey' (Gl. C.S. 962)

PB. -jiki, -jiki 'bee' (Gl. C.S. 2003)

PWS -mul 'Biene' (West. p. 259; yor).

C.S. 37

PN * tia

'blow (of wind)'

1. Nupe (ts^wa)
2. Nupe Tako (tsó)
3. Gwari sətʃi
4. Gwari Yamma ə-sepia
5. Gade à-fu

PEB * tu

'blow (of wind)'

6. Ebira Okene tú
7. Ebira Kwotto tú
8. Ètunọ (Igarra) tú

PYIG. fé 'blow (of wind, with mouth)' (AK. C.S. 63)

PE. phuphu 'blow (with mouth)' (EL. C.S. 179)

C.S. 27

PN *a-fakuN

'grinding stone'

1. Nupe tákù
2. Nupe Tako tákù
3. Gwari a-tá

- | | | | | |
|-------------------|--------------------|-------------------|--|------------------|
| 4. Gwari Yamma | taŋ ^w ū | | | |
| 5. Gade | (rū-gwojī) | | | |
| | PEB | * ire -t ɔku- | | 'grinding stone' |
| 6. Ebira Okene | ire-t ɔkwɔsɛ | < ireta + ku + sa | | 'stone' 'grind' |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | ɛ -tɔkusá | < ireta + ku | | 'stone' 'grind' |
| 8. Etunḡ (Igarra) | ire - t ɔkw ai | < ireta + ku + ai | | 'stone' 'grind' |

This word has been formed from two morphemes: stone and grind.

The forms in 5,6,7, and 8 are formed from two different nouns . For the components of the forms in 5,6,7, and 8 (see C.S. 28 'stone' and C.S. 69 'grind').

In Ebiroid, [iretɔkwɔsɛ] is for grinding = 'pepper, beans' while [iretɔkwai] is for grinding 'flour'

PYIG. V-lɔ 'grind' (AK. C.S. 208)

Cf. Yoruba gū 'grind to powder'

C.S. 29

- | | | | | |
|----|----------------|-----------|--------|---------|
| | PN | * gu-ta | | 'three' |
| 1. | Nupe | gútá | | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | gútá | | |
| 3. | Gwari | ñ-tá | | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | n-tʃiá | /-tia/ | |
| 5. | Gade | ta | | |
| | | PEB *ɛ-ta | | 'three' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɛɛ-tá | | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɛ-tá | | |
| 8. | Etunḡ (Igarra) | ɛ-tá | | |

PYIG. ɛ-ta 'three' (AK. C.S. 80)

PE. ɪ-chaGɪ 'three' (EL. C.S. 37)

PJ. tat (i-) 'three' (Sh. pp. 50-1)

PB. -tátú 'three' (Gt. C.S. 1689)

C.S. 96

PN *CV-tiuko

'head'

1.	Nupe	e-ti	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ti	
3.	Gwari	túk'ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	túg'ó	
5.	Gade	ru-tu	
		PEB *ire-su	'head'
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-sú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-sú	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	ìre-sú	

PYIG.	o-d'i	'head' (AK. C.S. 121)
PE.	U-chiamhi (A-)	'head' (EL. C.S. 42)
PB.	-tu	'head' (Gt. C.S. 1808)
PI.	tífi	'head' (Wil.)

C.S.	97		'vomit'
		PN *tu	
1.	Nupe	tu	
2.	Nupe Tako	tú	
3.	Gwari	tu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tú	
5.	Gade	(gwò)	
		PEB *huere	'vomit'
6.	Ebira Okene	hèré	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hwèré	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	(kárènu) v. (irèn) n	

PYIG	sē	'vomit', precipitate' (AK. p.s. 139)
PE.	kpa	'vomit' (EL. C.S. 128)

C.S.	228		'hair'
		PN *V-tiji	
1.	Nupe	tiji	
2.	Nupe Tako	atí	
3.	Gwari	eji, túkwòní	
4.	Gwari Yamma	eji	
5.	Gade	tiji	
		PEB *ε-ji	'hair'
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-í	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-ji	

B. Etunọ (Igarra) ɛ-ji

PYIG. u-rū /ul'ū/ (i-) 'hair' (AK. C.S. 183)
 PE. U-tuN (l-) 'hair' (EL. C.S. 186)

C.S. 23

	PN *CV-tuNukpua		'ear'
1.	Nupe	tukpa	
2.	Nupe Tako	tukpa	
3.	Gwari	ṭnubwà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ṭnubwà	
5.	Gade	gú-tapú	
	PEB *u-tɔkpa		'ear'
6.	Ebira Okene	u-tɔ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-tɔkpá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-tɔ	

PYIG e-ŋ 'ear' (AK. C.S. 88)
 PE. ghU-choGi 'ear' (EL. C.S. 45)
 PB -tūi 'ear' (Meeussen, 1973)
 PBC -tuŋ (ku-/a-) (Dew. p. 56)
 PLN ní-lni 'ear' (PBK, 7)

C.S. 24

	PN * tuNu (rdl).		'send'
1.	Nupe	tū	
2.	Nupe Tako	tū	
3.	Gwari	ṭnūtnú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ṭnutnú	
5.	Gade	(ne)	
	PEB *tu		'send'
6.	Ebira Okene	tútu	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tu(ɔ)	

PYOR. rā 'send (someone to do something)' (AK. C.S. 180)
 PE. ghia, jhia 'send (someone to do something)' (EL. C.S. 87)
 PB. tūm- 'send' (Gt. C.S. 1813).
 PWS. tūm- 'arbeiten, (Zur Arbeit) schicken' (West. pp. 292-3)

C.S. 25

PN *tuNu- (rdl.)		
1.	Nupe	tütünti
2.	Nupe Tako	tutimpti
3.	Gwari	(fidakulú)
4.	Gwari Yamma	tnütñü
5.	Gade	(igingbaazi)
PEB *ire-tu (rdl.)		
6.	Ebira Okene	i-tütü
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-tutu
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	iri-tütü

'rubbish heap'

'rubbish heap'

cf. Yoruba ààtā 'dunghill'

C.S. 26

PN *V-tuNu-		
1.	Nupe	tütüm̀pèrè
2.	Nupe Tako	tütüm̀pèrè
3.	Gwari	a-tnü
4.	Gwari Yamma	tnügu
5.	Gade	ñ-té
PEB *a-tr to		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-tító
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-tító
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	a-tító

'ashes'

'ashes'

PYIG. e-rirũ /e-l'li'ũ/ 'ashes' (AK. C.S. 186)

PE. A-nhuNə 'ashes' (EL. C.S. 154)

PB -tó 'ashes' (Gt. C.S. 1769)

-túé 'ashes' (Gt. C.S. 1810)

C.S. 98

PN *e-tuNu (rdl.)		
1.	Nupe	e-tü
2.	Nupe Tako	i -tü
3.	Gwari	tnutñü
4.	Gwari Yamma	tnütñü
5.	Gade	(gà-time)
PEB *-koro		
6.	Ebira Okene	u-kóró

'work' n

'work n.'

7. Ebira Kwotto u-kórǎ
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) u-kórǎ

PYIG. u-cé 'work (n.)' (AK. C.S. 229)

C.S. 36

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------|---------|
| | PN *tiu | | 'pound' |
| 1. | Nupe | tsu | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tsu | |
| 3. | Gwari | (bwa) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | tʃu | |
| 5. | Gade | tu | |
| | PEB *tu | | 'pound' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | tú | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | tú | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | tú | |

PYIG. gú 'pound(in mortar)' (AK. C.S. 307)

PE. dūmhi 'pound (in mortar)' (EL. C.S. 76)

C.S. 125

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----------|--------|
| | PN *CV-tiuNu | | 'five' |
| 1. | Nupe | gútsū | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | gútsū | |
| 3. | Gwari | ń-tnú | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (ɲákkjú) | |
| 5. | Gade | i-to | |
| | PEB *ε-ʃɪ | | 'five' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | è-hi | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | è-hi | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ε-ʃɪ | |

PYIG. à-rūā /al'ū/ 'five' (AK. C.S. 195)

PE. ii-chiNnhi 'five' (EL. C.S. 43)

PJ. ton (i-) 'five' (Sh. pp. 60-1)

PB. -cáánò 'five' (Gl. C.S. 275)

PBK. -T-ŋ-nh-

C.S. 38

- | | | | |
|--|---------|--|----------|
| | PN *tiu | | 'to die' |
|--|---------|--|----------|

1.	Nupe	tsu	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsutsu	
3.	Gwari	(fi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-tfu	
5.	Gade	tji	
	PEB *su		'to die'
6.	Ebira Okene	sú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	sú	

PYIG ku 'die' (AK. C.S. 286)

PE ghu 'die' (EL. C.S. 88)

PB. -kú- 'die' (Gt. C.S. 1249)

PWS. kú, kúé, kúí 'sterben, toten' (West. pp.237-8; Yor. and Ig. p.c.)

C.S. 126

	PN *o-tiu		'king/chief'
1.	Nupe	o-tsu	
2.	Nupe Tako	o-tsu	
3.	Gwari	e-tsu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-tfu	
5.	Gade	(u-gamɔ)	
	PEB *o-ʃinɔji		'king/chief'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-hinɔi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-hinɔji	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-ʃinɔji	

PE. O-via (l-) 'five' (EL. C.S. 195)

C.S. 106

	PN *tiu-		'push'
1.	Nupe	(dag ^w a) < da + eg ^w a 'walk' 'hand'	
2.	Nupe Tako	(dag ^w ɔ) < da + ago 'walk' 'hand'	
3.	Gwari	tjaɓwaja < tje + ofwa + ja 'throw' 'hand' 'away'	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃuja < tje + uja 'throw' 'away'	
5.	Gade	tʃu	
	PEB *tuuvo		'push'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------------|---------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | túvə < tu + uvə | 'send' 'hand' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (gbubə) < gbe+ ubə | 'hand' |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | túvə < tu + uvə | 'send' 'hand' |

PYIG. ti 'push' (AK. C.S. 89)

Igala kécè < kə ... ècè

Ife Togo télè (Arm.a)

C.S. 129

PN *tiaNtia			'tail'
1.	Nupe	tʃi ntara	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsitə	
3.	Gwari	səsi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	térɲi	
5.	Gade	(u-p ^w ə)	
PEB *o-mu-			'tail'
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-mùtə	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-mù	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-mù	

Forms in 3 and 4 are believed to have undergone metathesis.

C.S. 130

PN *V-ti			'yam'
1.	Nupe	e-tʃi	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-tsi	
3.	Gwari	(ʃjámá)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɔ-tʃi	
5.	Gade	(gi-zè)	
PEB *ε-nu			'yam'
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-nu	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-nu	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	(é-vina)	

PYIG. u-cū (i-) 'yam.' (AK. C.S. 236)

pWS. -ki, -ku 'Jams' (West. p. 233; Yor. and Okp.)

C.S. 30

PN *CV-dagba

'elephant'

1. Nupe dagba
2. Nupe Tako dàgba
3. Gwari dagbá
4. Gwari Yamma dagbá
5. Gade ga-dagba

PEB *ɔ-dagba

'elephant'

6. Ebira Okene ɔ-dɔbá
7. Ebira Kwotto à-dagbá
8. Ètunọ (Igarra) à-dába

cf. Igala à-dàgbá 'elephant' (AK. C.S. 174)
PYIG. e-ñ 'elephant' (AK. C.S. 174)
PE. E-ni (I-) 'elephant' (EL. C.S. 158)
PWS. -ni- 'elephant' (West. p. 264; Yor.)

C.S. 31

PN *CV-dabua

'shoe'

1. Nupe è-dà
2. Nupe Tako à-dába
3. Gwari à-bwàdà
4. Gwari Yamma bwàdà
5. Gade gù-dá ba

PEB *i-dava

'shoe'

6. Ebira Okene à-dáva
7. Ebira Kwotto à-dávà
8. Ètunọ (Igarra) ì-dávà

The Gwari and the Gwari Yamma forms have been realised through metathesis

C.S. 32

PN *V-da

'father'

1. Nupe ñ-dá
2. Nupe Tako ñ-dá
3. Gwari à-mūdada - o-da (Hyman and Magaji 1970)
4. Gwari Yamma mida
5. Gade a-dá

PEB *a-da

'father'

- | | | | |
|----|-----------------|------------|---------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | à-da, ñ-da | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | à-dá | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | à-dá | |
| | PE. O-chue (A-) | 'father' | (EL. C.S. 33) |

C.S. 100

- | | | | |
|----|---------------------------------------|---------------------------|---------------|
| | | PN *CV-da | 'matchet' |
| 1. | Nupe | gada | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | (mátsi) | |
| 3. | Gwari | à-da' | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | ò-dá | |
| 5. | Gade | à-ndá | |
| | | PEB *tokofi | 'matchet' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene (o-h ^w óbáńlì) | ò-h ^w + óbáńlì | 'knife' 'big' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | tókòfi | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | (ò-pija) | |
| | cf. Yoruba | à-dá | 'matchet' |

C.S. 101

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|----|----------------|----------------|---------------|
| | | PN *da- | '(be) wet' |
| 1. | Nupe | dà | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | dá | |
| 3. | Gwari | (búdó) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | dafi | |
| 5. | Gade | (u-mòzokwò) | |
| | | PEB * o-fuefu | '(be) wet' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (e-ńeńlì) | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | o-hwehùrù | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ó-fófú | |
| | PYIG. -tu | 'be wet, cold' | (AK. C.S. 96) |

Igala ridodo

C.S. 113

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|----|-------------|----------------------|---------|
| | | PN *V-doko | 'horse' |
| 1. | Nupe | dòkò | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-dòk ^w ò | |
| 3. | Gwari | dok ^w ò | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | dog ^w ò | |
| 5. | Gade | (ù-vakà) | |

PEB *V-baNta			'horse'
6.	Ebira Okene	u-mántà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-bátà	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-vurátà	

C.S. 104

PN *diəziəN			'walk v.'
1.	Nupe	dazā	
2.	Nupe Tako	dī zò	
3.	Gwari	zāzā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	dāzā	
5.	Gade	(zu)	

PEB *zUSE			'walk v.'
6.	Ebira Okene	ZUSE	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ZUSE	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ZUSE (use (n.))	

PYIG. rī/lī/ 'walk v.' (AK. C.S. 178)

PE. khīNa 'walk, go' (EL. C.S. 121)

C.S. 110

PN *-du			'cook'
1.	Nupe	du	
2.	Nupe Tako	du	
3.	Gwari	(na) du	
4.	Gwari Yamma		
5.	Gade	(nū) ~ (sa)	

PEB *fu			'cook'
6.	Ebira Okene	hú for solids; ne me (for liquids)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hú " " ne " "	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	fú	

PYIG si 'cook' (AK. C.S. 127)

PYIS se 'cook' (AK. C.S. 127)

PLN si 'cook' (Wil. 56)

C.S. 103

PN *ə-diəNsu			'fear n.'
1.	Nupe	dāsū	

2.	Nupe Tako	dòsu	
3.	Gwari	à-dnā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è-dnā	
5.	Gade	(n-zizè)	
	PEB *a-ɲwafɪ		'fear n.'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-ɲwàhí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ɲwàhí	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ɲwafɪ	

PYIG. à-rú 'fear (n.)' (AK. C.S. 190)
 PE. U-piN 'fear (n.)' (EL. C.S. 169)

C.S. 107

		PN *diuNa	'burn (tr.)'
1.	Nupe	dinā	
2.	Nupe Tako	dina	
3.	Gwari	dnādnā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(á-gi)nā	
5.	Gade	du	
		PEB *ɲra	'burn (tr.)'
6.	Ebira Okene	rí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	rírá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	rírá	

PYIG. jó 'burn (trans.)' (AK. C.S. 247)
 PE. tuchi 'burn (trans.)' (EL. C.S. 185)

C.S. 124

		PN *-dɔNa-	'fear' v.
1.	Nupe	tsudā	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsudò	
3.	Gwari	dnàwó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è- dnā	
5.	Gade	(n - zizè)	
		PEB * a- ɲ ^w afɪ	'fear'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-ɲwàhí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ɲwàhí	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-ɲwafɪ	

PYIG. à-rū 'fear n.' (AK. C.S. 190)
 Cf. Yoruba. i-dāwo 'fest'

C.S. 160

PN *e-die		'food'
1.	Nupe e-dʒè	
2.	Nupe Tako i-ʒè	
3.	Gwari (nagʷi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma e-dʲe	
5.	Gade (gi-já)	

PEB *i-sɔŋ		'food'
6.	Ebira Okene i-sá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto i-sɔŋ	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra) i-sɔŋ	

C.S. 64

PN *a-die		'wine/beer (general word)'
1.	Nupe e-gʷe	
2.	Nupe Tako i-ʒe	
3.	Gwari a-dʒe	
4.	Gwari Yamma e-dʲe	
5.	Gade bà-ʒe	

PEB *e-tʃe		'wine/beer (general word)'
6.	Ebira Okene è-tʃè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto è-tʃè	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra) è-tʃè	

PYIG. ɔ-tʃi 'wine, beer (general word)' (AK. C.S. 91)

PWS. tá (+nasal) 'zu Ende sei' (West. p.; Yor.)

C.S. 115

PN *nuNwɔN		'water'
1.	Nupe nūŋ ^w ā	
2.	Nupe Tako nūŋ ^w ɔ	
3.	Gwari nūŋ ^w ɔ̄	
4.	Gwari Yamma núŋ ^w ɔ̄	
5.	Gade (ù-zɔ)	

PEB *e-ji		'water'
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|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | e-ɲi |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | e-ɲi |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | e-ɲi |

PYIG. o-mī 'water' (AK. C.S. 52)
 PE. A-miN (l-) 'water' (EL. C.S. 146)
 Pl. (èDij) 'water' (PBK 42)
 PBK. -bh-dh-ŋ 'water' (PBK. 42)

C.S. 82

	PN *-niɔN		'hot (as fire)'
1.	Nupe	wó +nā	gbo + enā strong + fire
2.	Nupe Tako	wó +nɔ	gbo + inā strong + fire
3.	Gwari	ʒí +nā'	ʒi +ənā strong + fire
4.	Gwari Yamma	gɲū +nā	gɲū + nā strong + fire
5.	Gade	ɲa+gi-wa	< ɲa + giwa
	PEB *ɲ ^w ura		'hot (as fire)'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɲ ^w urá	< ɲ ^w u + ira 'dry fire'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɲ ^w urá	< ɲ ^w u + ira
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɲ ^w ùra	< ɲ ^w u + ira

PYIG. ta 'be hot as pepper' (AK. C.S. 79)
 Cf. Yoruba gbóná 'be hot'

C.S. 33

	PN *ə-na		'fire'
1.	Nupe	e-nā	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-nō	
3.	Gwari	ə-nā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ə-nā	
5.	Gade	(gi-wa)	
	PEB *i-ra		'fire'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-rá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-rá	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	i-rá	

PYIG. u-niā /u-ñiā/ (i-) 'fire' (AK. C.S. 223)

PWS. -nā- 'Feuer' (West. p. 262; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 116

	PN *ə-na		'goat'
1.	Nupe	nāngi	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-nā	
3.	Gwari	ə-nā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è-nā	
5.	Gade	(fubu)	
	PEB *ε-bu		'goat'
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-vú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-bú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-vú	

PYIG. ə-búko 'he goat' (AK. C.S. 19)

PYIG. ε-b'ó 'she goat' (AK. C.S. 32)

PE. E-bhu (i-) 'goat' (EL. C.S. 13)

PB. -búđj 'goat' (GL. C.S. 185)

PBC. -bwoni (i- / i-) (DeW. p. 55)

C.S. 119

	PN *nəkə-		'body'
1.	Nupe	naka	
2.	Nupe Tako	nəkətsigbà	
3.	Gwari	nají	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(pàtà)	
5.	Gade	(i-wu)	
	PEB *ε-ηυ		'body'
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-ηύ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-ηύ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-ηύ ~ εη ^{wu}	

PYIG. V- ra /l'a/ 'body' (AK. C.S. 158)

C.S. 118

	PN *nanə		'dream v.'
1.	Nupe	nānā	

2.	Nupe Tako	nānō	
3.	Gwari	nānā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	nānā	
5.	Gade	(kurubāna)	
	PEB *rura		'dream v.'
6.	Ebira Okene	rura	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	rūrā	
8.	Etunḡ (Igarra)	rura	

PYIG. lá 'dream v.' (AK. C.S. 202)
 PB. -dáád- 'lie down' (Gl. CS. 454)
 -daad- 'pass the night' (Gl. CS. 456)
 cf. Cama. lá rina / dá ádá/ 'sleep' (Maddieson 1974)

C.S. 117

	PN * nāNkpiaN		'leopard'
1.	Nupe	nāmpā	< ṅ-nā + e-pa 'animal' + 'skin'
2.	Nupe Tako	nōpā	
3.	Gwari	nakp̄mī	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(fū-zè)	
	PEB *ε-zu		'leopard'
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-zu	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(û-dòmī)	
8.	Etunḡ (Igarra)	ε-zu	

PE E-kp̄N (I-) 'leopard' (EL. C.S. 135)

C.S. 217

	PN *V-nōwu		'smoke'
1.	Nupe	e-nāwū	< ena + awu 'fire' + 'robe/gown'
2.	Nupe Tako	ɪ-nōwū	< inō+ awu
3.	Gwari	a-wū	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-wū	
5.	Gade	a-mū	
	PEB *are-ji		'smoke'
6.	Ebira Okene	áré-ji	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	aré-ji	
8.	Etunḡ (Igarra)	aré-ji	

C.S. 35

PN *gu-niə

'four'

- | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | gú-nī |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | gú-nì |
| 3. | Gwari | ñ-jí |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | gwa-jí |
| 5. | Gade | i-no |

PEB *ε-na

'four'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | è-nà |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | è-nà |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | è-na |
- PYIG. e-rī /el'ī/ 'four' (AK. C.S. 176)
 PE. -niə 'four' (EL. C.S. 159)

C.S. 122

PN *e-niəN

'soup'

- | | | |
|----|-------------|------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-nī |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | e-nì |
| 3. | Gwari | e-jí |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | e-jí |
| 5. | Gade | i-je |

PEB *ε-kpε

'soup'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | è-pè |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (o-bo) |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | è-pè |

C.S. 123

PN *ə-nieN-

'song'

- | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-ni |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-ni |
| 3. | Gwari | a-ji |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | ɲik ^w o |
| 5. | Gade | à-je |

PEB *a-ʃε

'song'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | a-hé |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | a-hé |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | a-ʃé |
- PYIG. e-rī /el'ī/ (AK. C.S. 175)

PE. I-yodho 'song' (EL. C.S. 206)

C.S. 157

	PN *huN		'extinguish'
1.	Nupe	nū	
2.	Nupe Tako	nū	
3.	Gwari	ŋ ^u ū	
4.	Gwari Yamma	-	
5.	Gade	(rī)	
	PEB *mi		'extinguish'
6.	Ebira Okene	mī	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	mī	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	míó	

PYIG. rū /l'ū / 'destroy, exterminate' (AK. C.S. 187)

PE. puN 'extinguish' (EL. C.S. 172)

C.S. 34

	PN *CV-nhi-		'one'
1.	Nupe	n-ní ~ nīnī	
2.	Nupe Tako	nīnī	
3.	Gwari	ū-nū	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gbɪŋmāri	
5.	Gade	(u-dè)	
	PEB *ɔ-ŋi, *ɔŋa		'one'
6.	Ebira Okene	òŋi ~ òŋa	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-ŋa	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-ŋá	

PYIG. i-né /ilē / 'one' (AK. C.S. 218)

C.S. 45

	PN *si		'buy'
1.	Nupe	ʃi	
2.	Nupe Tako	ʃi	
3.	Gwari	si	
4.	Gwari Yamma	si	
5.	Gade	sí	
	PEB *ʃi		'buy'
6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	

8. Etunọ (Igarra) ʃi

PYIG. rà /là/ 'buy' (AK. C.S. 160)
PE. de 'buy' (EL. C.S. 73)
PB. -dànd- 'buy' (Gl. CS. 490)
PWS. la, (lia, lua) 'kaufen' (West. p. 248, Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 139

PN *siəkəʃi 'God'

1. Nupe sòko
2. Nupe Tako sòko
3. Gwari ʃek^woʃi
4. Gwari Yamma (tʃwəʃe)
5. Gade sɪkapa

PEB. *i-ʃinɛgba 'God'

6. Ebira Okene i-hínébà
7. Ebira Kwotto i-hìnégbá
8. Etunọ (Igarra) (o-ʃomo:ʃi)

C.S. 138

PN *V-səN- 'salt'

1. Nupe e-sā
2. Nupe Tako i-sɔ
3. Gwari sãŋkpeje
4. Gwari Yamma (o-nū)
5. Gade (u-katsi)

PEB *a-nɔ 'salt'

6. Ebira Okene a-nó
7. Ebira Kwotto a-nó
8. Etunọ (Igarra) a-nó

PYIG. o-b'ū 'salt' (AK. C.S. 39)
PB. -nyù 'salt' (Gl. CS. 1396)
-yínò 'salt' (Gl. CS. 2072)
-yínyù 'salt' (Gl. CS. 2080)
PWS. (m)-ba- 'salz' (West. p. 204)
PJ. ɠwa 'salt' (Sh. p. 171)

C.S. 46

	PN *ɔ -za	
		'person'
1.	Nupe e-za	
2.	Nupe Tako a-za	
3.	Gwari ɔ-za	
4.	Gwari Yamma zãŋg ^w ò	
5.	Gade (ù-ní)	
	PEB * ɔ -za	'person'
6.	Ebira Okene ò -za	
7.	Ebira Kwotto ò -za	
8.	Etuno (Igarra) ò -za	

PYIG ɔ-nĩ /ɔlĩ (ɛ-) (AK. C.S.216)

C.S. 143

	PN *zo	
		'finish (intr.)'
1.	Nupe zó	
2.	Nupe Tako zo	
3.	Gwari zo	
4.	Gwari Yamma á-zuo	
5.	Gade (bjé)	
	PEB *ta	'finish (intr.)'
6.	Ebira Okene tá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto (mèhu)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra) tá	

PYIG kpaVdĩ 'end v. be finished' (AK. C.S. 343)

PYIG tā 'end v. be finished (intransitive)' (AK. C.S. 92)

PE pu 'be finished, end' (EL. C.S. 170)

PWS kua 'beenden' (West. p. 240)

C.S. 47

	PN *V-zu	
		'beans'
1.	Nupe e-zo	
2.	Nupe Tako i-zo	
3.	Gwari u-zu	
4.	Gwari Yamma (kapá)	
5.	Gade (ń -kapa)	
	PEB *ɛ-za	'beans'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɛ-za |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɛ-za |
| 8. | Etunḡ (Igarra) | ɛ-za |

PYIG. ɛ-gwa /ɛ-guà/ 'beans' (AK. C.S. 317)

Forms in 4 and 5 are considered to be innovations since they differ completely from the PN and PEB forms.

C.S. 140

	PN *zuN-		'rainy season'
1.	Nupe	zuzuka	
2.	Nupe Tako	zuzu	
3.	Gwari	(vĩĩĩk''ó)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	zũĩĩg''ò	
5.	Gade	(gũ-gu)	
	PEB *ĩĩĩ-su		'rainy season'
6.	Ebira Okene	ĩĩĩ-sũ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ĩĩĩ-sũ	
8.	Etunḡ (Igarra)	ĩĩĩ-sũ	

C.S. 52

	PN *o-zi- (rdl.)		'black'
1.	Nupe	zĩk''o	
2.	Nupe Tako	zĩk''o	
3.	Gwari	zĩĩĩzĩĩĩ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	dzĩdĩzĩ	
5.	Gade	(punu)	
	PEB *dĩzĩko (rdl.)		'black'
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-dĩ'ódĩzĩ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-dĩzĩ	
8.	Etunḡ (Igarra)	ó-dĩ'ódĩzĩ	

PYIG. dũ 'be black' (AK. C.S. 119)

PE bi 'be black' (EL. C.S. 21)

C.S. 161

PN *ɔ-zi 'town'

1.	Nupe	e-ʒi
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ʒi
3.	Gwari	a-ʒijako
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-ʒi
5.	Gade	(l-ré)

PEB *ire-kura

'town'

6.	Ebira Okene	è-kùrà
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-ráda
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ire-kùrà

C.S. 162

PN *zi-

'return (intr.)'

1.	Nupe	ʒí
2.	Nupe Tako	(dà)ʒí
3.	Gwari	ʒijí
4.	Gwari Yamma	(dʒeʒèkpéʒi)
5.	Gade	(kórègi)

PEB *babe

'return (intr.)'

6.	Ebira Okene	vàvé
7.	Ebira Kwotto	bà(hama)bé
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	và

C.S. 158

PN *zi

'make'

1.	Nupe	dʒí
2.	Nupe Tako	ʒí
3.	Gwari	ʒí
4.	Gwari Yamma	(sū)
5.	Gade	(mè)

PEB *me

'make'

6.	Ebira Okene	mè
7.	Ebira Kwotto	mè
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	mè

PYIG. ce	'make, do'	(AK. C.S. 227)
PE. di	'tie rope'	(EL. C.S. 56)
PE. fadhɪ	'tie (bundle); make (rope)'	(EL. C.S. 56)
PWS. kia	'machen'	(West. p. 233-4)

C.S. 109

		PN *CV-zinj-	
			'housefly'
1.	Nupe	(dīnī)	
2.	Nupe Tako	(ā-ndīnī)	
3.	Gwari	būzūk"ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	būzūg"ó	
5.	Gade	gū-ǰī	
		PEB *i-si-	
6.	Ebira Okene	ʔ-sī	'housefly'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ʔ-sikpá	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʔ-sī	

PYIG	V-cíci	'housefly'	(AK. C.S. 232)
PE	A-khíNa (l-)	'housefly'	(EL. C.S. 120)
PBC	-zin (i-ŋ-)	'fly'	(DeW. p. 55)
PB	-ǰí 'fly'		(Gt. C.S. 819)

C.S. 51

		PN *CV-zia	
			'egg'
1.	Nupe	è-ǰi	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ǰi	
3.	Gwari	ə-ǰi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è-ǰi	
5.	Gade	ń -ǰè	
		PEB *a-dʒɛ	
6.	Ebira Okene	a-dʒɛ	'egg'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	adʒɛ	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-dʒɛ	

PYIG	ɛ-g'ɪ	'egg'	(AK. C.S. 328)
PE	dhi-kiNə	'egg'	(EL. C.S. 112)
PB	gɛ	'egg'	(Gt. C.S. 79)
	gi	'egg'	(Gt. C.S. 809)
PBC	-kiŋ/-tiŋ (i-/a-)	'egg'	(DeW. p. 54)
PBK	-k-ŋ-	'egg'	(PBK. 8)

C.S. 147

		PN *la-	
			'untie'

1.	Nupe	lò
2.	Nupe Tako	lò
3.	Gwari	lèja
4.	Gwari Yamma	
5.	Gade	(bana)
	PEB *ɲua-	
6.	Ebira Okene	ɲwà
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɲwàri
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɲwàra

'untie'

PYIG tū	'untie'	(AK. C.S. 86)
PE thaN	'untie'	(EL. C.S. 187)
PLN.	to	(Wil.)

C.S. 149

	PN *la	
1.	Nupe	la
2.	Nupe Tako	-
3.	Gwari	lá
4.	Gwari Yamma	(g ^w o)
5.	Gade	(sú)

'take (one thing)'

	PEB *si	
6.	Ebira Okene	sí
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sí
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	sí

'take (one thing)'

PYIG. mū	'take (one thing) catch, seize, hold)'	(AK. C.S. 59)
PE da	'take (some thing)'	(EL. C.S. 50)
PWS. mu, mua-	'greifen, fangen'	(West. p 258, Yor. and Okp.)

C.S. 148

	PN *lo	
1.	Nupe	lo
2.	Nupe Tako	(túg ^w o)
3.	Gwari	lo
4.	Gwari Yamma	lo
5.	Gade	(ge)

'go' v.

	PEB *na	
6.	Ebira Okene	ná:
7.	Ebira Kwotto	nâ

'go' v.

8. Etuno (Igarra) ná

PYOR la 'go v.' (AK. C.S. 206)
cf Cama kù/ḍo 'go' (Maddieson '74)
PE khiNa 'walk, go' (EL. C.S. 121)

C.S. 146

PN *-luki

'bird'

1. Nupe e-lúgi
2. Nupe Tako a-lú
3. Gwari ɔ-lú
4. Gwari Yamma o-lú
5. Gade gú-nakjì

PEB *i-nomi

'bird'

6. Ebira Okene i-nomi
7. Ebira Kwotto i-nómí
8. Etuno (Igarra) u-nómí

PYIG. ɛ-we 'bird' (AK. C.S. 44)

PE. A-pi (l-) 'bird' (EL. C.S. 168)

C.S. 151

PN *le

'lie down'

1. Nupe iètʃi
2. Nupe Tako le
3. Gwari (jaʃi)
4. Gwari Yamma (játʃire)
5. Gade nènè, i

PEB *futu

'lie down'

6. Ebira Okene hùtú
7. Ebira Kwotto hùtó
8. Etuno (Igarra) fùte

C.S. 154

PN *lu

'weave' v.

1. Nupe lu
2. Nupe Tako lu
3. Gwari lu
4. Gwari Yamma lú

5.	Gade	rū	
	PEB *fj		
6.	Ebira Okene	hī	'weave'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hī	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ji	

PYIG. ŋu /ghū 'weave' (AK. C.S. 331)
 PE. do 'weave' (EL. C.S. 58)

C.S. 152

	PN *lhelhe		
1.	Nupe	lele	'sleep(v.)'
2.	Nupe Tako	file	
3.	Gwari	ŋ ^w āg ^l e	
4.	Gwari Yamma	jer ^l e	
5.	Gade	(bā-ná)	
	PEB *suara		
6.	Ebira Okene	swará < sū + ará	'sleep(v.)' (~ sùhutú)
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sará	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	sará	

PYIG. sū 'sleep' (AK. C.S. 145)
 PE. U-bhichìN(a) (or. bhichì ?) 'sleep (v.)' (EL. C.S. 9)

C.S. 48.

	PN *lhuN- (rdl.)		
1.	Nupe	lulufuka	'cotton/thread'
2.	Nupe Tako	lulu	
3.	Gwari	lùlu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ŋwūfu	
5.	Gade	(gèjè)	
	PEB *o-wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	o-ú	'cotton/thread'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-wú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-wú	

PE. O-dhudhu (l-) 'cotton' (EL. C.S. 69)

C.S. 153

	PN *lhu		
1.	Nupe	wu	'beat (person)'

2.	Nupe Tako	lu	
3.	Gwari	lu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	lu	
5.	Gade	ru	
	PEB *tu		
6.	Ebira Okene	tú	'beat (person)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(nísa)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tú	

PYIG. lù 'beat (person, drum)' (PYIG. C.S. 210)
 PE. gbeGi 'beat, kill' (PE. C.S. 90)
 PLN. lu 'fight' (Wil.50)

C.S. 40

	PN *ci		'descend'
1.	Nupe	tʃi	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsi	
3.	Gwari	(ká)ʃi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ʃiʒi	
5.	Gade	ʃi	
	PEB *tʃi		
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃi	'descend'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tʃi	

C.S. 41

	PN *V-cigbɔNa		'tree'
1.	Nupe	tʃigbã	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsigbɔ	
3.	Gwari	a-ʃi ɲwã	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃimwã	
5.	Gade	ù-kí	
	PEB *ɔ-tʃi		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-tʃi	'tree'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-tʃi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃi	

PYIG. e-gi (i-) 'tree, firewood' (AK. C.S. 305)
 PE. U-thaNi (I-) 'tree' (EI. C.S. 188)

PB. -kùnj 'firewood' (Gl. C.S. 1218)
 PWS -gi, -gìl- (-git-) 'Baum' (West. p.222-3; Yor. and Ig. p.c.)

C.S. 42	PN *cigbiə		'stick'
1.	Nupe	tʃigba	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsɪ'gbò	
3.	Gwari	bùsì	
4.	Gwari Yamma	buti	
5.	Gade	(ú-rùgbo)	
	PEB *ɔ-tʃi		'stick'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-tʃi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-tʃi	
8.	Etunò (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃi	

Forms in 3 and 4 are believed to have undergone metathesis.

C.S. 44	PN *cie		'throw'
1.	Nupe	tʃé - jé'	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsé	
3.	Gwari	ʃ'é	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃówó	
5.	Gade	tʃé	
	PEB *ne		'throw'
6.	Ebira Okene	ne	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ne	
8.	Etunò (Igarra)	ne	

PYIG. sɔ 'throw' (AK. C.S. 135)

PYOR. jù 'throw' (AK. C.S. 253)

PE. ca 'shoot, hit' (EL. C.S. 23)

C.S. 127	PN *cigbaN-		'firewood'
1.	Nupe	tʃigbò	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsigbònògú	
3.	Gwari	ʃiŋ ^w á	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃimwanà	

5.	Gade	(i-wu)	
	PEB *ɔ-ku		'firewood'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ku	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-kú	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-ku	

PYIG. e-gi (i-) 'tree, firewood' (AK. C.S. 305)

PBC. kwoni (bu-fi-) 'firewood' (DeW. p. 57)

PWS. -gí, -gíl- (-git-) 'Baum' (West. pp. 222-3; Yor. and Igalá p.c.)

C.S. 128

	PN *cigbe		'medicine (charm)'
1.	Nupe	tʃigbè	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsigbè	
3.	Gwari	ʃí gbé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(amùsùṅkpi)	
5.	Gade	—	
	PEB *ira-fɔnɔ		'medicine (charm)'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-hònò	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(e-tʃikpà)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ìrà-fɔnò	

PYIG. o-gū 'medicine' (AK. C.S. 311)

C.S. 43

	PN *tsie		'shoot'
1.	Nupe	tʃé	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsé	
3.	Gwari	ʃ'é	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃówó	
5.	Gade	tʃé	
	PEB *tʃe		'shoot'
6.	Ebira Okene	(ha)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃe	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tʃe	

PYIG. ta 'shoot (arrow, catapult)' (AK. C.S. 78)

PYIG. ɲí /yí/ 'shoot (gun)' (AK. C.S. 265)

PB. -tá 'bow' (Gl. CS. 1631)

PWS. -ta- 'schiessen, Geschoss, Bogen' (West. pp.280-1; Yor.)

C.S. 132	PN	* tse	'be full'
1.	Nupe	ʃe	
2.	Nupe Tako	tse	
3.	Gwari	(nūnūji)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(ā-nū)	
5.	Gade	(rere)	
	PEB *V-ʃi		'be full'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-hihi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Ẹtuno (Igarra)	ʃi	

3 and 4 have different forms for the lexical item. This is one innovation that distinguishes the two speech forms as a unit under PN.

PYIG. kū 'be full' (AK. C.S. 291)
 PE. vuNu 'be full' (EL. C.S. 198)

C.S. 131	PN	*e-tsi	'twenty'
1.	Nupe	e-ʃi	
2.	Nupe Tako	e-tsi	
3.	Gwari	—	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(wó)ʃi	
5.	Gade	(à-zaàvà)	
	PEB *o-fu		'twenty'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-hú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-hú	
8.	Ẹtuno (Igarra)	o-fú	

PYIG. o-gū 'twenty' (AK. C.S. 308)
 PE. U-gheGi 'twenty' (EL. C.S. 86)
 PE. I-və 'twenty' (EL. C.S. 194)

C.S. 99	PN	*tsiNi	'plait (hair)'
1.	Nupe	ti	
2.	Nupe Tako	ti	

3.	Gwari	kjĩ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kjĩ	
5.	Gade	(m ^w ɔ)	
	PEB	*za	'plait (hair)'
6.	Ebira Okene	(gú)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	zá	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	(và)	

PYIG bá 'plait' (hair, rope) (AK. C.S. 109)

di 'plait' (hair, rope) (AK. C.S. 23)

PE di 'tie (rope)' (EL. C.S. 56)

PB -dĩt- 'tie a knot' (Gt. C.S. 629)

C.S. 170

	PN *ji		'call v.'
1.	Nupe	ji	
2.	Nupe Tako	ji	
3.	Gwari	ji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ʒi	
5.	Gade	(vurà)	

	PEB *ʃi		'call v.'
6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃiɔ	

PYIG kpè 'call, summon' (AK. C.S. 338)

PLN. kpɔ 'call, summon' (Wil.42)

C.S. 54

	PN *je-		'in-law'
1.	Nupe	jèle	
2.	Nupe Tako	jèle	
3.	Gwari	jeʒihi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(mi)jéʒi	
5.	Gade	(ù-g ^w ɔ)	
	PEB *ɔ -je		'in-law'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-jé	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-jé	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-jéé	

C.S. 163

	PN	*je-	
1.	Nupe	jébo	'to like'
2.	Nupe Tako	jébo	
3.	Gwari	jé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	jé	
	PEB	*sire	
6.	Ebira Okene	si	'to like'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sireji	
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	siõ ~ sireáni	

C.S. 164

	PN	*CV-je	
1.	Nupe	(sunnä)	'name'
2.	Nupe Tako	(sunnä)	
3.	Gwari	e-je	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-je	
5.	Gade	n-je'	
	PEB	*ire-fa	
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-fa'	'name'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ire-fa'	
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	ire-fà	

Forms in 1 and 2 are borrowed from Hausa language.

PE. dhl-ni (A-) 'name' (EL. C.S. 157)

C.S. 55

	PN	*a-ja	
1.	Nupe	è-ja	'buffalo'
2.	Nupe Tako	e-ja	
3.	Gwari	à-ja	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(ü-fá)	
	PEB	*ε-ja	
6.	Ebira Okene	é-ja	'buffalo'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-ja	
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	ε-ja	

PYIG. ε-fā 'buffalo (bushcow) (AK. C.S. 72)

C.S. 168

		PN *e-ja	
1.	Nupe	e-ja	'boat (canoe)'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ja	
3.	Gwari	e-janũŋ ^w ájíá)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-janũŋ ^w ájíá)	
5.	Gade	(gú-kpá)	
		PEB *e-kpa	
6.	Ebira Okene	è-pà	'boat (canoe)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-kpa	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	(ó-kó)	

Only the form in 8 is cognate with the Yoruba and PE forms. It may have been borrowed.

cf. Yoruba ó-kò 'vehicle'

PE. U-kò (I-) 'boat canoe; mortar' (EL. C.S. 116)

C.S. 53.

		PN *ə-ja	
1.	Nupe	e-ja	'year'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ja	
3.	Gwari	ə-já	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-jé	
5.	Gade	ù-je	
		PEB *(ira)-je	
6.	Ebira Okene	ira-jé	'year'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-jí	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ira-jé	

PYIG. ó-dū 'year' (AK. C.S. 115)

PE. U-kpe (A-) 'year' (EL. C.S. 133)

C.S. 61

		PN *jɔNkpa	'iron (metal)'
1.	Nupe	ɲāŋkpa	
2.	Nupe Tako	ɲāŋkpa	
3.	Gwari	(sũŋkɲá)	

4.	Gwari Yamma	jajjá	
	Gade	(gə-tʃi)	
5.		PEB *ɔ-ɲise	'iron (metal)'
6.	Ebira Okene	è-ɲúsi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-ɲise	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	è-ɲisɛ	

PYIG. u-ñi (i-) 'iron (metal)' (AK. C.S. 177)

C.S. 59.

		PN *ji-	'sun/sunshine'
1.	Nupe	jigidi	
2.	Nupe Tako	jigidi	
3.	Gwari	ɲip ʲéi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	wlájgò	
5.	Gade	(ù-zù)	
		PEB *ɔ-ɲi	'sun/ sunshine'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ɲi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-ɲi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-ɲi	

PYIG o-rū /o-l'ū / 'sun' (AK. C.S. 192)

PS. ɣui 'Sonne, Gestirn' (West. p. 194 no. 312; Yor.)

C.S. 58

		PN *jiNkɔN	'tooth'
1.	Nupe	ɲikā	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ɲikɔ	
3.	Gwari	ɲikā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲigā	
5.	Gade	ɲiji	
		PEB *a-ɲi	'tooth'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ɲi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ɲi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ɲi	

PYIG e-ɲi /e-ɲi/ 'tooth' (AK. C.S. 263)

PE dhl-kuN (A-) 'tooth' (EL. C.S. 118)

C.S. 60

		PN *jiNko		
1.	Nupe	jiwo		'female'
2.	Nupe Tako	jiwó		
3.	Gwari	ɲik ^w ózá	ɲik ^w ó + ɔ-za	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲik ^w ózá	female + person ɲik ^w o + záŋg ^w ò	
5.	Gade	ɲí né(ní)	female + person	
		PEB *ɔ-jene		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ̀jéne		'female'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ̀njje		
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ɔ̀jéne		

The form in 3 and 4 are contracted from the nouns: female and person. See C.S. 46 for reconstruction of 'person'. The form in 7 is considered older. It seems like a derived word from Yoruba words [eni] 'person' + [je] 'lay'. The forms in 6 and 8 are similar to the Nupoid forms.

C.S. 176

		PN *V-jɔN		
1.	Nupe	e-ɲá		'thing'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ɲɔ		
3.	Gwari	ɔ-ɲá		
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲáàdò		
5.	Gade	(ù-be)		
		PEB *ɪ-sa		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɪ-sá		'thing'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-sá		
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	i-sá		

PE. -mhinhi 'thing, something' (EL. C.S. 153)

C.S. 175 PN *jiNi -

1.	Nupe	ɲĩmĩ	'wife'
2.	Nupe Tako	ɲĩmĩ	
3.	Gwari	ɲĩk ^w ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲĩg ^w ó	
5.	Gade	ɲinè	
PEB *u-si			
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-se'	'wife'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-si'	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	ò-sé	

C.S. 242 PN* minikini

1.	Nupe	mitfini, ébi	'saliva'
2.	Nupe Tako	ansinĩ	
3.	Gwari	a-kɲĩ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	mĩnti	
5.	Gade	(k ^J ɲk ^J ɛ)	
PEB *a-te			
6.	Ebira Okene	a-té	'saliva'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	--	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	a-té	

PYIG. i-t̄	'saliva'	(AK. C.S. 93)
PE. A-ɸiaNi(I-)	'saliva'	(EL. C.S. 29)
PB. -tai	'Spittle'	(Meussen 1973)
PBK. -T-ɲ-	'saliva'	(PBK 30)
PWS. -tá-	'speichel'	(West. p. 282; Yor.)
PBC. -ntáti (ma-)	'saliva'	(DeW. p. 58)
PS. tá	'speichel'	(West. p. 187 no. 282; Yor.)

C.S. 62

PN *jiNiko		'woman'
1.	Nupe	ɲĩzàgi
2.	Nupe Tako	nzàdʒi
3.	Gwari	ɲĩk ^w ózá
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲĩk ^w ózá

5.	Gade	jīnēni	
	PEB *ɔ-peŋe		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-peŋe	'woman'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-nijé	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-peŋe	

PYIG. ɔ-bīrī /o-bīl' ī 'woman, female' (AK. C.S. 1b)

C.S. 63

	PN *jiəN (rdl.)		
1.	Nupe	nānā	'dance (v.)'
2.	Nupe Tako	nīnā	
3.	Gwari	nānā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	nānā	
5.	Gade	(zimú)	
	PEB *jeze		
6.	Ebira Okene	jeze	'dance(v.)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	jeze	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	jeze	

PYIG. jó 'dance v.' (AK. C.S. 248)

C.S. 174

	PN *V-jiəNkəN		'fish'
1.	Nupe	nīkā	
2.	Nupe Tako	nīkə	
3.	Gwari	ə-bjǎ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(jèwò)	
5.	Gade	(rú-gbetù)	
	PEB *i-seŋi		'fish'
6.	Ebira Okene	(i-vòvò)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-ŋi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	i-séŋī < isá + eŋī	'thing' + 'water'

PYIG. e-ja 'fish' (AK. C.S. 242)

PJ. gyá (ki-/i-) 'fish' (West. pp. 163-4)

C.S. 185

PN *CV-ka-

	Nupe	k ^o oro	'navel'
1.	Nupe Tako	k ^o oro	
2.	Gwari	kəpu	
3.	Gwari Yamma	kəpu	
4.	Gade	(kú)-pómpo	
5.	PEB *ira-dʒe		
	Ebira Okene	ira-dʒe	'navel'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ndʒe	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ira-dʒe	
8.			

PYIG. u-do (i-) 'navel, umbilical cord' (AK. p.s. 107)
 PE. U-khaN (I-) 'navel' (EL. C.S. 119)

C.S. 186

PN *kaba

	Nupe	kaba	'maize'
1.	Nupe Tako	kàba	
2.	Gwari	(jãw ^ɔ i)	
3.	Gwari Yamma	kàmbà (~ ew ^ɔ e)	
4.	Gade	(gú-tsumpwá)	
5.	PEB *a-kpa(kpa)		
	Ebira Okene	à-pa'pa'	'maize'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	a:kpa	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	à-pápà	
8.			

C.S. 66

PN *ka(ra)(pu)

	Nupe	kara	'crab'
1.	Nupe Tako	a-kára	
2.	Gwari	kapú	
3.	Gwari Yamma	kapú	
4.	Gade	(r-tʃene)	
5.	PEB *V-kakara		
	Ebira Okene	ù-kákàrà	'crab'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	i-kákàrà	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ú-kákara	
8.			

PYIG. a-kiárá/akiãl'ã / 'crab' (AK. C.S. 300)
 PB. -kádá 'crab' (Gl. C.S. 981)
 PWS. -ka-.-kal- 'Krabbe' (West. p. 230; Yor.)

C.S. 80

	PN *kawia		
1.	Nupe	wo	'dry'
2.	Nupe Tako	wi'wo	
3.	Gwari	kawí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	a-k ^w okawu	
5.	Gade	(kikéré)	
	PEB *ɔ-wɛ		
6.	Ebira Okene	wu	'dry'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ó-wejĩ	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ɔ-wɛŋwā	

PYIG. gbɛ 'become dry' (of water, cloth etc.) (AK. C.S. 356)
 PE. ka 'dry' (EL. C.S. 103)

C.S. 184

	PN *ko + ani		
	'sing' + 'song'		'sing 'sing song'
1.	Nupe	kóni	
2.	Nupe Tako	k ^w anĩ	
3.	Gwari	kwajĩ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	k ^w óni	
5.	Gade	ka, aje	
	PEB *dʒi-	(v.) + aʒɛ (n.)	'sing'
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒahe < dʒi + ahe	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hahe < hi + ahe	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	dʒaʒɛ < dʒi + aʒɛ	

cf Yor. karĩ < ka + ori 'sing song'

PE.cu. 'sing' (EL. C.S. 31)

C.S. 180

	PN *kuti		'fetish (juju)
1.	Nupe	kútĩ	
2.	Nupe Tako	kútĩ	
3.	Gwari	—	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kutʃĩ	

5.	Gade	(3 3i)	
	PEB	*ira-fianò	
	Ebira Okene	a-vi	'fetish (juju)'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	(3 3i)	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	'ira-fianò	'medicine, charm'
8.			

PYIG. ò-gù 'medicine' (AK. C.S. 311)

C.S. 28

	PN	*takuN, *u-kuta	
			'stone'
1.	Nupe	tákù	
2.	Nupe Tako	takù	
3.	Gwari	kútá	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kuta	
5.	Gade	ù-ku	
	PEB	*irè-ta	
			'stone'
6.	Ebira Okene	irè-tá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ìrè -ta	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ìr è -tà	

PYIG ò-kúta 'stone' (AK. C.S. 81)
 PE. U-goGi, -dio (I-) (EL. C.S. 59)
 PB -tádè 'stone' (Gt. C.S. 1642)
 PWS -ta-, -tali 'stein' (West. P. 285)

C.S. 179

	PN	*a-kia	
			'thorn(s)'
1.	Nupe	e-kā	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ko	
3.	Gwari	a-kgā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-kgā	
5.	Gade	(kúkúbànti) (i-)	
	PEB	*i-kehi	
			'thorn(s)'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-kehi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i -ke'jǐ	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	i-kei	

PYIG. à-gù 'thorn, prickle' (AK. C.S. 306a)

Igala i-keke

C.S. 183

PN *kuNu

- | | | |
|----|-------------|------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | k ^w u |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | k ^w u |
| 3. | Gwari | kiú |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | kiú |
| 5. | Gade | (zine) |

'sell'

PEB *na

- | | | |
|----|----------------|----|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | na |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | na |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | na |

'sell'

PYIG. ta 'sell' (AK. C.S. 82)

PE. deGt 'sell' (EL. C.S. 55)

PB. -té-g- 'sell' (Gt. C.S. 1697)

PWS. ta- 'kaufen, verkaufen' (West. p.284, Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 181

PN *a-koNɔ

'monkey'

- | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | kānā |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-kōnɔ |
| 3. | Gwari | a-kiá |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (nākpa) |
| 5. | Gade | (fū-ka) |

PEB *ɔ-ntʃere

'monkey'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-ntʃerè |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɔ-n'ʃerè |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ɔ-ntʃerè |

C.S. 182

PN *koNa

'fry'

- | | | |
|----|-------------|------|
| 1. | Nupe | kā |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | ko |
| 3. | Gwari | kiā |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | kiā |
| 5. | Gade | kénè |

PEB *wara

'fry'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | wara |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | wara |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | wàrà |

PYIG. ði 'fry (in oil)' (AK. C.S. 110)

C.S. 187

PN *V-kiNi

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | kī | 'ground' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tjīm | |
| 3. | Gwari | à-kŋī | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | è-kŋī | |
| 5. | Gade | (tizè) | |
| | PEB *ε-tε | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ε-tε | 'ground' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ε-té | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ε-té | |

PE U-to (A-) 'ground' (EL. C.S. 181)

C.S. 189

PN *V-kiNi

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-kī | 'needle' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | à-tjī | |
| 3. | Gwari | à-tjī | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | è-kŋī | |
| 5. | Gade | (ú-géza) | |
| | PEB *ɔ-rɪhɪ | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-rɪ hɪ | 'needle' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɔ-ríhí | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ɔ-rɪhɪ | |

cf. Yoruba o-kinī 'needle'

C.S. 188

PN *kiN

- | | | | |
|----|------|----|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | kī | 'sew' |
|----|------|----|-------|

	Nupe Tako	tʃi
2.	Gwari	tʃi
3.	Gwari Yamma	(lu)
4.	Gade	(kwó)
5.	PEB *gɛ	
6.	Ebira Okene	gɛ
7.	Ebira Kwotto	gɛ
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	gɛ

PYIG rā 'sew with thread' (AK. C.S. 179)
 Igala gá

C.S. 65

	PN * V-ku				
1.	Nupe	e-k ^w ú			'corpse'
2.	Nupe Tako	í-ku			
3.	Gwari	(zàfi)	two morphemes:	eza + fi	
				'person' + 'die'	
4.	Gwari Yamma	zàtʃú		eza + tʃu	
				'person' + 'die'	
5.	Gade	gi-tʃi			
	PEB *o-ku				'corpse'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-kú			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-kú			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-kú			

PYIG ò-kú 'corpse' (AK. C.S. 286a)
 deverbal noun from 'die'

PE O-dhimhi (A-) 'corpse' (EL. C.S. 64)

PB -kú 'dead person' (Gt. C.S. 1247)

C.S. 39

	PN *CV-kiukuNu				'bone'
1.	Nupe	tsúkū			
2.	Nupe Tako	a-súkū			
3.	Gwari	a-súkɔ̃			
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃúŋ ^w ú			
5.	Gade	gu-k ^w ík ^w ú			
	PEB * -tʃ uku				'bone'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | é-tfóku |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | a-tfókù |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | o-tfókú |

PYIG V-k'íkù 'bone' (AK. C.S. 302)
 PB kúpà 'bone' (Gl. C.S. 1273)
 PWS. -kù, -kúp-, kúá 'knochen' (West. p. 238; Yor.)

C.S. 195

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|--------|
| | PN *CV-kə | | 'word' |
| 1. | Nupe | e-gā | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | i-gà | |
| 3. | Gwari | (bada) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (betá) | |
| 5. | Gade | ñ-ka' | |
| | PEB *ifɛ-ji | | 'word' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ifɛ-ɪ | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɛ-ji | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ifɛ-ɪ | |

PYIG. ð-rò /ol'á / 'word, matter' (AK. C.S. 167)

C.S. 69

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------------------|---------|
| | PN *go | | 'grind' |
| 1. | Nupe | g ^w o | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | g ^w o | |
| 3. | Gwari | g ^w o | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | g ^w o | |
| 5. | Gade | k ^w o | |
| | PEB *ku | | 'grind' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ku(sá) | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | kù | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | kù | |

PYIG. gū 'pound (in mortar)' (AK. C.S. 307)

lò 'grind' (AK. C.S. 207)

PE. ló 'grind' (EL. C.S. 140)

C.S. 226

PN* giə		
1. Nupe	(lájá)	'give'
2. Nupe Tako	(lájá)	
3. Gwari	gá	
4. Gwari Yamma	gimi	
5. Gade	gʲi	

PEB *sɪ		
6. Ebira Okene	sí	'give'
7. Ebira Kwotlo	(dɔ́)	
8. Etuno (Igarra)	sjám	

PE. na 'give' (EL. C.S. 155)

C.S. 239

PN *giə		
1. Nupe	gá	'say (something)'
2. Nupe Tako	gò	
3. Gwari	(da)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(m̀gadabotá)	
5. Gade	gè	

PEB *kare		
6. Ebira Okene	kà	'say (something)'
7. Ebira Kwotlo	òkikà	
8. Etuno (Igarra)	kàre	

PYIS. gwí /guí/ 'say something' (AK. C.S. 321)

PE. ta 'say, tell' (EL. C.S. 180)

weGi 'say (to someone)' (EL. C.S. 202)

C.S. 197

PN *gogɔN		
1. Nupe	gʷògā	'pass by'
2. Nupe Tako	gʷògɔ	
3. Gwari	(dùja)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(wádùja)	
5. Gade	(kʲé)	

PEB *pa(ra)fu		
6. Ebira Okene	pàràhu	'pass by'
7. Ebira Kwotlo	béhu	
8. Etuno (Igarra)	pàràfú	

C.S. 193

PN *guzija

1.	Nupe	guʒa	'groundnut'
2.	Nupe Tako	guz'a	
3.	Gwari	(gbàgbe)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(gbègbe)	
5.	Gade	guʒija	
	PEB *V-kusije		
6.	Ebira Okene	(é-tʃupà)	'groundnut'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-gúʒija	
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	e-kúʒájé	

C.S. 191

PN *guNu

1.	Nupe	gū	'climb'
2.	Nupe Tako	g"u	
3.	Gwari	gṛú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gṛū	
5.	Gade	g"o	
	PEB *ʃire		
6.	Ebira Okene	híre	'climb'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hírè	
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	ʃire	

PYIG. gū 'climb, mount' (AK. C.S. 310)

C.S. 196

PN *gɔN

1.	Nupe	gā	'surpass'
2.	Nupe Tako	gɔ	
3.	Gwari	dù gṛā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(pé)	

PEB *funa

6.	Ebira Okene	huna	'surpass'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	—	
8.	Etunõ (Igarra)	funa	

C.S. 68

PN *gia Na

'divide' (share out)

1.	Nupe	gá	
2.	Nupe Tako	gò	
3.	Gwari	gṛṛá	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gṛṛá	
5.	Gade	(zà)	
	PEB *ga		
6.	Ebira Okene	gà	'divide (share out)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	gà	
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	gà	

PYIG. kpī 'divide, share' (AK. C.S. 348)

C.S. 137

	PN *CV-giεNiko		'market'
1.	Nupe	(dzukó)	
2.	Nupe Tako	(duk ^w ó)	
3.	Gwari	gṛṛíḡ ^w ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gṛṛíḡ ^w ó	
5.	Gade	gì-g ^J é	
	PEB *o-fu		'market'
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-hù	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-hù	
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	ò-fù	

PYIG. a-jà 'market place' (AK. C.S. 245)

PE. A-ki (I-) 'market' (EL. C.S. 109)

PWS. gi,giá- 'kaufen' (West. pp.214-5; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 202

	PN * -giNtara		'tongue'
1.	Nupe	gìntara	
2.	Nupe Tako	à-gìn tara	
3.	Gwari	ḡítala	
4.	Gwari Yamma	mintá	
5.	Gade	(gà-kòre)	
	PEB *ira-rε		'tongue'
6.	Ebira Okene	ìrà-rè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ìrà-rè	

Etunọ (Igarra) ɾá-ré

PYIG. u-b'á (i-)	'tongue'	(AK. C.S. 36)
PE U-dhamhi	'tongue'	(EL. C.S. 63)
PEB. -Jemi (li-u-)	'tongue'	(DeW. p. 54)
PVK. -dh-mh-	'tongue'	(PBK. 39)
PP. dyam	'tongue'	(PBK. 39)

C.S. 198

	PN *gi		
1.	Nupe	gi	'eat'
2.	Nupe Tako	dʒi	
3.	Gwari	gʲi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gi	
5.	Gade	(n)	
	PEB *ri		
6.	Ebira Okene	ri	'eat'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ri	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ri	

PYIG. je	'eat'	(AK. C.S. 240)
PE dhi	'eat'	(EL. C.S. 65)
PJ. dyi	'to eat'	(Sh. pp. 90-1)
PWS. li, liá	'essen'	(West. p. 250-1; Yor. and Okp.)
PLN. dí	'eat'	(Wil. 14)

C.S. 201

	PN *V-giɛ		'blood'
1.	Nupe	e-g'a	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ʒɛ	
3.	Gwari	(a-mi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	é-g'á	
5.	Gade	(bà-ji)	
	PEB *a-na		'blood'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ná	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-na	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ná	

PYIG. ɛ-bjè /ɛbiɛ/	'blood'	(AK. C.S. 25)
PE. U-ji-, jia (A-)	'blood'	(EL. C.S. 101)

PS. giə
PWS. -gia

'Blut'
'Blut'

(West. p. 135 no. 109; Yor. p.c.)
(West. p. 215; Yor. p.c.)

C.S. 203

PN *kpe

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | kpe | 'to cover (a pot)' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | kpe | |
| 3. | Gwari | (kwapa) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | kpéré | |
| 5. | Gade | (kuru) | |
| | PEB *kuoku | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | k''oku | 'to cover (a pot)' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | | |
| 8. | Etunṣ (Igarra) | k''ókú: | |

PYIG. dé 'cover, put on (head, pot)' (AK. C.S. 99)

C.S. 204

PN *kpe

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | kpe | 'know' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | kpe | |
| 3. | Gwari | kpé | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | kpéjaje | |
| 5. | Gade | kpu | |
| | PEB *je | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | je | 'know' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | jé | |
| 8. | Etunṣ (Igarra) | jé | |

PYIG. mā 'know' (AK. C.S. 57)

PE. ninhə, nhiachə (EL. C.S. 165)

PLN. ɓnā 'know' (Wil. 9)

C.S. 205

PN *kpe

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | kpī | 'learn' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | kpī | |
| 3. | Gwari | kpéjé | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (mutúmù) | |
| 5. | Gade | (tsene) | |

PEB *kəse

'learn'

6	Ebira Okene	kóse
7	Ebira Kwotto	kóse
8	Etuno (Igarra)	kóswé

PYIG. kó 'learn, teach' (AK. C.S. 278)
 PE ma- 'learn' (EL. C.S. 142)

C.S. 71

		PN *V-kpa	
1	Nupe	e-kpa	'snail'
2	Nupe Tako	á-kpāṅkúrú	
3	Gwari	ɔ-ká	
4	Gwari Yamma	ɔ-ka	
5	Gade	ú-kpa	
		PEB * -kókɔɾɪ	
6	Ebira Okene	ú-kókɔɾɪ	'snail'
7	Ebira Kwotto	(ire-kpá)	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	á-kí'kóɾí	

PYIG. u-gbī (i-) 'snail' (AK. C.S. 363)

C.S. 72

		PN *ə-kpɔNi	
1	Nupe	kpomi	'okro'
2	Nupe Tako	á-kpɔm(i)	
3	Gwari	ə-kpɛ̃mí	
4	Gwari Yamma	ò-kpɛ̃mí	
5	Gade	(rì-k*óibí)	
		PEB *ε-kpɛfu	
6	Ebira Okene	e-péhu	'okro'
7	Ebira Kwotto	è-kpè	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	e-péfú	

C.S. 208

		PN *CV -gbakhuN	
1	Nupe	e-gbà	'axe'
2	Nupe Tako	a-gbà	
3	Gwari	gbakɛ̃ù	
4	Gwari Yamma	gbakɛ̃ù	
5	Gade	dùgbà	

	PEB *ira-ga		
6.	Ebira Okene	irà-gà	'axe'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	irà-gà	
8.	Eṭunṭ (Igarra)	irà-gà	

PYIG. e-dū	'axe'	(AK. C.S. 117)
PYOR -ké	'axe'	(AK. C.S. 272)
PE. A-juani (I-)	'axe'	(EL. C.S. 102)

C.S. 212

	PN *gbigòN		
1.	Nupe	gbìgà	'ask'
2.	Nupe Tako	gbìgò	
3.	Gwari	ṣà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(bi...ngè) ('to know how')	

	PEB *fusetje		
6.	Ebira Okene	hùsè	'ask'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hùretjé	
8.	Eṭunṭ (Igarra)	fò ~ fùswè	

PYIG. bí	'ask (question)	(AK. C.S. 2)
PE. bhianha	'ask'	(EL. C.S. 7)
PE. no	'ask, question'	(EL. C.S. 162)
PWS. bí- (bifíá)	'fragen'	(West. p. 208; Yor. and Okp.)
Pl. fi	'ask'	(Wil.)

C.S. 73.

	PN *CV-gbəgbə		
1.	Nupe	gbèrè	'root'
2.	Nupe Tako	gbèrè	
3.	Gwari	à-gbeg'è	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gbèr'è	
5.	Gade	tú-gbògbò	

	PEB *ε -kpa		
6.	Ebira Okene	è-potfí	εpa + otfí Body + stick/tree
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-kpà	

8. Etunọ (Igarra) e-pà
 cf. Yoruba 'gbòṅgbò 'root'

C.S. 88

PN *gbuodiNko

- | | | | |
|------|--------------------|-----------------------------------|---------|
| | | | 'thigh' |
| 1. | Nupe | gbòko | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | bu ₃ ik ^w o | |
| 3. | Gwari | bù ₃ ik ^w ó | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bwò ₃ ṅgwó | |
| 5. | Gade | gwògji | |
| | PEB *u-siji | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-sí | 'thigh' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | i -siji | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | u-sí | |
| PYIG | u-tiā (i-) 'thigh' | (AK. C.S. 97) | |

C.S. 210

PN *gba

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------|-------|
| | | | 'dig' |
| 1. | Nupe | gbà | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | gbà | |
| 3. | Gwari | (ṅi) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (ṅi) | |
| 5. | Gade | gbà | |
| | PEB *gba | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (tṣi) | 'dig' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | gbà | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | bà | |

PYIG. gwà/guà 'dig' (AK. C.S. 316)

PE. tɔN 'dig' (EL. C.S. 182)

PLN. gwu 'dig' (Wil.33)

C.S. 74

PN *-gbhuopiNi

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------------|--------|
| | | | 'left' |
| 1. | Nupe | g ^w àpì | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-gòpi | |
| 3. | Gwari | bwápmi | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bwápmí | |
| 5. | Gade | (gà-pèrè) | |

	PEB *u-bɔfa		
6.	Ebira Okene	u-vɔhá	'left'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-bɔ́há	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	u-vɔ́fa	

PYIG. o-si 'left (hand side)' (AK. C.S. 130)

C.S. 75

	PN *-gbhuɔ-		
1.	Nupe	a-g ^w alò	'right (side)'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-golò	
3.	Gwari	bwai ₃ è	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bwańd ₃ ie	
5.	Gade	(gà-rí rí')	

	PEB *-bɔri		
6.	Ebira Okene	u-vɔ́ri	'right (side)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-bɔ́ri	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	u-v ɔ́ri	

PYIG. ɔ-tu 'right (hand side)' (AK. C.S. 94)

C.S. 194

	PN *e-gbhə		
1.	Nupe	e-g ^w o'	'grass'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-g ^w ó	
3.	Gwari	gbógbè	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(sáíjgo)	
5.	Gade	(à-bi)	

	PEB *a-bi		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ví	'grass'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-bī	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-ví	

The similarity observed between 5 and PEB suggests that i the parent.
Cl. Yoruba igbó 'grass'

C.S. 76

	PN *CV-gbhɔɔ-		
			'hand'

1.	Nupe	e-g*a
2.	Nupe Tako	a-go
3.	Gwari	o-bwá
4.	Gwari Yamma	wagmá
5.	Gade	gʉ-b*o

PEB *u-bɔ

6.	Ebira Okene	u-vɔ	'hand'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-bɔ	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	u-vɔ	

- PYIG. ɔ-b'ɔ 'hand' (AK. C.S. 31)
 PE. ghU-bɔ (A-) 'hand' (EL. C.S. 17)
 PB. -bókò 'arm' (Gl. C.S. 158)
 PWS. -búá, -búák- 'oberarm' (West. p. 212)

C.S. 199

PN *e-gbhi

1.	Nupe	e-gi	(ʒi)	'child(ren)'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-dʒl	(ʒi)	
3.	Gwari	e-bí	(a-)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-bí	(a-)	
5.	Gade	ú-bí	(ba-)	

PEB *o-zi

6.	Ebira Okene	o-zi	(e-)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-zi	(-ni)	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	o-zi	(e-)	

C.S. 216

PN *gbhokana

1.	Nupe	gbóká	'strong'
2.	Nupe Tako	gbóká	
3.	Gwari	(kárá)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	wógānā	
5.	Gade	(ɲantsɪ)	

PEB *u-kata

6.	Ebira Okene	u-kata	'strong'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ɲúŋkpahɪ)	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	kátá	

cf. Yoruba gbókeke 'very strong'

C.S. 215

PN *gbhiə

1.	Nupe	g ^ɔ e	'good'
2.	Nupe Tako	gb ^ɔ e	
3.	Gwari	b ^ɔ a	
4.	Gwari Yamma	b ^ɔ a	
5.	Gade	jéjé	
	PEB *-zoza		
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-zózà	'good'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(wúsà)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	zózà	

PE chiamhi 'be good' (EL C.S. 41)

C.S. 214

PN *gbhiə

1.	Nupe	gbè ~ bè	'blow (with mouth)'
2.	Nupe Tako	bè	
3.	Gwari	(sufi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	biá	
5.	Gade	(re afu, sú, wu) 'blow'	
	PEB *kuahɪ		'blow (with mouth)'
6.	Ebira Okene	(tu)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	kwahɪ	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	kwahɪ , fáfe	

PYIG. fé 'blow (of wind, with mouth)' (AK C.S. 63)

PE. phupho 'blow (with mouth)' (EL C.S. 179)

PWS. -pap, -pep- 'wind' (West. p.274 ; Yor.)

PB. -pèèpè 'wind' (Gt. C.S. 1491)

PB. -pépè 'wind' (Gt. C.S. 1493)

C.S. 213

PN *gbhiti

'run'

1.	Nupe	gbitɪ	
2.	Nupe Tako	bitsi	
3.	Gwari	busi	

4	Gwari Yamma	buti	
	Gade	(tsaakji)	
5.	PEB *zuetji		
	Ebira Okene	zwétji	'run'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	(detji)	
7.	Etunọ (Igarra)	zwe	
8.			

PYIG. sá 'run (a race)' (AK. 134)

C.S. 233

	PN *gbaghi		
1.	Nupe	bági	'man'
2.	Nupe Tako	bádzi	
3.	Gwari	zánugbáji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(mísa)	
5.	Gade	(úròòrò)	
	PEB *ɔ-nɔru		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-nɔrú	'man'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-nɔrú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-nɔrú	

PYIG. ɔ-kɔ 'husband (male) (AK. C.S. 283)
 PE O-chi- (I-) 'husband' (EL. C.S. 44)

C.S. 172

	PN *wia		
1.	Nupe	wáza	'look for'
2.	Nupe Tako	wáza	
3.	Gwari	w ^ɔ èká	
4.	Gwari Yamma	w ^ɔ è	
5.	Gade	(dejapú)	
	PEB *si		
6.	Ebira Okene	si	'look for'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	si	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	si	

cf. Yoruba wa 'look for'

C.S. 81

	PN *CV-wa		
1.	Nupe	e-wa	'snake'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-wa	

3	Gwari	o-wa	
4	Gwari Yamma	o-wa	
5	Gade	gù-wá	

PEB *ε-wu

6	Ebira Okene	ε-u	'snake'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ε-wu	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	(i-st(f))	

C.S. 78

PN *wu

1	Nupe	wo	'hear'
2	Nupe Tako	wo	
3	Gwari	wo	
4	Gwari Yamma	hávó	
5	Gade	wu	

PEB *wu

6	Ebira Okene	wú	'hear'
7	Ebira Kwotto	wú	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	wú	

PYIG. gbó 'hear' (AK. C.S. 360)

PE. chuánhə, chianhi 'hear' (EL. C.S. 48)

C.S. 77

PN *wu

1	Nupe	wu	'kill'
2	Nupe Tako	wu	
3	Gwari	wu	
4	Gwari Yamma	wú	
5	Gade	wó	

PEB *wu

6	Ebira Okene	wu	'kill'
7	Ebira Kwotto	wu	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	wu	

PYIG. lú 'beat (person, drum) (AK. C.S. 210)

PE. gbeGi 'beat, kill' (EL. C.S. 90)

C.S. 79

PN *wo

'new'

1.	Nupe	woro	
2.	Nupe Tako	woro	
3.	Gwari	welwei	(wo)we+i (rdl.)
4.	Gwari Yamma	wowe	
5.	Gade	(pɪpa)	
	PEB *ɔ-wɔwɔ		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-wɔwá	'new'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-wɔ:wá	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-wɔwá	

PYIG. -tù	'be new (rdl.)'	(AK. C.S. 95)
PE pha	'be new'	(EL. C.S. 174)
-gbo	'newness'	(EL. C.S. 93)

C.S. 219

	PN * CV-wo		
1.	Nupe	gúwo	'ten'
2.	Nupe Tako	guwo	
3.	Gwari	ñ-wó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	piawo	
5.	Gade	ú-bwó	
	PEB *ɛ-wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɛ-u	'ten'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-wú	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɛ-wú	

PYIG. ɛ-gwá /ɛ-guá/	'ten'	(AK. C.S. 313)
PE. gbeNi	'ten'	(EL. C.S. 91)
PWS. -guá	'Zehn'	(West. p. 225-6; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 220

	PN * V-wu		'robe/gown/smock'
1.	Nupe	e-wò	
2.	Nupe Tako	à-wúbádʒí	
3.	Gwari	(dʒékpe)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(è-djelugwe)	
5.	Gade	tégwo	
	PEB *a-ruɔbapi		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-rúɔbápi	'robe/gown/smock'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(i-tógbe)	

8 Etuno (Igarra) a-rò
 PYIG á-wù 'gown, robe' (AK, C.S. 50)

C.S. 231 PN* wuNakpa

- | | | |
|----------------|------------|--------|
| 1. Nupe | ŋ*ŋkpá | 'long' |
| 2. Nupe Tako | (gbàrò) | |
| 3. Gwari | (dàláláji) | |
| 4. Gwari Yamma | m*ákpa | |
| 5. Gade | --- | |

PEB *ɔ-gòdò

- | | | |
|-------------------|--------|--------|
| 6. Ebira Okene | ɔ-gòdò | 'long' |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | ɔ-gòdò | |
| 8. Etuno (Igarra) | ɔ-gòdò | |

Yoruba gù 'be long'
 PE. dedhi 'be long (of stick)' (EL. C.S. 53)

C.S. 221

PN *wáN

- | | | |
|----------------|-----|---------|
| 1. Nupe | ŋ*á | 'catch' |
| 2. Nupe Tako | ŋ*ɔ | |
| 3. Gwari | ŋ*á | |
| 4. Gwari Yamma | ŋ*á | |
| 5. Gade | m*ɔ | |

PEB *za

- | | | |
|-------------------|---------|---------|
| 6. Ebira Okene | za | 'catch' |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | zá | |
| 8. Etuno (Igarra) | za, g*ɔ | |

PYIG. mū 'take (one thing), catch, seize hold' (AK. C.S. 59)
 PE. mu 'catch hold (in hand)' (EL. C.S. 149)
 PWS. mu, mua- 'greifen, fangen' (West. p.258; Yor. and Okp.)
 PLN. wnu 'catch' (Wil. 68)

C.S. 56

PN *wi

- | | | |
|--------------|----|---------|
| 1. Nupe | jí | 'steal' |
| 2. Nupe Tako | jí | |

	Gwari	w ^ɔ ɪ	
3.	Gwari Yamma	w ^ɔ ɪ	
4.	Gade	ji	
5.	PEB *ji		
	Ebira Okene	ji	'steal'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	ji	
7.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ji	
8.			

PYIG	ji	'steal'	(AK. C.S. 238)
PE.	o-ji (A-)	'thief'	(EL. C.S. 67)
PB.	-yib-	'steal'	(Gt. C.S. 1988)
	-yib-	'steal'	(Gt. C.S. 2020)

C.S. 57

PN *e-wie

	Nupe	è-jè	'eye'
1.	Nupe Tako	à-je	
2.	Gwari	e-w ^ɔ ɪ	
3.	Gwari Yamma	e-w ^ɔ ɪ	
4.	Gade	(japí)	
5.	PEB *e-ji		
	Ebira Okene	e-i	'eye'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	e-ji	
7.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-i	
8.			

PYIG e-jú 'eye' (AK. C.S. 252)

PE. dhl-dhu 'eye' (EL. C.S. 71)

C.S. 171

PN *V-wiji

	Nupe	e-ji	'guinea corn'
1.	Nupe Tako	a-ji	
2.	Gwari	á-w ^ɔ ɪ	
3.	Gwari Yamma	ò-w ^ɔ ɪ	
4.	Gade	(gù-tfù)	
5.	PEB *a-ku		
	Ebira Okene	à-kú	'guinea corn'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	à-kú	
7.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-kú	
8.			

C.S. 218

PN *wa

	Nupe	wá	'want, desire'
1.			

2.	Nupe Tako	wá	
3.	Gwari	(jé)	
3.	Gwari Yamma	—	
4.	Gade	(jé)	
5.	PEB *si		
6.	Ebira Okene	si	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	si	'want, desire'
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	si	

PYIG. fe 'want(desire)' (AK. C.S. 62)

5.6 PN Consonant System Reduction

PN consonant system is a lot richer than that of the daughter languages. This is due to mergers that have taken place in the development of the sounds in Nupoid. Restructuring within the different sound systems also influence reduction of the PN sound system. Some of the sound changes observed in the development of Nupoid from PN are presented below.

(5)

- *m > [ɲ] = palatalisation
- *ɸ > [b] = loss of suction = merger of both.
- *p > [b] / -i, ts = affrication = overlap
- *bh > [v] = spirantisation
- *ph > [f], [s] = spirantisation = merger
- *t > [ts], [tʃ] = affrication; [ʃ] = spirantisation; [tn] = nasal release = overlap
- *d > [dʒ], [ʒ], [dʲ] = affrication; spirantisation; palatalisation=overlap
- *n > [ɲ] = palatalisation, [ɲʷ] weakening i.e. to /w/ = overlap
- *nh > [n] = hardening, [r] = overlap
- *s > [ʃ], /i + palatalisation
- *z > [dʒ], [ʒ] / -i = palatalisation
- *tʃ / > [tʃ] / -[V, -bk] = affrication, [ʃ] = spirantisation
- *tʃ / > [ɲ] = nasalisation
- *k > [kɲ] = nasal release, tʃ = affrication, s = spirantisation, kʲ = palatalization
- *k > [g] = voicing intervocalically
- *g > [dʒ], [ʒ], [gʲ] = affrication; spirantisation, palatalisation respectively; [gɲ] = nasal release

- *gh > [dʒ/ʒ], [v] = spirantisation, [gʲ] = palatalisation, [ŋŋ] = nasalization
- *kp > [kpiŋm] = nasal release
- *gbh > [g],[b],[w] = hardening, [ŋʷ] = nasalization of [w]
- */kh/ > [ŋʷ] in C² position in some languages = weakening
- */w/ > [ŋʷ] = nasalisation, [m] = loss of velar articulation; [j] = loss of labial-velar articulation.
- */wh/ > [w] = hardening
- *C > [ø] = loss

5.7 Vowels of PN

(6) A phonetic inventory of PN vowels

i	u
ɪ	ʊ
e	o
ɛ	ɔ
	ɔ̃
	a

Ten vowels are reconstructed in PN although Nupe has five and some others seven. They are *i, *ɪ, *e, *ɛ, *ə, *a, *ɔ, *o, *u, and *u. There are no nasalised counterparts since nasalization is traceable to a nasal consonant in the second syllable in the stem. These vowels can easily be classified into two sets based on harmony: [-ATR] and [+ATR] vowels. As a result of vowel system reduction only vestiges of vowel harmony is observed in some of the Nupoid languages. Where vowel harmony is attested the vowels harmonise with the stem affixes.

5.7.1 PN Stem Vowels

PN vowels all occur in the stem. They are *i, *ɪ, *e, *ɛ, *a, *ɔ, *o, *u, and *u. Each of them has reflexes of identical phonetic shape as itself. Some of the vowels also have

reflexes of differing phonetic shapes. The differences are sometimes caused by the fact that vowels in 3 and 4 are traceable to the V^2 while those in 1, 2 and 3 are traceable to V^1 . This is as a result of the development of preceding nasally released consonants (see 2.2 and 5.2.2).

The development of nasalised vowels in Nupoid sometimes result in the occurrence of nasalised vowels in languages 1 and 2 and oral in languages 3 and 4 where the conditioning consonant (i.e. the second consonant in the stem) is realised as nasal release on the preceding consonant but is deleted in languages 1 and 2 leaving its effect on the retained vowel as nasalisation. The different reflexes in each language are presented along with the PN vowel. As can be observed in the Tables, Gade's vowels are often not identical with those in the other languages. This may be indicator of greater diversity in its development from PN.

5.7.2 Prefix Vowels

Prefix vowels are observed in PN although the nature of such vowels is not very clear since in most cases the reflexes are very varied in phonetic form. Prefixes in Gade are determined by the harmonic set of the stem vowel. In Nupe there has been a lot of vowel merging in the prefix since [e] is often the prefix vowel. As a result not much reconstruction of prefix vowels having reflexes of differing phonetic shape is done. Only where the phonetic shape of the reflexes is identical have we reconstructed the parent form.

5.8 Development of vowels from PN

The development of the reflexes from PN vowels are as follows:

Nasalised reflexes occur in the environment of a nasal consonant i.e. they become nasalised.

[u] occurs as reflex of *i and sometimes [o] occurs as reflex of *e in Gwari and Gwari Yamma when they assimilate the labial features of a preceding labial consonant sound.

Whenever ø is found in the correspondence sets it means the Proto has no segmental realisation. A vowel of different phonetic shape sometimes occurs as reflex of a reduplicated stem vowel. Synchronic evidence in the phonology of the languages reveals vowel system reduction as such reflexes of differing phonetic shape from the parent vowel occur phonetically. E.g. neutralisation of contrast between /ɛ/, /ɔ/ and /a/. Reconstruction of vowel sequences such as *[iə], *[uɔ], *[iɛ], *[iu] is informed by the nature of the correspondences. For instance when a consonant that precedes a vowel which normally does not trigger palatalisation is palatalised then [i] is reconstructed before such a vowel to account for the palatalisation. Basically the vowel sequences reconstructed are those from which the reflexes may develop through phonological changes. For example [e] as reflex of *iə is explained as instance of change in quality as a result of realisation of a mid vowel quality between [i] and [ə]: *iə > e. To a large extent, development of reflexes from PN reveals reduction of the PN vowels. For instance ten vowels are reconstructed in PN but Nupe has five while some others have seven and yet others nine or ten.

Some PN prefixes of differing phonetic shape are presented in the table below.

Table 6. PN front vowels with reflexes of differing phonetic shape

PN	1	2	3	4	5
*i	i, i	i, i	i, i, u, ø	u, i, ø	i, i
*e	i, e	i, e	e, a, ø	e, e, o	eu
*ε	a	ε	i	i, a	ε

Table 7. PN central vowels having reflexes of differing phonetic shape

*ɔ	e, a, o	e, ɔ, o	ɔ, a	ɔ, e	e, ɔ
*ɛ	i, e, a, o	i, e, a, ɔ, o	i, e, ɔ	i, e, a	e, ε, ɔ
*a	o, a, ā,	a, e, ɔ	a, a, e	a, e, ā	e, a

Table 8. PN back vowels having reflexes of differing phonetic shape

PN	1	2	3	4	5
*u	u, ū	u, ū	u	ū	u, o, i
*iu	i, u	i, u	u	u	u, i
*o	o, u	o, u	u, o, u,	o, u	u, u
*i	i	i	-	-	u
*o	o	o	o, e	o	u, i
*ɔ	a, ā, ɔ, o	ɔ, ɔ	a, ā, ɔ	a, ā, ɔ	a, ε

CHAPTER SIX

6.0 COMPARATIVE EBIROID PHONOLOGY

6.0.1 Introduction

This chapter contains Proto-Ebiroid (PEB) consonant and vowel reconstructions. The reconstructions are made after an examination of the phonetic sound correspondences drawn from the languages. Sounds are reconstructed on the basis of phonetic plausibility governed by principles of sound change. Where the corresponding sounds are varied, my choice is determined the most widespread sound or by the phonetic plausibility of deriving the majority of corresponding sounds from one of them provided it has not been reconstructed earlier. I try to provide explanations to account for the development of each sound from the reconstructed one in such cases.

The correspondence sets (c.s.) are of two types: those of identical phonetic shape and those with unidentical phonetic shape. In the former, no change is reflected in the sound shift whereas in the latter assumptions that some sound shift has taken place is made. The vocalic environments responsible for such sound shifts are considered before reconstruction is made and where there is no evidence from such environments, reconstruction is made on the basis of other phonological processes that may have occurred such as weakening, elision etc. The overall pattern of the phonetic sound inventory as well as reconstructions in other branches of Niger-Congo is considered to determine the possible phonetic shape of the Proto-sound. The c.s. are presented only in phonetic form for easy comprehension.

Reconstructed sounds are presented along their c.s. and a list of the relevant

C.S. c.s.'s of differing phonetic shape and those with non-cognate items are listed separately from those having similar shape. Also a dash is placed in parentheses where the correspondences are not cognate. The possible line of development of reflexes from the reconstructed sounds is discussed. Consonants are discussed before vowels starting with the labial place of articulation followed by the alveolar, the palatal, velar, glottal and finally the labial-velar.

For ease of reference the languages and dialect are indicated by the following numbers which is a continuation of the numbers representing the Nupoid languages.

Ebira Okene	6
Ebira Kwotto	7
Etuno	8

PEB reconstructed items from which correspondence sets are established to reconstruct the PEB consonants are cited here from Volume Two for easy and quick reference. This is why the numbering is not serial here unlike in Volume Two. The PEB reconstructions for each item are also presented to show the extent of cognation with PN.

PEB CONSONANTS

(1) A PHONETIC INVENTORY OF PEB CONSONANTS:

	Labial	Alveolar	Palato- alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Glottal	Labial- velar
Nasal	m	n		ɲ	ŋ		
Labialised Nasal							ŋ ^w
Plosive	(p) b	t d			k g		kp gb
Affricate			tʃ dʒ				
Fricative	f	s z	ʃ			h	
Approximant		r		j			w

6.1.1 Notes on consonants

[p] is enclosed in brackets because its reconstruction is tentative.

In PEB, only nasals, plosives and affricates are the stops reconstructed. There are no lenis sounds as observable seen in 1. Fricatives and approximants are also reconstructed in PEB. Palatalisation, affrication, deaffrication, spirantisation (fricativisation), hardening and weakening are processes that seem to have brought about the sound changes observed in the development of reflexes. The role of assumed role of each process is discussed below.

6.1.1.1 Nasals

*m *n *ɲ *ŋ

Reconstructed nasals in PEB are *m, *n, *ɲ and *ŋ produced at the bilabial, alveolar, palatal and velar places of articulation respectively. Their development in PEB is regular and synchronic evidence for their reconstruction can be found in the Tables below.

6.1.1.2 Plosives

*(p) *b *t *d *k *g *kp *gb

Pairs of voiceless and voiced plosives are reconstructed at four different places of articulation in PEB: bilabial, alveolar, velar and labial-velar. The development of each pair except the labial-velar is regular as observable in the Tables below. The labial-velars, *kp and *gb developed into [p] and [b] respectively in 6 and 8. This development involves loss of the velar articulation or better still the suction aspect of the articulation.

There is no evidence of suction or implosives in PEB

6.1.1.3 Implosives

No Implosives are attested in Ebiroid

6.1.1.4 Affricates and Fricatives

*tʃ : *dʒ
*f : - *s : *z *ʃ : - *h : -

PEB affricates are the voiceless and voiced palato-alveolar: *tʃ, *dʒ. The reconstructed fricatives are the voiceless labiodental fricative *f, the voiceless and voiced alveolar fricatives *s, *z; the voiceless palato-alveolar *ʃ and the voiceless glottal fricative *h. Synchronic evidence for their reconstruction can be found in the Tables below. All the voiceless fricatives except the alveolar pair have gaps in the voiced columns.

6.1.1.5 Approximants

PEB approximant sounds are *r and *w. *w sometimes develops into ə apart from [w]. [r] developed from *r and is in free variation with [l] in 7.

Synchronic evidence for their reconstruction can be found in the Tables below.

6.2 Development of Consonants from PEB

The changes observed in the development of the reflexes from PEB seem to have been as a result of different processes such as palatalisation, nasalisation, affrication, deaffrication, spirantisation (fricativisation), hardening and even weakening.

6.2.1 Palatalisation

Palatalisation is observed in the development of some Ebiroid sounds. For instance *k and *g before [i] and [ɪ] are [tʃ] and [dʒ] respectively. The place of

articulation changes from velar to palato-alveolar.

6.2.2 Nasalisation

Nasalisation in Ebiroid is predictable and therefore not significant. Sounds are nasalised after nasal consonants. Significant nasalization is therefore not reconstructed in PEB.

6.2.3 Affrication and Deaffrication

Affrication is observed in the development of *k and *g before [i] and [ɪ] in PEB. They become [tʃ] and [dʒ] respectively through palatalisation, but by affrication the manner changes from stop to affricate. Affrication thus refers to the sound change involving stop becoming affricate. *tʃ > s is one instance of deaffrication found in Etuno.

6.2.4 Spirantisation

Spirantisation involves change of a sound to fricative. This could involve a plosive or affricate becoming a fricative. The process thus involves some weakening process. Both spirantisation and weakening are observed in the development of sounds from PEB. A change in manner of production in the development of the consonants is demonstrated in *b, *tʃ, *dʒ, becoming [v], [s] and [h], respectively i.e. stop becomes fricative and affricate becomes fricative *b developing into [v] in 6 and 8, *dʒ becoming [h] and tʃ* becoming [s] are instances of spirantisation.

6.2.5 Hardening

Hardening is achieved when a sound derived from an original one is of a stronger articulation than the original. This is not observed in the development of reflexes of PEB since there are no implosives.

6.2.6 Weakening

Weakening is the process by which a stop sound becomes fricative, approximant, and, finally, a zero (Elugbe 1989:109). It involves development of a sound that is of weaker articulation than the original, *b, *j and *w became [v], [ʝ] and [ø] respectively i.e. approximant becomes null are instances of weakening.

6.3 Tables showing PEB Consonants and their reflexes

Table 9 Labials

PEB	*m	*p?	*b	*f
Ebira Okene	m	p	v	h
Ebira Kwotto	m	-	b	h
Etuno	m	p	v	f

Table 10 Alveolars

PEB	*n	*t	*d	*r	*s	*z
Ebira Okene	n	t	d	r	s	z
Ebira Kwotto	n	t	d	r/l	s	z
Etuno	n	t	d	r	s	z

Table 11 Palatals

PEB	*ɲ	*tʃ	*dʒ	*ʃ	*j
Ebira Okene	ɲ	tʃ	dʒ	h	j/ø
Ebira Kwotto	ɲ	tʃ	dʒ/h	h	j
Etuno	ɲ	tʃ/s	dʒ	ʃ/s	j/ø

Table 12 Velars

PEB	*ŋ ^w	*k	*g
Ebira Okene	ŋ ^w	k	g
Ebira Kwotto	ŋ ^w	k	g
Etuno	ŋ ^w	k	g

Table 13 Labial-Velars

PEB	*kp	*gb	*w
Ebira Okene	p	b	w/ø
Ebira Kwotto	kp	gb	w
Etuno	p	b	w

Table 14 Glottal

PEB	*h
Ebira Okene	h
Ebira Kwotto	h
Etuno	h

6.4 Correspondence Sets and Development of Consonants from PEB to Ebiroid

Reconstructed sounds are presented in the following order: Labials, Alveolars, Palatals, Velars, and Labial-velars. Within each class of consonant sounds, the stops are presented first, next the fricatives and then the approximants. Of the stop class nasals are presented first next the plosives followed by the affricates. Below are the PEB sounds and the correspondences from which they are reconstructed. Identical correspondences are indicated first where attested and then those of non-identical shape are explained.

6.4.1 Labials

c.s.1 PEB *m	:C.S. 1,2, 16,129, 157, 158,159
	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	m ~ m ~ m
	C.S. 16 (-) ~ m ~ m
	C.S. 59 m ~ (-) ~ m

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape with *m but for the non-cognate items.

c.s. 2 PEB *p?	:C.S. 122, 159, 197, 227
	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	C.S. 122 p ~ (-) ~ p
	C.S. 159 p ~ (-) ~ p
	C.S. 197 p ~ (-) ~ p
	C.S. 227 p ~ (-) ~ p

The reconstruction here is tentative because correspondence in 7 is not

cognate. It is interesting to note that in these items: 'C.S. 122: soup', C.S. 159: bag' and 'C.S. 197: pass by' 7 is not cognate with 6 and 8. In most other C.S 7 is cognate with [p] corresponding to [p] in the other two dialects e.g. C.S. 3, 72, 73 More data may confirm this c.s as a different set in which 7 has [p]. C.S. 227- 'horn' is a basic item in which there is no cognate situation between 7 and 6/8.

c.s. 3 PEB *b :C.S. 9-15, 74-76, 113, 145, 116, 162, 194
6 ~ 7 ~ 8
v ~ b ~ v
C.S. 113 m ~ b ~ v

The c.s is of differing phonetic shape: [v] and [b]. *b from which [v] can develop through weakening is reconstructed (i.e. stop becoming fricative). Only in 7 is the Proto shape retained. Correspondences in 6 and 8 have undergone weakening. In C.S. 113, the correspondence in 6 is [m] suggestive of *b becoming [m] in the environment of a nasal sound.

c.s. 4 PEB *b? :C.S. 19, 133
6 ~ 7 ~ 8
C.S. 19 v ~ (-) ~ v
C.S. 133 v ~ (-) ~ v

The reconstruction here is considered to be *b but with a ? because 7 which normally has [b] when 6 and 8 have [v], is non-cognate here. The correspondences in 6 and 8 are considered reflexes of *b since 7 is not cognate.

More data may reveal a cognate form in 7 with stem consonant [b] or even a [v] in which case *v would be reconstructed.

c.s. 5 PEB *f / [V, +bk] :C.S. 4,5,7,20,22, 86, 110, 111,128, 131 137, 155, 166, 167,
196, 101,211, 212, 223
6 ~ 7 ~ 8

C.S. 128	h ~ h ~ f
C.S. 196	h ~ (-) ~ f
C.S. 101	h ~ (-) ~ f
	(-) ~ h ~ f

The c.s. is of non-identical phonetic shapes: 6 - [h], 7 - [h], 8 - [f]. It excludes the environment before front vowels discussed in c.s. 17. *f not *h is reconstructed because of the phonetic plausibility of development of [h] from *f than the reverse.

6.4.2 Alveolars

c.s. 6 PEB *n : C.S. 35, 44, 112, 114, 130, 138, 146, 148, 183, 209, 224, 233, 234

	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	n ~ n ~ n
C.S. 130	n ~ n ~ (-)
C.S. 209	(-) ~ n ~ n
C.S. 224	n ~ - ~ n

The PEB c.s. is of identical phonetic shape with the reconstructed sound *n where the forms are cognate.

c.s. 7 PEB *t : C.S. 23-29, 36-37, 85, 106, 108, 135, 143, 153, 169, 187, 232, 242

	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	t ~ t ~ t
C.S. 143	t ~ (-) ~ t
C.S. 153	t ~ (-) ~ t
C.S. 242	t ~ - ~ t

The corresponding sounds have developed from the Proto in a similar way. I consider the C.S. in 143, 153 and 245 to have developed from *t although 7 is not cognate.

c.s. 8 PEB *d : C.S. 30-32, 144, 230

	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	d ~ d ~ d
C.S. 144	d ~ (-) ~ d

c.s. 9 PEB *r : C.S. 33, 49, 107, 118, 142, 177, 189, 198, 202, 220

	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	r ~ r ~ r
C.S. 142	r ~ (-) ~ r

C.S. 220 r ~ (-) ~ r
 C.S. 49 r ~ l ~ r

The occurrence of [l] in 7 in C.S. 49 is traced to the Hausa item for citrus fruit = [lɛmo]. It is cognate with the other forms in Ebiroid. The forms in 6 and 8 are also cognate with the Yoruba form [òrombó] 'orange'.

c.s. 10 PEB *s C.S. 38, 84, 88, 96, 109, 140, 149, 152, 160, 163, 172, 175, 176, 218, 225, 226
 6 ~ 7 ~ 8
 s ~ s ~ s
 C.S. 225 s ~ - ~ s
 C.S. 226 s ~ (-) ~ s

c.s. 11 PEB *z C.S. 46, 47, 50, 70, 104, 105, 117, 199, 213, 215, 221, 236, 240
 6 ~ 7 ~ 8
 z ~ z ~ z
 C.S. 50 z ~ (-) ~ z
 C.S. 117, 213 z ~ (-) ~ z
 C.S. 240 z ~ - ~ z

The reconstructed sound is of identical phonetic shape with their respective reflexes.

6.4.3 Palatals

c.s. 12 PEB *ɲ C.S. 34, 58, 61, 62, 63, 91, 94, 115, 174, 201, C.S. 61, 62
 6 ~ 7 ~ 8
 ɲ ~ ɲ ~ ɲ
 C.S. 174 (-) ~ ɲ ~ ɲ
 C.S. 61 ɲ ~ ɲ ~ ɲ
 C.S. 62 ɲ ~ n ~ ɲ

[n] in 7 in C.S. 61 is derived through coalescence of [ɲ] and the following vowel [i] to give a syllabic [ɲ]. In C.S. 62, the form in 7 is considered an older form and therefore the difference in word structure.

c.s. 13 PEB *tʃ C.S. 39, 40-43, 64, 134, 141, 181
 6 ~ 7 ~ 8

tʃ ~ tʃ ~ tʃ

tʃ is reconstructed here since the reflexes are of identical phonetic shape. This C.S. excludes the environment before back vowels discussed in c.s. 21. C.S. 39 is the only instance of [tʃ] occurring before back vowel [u] and this is may have been as a result of loss of a front vowel before [u] in the derivation of the surface form from two different morphemes.

c.s. 14 PEB *tʃ ?

C.S. 89

6 ~ 7 ~ 8

C.S. 89

tʃ ~ tʃ ~ s

The reconstruction here is tentative pending availability of more data from which more correspondences can be drawn. Here *s, the alternative to *tʃ is not reconstructed because it has been reconstructed in c.s. 10 where the correspondences are regular with *s. Also, [s] in 8 can be explained as an instance of spirantisation. *ts a possible proto-sound is not reconstructed here because the vowel after the consonant in C.S. 89 is [a] and this vowel normally does not initiate palatalisation whereby *ts > tʃ. Secondly in Ebira it is [k] that becomes [tʃ] before [i]/[ɪ] not [ts]. Existing correspondences are first considered in the reconstructions before speculating intermediate stages in the development of the reflexes.

c.s. 15 PEB *dʒ

: C.S. 51, 52, 185, 200, 229

6 ~ 7 ~ 8

dʒ ~ dʒ ~ dʒ

C.S. 200

dʒ ~ (-) ~ dʒ

C.S. 229

dʒ ~ -- ~ dʒ

This c.s. excludes the environment before back vowels found in c.s. 22.

c.s. 16 PEB *d₃? : C.S. 184

6 ~ 7 ~ 8
d₃ ~ h ~ d₃

This c.s. is tentative since it is supported by only one item. It is slightly different from c.s. 16 in that [d₃] corresponds to [h], an approximant. *d₃ rather than *h is reconstructed here because [h] can develop from *d₃ through spirantisation before [ɪ]. A hardening process whereby an *h develops into [d₃] is not very likely. The c.s. excludes the environment before back vowels found in c.s. 22. Again as argued in c.s. 14, *dz a possible proto-sound is not reconstructed here because in Ebira [g] becomes [d₃] before [ɪ] not [dz]. Also the existing correspondences are first considered in the reconstructions before speculating intermediate stages in the development of the reflexes.

c.s. 17 PEB *j /- [V, -bk] : C.S. 6, 8, 17/18, 21, 45, 92, 123, 125, 126, 132, 151, 154, 164, 165, 170, 191
6 ~ 7 ~ 8
h ~ h ~ j
C.S. 156 h ~ (-) ~ s

The c.s. here is different from that in c.s. 5 because in 8 [j] is the corresponding sound not [f]. It is important to note that in 8 [f] occurs before back vowels and [j] before front ones at the phonetic level. In C.S. 156, [s] is found before [ɛ] and as such does not become [j].

c.s. 18 PEB *j : C.S. 53-57, 59, 120, 121, 195, 204, 217, 228, 237
6 ~ 7 ~ 8
j ~ j ~ j

C.S. 57, 195 ø ~ j ~ ø
 C.S. 228 ø ~ j ~ j

The c.s. is of identical phonetic shape with the reconstructed sound but in C.S. 195. [j] has weakened to zero point in 6 and 8 therefore no consonant is attested.

c.s. 19 PEB *j ? C.S. 60
 6 ~ 7 ~ 8
 j ~ n ~ j

In C.S. 60, 6 and 7 have different correspondences. The form in 6 is actually /j/ phonemically. Metathesis can be said to have caused the presence of [n] in 7. Some relationship is observed between the form in 7 and the Yoruba morphemes.

7	Yoruba
[>-nǫé] 'woman / female'	[ɛni] 'person' + [jé] 'to lay / give birth'

6.4.4 Velars

c.s. 20PEB *ŋ^w : C.S. 82, 90, 93, 103, 124, 147, 119
 6 ~ 7 ~ 8
 ŋ^w ~ ŋ^w ~ ŋ^w

*ŋ^w is labialised [ŋ] before back vowels.

c.s. 21 PEB *k : C.S. 65-67, 69, 87, 98, 127, 150, 161, 171, 179, 203, 205 214, 216, 239

	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	k ~ k ~ k
C.S. 67	k ~ (-) ~ k
C.S. 161	k ~ (-) ~ k
C.S. 216	k ~ (-) ~ k
C.S. 215	(-) ~ k ~ k
C.S. 71	k ~ (-) ~ k
C.S. 238	k ~ -- ~ k
C.S. 193	(-) ~ g ~ k

This c.s. excludes environment before front vowels discussed in c.s. 13/14. The c.s. (with the exception of non-cognate items) are of identical phonetic shape with the

reconstructed sounds respectively therefore *k is reconstructed here. [g] in 7 (C.S. 193) is explained as an instance of voiced [k].

c.s. 22 PEB *g : C.S. 68, 102, 178, 188, 208, 231

6 ~ 7 ~ 8

g ~ g ~ g

C.S. 178 g ~ (-) ~ g

(c.s. 22 excludes the environment before front vowels).

6.4.5 Glottal

c.s. 23 PEB *h?

C.S. 97, 139, 189

6 ~ 7 ~ 8

C.S. 97

h ~ h ~ (-)

C.S. 139

h ~ h ~ (-)

C.S. 189

h ~ h ~ h

This c.s. is tentative because only one item, C.S. 189, actually supports it. More data may confirm this c.s. in which 8 has [h] as found in the others.

c.s. 24 PEB *h?

C.S. 179

6 ~ 7 ~ 8

C.S. 179 h ~ j ~ ø

In this c.s. (which is also tentative because only one item is cited.) the sound is weakened to [j] in 7 and to ø in 8.

Labial-velar

c.s. 25 PEB *kp

C.S. 3, 72-73, 168, 173, 186

6 ~ 7 ~ 8

p ~ kp ~ p

C.S. 168 p ~ kp ~ (-)

The c.s. is of differing phonetic shapes: [p] and [kp]. *kp not *p is reconstructed because [p] can easily develop from *kp through loss of the velar articulation. A diachronic development of [kp] from *p (although historically possible), is highly unlikely

especially when the following vowel is not a high back vowel.

c.s. 26 PEB *gb

	C.S. 192, 206, 210, 222
	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
C.S. 192	b ~ gb ~ b
C.S. 206	(-) ~ gb ~ b
C.S. 210	(-) ~ gb ~ b
C.S. 222	b ~ (-) ~ b

I reconstruct *gb not *b because it is more natural for *gb to become simplified to [p] through loss of the velar articulation than the reverse i.e. acquisition of the velar feature by [b] before a front non-high vowel. C.S. 222 is included because only in 7 is the reflex not cognate and as the other correspondences show [b] in 6 and 8 always correspond to [gb] in 7.

c.s. 27 PEB *w

	C.S. 48, 77-81 83, 182, 219
	6 ~ 7 ~ 8
	w ~ w ~ w
C.S. 48, 219	ø ~ w ~ w
C.S. 81	ø ~ w ~ (-)

The c.s. are of identical phonetic shape with the reconstructed sound. The loss of [w] in 6 indicated by the null sign:ø is explained as an instance of total weakening of *w to zero.

6.5 PEB Reconstructions

The reconstructions are presented in the following order using the stem initial consonants: labial, alveolar, palatal, velar, glottal and labial-velar. The Labials sounds reconstructed are m, p, b, bh, ʃ, f, ph; alveolars: t, d, n, nh, s, z, l, lh; Palatals: c, ts, dʒ, j; Velars: k, g and the Labial-velars: kp, gb, gbh, w.

6.5.1 Labials

c.s. 1 PEB *m

C.S. 1 PEB *mazi 'give birth'

6.	Ebira Okene	muzi	<	ma + ozi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	mozi	<	bear + child	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ma		ma + ozi	
				bear + child	

C.S. 2 PEB *mune 'swallow'

6.	Ebira Okene	mú			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	múnè			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	múné			

C.S. 129 PEB *o-mu(ta) 'tail'

6.	Ebira Okene	ò-mùtá			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-mù			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-mù			

C.S. 157 PEB *mi 'extinguish'

6.	Ebira Okene	mi			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	mí			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	míó			

C.S. 158 PEB *me 'make'

6.	Ebira Okene	mè			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	mè			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	mè			

C.S. 16 PEB *e-mi 'feaces'

--	--	--	--	--	--

6	Ebira Okene	(è-hè)
7	Ebira Kwotto	e-mi
8	Etuno (Igarra)	e-mi

C.S. 159 PEB *a-mpo 'bag'

6	Ebira Okene	â-mpô
7	Ebira Kwotto	(â-diko)
8	Etuno (Igarra)	â-mpò

C.S. 122 PEB *ε-pe 'soup'

6	Ebira Okene	è-pè
7	Ebira Kwotto	(o'bo)
8	Etuno (Igarra)	è-pè

C.S. 197 PEB *pa(ra)fu 'pass by'

6	Ebira Okene	pàráhu
7	Ebira Kwotto	béhu
8	Etuno (Igarra)	pàràfú

C.S. 227 PEB *ɔ-paɲi 'horn'

5	Ebira Okene	ɔ-pàɲi
6	Ebira Kwotto	(ɔ-kàhu)
7	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-pàɲi

C.S. 9 PEB *irɛ-vu 'kolanut'

6	Ebira Okene	irɛ-vu
7	Ebira Kwotto	(oó-bi)
8	Etuno (Igarra)	irɛ-vú

C.S. 10 PEB *ɔ-ba 'husband'

6	Ebira Okene	ɔ̌-vá
7	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ̌-bá
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ̌-vá

C.S. 11

	PEB *ɔ̌-bu			'be white'
6	Ebira Okene	ɔ̌-vuúɔ̌vu	ɔ̌-vu + (ɔ̌vu)	
7	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ̌-ɔ̌bu		
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ̌-vuɔ̌vu	ɔ̌-vu + (ɔ̌vu)	

C.S. 12

	PEB *bu			'be rotten'
6	Ebira Okene	vù		
7	Ebira Kwotto	bù		
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	vù		

C.S. 13

	PEB *e-ba			'two'
6	Ebira Okene	è-va		
7	Ebira Kwotto	è-ba		
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	è-va		

C.S. 14

	PEB *irɛ-ba			'breasts'
6	Ebira Okene	iré-vá		
7	Ebira Kwotto	iré-bá		
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	iré-vá		

C.S. 15

	PEB *be			'come'
6	Ebira Okene	vé		
7	Ebira Kwotto	bé		
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	vé		

C.S. 74

	PEB *u-bɔha		
6	Ebira Okene	u-vóhá	'left'
7	Ebira Kwotto	u-bóha	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	u-vɔ'fa	

C.S. 75	PEB * -bɔri		
6	Ebira Okene	u-vóri	'right (side)'
7	Ebira Kwotto	u-bóri	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	u-vóri	

C.S. 76	PEB *u-bɔ		
6	Ebira Okene	u-vɔ'	'hand'
7	Ebira Kwotto	u-bɔ'	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	u-vɔ'	

C.S. 113	PEB *V-baNta		
6	Ebira Okene	u-mántà	'horse'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-bátà	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-vurátà	

C.S. 116	PEB *e-bu		
6	Ebira Okene	e-vú	'goat'
7	Ebira Kwotto	e-bú	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	e-vú	

C.S. 162	PEB *babe		
6	Ebira Okene	vávé	'return (intr.)'
7	Ebira Kwotto	bá(hama)bé	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	vá	

C.S. 194

PEB *a-bi			
6.	Ebira Okene	a-vi	'grass'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-bi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-vi	

C.S. 19 PEB *a-bi			
6.	Ebira Okene	a-vi	'leaf'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(a-surukpá)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-vi	

C.S. 133 PEB *o-bivi			
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-vivi	'red'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(o-zájá)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-vivi	

C.S. 145 PEB *ε- bareu			
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-vareu	'fifty'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ì-hwebarèù	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ε-bèrèvatùreu	

C.S. 3 PEB *u-kpa			
6.	Ebira Okene	ú-péjwū	< upa + eju skin' + body
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-kpáhá	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	u-pá	

C.S. 72 PEB *ε-kpɛfu			
6.	Ebira Okene	e-péhu	'okro'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-kpè	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	e-péfú	

C.S. 73

PEB *ε -kpa

'root'

6.	Ebira Okene	è-pətʃi	εpa	+	ətʃi	
			body	+	stick/tree	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-kpà				
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-pà				

C.S. 168

PEB *ε-kpa

'boat (canoe)'

6.	Ebira Okene	è-pà			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-kpa			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(ɔ-kɔ)			

C.S. 173

PEB *a-kpɔkɔ

'pepper'

6.	Ebira Okene	á-kɔkɔ			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-kpɔkɔ			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-pɔkɔ			

C.S. 186

PEB *a-kpa(kpa)

'maize'

6.	Ebira Okene	à-pá'pá'			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	akpà			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-pápà			

C.S. 192

PEB *u-gba

'vulture'

6.	Ebira Okene	ù-bà			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-gbà			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ù-bà			

C.S. 206

PEB *ɔ-gbe

'neck'

6.	Ebira Okene	(ɔ-rɔkɔ)			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-gbe			

8. Etuno (Igarra) ɔ-be

C.S. 210

PEB *gba

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (tʃi) | 'dig' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | gbà | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | bá | |

C.S. 222

PEB *ɔgbajɪ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-bajɪ | 'big' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (ɔ-ɪza) | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ɔ-bájɪ | |

C.S. 4

PEB *fu

'roast'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hù | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hù | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | fù | |

C.S. 5

PEB *a-fu

'leg'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | a-hù | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | a-hù | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | a-fù | |

C.S. 7

PEB *u-fe

'moon'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------------|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-h ^w é | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-h ^w é | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | u-fe | |

C.S. 20

PEB *fu

'drink'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hú | |
|----|-------------|----|--|

7. Ebira Kwotto hú
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) fú

C.S. 22 PEB *ε-fu

6. Ebira Okene ε-hù 'bee'
 7. Ebira Kwotto ε-hù
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) ε-fú

C.S. 86 PEB *-f(u)ɔ

6. Ebira Okene ù-hwà 'knife'
 7. Ebira Kwotto ù-hà
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) ù-fà

C.S. 110 PEB *fu

6. Ebira Okene hú 'cook'
 7. Ebira Kwotto hú
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) fú
 for solids; ne me (for liquids)
 " " ; ne " "

C.S. 111 PEB *ire-fu

6. Ebira Okene irè-hù 'sea'
 7. Ebira Kwotto è-hù
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) irè-fù

C.S. 128 PEB *ira-fə̀nə

6. Ebira Okene á-hà̀nə 'medicine (charm)'
 7. Ebira Kwotto (ε-tʃɪ́kpà)
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) irá-fə̀nə

C.S. 131 PEB *o-fu

6. Ebira Okene o-hù 'twenty'
 7. Ebira Kwotto o-hù
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) o-fú

C.S. 137 PEB *o-fu

'market'

6	Ebira Okene	ò-hù	
7	Ebira Kwotto	ò-hù	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-fù	

C.S. 155 PEB *fu

6	Ebira Okene	hù	'beat (drum)'
7	Ebira Kwotto	hù	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	fù	

C.S. 166 PEB *ira-fu

6	Ebira Okene	irà-fù	'night'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ira-fu	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ìrà-fu	

C.S. 167 PEB *V-fuefu

6	Ebira Okene	hù (néne)	'cold (v.)'
7	Ebira Kwotto	hwèhùrù	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	o-fùofù	

C.S. 196 PEB *funa

6	Ebira Okene	huna	'surpass'
7	Ebira Kwotto		
8	Etuno (Igarra)	funa	

C.S. 101 PEB *o-fuefu

6	Ebira Okene	(e-nejì)	'(be) wet'
7	Ebira Kwotto	o-hwèhùrù	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ó-fófù	

C.S. 211 PEB *o-furewu

6	Ebira Okene	o- hùrè(w)ù	'thirty'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ò- hùrèwù	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ò- fureu	

C.S. 212

PEB *fusetʃe

'ask'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hùsè |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hùretʃe |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | fə ~ fúswe |

C.S. 223

PEB *fueɲi

'wash body'/bathe'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hwéɲi |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hweɲi |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | fweɲi |

C.S. 48

PEB *o-wu

'cotton/thread'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | o-ù |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ò-wú |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ò-wú |

C.S. 77

PEB *wu

'kill'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|----|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | wu |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | wu |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | wu |

C.S. 78

PEB *wu

'hear'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|----|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | wú |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | wú |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | wú |

C.S. 79

PEB *ɔ-wɔwɔ

'new'

- | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-wɔwá |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɔ-wɔ:wá |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ɔ-wɔwá |

C.S. 80

PEB *ɔ-we

'dry'

- | | | |
|----|--------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | wu |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ó-weɲi |

5. Etuno (Igarra) ð-wèŋwā

C.S. 83

	PEB *wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	wù	'swell (of boil)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	wù	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	wù	

C.S. 182

	PEB *wara		
6.	Ebira Okene	wara	'fry'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	wara	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	wàrà	

C.S. 219

	PEB *ε-wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-u	'ten'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-wú	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ε-wú	

C.S. 81

	PEB *ε-wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-u	'snake'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-wu	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	(i-setʃi)	

6.5.2 Alveolars

C.S. 35

	PEB *ε-na		
6.	Ebira Okene	è-nà	'four'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-nà	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	è-na	

C.S. 44

	PEB *ne		
6.	Ebira Okene	ne	'throw'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ne	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ne	

C.S. 112

PEB *i-nɔkɔ

'(water) pot'

6.	Ebira Okene	i-nɔkɔ	~	u-rùkù
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-nɔkɔ		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-nɔkɔ		ò-dzĩ

C.S. 114

PEB *i-ne

'mortar'

6.	Ebira Okene	i-nè		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-nè		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	i-nè		

C.S. 130

PEB *ɛ-nu

'yam'

6.	Ebira Okene	ɛ-nu		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-nu		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(é-vina)		

C.S. 138

PEB *a-nɔ

'salt'

6.	Ebira Okene	a-nɔ		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-nɔ		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ńɔ		

C.S. 146

PEB *i-nomi

'bird'

6.	Ebira Okene	i-nomi		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-nómí		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-nómí		

C.S. 148

PEB *na

'go (v.)'

6.	Ebira Okene	ná		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ná		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ná		

C.S. 183.

PEB *na
6. Ebira Okene
7. Ebira Kwotto
8. Etuno (Igarra)

na
na
na

'sell'

C.S. 209

PEB *i-ne
6. Ebira Okene
7. Ebira Kwotto
8. Etuno (Igarra)

(irè-ká)
i-ne'
i-ne'

'belly (ext./stomach)'

C.S. 224

PEB *ne
6. Ebira Okene
7. Ebira Kwotto
8. Etuno (Igarra)

ne
--
ně

'bury'

C.S. 233

PEB *ɔ-nɔru
6. Ebira Okene
7. Ebira Kwotto
8. Etuno (Igarra)

ɔ-nɔrú
ɔ-nɔrú
ɔ-nɔrú

'man'

C.S. 234

PEB *ire-nu
6. Ebira Okene
7. Ebira Kwotto
8. Etuno (Igarra)

ire-nu
irè-nù
iré-nú

'mouth'

C.S. 23

PEB *u-tɔkpa
6. Ebira Okene
7. Ebira Kwotto
8. Etuno (Igarra)

u-tɔ
u-tɔkpá
u-tɔ

'ear'

C.S. 24

PEB *tu

'send'

6	Ebira Okene	tutu
7	Ebira Kwotto	tú
8	Etuno (Igarra)	tu(5)

C.S. 25

	PEB *ire-tutu		'rubbish heap'
6	Ebira Okene	i-tutu	
7	Ebira Kwotto	e-tutu	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	iri-tutu	

C.S. 26

	PEB *a-tito		'ashes'
6	Ebira Okene	a-ti'ts	
7	Ebira Kwotto	a-tr'ts	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	a-ti'ts	

C.S. 27

	PEB *ire-tokuse		'grinding stone'
6	Ebira Okene	ire-tokwòsè	< ireta + kusa 'stone' 'grind'
7	Ebira Kwotto	è -tókusá	< ireta + ku 'stone' 'grind'
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ire-t ókw ai	< ireta + ku + i 'stone' 'grind'

[iretokwòsè] is for grinding = 'pepper, beans' while [iretokwáí] is for grinding 'flour'

C.S. 28

	PEB *ire-ta		'stone'
6	Ebira Okene	ire-tá	
7	Ebira Kwotto	ìrè-ta	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ìrè-tá	

C.S. 29

	PEB *é-ta		'three'
6	Ebira Okene	èè-tá	
7	Ebira Kwotto	è-tá	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	è-tá	

C.S. 36

	PEB *tu		'pound'
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6.	Ebira Okene	tù
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tù
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tù

C.S. 37

PEB *tu

'blow (of wind)'

6.	Ebira Okene	tù
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tù
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tù

C.S. 85

PEB *tamaji

'remember'

6.	Ebira Okene	támáí
7.	Ebira Kwotto	támají
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	támáí

C.S. 106

PEB *tuova

'push'

6.	Ebira Okene	tuova	<	tu	+	ova
				'send'		'hand'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(gbubə)	<	gbe	+	ubə
						'hand'
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	túova	<	tu	+	ova
				'send'		'hand'

C.S. 108

PEB *tura

'pull'

6.	Ebira Okene	tùrà
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tùrà
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tùrà

C.S. 135

PEB *V-tutu

'seed'

6.	Ebira Okene	è -tutu
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ə-tùtu
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	è-tùtú

C.S. 143

PEB *ta

'finish' (intr)

6.	Ebira Okene	tá
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(mèhu)

8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tá	
C.S. 153			
PEB *tu			
6.	Ebira Okene	tú	'beat (person)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(nísá)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tú	

C.S. 169			
PEB *ɔ-ta			
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-tá	'friend'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-tá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-tá	

C.S. 187			
PEB *ɛ-te			
6.	Ebira Okene	ɛ-te	'ground'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-te	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɛ-te	

C.S. 232			
PEB *a-taba			
6.	Ebira Okene	a-taba	'mountain'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-tábà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(irèsúfá)	

C.S. 242			
PEB *a-te			
8.	Ebira Okene	a-té	'saliva'
9.	Ebira Kwotto	--	
10.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-té	

C.S. 30			
PEB *ɔ-dɔgba			
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-dóbá	'elephant'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-dagbá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-dába	

C.S. 31			
PEB *ɪ-dava			
6.	Ebira Okene	à-dáva	'shoe'

7. Ebira Kwotto à-dàvà
8. Etunọ (Igarra) ì-dàvà

C.S. 32 PEB *a-da

6. Ebira Okene à-dá 'father'
7. Ebira Kwotto à-dá
8. Etunọ (Igarra) à-dá

C.S. 144 PEB *e-dudu

6. Ebira Okene è-dùdù 'dust'
7. Ebira Kwotto (è-bùtù)
8. Etunọ (Igarra) è-dùdù

C.S. 230 PEB *i-duṅku

6. Ebira Okene iduṅkù 'knee'
7. Ebira Kwotto idèhèkù
8. Etunọ (Igarra) idùṅkù

C.S. 33 PEB *i-ra

6. Ebira Okene ɪ-rá 'fire'
7. Ebira Kwotto ɪ-rá
8. Etunọ (Igarra) ɪ-rá

C.S. 49 PEB *o-romi

6. Ebira Okene o-ròmí 'orange'
7. Ebira Kwotto à-lèmí
8. Etunọ (Igarra) ò-ròmí

C.S. 107 PEB *rira

6. Ebira Okene rí 'burn' tr.
7. Ebira Kwotto rí rá
8. Etunọ (Igarra) rí rá

C.S. 118

	PEB	* rura	
	Ebira Okene	rura	'dream' v
6.	Ebira Kwotto	rúrá	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	rura	
8.			

C.S. 142	PEB	*a-remi	
	Ebira Okene	á-rémi	'charcoal'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	(a-giginibi)	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	á-rémi	
8.			

C.S. 177	PEB	*ira-re	
	Ebira Okene	a-ré'	'farm'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ré'	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ira-ré'	
8.			

C.S. 189	PEB	*o-rihi	
	Ebira Okene	o-rihi	'needle'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	o-rí' hí'	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	o-rí hí	
8.			

C.S. 198	PEB	*ri	
	Ebira Okene	rí	'eat'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	rí	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	rí'	
8.			

C.S. 202	PEB	*ira-rè	
	Ebira Okene	ira-rè	'tongue'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	ira-rè	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ira-rè	
8.			

C.S. 220	PEB	*a-ruóbají	
	Ebira Okene	a-rúóbá jí	'robe/gown/smock'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	(itógbe)	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	à-rù	
8.			

C.S. 38	PEB *su		
6.	Ebira Okene	sú	'to die'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	sú	

C.S. 84	PEB *su		
6.	Ebira Okene	sú	'to tie (rope)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	sú	

C.S. 88	PEB *u-siji		
6.	Ebira Okene	u-si	'thigh'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-siji	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-si	

C.S. 96	PEB *ire-su		
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-sù	'head'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-sù	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ire-sù	

C.S. 109	PEB *i-sikpa		
6.	Ebira Okene	i-si	'housefly'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-sikpá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	i-si	

C.S. 140	PEB *ire-su		
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-sù	'rainy season'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ire-sù	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ire-sù	

C.S. 149	PEB *si		
6.	Ebira Okene	si	'take (one thing)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	si	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	si	

C.S. 152		PEB *suara			'sleep (v.)'
6.	Ebira Okene	swará <	sù + ará	(~ sùhutù)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sará			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	sará			

C.S. 156		PEB *szdu			'fall' v.
6.	Ebira Okene	hjédó			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(kwété)	< ku + été	+ ground	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	sédú			

C.S. 160		PEB *i-sori			'food'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-sá'			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-sóri'			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	i-sóri'			

C.S. 163		PEB *sire			'to like'
6.	Ebira Okene	si			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sireyi			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	si' ~ sireáni			

C.S. 172		PEB *si			'look for'
6.	Ebira Okene	si			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	si			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	si			

C.S. 175		PEB *o-se			'wife'
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-se'			
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-sí'			
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-sé			

C.S. 176		PEB *i-sa			'thing'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-sá			

7. Ebira Kwotto i-sá
 8. Etuno (Igarra) i-sá

C.S. 218 PEB *si 'want/desire'
 6. Ebira Okene si
 7. Ebira Kwotto si
 8. Etuno (Igarra) si

C.S. 225 PEB *asise 'feather'
 6. Ebira Okene asise
 7. Ebira Kwotto ---
 8. Etuno (Igarra) asise

C.S. 226 PEB *si 'give'
 6. Ebira Okene si
 7. Ebira Kwotto (dó)
 8. Etuno (Igarra) sjóm

C.S. 46 PEB *ɔ -za 'person'
 6. Ebira Okene ɔ -zà
 7. Ebira Kwotto ɔ -zà
 8. Etuno (Igarra) ɔ -zà

C.S. 47 PEB *ε-za 'beans'
 6. Ebira Okene ε-za
 7. Ebira Kwotto ε-za
 8. Etuno (Igarra) ε-za

C.S. 50 PEB *ire-zi 'dog'
 6. Ebira Okene ire-zi
 7. Ebira Kwotto (a-bjá)
 8. Etuno (Igarra) ire-zi

C.S. 70

	PEB *o-zɔga		
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-zɔga	'guest (stranger)
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-zɔga	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-zɔga	

	PEB *zuse		
6.	Ebira Okene	zuse	'walk' v.
7.	Ebira Kwotto	zuse	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	zuse use (n.)	

	PEB *o-(zu)gbe		
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-zùbè	'hunter'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-zùgbèl	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-bè	

	PEB *ε-zu		
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-zu	'leopard'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(u-dòmi)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-zu	

	PEB *o-zi		
6.	Ebira Okene	o-zi (e-)	'child(ren)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-zi (-ni)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-zi (e-)	

	PEB *zuetfi		
6.	Ebira Okene	zwetfi	'run'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(detfi)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	zwe	

	PEB *-zoza		
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-zózà	'good'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(wúsà)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	zózà	

C.S. 221

PEB *za

6	Ebira Okene	za	'catch'
7	Ebira Kwotto	zá	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	za, gwɔ	

C.S. 236

PEB *o-ze

6	Ebira Okene	ò-zè	'road'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ò-zi	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-zè	

C.S. 240

PEB *ɔ-zòmɪ

6	Ebira Okene	ù-zòmɪ	'star'
7	Ebira Kwotto	(ò-làùrárú)	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	ù-zòmɪ	

6.5.3 Palatals

C.S. 34

PEB *ɔ-ɲɪ, *ɔ-ɲa

6	Ebira Okene	ò-ɲí ~ òɲa	'one'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ò-ɲa	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-ɲá	

C.S. 58

PEB *a-ɲɪ

6	Ebira Okene	a-ɲí	'tooth'
7	Ebira Kwotto	a-ɲí	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ɲí	

C.S. 61

PEB *ɔ-ɲise

6	Ebira Okene	è-ɲūsè	'iron (metal)'
7	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ -ńise	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-ɲísé	

C.S. 62

PEB

*ɔ-ɲene

6	Ebira Okene	ò-ɲéne	'woman'
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7. Ebira Kwotto ɔ-nijé
 8. Etuno (Igarra) ɔ-néne

C.S. 63

PEB *nepe

6. Ebira Okene néné
 7. Ebira Kwotto néné
 8. Etuno (Igarra) néné

'dance' (v.)

C.S. 91

PEB *niji

6. Ebira Okene níjī
 7. Ebira Kwotto nūjī
 8. Etuno (Igarra) nūjī

'laugh' v.

C.S. 94

PEB *nina

6. Ebira Okene jínà
 7. Ebira Kwotto jínà
 8. Etuno (Igarra) jínà

'wash (things)'

C.S. 115

PEB *e-ni

6. Ebira Okene e-ni
 7. Ebira Kwotto e-ni
 8. Etuno (Igarra) e-ni

'water'

C.S. 174

PEB *i-sepi

6. Ebira Okene (i-vónò)
 7. Ebira Kwotto u-ni
 8. Etuno (Igarra) i-sépi

'fish'

< isá + epi
 'thing' + 'water'

C.S. 201

PEB *a-ja

6. Ebira Okene a-já
 7. Ebira Kwotto a-ja
 8. Etuno (Igarra) a-já

'blood'

C.S. 61

	PEB *ɔ-pisɛ		'iron (metal)'
6.	Ebira Okene	è-püsè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-n̄sɛ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-písé	

C.S. 62	PEB *ɔ-pɛnɛ		'woman'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-pɛnɛ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-nijé	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-pɛnɛ	

C.S. 39	PEB *-tʃuku		'bone'
6.	Ebira Okene	é-tʃóku	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-tʃókù	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃókú	

C.S. 40	PEB *tʃi		'descend'
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tʃi	

C.S. 41	PEB *ɔ-tʃi		'tree'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-tʃi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-tʃi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃi	

C.S. 42	PEB *ɔ-tʃi		'stick'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-tʃi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-tʃi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃi	

C.S. 43	PEB *tʃe		'shoot'
6.	Ebira Okene	(ha)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃe	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tʃe	

C.S. 64	PEB *e-tʃe		'wine/beer (general word)
6.	Ebira Okene	è-tʃè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-tʃè	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	è-tʃè	

C.S. 134	PEB *tʃire		'sow (seeds in holes)
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃire	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(tú)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tʃirè	

C.S. 141	PEB *tʃe		'break (stick)
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃe	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃe	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	tʃe	

C.S. 181	PEB *ɔ-ntʃere		'monkey'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ntʃerè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-ntʃerè	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-ntʃerè	

C.S. 89	PEB *tʃaka		'break (pot, calabash)
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃáká	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃáká	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	sáká	

C.S. 51	PEB *a-dʒe		'egg'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-dʒe	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-dʒe	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-dʒe	

C.S. 52	PEB *dʒiko		'black'
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-dʒí'ódʒí	

7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-dʒi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ó-dʒódʒi	

C.S. 185

	PEB *ira-dʒɛ		'navel'
6.	Ebira Okene	ira-dʒɛ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ndʒɛ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ira-dʒɛ	

C.S. 200

	PEB *dʒireru		'bite'
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒirerú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(dàrì)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	dʒirerú	

C.S. 229

	PEB *dʒi		'jump'
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒiriga	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	---	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	dʒì	

C.S. 184

	PEB *dʒi (v.) + aʃɛ (n.)		'sing'
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒahe < dʒi + ahe	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hahe < hi + ahe	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	dʒaʃɛ < dʒi + aʃɛ	

C.S.61

	PEB *V-ʃɛ		chicken (domestic fowl)'
6.	Ebira Okene	áó -hwé	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	uú-hè	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	àu-ʃé	

C.S. 8

	PEB *ire-ʃɪ		'house'
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-hí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-hí	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ire-ʃí	

C.S. 17

PEB *ʃira

6.	Ebira Okene	hirà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hirà	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃirà	

'fly'

C.S. 18

PEB *ʃi

6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃi	

'sweep'

C.S. 21

PEB *a-ʃe

6.	Ebira Okene	a-hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-hi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-si ~ (aʃi)	

'wind'

C.S. 45

PEB *ʃi

6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃi	

'buy'

C.S. 92

PEB *ʃine

6.	Ebira Okene	hi' nè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi' nè	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃinè	

'sweet, (tasty)'

C.S. 123

PEB *a-ʃε

6.	Ebira Okene	a-hé	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-hé	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-ʃé	

'song'

C.S. 125

PEB *ε-ʃi

6.	Ebira Okene	è-hí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-hí	

'five'

8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-ʃi	
C.S. 126	PEB *o-ʃmɔʃi		'king/chief'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-himɔɪ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-hi' nɔʃi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-ʃi' nɔʃi	

C.S. 132	PEB *V-ʃi		'be full'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-hi' hi'	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi'	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ʃi'	

C.S. 151	PEB *ʃutu		'lie down'
6.	Ebira Okene	hütó	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hütó	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ʃüte	

C.S. 154	PEB *ʃi		'weave' v.
6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ʃi	

C.S. 164	PEB *ire-ʃa		'name'
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-ʃa'	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ire-ʃa'	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ire-ʃá	

C.S. 165	PEB *a-ʃi		'nose'
6.	Ebira Okene	á-hʃi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	á-hi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	á-ʃi' ʃi	

C.S. 170	PEB *ʃi		'call' v
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6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi'	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃi'a'	

C.S. 191

PEB *ʃire

6.	Ebira Okene	hire	'climb'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hire	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ʃi're	

C.S. 53

PEB *(ir)a-je

6.	Ebira Okene	ira-je	'year'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ji'	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	'ira-je	

C.S. 54

PEB *ɔ-je

6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-je	'in-law'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-je	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-jeé	

C.S. 55

PEB *e-ja

6.	Ebira Okene	e-ja	'buffalo'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-ja	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	e-ja	

C.S. 56

PEB *ji

6.	Ebira Okene	ji	'steal'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ji	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ji	

C.S. 57

PEB *e-ji

6.	Ebira Okene	e-ji	'eye'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-ji'	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	e-ji	

C.S. 59

PEB *ɔ-ji			
	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ji	'sun/sunshine'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-ji	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-ji	
8.			

C.S. 120 PEB *u-je			
	Ebira Okene	u-je	'meat'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	u-je	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	u-je	
8.			

C.S. 121 PEB *ji			
	Ebira Okene	ji	'refuse'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	ji	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ji	
8.			

C.S. 195 PEB *(ir)e-i			
	Ebira Okene	irɛ-i	'word'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-j-i	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɪrɛ-i	
8.			

C.S. 204 PEB *je			
	Ebira Okene	je	'know'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	jé	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	jé	
8.			

C.S. 217 PEB *(ar)e-ji			
	Ebira Okene	áré-ji	'smoke'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	aré-ji	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	aré-ji	
8.			

C.S. 228 PEB *ɛ-ji			
	Ebira Okene	ɛ-ji	'hair'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛji	
7.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɛji	
8.			

C.S. 237

PEB *jatu

- 6. Ebira Okene jaátu
- 7. Ebira Kwotto jatú
- 8. Ètunọ (Igarra) já:tú

'sit down'

C.S. 60

PEB *ɔ-je ne

- 6. Ebira Okene ð-je ne
- 7. Ebira Kwotto ɔ-nije
- 8. Ètunọ (Igarra) ð-je ne

'female'

6.5.4 Velars

C.S. 82

PEB *ŋ^wura

- 6. Ebira Okene ŋ^wurá
- 7. Ebira Kwotto ŋ^wurá
- 8. Ètunọ (Igarra) ŋ^wùra

'hot (as fire)'

C.S. 90

PEB *a-ŋwe

- 6. Ebira Okene a-ŋwé
- 7. Ebira Kwotto a-ŋwé
- 8. Ètunọ (Igarra) a-ŋwé

'oil'

C.S. 93

PEB *u-ŋwe

- 6. Ebira Okene u-ŋwe
- 7. Ebira Kwotto u-ŋwe
- 8. Ètunọ (Igarra) u-ŋwe

'hunger' n.

C.S. 103

PEB *a-ŋwafi

- 6. Ebira Okene à-ŋwáhi
- 7. Ebira Kwotto à-ŋwáhi
- 8. Ètunọ (Igarra) a-ŋwafi

'fear' n.

C.S. 124

PEB * a-ŋwafi

'fear' v.

6.	Etunọ Okene	à-ɲwàhí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ɲwàhí	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-ɲwàjí	

C.S. 147

PEB *ɲwari

6.	Ebira Okene	ɲwà	'untie'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɲwàrí	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɲwàra	

C.S. 119

PEB *ε-ɲu

6.	Ebira Okene	ε-ɲú	'body'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-ɲú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-ɲú ~ εɲ*ú	

C.S. 65

PEB *o-ku

6.	Ebira Okene	o-kú	'corpse'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-kú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-kú	

C.S. 66

PEB *-kákara

6.	Ebira Okene	ù-kákàrà	'crab'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	í-kákàrà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ú-kákara	

C.S. 67

PEB *kama

6.	Ebira Okene	kámá	'wring (clothes)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(pìrí)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kámá	

C.S. 69

PEB *ku

6.	Ebira Okene	ku(sá)	'grind'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ku	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kù	

C.S. 87

PEB *(zi)ka

'count'

6.	Ebira Okene	kà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(zì)kà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kà	

C.S. 98

	PEB *u-kòrò		'work' n.
6.	Ebira Okene	u-kòrò	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-kòrò	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-kòrò	

C.S. 127

	PEB *ɔ-ku		'firewood'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ku	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-kú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-ku	

C.S. 150

	PEB *(yubò)kani		'touch (with hand)
6.	Ebira Okene	kàjí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(yúbò)kàní	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kani	

C.S. 161

	PEB *ire-kura		'town'
6.	Ebira Okene	è-kùrà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(u-ráda)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ire-kùrà	

C.S. 171

	PEB *a-ku		'guinea corn'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-kú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-kú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-kú	

C.S. 179

	PEB *i-kehi		'thorn(s)'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-kehi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-ke'jĩ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	i-ke'ĩ	

C.S. 203

PEB *kuoku 'to cover (a pot)'
 6. Ebira Okene kwoku
 7. Ebira Kwotto kwóku
 8. Etuno (Igarra)

C.S. 205 PEB *kase 'learn'
 6. Ebira Okene kási
 7. Ebira Kwotto kóse
 8. Etuno (Igarra) kóswé

C.S. 214 PEB *kuahı 'blow' (with mouth)
 6. Ebira Okene (tu)
 7. Ebira Kwotto kwahı
 8. Etuno (Igarra) kwahı , fájé

C.S. 216 PEB *u-kata 'strong'
 6. Ebira Okene u-kata
 7. Ebira Kwotto (núnkpahı)
 8. Etuno (Igarra) kátá

C.S. 71 PEB *-kókóri 'snail'
 6. Ebira Okene ú-kókóri
 7. Ebira Kwotto (ire-kpá)
 8. Etuno (Igarra) à-kí kóri

C.S. 190 PEB *ira-kumı 'donkey'
 6. Ebira Okene ira-kumı
 7. Ebira Kwotto ketekete 'donkey'
 8. Etuno (Igarra) ketekete (ira-kumı 'camel')

C.S. 193 PEB*-kusije 'groundnut'
 6. Ebira Okene (e-tʃupa)
 7. Ebira Kwotto o-gúzijá
 8. Etuno (Igarra) e-kújájé

C.S. 238	PEB *kjiiki		
6.	Ebira Okene	kʒii ki	'small'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	---	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	---	

C.S. 239	PEB *kare		
6.	Ebira Okene	kaà	'say (smth)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-kikà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kàre	

C.S. 68	PEB *ga		
6.	Ebira Okene	gà	'divide (share out)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	gà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	gà	

C.S. 102	PEB *ari-ga		
6.	Ebira Okene	àri-ga	'bat'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ìrú-ga	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	àri-ga	

C.S. 178	PEB *a-gugu		
6.	Ebira Okene	à-gugu	'crocodile'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ò-jiè)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-gúgù	

C.S. 188	PEB *ge		
6.	Ebira Okene	gé	'sew'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ge'	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ge'	

C.S. 208	PEB *ira-ga		
6.	Ebira Okene	ìrà-gà	'axe'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ìrà-gà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ìrà-gà	

C.S. 231

PEB *ɔ-gɔdɔ

'long'

- 6. Ebira Okene ɔ-gɔdɔ
- 7. Ebira Kwotto ɔ-gɔdɔ
- 8. Etunɔ (Igarra) ɔ-gɔdɔ

6.5. Glottal

C.S. 97

PEB *huɛɛ

'vomit (v.)'

- 6. Ebira Okene hɛɛ
- 7. Ebira Kwotto hwɛɛ
- 8. Etunɔ (Igarra) (káɛnu) v. (íɛɛn) n.

C.S. 139

PEB *i-hinegba

'God'

- 6. Ebira Okene ɪ-hínéba
- 7. Ebira Kwotto ɪ-hínégbá
- 8. Etunɔ (Igarra) (o-fo:mo:fi)

6.5.5 Labial-Velars

C.S. 3

PEB *u-kpa

'skin'

- 6. Ebira Okene ú-péjwū < upa + ɛɣu
skin + body
- 7. Ebira Kwotto u-kpáhá
- 8. Etunɔ (Igarra) u-pá

C.S. 72

PEB *ɛ-kpɛfu

'okro'

- 6. Ebira Okene e-péhu
- 7. Ebira Kwotto è-kpè
- 8. Etunɔ (Igarra) e-péfú

C.S. 73

PEB *ɛ-kpa

'root'

- 8. Ebira Okene è-pɔtʃi ɛpa + ɔtʃi
body + stick/tree
- 7. Ebira Kwotto è-kpà

8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-pà	
C.S. 168			
		PEB *e-kpa	
6.	Ebira Okene	è-pà	'boat (canoe)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-kpa	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(s-kó)	

C.S. 173			
		PEB *a-kpọkọ	
6.	Ebira Okene	á-kọkọ	'pepper'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-kpọkọ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-pọkọ	

C.S. 186			
		PEB *a-kpa(kpa)	
6.	Ebira Okene	à-pá'pá'	'maize'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	akpà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-pápà	

C.S. 192			
		PEB *u-gba	'vulture'
6.	Ebira Okene	ù-bà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-gbà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ù-bà	

C.S. 206			
		PEB *o-gbe	'neck'
6.	Ebira Okene	(o-rọkọ)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-gbe	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-be	

C.S. 210			
		PEB *gba	'dig'
6.	Ebira Okene	(tji)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	gbà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	bà	

C.S. 222			
		PEB *ogbanl	'big'
8.	Ebira Okene	o-bajl	

9. Ebira Kwotto (ɔ-ɪza)
8. Etuno (Igarra) ɔ-báji

C.S. 48

- PEB *o-wu 'cotton/thread'
6. Ebira Okene o-ú
7. Ebira Kwotto ó-wú
8. Etuno (Igarra) ó-wú

C.S. 77

- PEB *wu 'kill'
6. Ebira Okene wu
7. Ebira Kwotto wu
8. Etuno (Igarra) wu

C.S. 78

- PEB *wu 'hear'
6. Ebira Okene wú
7. Ebira Kwotto wú
8. Etuno (Igarra) wú

C.S. 79

- PEB *ɔ-wɔwɔ 'new'
6. Ebira Okene ɔ-wɔwá
7. Ebira Kwotto ɔ-wɔwá
8. Etuno (Igarra) ɔ-wɔwá

C.S. 80

- PEB *ɔ-we 'dry'
6. Ebira Okene wu
7. Ebira Kwotto ó-wejĩ
8. Etuno (Igarra) ɔ-wèjwá

C.S. 83

- PEB *wu 'swell (of boil)'
6. Ebira Okene wú
7. Ebira Kwotto wú
8. Etuno (Igarra) wú

C.S. 182

- PEB *wara 'fry'

6.	Ebira Okene	wara
7.	Ebira Kwotto	wara
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	wàrà

C.S. 219

PEB *ε-wu

6.	Ebira Okene	ε-U	'ten'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-WU	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-WU	

C.S. 81

PEB *ε-wu

6.	Ebira Okene	ε-U	'snake'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-WU	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(i-sɛtʃi)	

6.6

PEB Consonant System Reduction

The development of reflexes from PEB to the languages shows merger of sounds. Different phonemes share allophones. Some of the sound changes observed in the development of Ebiroid from PEB are presented in 2. below.

(2)

- *b > [v]
- > [b]
- *kp > [p]
- > [kp]
- *gb > [b]
- > [gb]
- *d₃ > [h]
- > [d₃]
- *f > [ʃ]
- > [f]
- *s > [ʃ]
- > [s]

6.7 VOWELS OF PEB

A nine vowel system is reconstructed for PEB. They are *i, *ɪ, *e, *ε, *a, *ɔ, *o, *u

and *u. There are no phonemic nasal vowels in Ebiroid; all the vowels are nasalised in the environment of nasal consonants.

(3) PEB Phonetic Vowel Inventory

i	u
ɪ	ʊ
e	o
ɛ	ɔ
a	

6.7.1 PEB Stem Vowels

All the PEB vowels occur as stem vowels. They are *i, *ɪ, *e, *ɛ, *a, *ɔ, *o, *u, and *ʊ. Each of them has reflexes of identical phonetic shape as the reconstructed vowel in the languages. Of the vowels with regular phonetic shapes vowel, *o rarely occurs as stem vowel.

6.7.2 Prefix Vowels

All the PEB vowels: *i, *ɪ, *e, *ɛ, *a, *ɔ, *o, *u and *ʊ occur as prefix vowels and they harmonise with stem vowels in such positions. Noun prefixes are observed in the development of Ebiroid from PEB. Evidence lies in the fact that no verb starts with a vowel whereas nouns do. Also singular and plural prefix alternation though not common is found in nouns. Prefixes in Ebiroid are usually of the CV structure and often there is a prothetic vowel which is usually ɪ- or a-. The prefix consonant is usually [r], while the vowels found after it are either ɪ-, e-, ɛ- or a-. Since PEB prefix consonant is often r-, no prefix vowel is nasalised.

(4)

6	7	8	gloss
irè-vá	iré-bá	ìré-vá	'breasts'
irè-tá	ìrè-ta	ìrè-tá	'stone'
irá-hú	ira-hu	ìrà-fu	'night'
árè-ji	aré-ji	aré-ji	'smoke'

As observable in 2. the prefix is usually the same. Only in 'bat' is the prefix different in 7 i.e. *irú-* not *ári-* found in 6 and 8.

(5)	6	7	8	gloss
	<i>án-ga</i>	<i>irú-ga</i>	<i>ári-ga</i>	'bat'

Some vowel clusters observed as prefixes in Ebiroid are actually derived through loss of the stem of a reduplicated morpheme and are actually not instances of np clusters.

(6)	6	7	8	gloss
	<i>á-óhué</i>	<i>u-úhué</i>	<i>á-ufé</i>	'chicken (domestic fowl)'
>	<i>á-hué+ó-hué</i>	<i>uhué+úhué</i>	<i>ahué+á-ufé</i>	'chicken (domestic fowl)'
	<i>á-óh^wé</i>	<i>u-úh^wé</i>	<i>á-ufé</i>	loss of reduplicated CV stem'
	<i>á-óh^wé</i>	<i>u-úh^wé</i>	<i>á-ufé</i>	surface form
	<i>ɔ-vúɔvu</i>	<i>ɔ-óbu</i>	<i>ɔ-vuɔvu</i>	'white'
>	<i>ɔvú+ɔvu</i>	<i>ɔbu+óbu</i>	<i>ɔvu+ɔvu</i>	'white'
	<i>ɔ-vu+ɔvu</i>	<i>ɔ-+óbu</i>	<i>ɔ-vu+ɔvu</i>	loss of reduplicated CV stem'
	<i>ɔ-vúɔvu</i>	<i>ɔ-óbu</i>	<i>ɔ-vuɔvu</i>	surface form
	<i>èva+èva</i>	<i>è-ba</i>	<i>è-va</i>	'two'
>	<i>è-+èva</i>	<i>è-ba</i>	<i>è-va</i>	loss of reduplicated CV stem'
	<i>è-èva</i>	<i>è-ba</i>	<i>è-va</i>	surface form

6.8 Development of vowels from PEB

PEB vowels having c.s. of differing phonetic shapes are presented in Tables. The possible line of development is traced from PEB to the languages.

Table 15 PEB front vowels with reflexes of differing phonetic shape

PEB	6	7	8
c.s.29 *i	i	u	u

c.s.30 *i'	u	ɲ	l
c.s.31 *e	e	ɪ	e
c.s.32 *ɛ	ɛ, e	ɛ	ɛ, e

Table 16 PEB central vowels with reflexes of differing phonetic shape

Vc.s.33 *a	ɔ, u	a, o	a, u
------------	------	------	------

Table 17 PEB back vowels with reflexes of differing phonetic shape

PEB	6	7	8
c.s.34 *ɔ	ɔ, a	a	a, ɔ
c.s.35 *u	u	u, e	u, ɛ, u
c.s.36 *o	o, u	e	o

c.s.29 PEB *i C.S. 91

Corresponding vowel [u] in 7 and 8 (C.S. 91) are actually prefix vowel of the second morpheme in 'laugh' (v.) I therefore reconstruct *i.

c.s.30 PEB *i' C.S. 61 u ɲ l

The reconstructed vowel here is considered different from that in c.s.29 because a syllabic nasal realised from coalescence of C¹ and V¹ in 7 surfaces as reflex of *i. This process is not observed in c.s.29 hence reconstruction of *i'.

c.s.31 PEB *e C.S. 53, 175

I reconstruct *e not *ɪ since the former has greater distribution and both vowels are close and front. I however, have no explanation for the occurrence of [ɪ] as reflex of *e in 7. It may just be the beginning of a merger between [e] and [ɪ] in 7.

c.s.32 PEB *e

C.S. 62, 72

Here *e not *e which is found in 6 and 8 (C.S. 72) is reconstructed. It is the lower of both and therefore the more marked. It occurs in 7. In C.S. 62 [i] found in 7 corresponds to [e]. I explain this to be due to the difference in word structure in 7 even though a cognate set is established.

c.s.33 PEB *a

C.S. 73, 113

*a not *a is reconstructed in C.S. 73 because in 6 the noun stem vowel is [a] while the prefix vowel of the second noun in the word is [a]. I have no explanation for [u] occurring as reflex of *a. in C.S. 113

c.s.34 PEB *a

C.S. 30, 71, 160, 180

[a] as a reflex of *a is considered to be the manifestation of a possible on-going merger of [a] with [a] in the languages.

c.s.35 PEB *u

C.S. 37, 80, 106, 108, 118, 196

[e] and [e] as reflexes of *u are considered to be instances of nps of nouns that have been merged with other nouns having different vowels (in this case [u]) as stem vowel, to form compound nouns. [u] as reflex of *u is however due to an on-going merger between [u] and [u].

c.s. 36 PEB *o

C.S. 49, 101, 159

I have no explanation for [e] occurring as reflex of *o but [u] as a reflex of *o. I consider to be an instance of an on-going merger between [o] and [u] in 6. The deduction to be made is that the vowel system of PEB is undergoing reduction in the languages.

CHAPTER SEVEN

7.0 ARGUMENTS IN SUPPORT OF EBIROID

7.0.1 Introduction

The internal classification of Benue-Congo and even Niger Congo has undergone a lot of re-examination since Greenberg (1963) borne out of availability of more data and in-depth study of the languages with particular reference to the then Kwa and Benue-Congo groups. These include reconstructions of Proto-Edoid (Elugbe 1973, 1989), Proto-Yoruboid (Akinkugbe 1978), Proto Igboid, Yoruboid and Edoid Consonants (Aniche 1991) and Proto-Ijo (Williamson, forthcoming) and Proto-Jukunoid (Shimizu 1971a/1980).

A clearer picture of the internal and external grouping of the languages is thus emerging. However, a lot of refinement of criteria still need be done. For instance in 2004, Elugbe and Bankale drew attention *'to what appear to be inconsistencies in the use of lexicostatistic data in sub-classification of BC*. These, according to them, arise from *'the lack of word list approved and used by all, the employment of look-alikes in counting cognates, 'lack of inter-group comparison' meaning 'there is no consistent cut-off point'* for the present coordinate branches of BC. This means that a lot of flaws still exist in the procedure and process of classifying or grouping languages. For example, Elugbe (2001) proposed the inclusion of Akpes and AIKA within Edoid, having demonstrated flaws in the method applied by scholars who had earlier looked at both languages alongside other Benue-Congo groups and had proposed them as *'important link between the eastern and the western halves of Benue-Congo based on similarities in some lexical items between Ikaan (=AIKA-BE: Ayaran-Ishe-Kakumo-Auga), and*

some languages of the eastern half of Benue-Congo (e.g. Kainji-Platoid, Bantu, Tiv, Cross Rivers languages). Elugbe and Bankale (2004:2) observed that

... a major weakness of lexicostatistics arises from general practice: linguists use look-alikes in compiling cognate percentages. This means that lexical similarities, which may not necessarily reflect a genetic relationship, are presented as such.

In order to adequately tackle the problem of classification of Epira within Nupoid all the methods have been applied here. With regards 'to what appear to be inconsistencies in the use of lexicostatic data in sub-classification of BC' Elugbe and Bankale (2004) suggested a 30 percent cognation bar for coordinate branching under BC. They also suggested provision of evidence such as innovation in sound change and where possible in vocabulary.

Reconstructing the parent of Nupoid and of Ebiroid has helped eliminate the counting of look-alikes as cognates. The lexicostatic study shows that Ebiroid is not closer to Nupoid than it is to Idomoid or even Yoruba as Oyelowo 1990 figures show.

7.1 Evidence from Lexicostatic study

Table 18: Percentage count of shared cognates between Epira, and Nupe, Gwari, Gade, Idoma and Yoruba culled from Bennett and Sterk's (1977) Table 3.

	Nupe	Gwari	Gade	Idoma	Yoruba
Epira	49	40	45	44	38

Table 19 Actual number of shared items between languages sharing the most cognates. The figures are for Epira and Nupe, Gwari, Gade, Idoma and Yoruba culled from Bennett and Sterk's (1977) Table 4. ('A' = 1st level of closeness; 'B' = 2nd level of closeness which gives 'evidence of close-knit sub groupings within the clusters indicated at the more generous level 'A' (Bennett and Sterk (1977:268)).

'A'	1	2	3	4	5
	Nupe	Gade	Idoma	Gwari	Yoruba
Igbira	42	39	38	34	33

	6	7	8	9	10
Igbira	Ife Togo 32	Igala 28	Tunen 27	Igbo 26	Degema 25
B	1	2	3	4	5
Igbira	Gade 22	Nupe 17	Idoma 15	Gwari 13	Bini 12
	6	7	8	9	10
Igbira	Ora 11	Igbo 11	Ife Togo 8	Ewe 8	Newole? 8

An examination of the figures in Tables 18 and 19 shows

- i) That Ebira is closer to Idoma (44%) and Gade (45%) than it is to Gwari (40%), the closest language to Nupe (see Bennett and Sterk 1977: 268 = Nupe:Gwari at 'A' 49 items, at 'B' 38 items).
- ii) That Ebira is closest to Nupe at 'A' (42 items) and to Gade at 'B' (22 items).
- iii) That Ebira which at 'A' is the closest language to Nupe is now next closest to Nupe after Gade at 'B' with just 17 items.

Ebira's high score with Nupe at 'A' must therefore be taken in the context of their geographic closeness.

Another issue is that according to Bennett and Sterk, Idoma, is at a higher branch level in the tree diagram than Igbiroid even though the figures suggest that Ebiroid is as close to Idomoid as it is to Gade (difference being just 1%). Their tree reflects a coordinate branching for Igbiroid, Gade and Nupe-Gwari within Niger-Kaduna, which, according to the tree, is coordinate with Idomoid within a Central Niger arm of Benue-Congo. It is obvious then that their proposed relationship is skewed. One would have expected to see a coordinate branching between Ebiroid, Idomoid and Gade.

Williamson (1989) rejected the Central Niger node proposed by Bennett and

Sterk (1977) but retained the term Nupoid for the sub-grouping within Bennett and Sterk's Niger-Kaduna. She obviously had her doubts as to the classification of Idomoid with Nupoid.

Blench (1989) also did a lexicostatistic study to establish the unity of Nupoid. His figures showed Ebira Cluster (i.e. Ebira-Okene, Eṭunṭ and Ebira Koto) here called Ebiroid, to be related to other Nupoid language clusters with an average of 35.8 percent lexical cognation. Nupe/Gwari clusters share average of 35.6 percent with Ebiroid. Gade shares an average of 37 percent with Ebiroid. What this means is that Ebiroid is closer to Gade than any other cluster. His figures however show that the Nupe and Gwari Clusters share percentages in the sixties with each other while Gade shares percentages in the forties with Nupe and Gwari clusters. Lexical cognate percentages within the Ebira Cluster are in the eighties. As already pointed out by Elugbe and Bankale (2004), the 36 percent cognate count recorded between Ebira-Okene and Ebira-Koto in Blench's figure 14.1 (1989:306) is considered a typographical error. A comparison of Blench's figures between Gade and Ebiroid (37% average) and that of Bennett and Sterk between Gade and Ebira (45%) reveal a difference of over 10 percent in cognation. This is statistically significant going by Dyen (1962). This outcome indicates that the use of lexicostatistics in the establishment of subgroups is not without its problems as observed by Elugbe and Bankale (2004)

In this study, I record average percentages between 33 and 36 percent between Ebiroid and Nupoid.

Table 20 Cognation Percentages between Nupoid and Ebiroid

	Nupe Tako	Gwari	Gwari Yamma	Gade	Ebira Okene	Etuno	Ebira Kwotto
Nupe Tako	89	46	46	22	45	40	33
Gwari		47	42	27	37	33	31
Gwari Yamma			82	35	37	33	31
Gade				35	37	31	31
Ebira Okene					39	38	33
Etuno						88	86
							78

In Table 20, Ebiroid and Gade share an average percentage of 36.6 while Ebiroid and Nupe share an average percentage of 33.3. Ebiroid and Nupoid share an average percentage of 36.5 percent. It is surprising that Ebiroid/Gade figure tie with Ebiroid/Nupoid figure (36.6/36.5) however this fairly high average percentage of 36.5 between Ebiroid and Nupoid may be explained by the fact that they are neighbours geographically. The general pattern is that Ebiroid is closer to Gade than to Nupe/Gwari. A similar pattern is seen in Blench's (1989) internal classification of Nupoid based on his cognate count percentages between samples of Nupoid languages. His figures show that Ebiroid is closest to Gade followed by Gwari and finally Nupe.

Even Bennett and Sterk's (1989) figures show that Ebiroid is closest to Gade at 'B' and at 'A' after Nupe whose geographic location in relation to Ebira cannot be overlooked. Elugbe and Bankale (2004:3) noted that

...It is not quite clear what the difference is between 'geographic proximity' and 'borrowing' in terms of linguistic relationships. We would normally assume that proximity begets contact and contact begets borrowing or influence.

The very low percentage between Gade and Nupe in Table 20 i.e. average

percentage of 24.5 is instructive. This figure suggests that Nupe and Gade are very distant and going by Williamson's (1988) percentages between branches of BC (Table 4.9 (p. 85)) in the range of 20 percent and 34 percent suggest that Nupe and Gade should normally be branches within Benue-Congo.

It is significant that Ebira and Gade as well as Idoma almost tie in Bennett and Sterk's (1977) lexicostatistic study (Igbirra/Gade 45%, Igbirra/Idoma 44%, Idoma/Gade 43%) and that the relationship between Ebira and Yoruba is just 6 percent less than what it is between Ebira and Idoma, (Ebira/Yoruba 38%). This notwithstanding, Yoruba enjoys branch status under ESCNC and Idomoid and Niger-Kaduna are grouped as coordinate branches under Cental-Niger (see Fig.5).

Another issue is that Bennett and Sterk's (1977) figures show Igbirra to be close to Nupe and at other times show Gwari to be the closest language to Nupe. Their figures at no time show Igbirra to be close to Gwari, the closest language to Nupe as reflected in the tree. Nupe and Igbirra, according to them, share 42 items at 'A', the first level of closeness, (this is understandable again seeing that they are neighbours geographically) and at 'B' the second level of closeness, which gives 'evidence of close-knit sub groupings within the clusters, they share 17 items. This suggests that they are not close at all (cf. Nupe/Idoma 13 items at 'B' (Bennett and Sterk (1977:268) i.e. just 4 items more than the number found between Nupe and Idoma) although Idoma is given a different branching status from Igbirra in their tree. Even though Igbirra and Nupe do not form a cluster, the difference in the figures between 'A' and 'B' (the different levels of closeness), is rather too great compared to what is recorded between Nupe and Gwari at 'A' and 'B', yet these are coordinate branches of Niger-Kaduna.

	'A'	'B'
Nu./Gw.	49	38
Nu./Eb.	42	17
Nu./Id.	38	13

The skewing in the classification of Ebiroid is not in doubt.

7.2 Evidence from Inter-group Comparison

Inter-group comparison of some BC groups was carried out by Oyelowo (1990)

The average cognate count percentages between the branches are

- i) Nupoid/Ebiroid 25%
- ii) Ebiroid /Yoruboid 25.1%
- iii) Yoruboid/ Edoid 18.6%

These figures are similar to what Williamson (1988:86) has in Table 4.9. Part of the table is reproduced here.

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Oyelowo(1990) noted that

Ebira is equally distanced between Nupoid and Yoruboid, and as such should be regarded or classified as a separate branch of the (New) Benue-Congo.

Elugbe and Bankale (2004:1) also noted that

In a normal and consistent practice of lexicostatistics, all coordinate daughter arms of a common ancestor should be approximately equidistant.

The figures show that Ebiroid is equally distanced from Nupoid and Yoruboid.

Oyelowo's intra-group comparison figures (i.e. the average cognation percentage

within the groups are presented) below.

- i) Nupoid = 45 %,
- ii) Edoid = 46.3 %,
- iii) Yoruboid = 65%.

In this study average cognation figures within Ebiroid is 86 percent (see Table 20). This implies that Ebiroid existed untainted or isolated for a long period of time.

7.3 Other types of evidence: lack of lexical innovation in sound change and in vocabulary

Nurse and Hinnebusch (1993:285) as quoted by Elugbe and Bankale (2004:5) pointed out that

Lexicostatistics is a quantitative measure of lexical retention. For diagnostic purposes we need to supplement that by some measure of qualitative innovation. When we speak of qualitative lexical evidence for a language or group of languages, we need to refer to lexical innovation within them that are unique and thus diagnostic.

Data examined do not reveal any form of lexical innovations between Nupoid and Ebiroid. This further buttresses the fact that there is nothing unique to them. A comparison of basic lexical items in actual fact reveal that the items shared by Nupoid and Ebiroid exist even outside both units. They occur in most arms of BC.

Oyelowo (1990) also showed that Ebiroid had regular sound correspondences not just with Nupoid but also with Yoruboid in about the same number of lexical items. She also had a table of Ebiroid consonants differing from Nupoid consonant but similar to those of Yoruboid (Oyelowo 1990: 45-47).

Below is a table containing such items; the reconstructions of some of the items in some BC and NC groups and the languages in which cognates are found. One easily sees that that there are no lexical innovations exclusive to Nupoid and Ebiroid. In fact I

And three items which are exclusive to Ebiroid: aréyí 'smoke', ìvòvò 'fish', gbé 'neck' and ǎǎǎǎ 'feather'. I consider these innovations diagnostic of Ebiroid particularly because Ebiroid exhibits a lot of cognates across BC. There are no cognates with these words within BC for them to be considered as older forms.

Table 21 Some Cognate items within BC and NC

Gloss	Proto	Nupoid	Ebiroid	Idomoid	Edoid	Yoruboid	Lower-Niger	Western Kwa
I	PWS *mi	Nu. -mi Gw. -mi Gd. nam	Eb. -mɪ	Id. -mi El. -mi	EdB.mɛ	Yor. -mi Ig. -mi	Ekp. mɛ	Twɪ mɛ Ewe mɛ
We		Nu. -ji Gw. -ji	Eb. -jɛ	Akw. -ji			Ekp. jɛɛ	Twɪ jɛ
You		Nu. wo Gw. ho	Eb. wu	Id. -wo Akw. -wi	EdB.wɛ	Yor. -wɔ Ig. -wɛ		Twɪ wɔ Ewe wɔ
One	PWS *le PJ *ji	Nu. nini Gw. nnu	Eb. -ɲɪ	El. -ɲi		Yor. -ni Ig. -ɲɛ	Ekp. ɲɛ	
Two	PWS *-bà- PJ *pá	Nu. -bà Gw. -bà Gd. -vâ	Eb. -vá	Id. -pá El. -pò	EdB.vá		Igb. -búɔ	Twɪ -biɛɲ Ewe vɛ
Three	PJ *tat(i)	Nu. -ta Gw. -ta Gd. -ta	Eb. -ta			Yor. -ta		
Four	PE *-niɔ	Nu. -ni Gw. -ɲi Gd. -no	Eb. -ná			Yor. -ɲi		
Belly	PBC *mani PE*phaNi	Gw. núb ^w ó Gd. ɲɲɛ	Eb. -né			Yor. -nú		
Blood	PWS *-gia	Nu. -gǎ	Eb. -ɲá			Yor. -jɛ Ig. -b'ɛ		

Bone	PWS *-ku	Nu. tsúkú Gw. súkǵú Gd. -k'ík'u	Eb. -tʃuku			Yor. -gúgú Igb. - Igb. kpúkpú Igb. -tʃík'u	Ewe fú
Breast	PWS *-bi- PBC *bani	Nu. -be Gw. -be Gd. be	Eb. -vá	Id. -mɛ El. -mɛ		Yor. -mu Ekp. -má	
Ear	PBC *tugi	Nu. tukpa Gw. tñubwa	Eb. -tʃ	Yala(Ik) -rɔ Akw. -rɔ		Yor. -fi Igb. -fi	Ekp. -tɛ Twi sɔ Ewe tó
Eye	PJ *giP	Nu. -je Gw. -w'i	Eb. -ji	Id. -ji El. -ji		Yor. dʒú Igb. -dʒú	
Foot	PWS *-kua		Eb. -hù	Akw. -pu		Igb. -k'u Ekp. -kó	
Hair	PBC *-titi PJ *dʒi	Nu. -ni Gw. ji Gd. tiji	Eb. -ji	El. -ji Akw. -ji			Twi nhwi
Hand		Nu. -g'a Gw. -bwa Gd. -b'o	Eb. -vɔ	Id. -bɔ Ar. -bɔ Akw. -wa		Yor. -wɔ Igb. -wɔ	
Head	PBC *to	Nu. -ti Gw. tuk'o Gd. -tu	Eb. -su	Akw. -tfu		Yor. -ri Igb. -si Ekp. -ʃi	Twi -fi
Knee	PBC *-duno *kudu	Gw. jikutuk'o	Eb. -dunku			Yor. -kú Igb. -k'u	
Mouth	PWS *-nu PBC *nuɲa	Gd. -nu	Eb. -nu		EdB. -nu	Yor. -nu Igb. -lu Ekp. -nu	Twi -nò Ewe nú
Neck	PWS *-kúá	Nu. kóro, kpatsú	Eb. -gbe -rɔkɔ			Yor. ɔrú	Twi -kɔɲ Ewe kɔ

				older form?					
Nose									
Skin	PWS *-ku PJ *kwa	Nu. -pá Gw. -pá Gd. -pu		Eb. - p(a)éŋ ^w u	Tiv -hingga	EdB. -hué			
Tooth	PWS *-ni	Nu. -nīkā Gw. -nīkā Gd. -ji		Eb. -jī	Yala(Ik) -jī Akw. -jī		Yor. jī Igb. jī	Ekp. kpó	Ewe gbatè Lelemi - jī
Tongue	PWS *-lima	Nu. gīntara Gw. mīntala		Eb. -rè					Ewe dè
Person		Nu. -za Gw. zagg ^w o		Eb. -zà	Yala(Ik) -sè Ar. -sè				
Man	PWS*-ni-	Gd. -ru		Eb. -naru	Yala(Ik) nrò Tiv nóm				Twi ri
Woman	PBC *-nine			Eb. néné	Id. -na				Ewe nónu
Come	PWS *ba	Nu. bé Gw. fé Gd. be		Eb. vé	Et. ba		Yor. -ba, wa Igb. -wa	Igb. bja	Twi bā Ewe vā
Die	PWS -kú; pī	Nu. tsu Gw. fi Gd. tʃi		Eb. sú	Akw. hī				
Drink		Nu. fi Gd. wú		Eb. hú	Akw. tfú				
Eat	PWS *li	Gd. ri		Eb. rí	Id. lé El. rí Ige. ři		Igb. ri	Twi di	
Give				Eb. si	El. ři				
Give birth	PYIG *bí PE *biə	Nu. ma Gw. bima Gd. m ^w ó		Eb. mā			Yor. bima		

Hear	PJ *pwog	Nu. wo Gw. wo Gd. wu	Eb. wu	Id. pó		Yor. gbás	
Hot		Nu. wona	Eb. ɣ*orá			Yor. gbóná	
Know	PCJ *ji		Eb. je	Id. dʒr Ige. dʒe	EdB. gwé	Yor. má, Jé = 'be understa ndable'	
Kill		Nu. wu Gw. wu Gd. wu	Eb. wù	Tiv wúá		Igb. -gbu Ekp. gbù	
Roast	PYIG *sū PE *bN	Nu. po Gw. pó Gd. so	Eb. hú			Yor. sū	
Smoke		Nu. -nawu Gw. -wu Gd. -mu	Eb. -réjì	Id. -dudu Ige. -mú El. -wú Akw. -wu		Yor. fí Ige. -dudu	
Say	PWS *ka-	Nu. gā	Eb. ká	Id. ká Yala(lk) ká		Ige. ká	Twí ka Ewe ká
See			Eb. ré	Et. dī		Yor. -rí Ige. -lí	
Sleep	PWS *la PJ *da		Eb. šù			Yor. sū	Ewe dós
wallow	PYIG m'i PE dhoNɪ	Nu. jɪ Gw. mi Gd. muɪ	Eb. mú			Yor. mī	
Steal	PYIG *ji PE *oʒi 'thief'	Nu. ji Gw. w'i Gd. ji	Eb. jì			Yor. dʒi	
Walk		Gd. zu	Eb. zuse				Ewe zò
Bird		Gw. lú	Eb. -nomí			Ekp. -nù	Twí -nomá
Dog		Nu. -šigi	Eb. -zì	El. zù			

Elephant					Eb. -dɔbá	Id. -dagbá		Ig. -dágbá	
Fish					Eb. iseji -vóvó	Id. -béjì Ige. -jeji			
Ash	PJ *tò	Gw. -tnu Gd. -te			Eb. -tító			Yor. -rú Ig. -lúlú	Twi -so
Bark	PBC *kpaga				Eb. -gúha			Yor. -kpo Ig. -kpa	
Egg	PWS* -gi- * -già				Eb. -dʒe	Id. -ji Ige. -ji		Yor. ɲí Ig. ge	
Feather	PWS * -pi-				Eb. -ʃiʃé	Id. -fu Akw. -wu			Ewe fú
Grass	PWS * -pi * -pa	Gd. -bɪ			Eb. -vɪ				
Horn	PBC * -tano	Gd. tótó			Eb. -lópá				
Leaf	PWS * -pita	Gd. -fɛ			Eb. -vɪ				
Moon	PWS * -pian	Gw. -p'á Gd. -p'á			Eb. -hwe	Id. -ja			
Root	PJ *kwap				Eb. -pá	Id. -gbá El. -kwakpa		Yor. -gbó gbòjgbó	
Sand	PYK *sa	Gd. -ʃɛ			Eb. -zi				Ekp. -za
Seed	PJ * -tu				Eb. -tú			Yor. -ru Ig. -lú Yor. -kuta	
Stone	PWS* -ta- PBC *tadi	Nu. takū			Eb. -tá	Akw. -tá			
Tree	PWS * -ti	Nu. tʃigbā Gw. ʃinj'ā Gd. -kí			Eb. -tʃi	Id. -tʃi		Yor. -gí Igb. -sisu	Twi -fi
Water	PWS* -ni-				Eb. -ɲi	Id. -ɲi Ige. -ɲi		Yor. -mí Ig. -mí	Igb. -míííí

Fra	PWS*na-	Nu. -na	Eb. -ná	Id. -lá			
		Gw. -ná		Akw. -la			
BU	PWN		Eb.				
	*-nian-		-bajii			Yor. tobi	
snack	PWS *gi	Nu. ʒik ^w o	Eb.	El.		Ig. -wana	
		Gw. ʒiji	-dʒiodʒi	-rúkúgʻi			Igb. -dʒi Ewe
Dry		Nu. wo	Eb. wū	Akw.			-jibò
		Gw. kawo		wówú			
Long	PCJ *gū		Eb.				
			-gòdò			Yor. gū	
New		Nu. woro	Eb.	Akw.			
			-wówá	-wowa			Lelemi
Name			Eb. -ha				-wóǰi
						Igb. -ña	
						Ekp.	
						-wá	
Small	PWN		Eb.				
	*-keke		kiiki			Yor.	
						kékeré	
						Ig. kéké	
Sun	PWS	Nu. jigídi	Eb. -ji	Akw.			
	*-gui-			-dʒí			Ewe yé
White	PWS	Nu. bokū	Eb.	Akw.	EdB. fuá	Yor. fufú	
	*pu-		-vovv	-púúpú			

1. Italicized words are unique to Ebirá

A lexicostatistic comparison of Proto-Ebiroid and Proto-Nupoid revealed 38 percent cognation at a most generous level using the revised Swadesh 100 word list. Below are the stem initial consonants of the shared items. They are presented in order of place of articulation i.e. Labials followed by alveolars, palatals etc. Reconstructions in Proto Yoruboid Isekiri and Igala (PYIG), Proto Edoid (PE) and Proto Igboid Yoruboid and Edoid (PIYE) are also presented to further show that there are no sound innovations unique to Ebiroid and Nupoid. We observe that most of the sounds similar in PN and PEB are also found across BC. In 6. all reconstructed consonants are entered although some may not be cognate with PEB or even PN as in PE and PIYE consonants for

'swallow'; PYIG and PIYE for skin; 'new' 'hear' 'eye'.

(6) Reconstructed Stem initial consonants

	PN	PEB	PYIG	PE	PIYE	
Labials						
1.	*m	*m	*b	*b	*m, b	'give birth'
2.	*m	*m	*m	*mh	*b	'I'
3.	*m	*m	*m	*dh	*d	'swallow'
4.	*p	*kp	*g	*ph	*g	'skin'
5.	*p	*f	*s	*t	*s	'roast'
6.	*p	*f	*c	-	*kp	'moon'
7.	*b	*b	*f	*p	*p	'white'
8.	*b	*b	*j	*v	*b	'two'
9.	*b	*b	*j	-	*b, y	'breast'
10.	*b	*b	*b	-	*b	'come'
11.	*f	*b	*w	*b	*b	'leaf'
12.	*ph	*f	*gm	*d, y	*g	'drink'
Alveolars						
13.	*nh	*j	*n	-	*n	'one'
14.	*n	*n	*r	*n	*l	'four'
15.	*n	*r	*n	*n	*d	'fire'
16.	*n	*g ^w	*t	-	d	'hot'
17.	*t	*t	*t	*ch	*t	'ear'
18.	*t	*t	*r	*nh	*t	'ashes'
19.	*t	*t	*t	*ch	*t	'three'
20.	*t	*s	*d	*ch	*t	'head'
21.	*t	*s	*k	*gh	*k	'die'
22.	*t	*j	*r	*t	*t	'hair'
23.	*z	*z	*n	-	*n	'person'
24.	*z	*d ₃	*g	*k	*k	'egg'
25.	*z	*d ₃	*d	*b	*d, c	'black'

Palataals						
26.	*c	*ʃ	*g	*th	*t	'tree'
27.	*j	*j	*r	-	*d	'sun'
28.	*j	*j	-	-	*n	'we'
29.	*j	*ɲ	*ɲ	*k	*k	'tooth'
Velars						
30.	*k	*t	*k	*g	*k	'stone' (with metathesis)
31.	*k	*tʃ	*k'	-	*k	'bone'
Labial-velar						
32.	*w	*w	*t	*ph	*p	'new'
33.	*w	*w	*gb	*ch	*l	'hear'
34.	*w	*w	*l	*gb	*kp	'kill'
35.	*w	*w	*w	-	*b	'you' (sg.)
36.	*w	*j	*j	*mh	*g	'eye'
37.	*w	*j	*j	*j	*d	'steal'
38.	*gbh	*b	*b'	*ʒ	*k	'hand'

Finally the sound inventory and changes observed in Ebiroid are different from those in Nupoid. In Ebiroid there are no implosives and no lenis or nasally released sounds. The development of Ebiroid from PEB, basically involves a change in place of articulation from double place to single e.g. *kp > p, gb > b and spirantisation *b > v, *f > ʃ, h. A change from double place of articulation to single is not observed in Nupoid (see the development of sounds from PN to Nupoid (section 5.4) and from PEB to Ebiroid (section 6.4)).

In view of Ebiroid's multiple affiliation observable in the lexicostatistic study, the PN and PEB reconstructions as well as the entries in Table 19, differences in the sound inventory and change in Ebiroid, I propose an Ebiroid branch of BC (see Fig.8). Ebiroid and Nupoid are related at a higher level Proto Benue-Congo, but are independent of

each other under BC. The comparative method noted for establishing the actual genetic relationships between languages has been applied after the lexicostatistic study which served as a preliminary step towards sub-grouping and classification within BC.

7.4 The classification of Nupoid and Ebiroid

Fig. 8 Proposed classification within BC

In Fig.8 Ebiroid is set up as sister to Nupoid and Yoruboid coordinate with other groups under Benue-Congo proposed by Williamson (1989). I have used the University of Ibadan revised Swadesh 100 word list as well as the 400 word list of basic items. Cognates were established on the basis of regular sound correspondences before reconstructions were made. This method makes it possible to count as cognate lexical items, which, on the surface, show no resemblances.

The differences in the percentages recorded by Bennett and Sterk (1977), Tables 18 and 19 and those presented in Table 20, may be as a result of the different wordlists used and method employed in identifying cognates in the two studies. Bennett and Sterk (1977) calculated their percentage figures using a wordlist of about 87 item (see Appendix 1). The items although slightly different from those used here (see Appendix

11) are included in Swadesh's 200 wordlist (see Appendix). The picture that emerges from their lexicostatistic study is that Ebiroid is not as close to 'Nupoid' as their diagram seems to suggest. (Blench's (1989) figures also reflect this).

Going by all these figures, it is obvious that Ebiroid should enjoy independent status within Benue-Congo especially because it shares an average of 37 percent, 33 percent and 36 percent cognate count with Nupe, Gwari and Gade respectively. These figures are quite low in comparison with the 60 percent suggested by Williamson for the Group level. Ebira had earlier been classified with Nupe, Gwari and Gade in the same Group. Gade according to Table 20 should actually be slightly higher up the tree than Nupe-Gwari since it shares percentages in the neighbourhood of twenties and thirties with it. I proposed the following tree diagram for the internal classification of Nupoid going by Table 20.

Fig. 9

Proposed classification within Nupoid

This classification is based on figures in Tables 19-20. Idomoid is most distant from all of the languages and so it is placed higher up in the tree. Nupe-Gwari is just about equidistant between Gade and Idoma going by Bennett and Sterk 1977 percentage figures shared: Gade / Nupe = 38% ; Idoma/ Nupe 41% . Gade is closer to

Ebiroid and so is placed to the left hand side on the tree. Nupe and Gwari are closest and as such are sisters under the Nupe-Gwari node. An in-depth study of the relationship between Idomoid and Nupoid and with Yoruboid may indicate an even higher status for Idomoid seeing that it shares cognate count percentages in the same range as Ebiroid with Nupoid in Table 20. (Bennett and Sterk 1977 - Idoma/Yoruba= 43% Idoma / Igbirra 41%). The summary is that the internal classification of Benue-Congo calls for revisitation. This study serves as an aspect of this through the examination of the status of Ebiroid within Nupoid.

PART TWO

II.0 Reconstructions

There are two Reconstructions:

- i) PN (Proto-Nupoid) presented in Chapter Five. (These reconstructions are found in any Nupoid language).
- ii) PEB (Proto-Ebiroid) presented in Chapter Six. (These reconstructions are found in any Ebiroid language).

The C.S are numbered 1-242 for easy reference. The word stem system is used as the basis of the reconstructions. The reconstructions are presented starting from the Nupoid languages and then followed by the Ebiroid. For ease of reference the languages are indicated by the following numbers:

1. Nupe
2. Nupe Tako
3. Gwari
4. Gwari Yamma
5. Gade
6. Etuno
7. Ebiro Okene
8. Ebiro Kwotto

In the reconstructions, phonemic nasalisation is indicated on vowels and the nasalised consonants are also presented in the phonetic form however only where nasalisation is not phonemic after nasal consonants is it not indicated.

In the data, non-cognate items are enclosed in parentheses. Each C.S. is followed by comments on the particular C.S where necessary and cross references are made by citing the number of the relevant c.s., C.S or number of the relevant language.

No reconstruction is provided where cognate items are not wide spread. A stem found beyond PN, PEB or as the case may be is indicated by citing cognates or relevant lexical items or reconstructions from Benue-Congo or Niger-Congo. The reconstructions cited are as follows

- PYIG = Proto Yoruba-Isekiri-Igala (Akinkugbe 1978)
 PE = Proto Edoid from Elugbe (1973) / (1989).
 PI = Proto Ijo, from Williamson (unpublished notes) cited by Akinkugbe (1978).
 PLN = Proto-Lower Niger as cited in Akinkugbe (1978).
 PJ = Proto Jukunoid from Shimizu (1971). Items reconstructed for sub-groups of PJ are cited thus:
 PCJ = Proto-Central Jukunoid
 PYK = Yukuben-Kutep
 BCCW = Benue-Congo Comparative Wordlist, from Williamson and Shimizu (ed.) (1968) (Vol.I) and Williamson (ed.) (1973) (Vol II).
 PBC = Proto-Benue-Congo (nouns only), from De Wolf (1971) cited in Akinkugbe (1978).
 PBK = Proto-Benue-Kwa (consonants only), from Williamson and Elugbe (1977) cited in Akinkugbe (1978).
 PB = Proto-Bantu, from Guthrie (1967-71) cited in Akinkugbe (1978).
 PS = Proto-Sudanic from Westermann (1911) cited in Akinkugbe (1978).
 PWS = Proto-West Sudanic, from Westermann (1927) cited in Akinkugbe (1978)

C.S. 1

	PN *mə			'give birth'
1.	Nupe	ma		
2.	Nupe Tako	mɔ		
3.	Gwari	bímá		
4.	Gwari Yamma	mabí	< ma + efi bear + child	
5.	Gade	m ^w ɔ		
	PEB *ma			'give birth'
6.	Ebira Okene	muzí	< ma + ozi bear + child	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	mozí	< ma + ozi bear + child	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ma		

PYIG. bí 'give birth' (AK. C.S. 1)

- cf. Yoruba bimɔ 'give birth (to a child)'
 PE. bia 'give birth, bear (child)' (EL. C.S. 15)
 PB. biád 'bear child' (Gl. C.S. 136)

Two morphemes are observed in 3 and 4: [ebi] 'child' and [ma] 'to bear'. In the combined forms the verbal morpheme comes after the noun 'child' in 3. Akinkugbe (1978) noted that the PYIG noun [ɔmɔ] is a deverbal noun which verb stems no longer exist having observed the Tiv and Kambari cognate verb stems:

Tiv. mál 'offspring' < mál 'give birth to, beget' (Hoffmann)

C. Kambari mà(tsā) 'bear (child, fruit), beget' (Hoffmann)

A similar situation is evident in Gwari. *ma is reconstructed in PEB as evident in 9 since 7 and 8 forms are derived from two morphemes.

C.S. 2

	PN *miNi		'swallow'
1.	Nupe	ɲi	/ji/
2.	Nupe Tako	ɲi	/ji/
3.	Gwari	mí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	mí	
5.	Gade	muni	
	PEB *mune		'swallow'
6.	Ebira Okene	mú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	múnè	
8.	Ètunɔ (Igarra)	múné	

PE *dh i.e. C' of the item has reflex [m] in Ghotuo 'take': mu 'take'+ lholho 'swallow' and it is obviously cognate with not just PN and PEB but with all other reconstructions presented below

- PYIG. m'i 'swallow' (AK. C.S. 61)
 PE. dhɔNi 'swallow' (EL. C.S. 67) cf. Ebira Okene [dɔ] 'take' / [si] 'take'

PB. -min- 'swallow' (Gt. C.S. 1311)
 PBK. mh-dh 'swallow' (PBK. 36)
 pl. mēni 'swallow' (PBK. 36)

C.S. 3

PN *ə-pa			
1.	Nupe	e-pà	'skin'
2.	Nupe Tako	í-pà	
3.	Gwari	ə-pà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-pa	
5.	Gade	gù-pùtá	
PEB *u-kpa			
6.	Ebira Okene	ú-péŋ ^w ú	'skin' < upa + εŋu skin + body or 'hide of body'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-kpáhá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-pá	

The form in 6 is contracted from [u-pa] 'skin' and [εŋu] 'body' (C.S. 119)

PYIG. a-g'3 'skin, hide' (AK. C.S. 329)

PE. U-phɪNa (I-) 'skin' (EL. C.S. 178)

cf. Ghotuo a) /yofíá/ 'skin (of fruit, etc.) is a development from PE 'skin' in the preceding line.

b) /ɛ-kpà / 'skin, bag'

C.S. 4

PN *po			
1.	Nupe	po	'roast'
2.	Nupe Tako	po	
3.	Gwari	pó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	pó	
5.	Gade	(sɔ).	
PEB *fu			
6.	Ebira Okene	hù	'roast'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hù	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	fù	

PYIG. sū 'roast (in fire)' (AK. C.S. 143)

PE. ɪN 'roast' (EL. C.S. 183)

C.S. 5

PN *pitia

1.	Nupe	bitʃi	
	Nupe Tako	bitsi	'leg'
2.	Gwari	_____	
3.	Gwari Yamma	-putà	
4.	Gade	(gi-né)	
5.	PEB *a-fu		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-hù	'leg'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-hù	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-fù	

PYIG

ɔ-sē (ɛ-) 'foot, leg'

Ilaje

ɛ-hɛ 'foot, leg'

Ijumu

ɔ-hi 'foot, leg'

(AK. C.S. 40)

cf. Ebira Okene and Kwotto forms.

" " " " " " "

C.S. 6

PN *pitie

1.	Nupe	bije	'chicken (domestic fowl)'
2.	Nupe Tako	(a)-bitse	
3.	Gwari	pusé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	pusé (lug ^w é)	
5.	Gade	(gù-tɛnè)	
	PEB *V-ʃiuɛ		
6.	Ebira Okene	á-ɔhwé	'chicken (domestic fowl)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-úhè	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-ufé	

The vowel cluster situation noticeable in the PEB forms are derived from a reduction of the reduplicated stems as observable in 7. in C.S. 11 The C' of the reduplicated stem is deleted thus generating the vowel cluster (cf. Edoid).

PYIG a-ɔiwe 'chicken, fowl' (AK. C.S. 45)

PE O- khəkhə (l-) 'chicken (domestic fowl)' (EL. C.S. 122)

C.S. 7

PN *ɔ-pɔ

'moon'

- | | | |
|----|-------------|---------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-ts ^w a |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-tso |
| 3. | Gwari | o-pjã |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | o-pja |
| 5. | Gade | ù-pja |

PEB *u-fuc

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-hwɛ | 'moon' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-h ^w ɛ | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | u-fɛ | |

PYIG. -cù kpá 'moon' (AK. C.S. 237a)
 Yoruba o-fu kpa 'moon'
 Igala u-pja 'moon'

C.S. 8

PN *(-)piN

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | è-mi | 'house' |
| 2. | Nupe-Tako | è-m(i) | |
| 3. | Gwari | a-pi | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | o-p' i | |
| 5. | Gade | (gãm) | |

PEB *ire-ʃi

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|---------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ire-hi | 'house' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | è-hi | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ire-ʃi | |

PE U-bhaGɪ/U-baGɪ 'house, room' (EL. C.S. 5)

C.S. 9

PN *e-bi

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----------------------|-----------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-bi | 'kolanut' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | e-bi | |
| 3. | Gwari | (g ^w órò) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (g ^w órò) | |
| 5. | Gade | (górò) | |

PEB *irɛ-bu

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|-----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | irɛ-vu | 'kolanut' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (oó-bi) | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | irɛ-vú | |

The forms in 3-5 are borrowed from Hausa. The forms in 1 and 2 are cognate with PEB cf. Yoruba *o-bi* 'kolanut' and the PEB forms.

C.S. 10

PN *V-ba-

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|-----------|
| 1. | Nupe | è-ba | 'husband' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | i-bá | |
| 3. | Gwari | ǎ-bá | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | o-bá | |
| 5. | Gade | ù-bana | |

PEB *ɔ-ba

- | | | | |
|----|-----------------|------|-----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ǎ-vá | 'husband' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ǎ-bá | |
| 8. | Etunṣo (Igarra) | ǎ-vá | |

PYIG. ɔ-kɔ 'husband (male)' (AK. C.S. 283)

PE. O-chi (I-) 'man, male' (EL. C.S. 44)

C.S. 11

PN * bu-

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------------------|------------|
| | | | 'be white' |
| 1. | Nupe | bókù | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | bókù | |
| 3. | Gwari | bùibùl < bu (+i) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bùb"l < bu (+i) | |
| 5. | Gade | (zìré) | |

PEB *ɔ-bu

- | | | | |
|----|-----------------|----------------------|------------|
| | | | 'be white' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ǎ-vúɔvu ɔ-vu + (ɔvu) | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɔǎ-bu | |
| 8. | Etunṣo (Igarra) | ɔ-vuɔvu ɔ-vu + (ɔvu) | |

A suffix -i often occurs in 3 and 4 after the stem.

PYIG. -fù 'be white (rdl.)' (AK. C.S. 74)

PE. puNa 'be white' (EL. C.S. 173)

PWS. pù- 'weiss' (West. P. 279; Yor. And Okp.)

C.S. 12

PN *(a)-buo

- | | | | |
|----|------|----|-------------|
| | | | 'be rotten' |
| 1. | Nupe | vò | |

2.	Nupe Tako	vò
3.	Gwari	b ^w ò
4.	Gwari Yamma	à-b ^w ò
5.	Gade	vù
	PEB *bu	
6.	Ebira Okene	vù
7.	Ebira Kwotto	bù
8.	Ẹ̀tunọ̀ (Igarra)	vù

'be rotten'

- PYIG. bu 'become mouldy, rotten' (AK. p.s 20)
 Pl. buru 'become rotten' (Wil.)
 PB. -bòd- 'become rotten' (Gt. C.S. 153)
 PE. vuaNı 'stink' (EL. C.S. 201)
 PWS. buó 'faulen' (West. p.213)

C.S. 13

PN *gu-ba

1.	Nupe	gubà
2.	Nupe Tako	gúbà
3.	Gwari	m̩-bà
4.	Gwari Yamma	m̩-bà
5.	Gade	i-va

'two'

PEB *e-ba

6.	Ebira Okene	è:va
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-bà
8.	Ẹ̀tunọ̀ (Igarra)	è-va

'two'

- PYIG. è-ji 'two' (AK. C.S. 239)
 PE. i-va 'two' (EL. C.S. 194)
 PWS. -gi (-gi) 'zwei' (West. p. 221; Yor. Ig.)

1 and 2 have a CV prefix 'gu-' while 3 and 4 each have a syllabic nasal [m̩] as prefix. A CV-prefix is therefore reconstructed to show its existence in PN.

C.S. 14

PN *rɪ-βɛ

'breasts'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | e-bé | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | l-bé | |
| 3. | Gwari | ḡéḡé | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bebe | |
| 5. | Gade | ri-batù | |

PEB *iré-ba

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|-----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | iré-vá | 'breasts' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | iré-bá | |
| 8. | Etunḡ (Igarra) | iré-vá | |

PYIG. e-pá /e-yā/ 'breast' (AK. C.S. 270)

C.S. 15

PN *ḡe

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | be | 'come' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | bé | |
| 3. | Gwari | ḡe | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (ḡi) | |
| 5. | Gade | be | |

PEB *ḡe

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | vé | 'come' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | bé | |
| 8. | Etunḡ (Igarra) | vé | |

cf. Ghotuo vare 'come'

PYIG b'a 'come' (AK. C.S. 29)

cf. Tiv vá 'come' (Arm. b)

Cama. ḡá /ḡá/ 'come' (Maddieson, 1974)

PLN. bíà 'come' (Wil. 2)

PVP. b'a 'come' (St. p.5)

PWS. bíà, bá 'kommen' (West. p. 209; Yor. n.c.)

C.S. 16

PN *CV-biNi-

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-bi | 'feaces' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-bi | |
| 3. | Gwari | a-m ^ɔ i | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | e-m ^ɔ i | |
| 5. | Gade | ti-mí | |

PEB *e-mi

- | | | | |
|----|--------------|--------|----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (è-hè) | 'feaces' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | e-mí | |

Etunọ (Igarra) e-mí
 B. The form in 6 [èhè] is considered an innovation (cf. [èhèpí] 'urine', [ejí] 'water') since the other form for 'feaces', [emí] is cognate with PYIG and PWS.
 of Cama, a-bí, bí 'excrement'
 PYIG. V-b'V > PYOR i-wí 'feaces, excrement'
 PWS. (m)-bí, (m)-bin - 'kot'
 Pl. bíni 'defecate, buttocks'
 PB. -bí 'excreta'
 PBC. -bíj (a-) 'excrements'
 PE A-phéNí 'urine'
 (Maddieson 1974)
 (AK. C.S. 51)
 (West. p. 209, Yor.)
 (PBK11)
 (Gl. C.S. 135)
 (DeW. p. 59)
 (AK. C.S. 177)

C.S. 17 PN *fú

- | | | | |
|-----------|----------------|----------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | fù | 'fly' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | fù | |
| 3. | Gwari | (ja)fù | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (wata)fù | |
| 5. | Gade | furu | |
| PEB *ʃira | | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hirà | 'fly' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hirà | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ʃira | |

PYIG. fò 'fly, jump' (AK. C.S. 70) cf. Yor. sira 'hurry up'
 PS. pī 'fliegen' (West. p. 180 no.264a; Yor. p.c.)

C.S. 18

PN *fiN-

- | | | | |
|---------|----------------|-------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | fī | 'sweep' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | fī | |
| 3. | Gwari | fī | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | fībà | |
| 5. | Gade | (k*ú) | |
| PEB *ʃi | | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hi | 'sweep' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hi | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ʃi | |

PYIG. gbá 'sweep' (AK. C.S. 357)
 PWS. kùà, kùàli 'fegen, bursten' (West. p. 241)

C.S. 19

PN *CV -fiNít-

- | | | | |
|----|------|---------------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | firi ~ (fere) | 'leaf' |
|----|------|---------------|--------|

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--|
| 2. | Nupe Tako | fini | |
| 3. | Gwari | fintolo | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | fünt' e | |
| 5. | Gade | gu-fe | |

PEB *a-bi

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | a-vi | 'leaf' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (a-surukpa) | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | a-vi' | |

PYIG e-we (i-) 'leaf' (AK. C.S. 41)
 PE U-bi 'leaf' (EL. C.S. 16)

C.S. 20

PN *phiNi

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | fi | 'drink' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | fi | |
| 3. | Gwari | si(ni) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | si | |
| 5. | Gade | (wu) | |
- PEB *fu
- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|---------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hu | 'drink' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hu | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | fu | |

PYIG. ŋmū 'drink' (AK. C.S. 370)

PYIS. mu 'drink' (AK. C.S. 370)

PE. da 'to drink (alcohol)' (EL. C.S. 72)

A-yen 'drink (alcoholic)' (EL. C.S. 205)

yoNu drink '(water)' (EL. C.S. 207)

PB. -mū- 'drink' (Gt. C.S. 1332)

PWS. ni, nu, niu, niua 'trinken' (West. p. 269)

C.S. 21

PN *-phe

'wind'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | e-fè | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | i-fè | |
| 3. | Gwari | á-sé | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | o-se | |
| 5. | Gade | a-fu | |

PEB *a-fe

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | a-hi | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | a-hi | 'wind' |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | a-si - (afi) | |

- | | | | |
|-------|--------------|--------|--------------------------------|
| PYIG. | V-fu | 'wind' | |
| PE. | O-fedh- | 'wind' | (AK. C.S. 71) |
| PB. | -pèèpè | 'wind' | (EL. C.S. 78) |
| | -pépò | 'wind' | (Gl. C.S. 1491) |
| PWS. | -pap-, -pep- | 'wind' | (Gl. C.S. 1493) |
| Pl. | e-fèrù | 'wind' | (West. p. 274; Yor.)
(Wil.) |

C.S. 22

PN * -phu

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-fú | 'bee' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | è-fú | |
| 3. | Gwari | à-su | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | à-su | |
| 5. | Gade | (fité) | |

PEB *e-fu

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | e-hú | 'bee' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | e-hú | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | e-fú | |

- | | | | |
|-------|------------------|--------------|----------------------|
| PYIS. | ojī /oyī/ | 'bee' | (AK. C.S. 264) |
| PB. | -júki, -júkì | 'bee, honey' | (Gl. C.S. 962) |
| | PB. -jiki, -jiki | 'bee' | (Gl. C.S. 2003) |
| FWS | -mul 'Biene' | | (West. p. 259; yor.) |

C.S. 23

PN *CV-tuNukpua

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | tukpa | 'ear' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tukpa | |
| 3. | Gwari | tnubwà | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | tnubwà | |
| 5. | Gade | gú-tapú | |

PEB *u-tokpa

- | | | | |
|----|--------------|---------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-tó | 'ear' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-tókpá | |

- B Etunọ (Igarra) u-tɔ
 PYIG e-fl 'ear' (AK. C.S. 88)
 PE. ghU-chɔGr 'ear' (EL. C.S. 45)
 PB -tūi 'ear' (Meeussen, 1973)
 PBC -tuɲ (ku-/a-) (Dew. p. 56)
 PLN ń-tni 'ear' (PBK, 7)

C.S. 24

PN *tuNu (rdl.)		
1.	Nupe	tū 'send'
2.	Nupe Tako	tū
3.	Gwari	tnùtnù
4.	Gwari Yamma	tnutnù
5.	Gade	(ne)
PEB *tu		
6.	Ebira Okene	tútu 'send'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tū
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tɔ(ɔ)

- PYOR. rā 'send (someone to do something)' (AK. C.S. 180)
 PE. ghia, jhia 'send (someone to do something)' (EL. C.S. 87)
 PB. tùm- 'send' (Gt. C.S. 1813).
 PWS. tùm- 'arbeiten, (Zur Arbeit) schicken' (West. pp. 292-3)

C.S. 25

PN *tuNu- (rdl.)		'rubbish heap'
1.	Nupe	tùtùnti
2.	Nupe Tako	tutimpfi
3.	Gwari	(fidàkúlú)
4.	Gwari Yamma	tnùtnù
5.	Gade	(igíngbaàǝi)
PEB *ire-tu (rdl.)		'rubbish heap'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-tùtù
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-tutu
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	iri-tùtù

cf. Yoruba ààtā 'dunghill'

C.S. 26

PN *V-tuNu-

'ashes'

- 1. Nupe tūtūmpèrè
- 2. Nupe Tako tūtūmpèrè
- 3. Gwari a-tnú
- 4. Gwari Yamma tnúgu
- 5. Gade ñ-té

PEB *a-ti to

- 6. Ebira Okene a-titís
- 7. Ebira Kwotto a-titís
- 8. Etunò (Igarra) a-titís

'ashes'

- PYIG. e-rírú /e-l'íl'ú/ 'ashes' (AK. C.S. 186)
- PE. A-nhuNa 'ashes' (EL. C.S. 154)
- PB. -tó 'ashes' (Gt. C.S. 1769)
- túé 'ashes' (Gt. C.S. 1810)

C.S. 27

PN *a-takuN

- 1. Nupe tákù
- 2. Nupe Tako tákù
- 3. Gwari a-tá
- 4. Gwari Yamma tag*ú
- 5. Gade (rù-gwojĩ)

'grinding stone'

PEB *ire -t oku-

- 6. Ebira Okene ire-t-ókwòsè < ireta + ku + sa
'stone' 'grind'
- 7. Ebira Kwotto è-tókusá < ireta + ku
'stone' 'grind'
- 8. Etunò (Igarra) ire -t-ókw a: < ireta + ku + ai
'stone' 'grind'

'grinding stone'

This word has been formed from two morphemes: stone and grind.

The forms in 5,6,7, and 8 are formed from two different nouns. For the components of the forms in 5,6,7, and 8 (see C.S. 28 'stone' and C.S. 69 'grind').

In Ebiroid, [iretókwoɛ] is for grinding = 'pepper, beans' while [iretókwaɪ] is for grinding 'flour'

PYIG. V-ló 'grind' (AK. C.S. 208)

Cf. Yoruba gū 'grind to powder'

C.S. 28

PN *takuN, *u-kuta

	Nupe	táku	
1.	Nupe Tako	takù	'stone'
2.	Gwari	kùtá	
3.	Gwari Yamma	kuta	
4.	Gade	ù-ku	

PEB *ire-ta

6.	Ebira Okene	ire-tá	'stone'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ìrè -ta	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	ìr è -tà	

PYIG ɔ-kúta 'stone' (AK. C.S. 81)

PE U-goGɪ, -dio (I-) (EL. C.S. 59)

PB -tádè 'stone' (Gt. C.S. 1642)

PWS -ta-, -tali 'stein' (West. P. 285)

C.S. 29

PN*gu-ta

	Nupe	gútá			'three'
1.	Nupe Tako	gútá			
2.	Gwari	h-tá			
3.	Gwari Yamma		n-tjía	/-tia/	
4.	Gade	ta			

PEB *

e-ta

'three'

6.	Ebira Okene	èè-tá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-tá	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	è-tá	

PYIG è-ta 'three' (AK. C.S. 80)

PE ɪi-chaGɪ 'three' (EL. C.S. 37)

PJ tat (I-) 'three' (Sh. pp. 50-1)

PB -látù 'three' (Gt. C.S. 1689)

C.S. 30

PN *CV-dagba

'elephant'

1.	Nupe	dagba	
2.	Nupe Tako	dàgba	
3.	Gwari	dagbá	
4.	Gwari Yamma	dagbá	
5.	Gade	ga-dagba	

PEB *ɔ-dɔgba

6.	Ebira Okene	à-dɔbá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-dagbá	'elephant'
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-dába	
	cf. Igala à-dágbá	'elephant'	(AK. C.S. 174)
	PYIG. e-ń	'elephant'	(AK. C.S. 174)
	PE. E-ńi (I-)	'elephant'	(EL. C.S. 158)
	PWS. -ńi-	'elephant'	(West. p. 264, Yor.)

C.S. 31

PN *CV-dabua

1.	Nupe	è-dà	'shoe'
2.	Nupe Tako	à-dàba	
3.	Gwari	à-bwàdà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bwàdà	
5.	Gade	gù-dà ba	

PEB *r-dava

6.	Ebira Okene	à-dàva	'shoe'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-dàvà	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ì-dàvà	

The Gwari and the Gwari Yamma forms have been realised through metathesis.

C.S. 32

PN *V-da

			'father'
1.	Nupe	ń-dá	
2.	Nupe Tako	ń-dá	
3.	Gwari	à-mùdada - o-da	(Hyman and Magaji 1970)
4.	Gwari Yamma	mida	
5.	Gade	a-dá	

PEB *a-da

			'father'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-da, ń-da	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-dá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-dá	
	PE. O-chue (A-)	'father'	(EL. C.S. 33)

C.S. 33

PN *a-na

			'fire'
1.	Nupe	e-nā	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-nō	
3.	Gwari	ɔ-ná	

4.	Gwari Yamma	ɔ-nǎ	
5.	Gade	(gí-wa)	
	PEB *i-ra		
6.	Ebira Okene	i-rá	'fire'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-rá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	i-rá	

PYIG. u-niā /u-liā/ (i-) 'fire' (AK. C.S. 223)
 PWS. -ná- 'Feuer' (West. p. 282; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 34

PN *CV-nhi-

1.	Nupe	n-ní ~ nīnī	'one'
2.	Nupe Tako	nīnī	
3.	Gwari	ú-nú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gb̄h̄māri	
5.	Gade	(u-dè)	
	PEB *ɔ-ni, *ɔna		
6.	Ebira Okene	òni ~ òna	'one'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-na	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-ná	

PYIG. i-né /iñé/ 'one' (AK. C.S. 218)

C.S. 35

PN *gu-nia

'four'

1.	Nupe	gú-ní
2.	Nupe Tako	gú-nī
3.	Gwari	ñ-ní
4.	Gwari Yamma	gwa-ní
5.	Gade	i-nɔ

PEB *ε-na

'four'

6.	Ebira Okene	è-nà
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-nà
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	è-na

PYIG. ε-nī /εl'ī/ 'four' (AK. C.S. 176)

PE. -nia 'four' (EL. C.S. 159)

C.S. 36

PN *tiu

'pound'

1.	Nupe	tsu	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsu	
3.	Gwari	(bwa)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃu	
5.	Gade	tu	
	PEB *tu		
6.	Ebira Okene	tú	'pound'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tú	
PYIG	gú	'pound(in mortar)'	(AK. C.S. 307)
PE	đumhi	'pound (in mortar)'	(EL. C.S. 76)

C.S. 37

PN *tia

1.	Nupe	(ts ^w a)	'blow (of wind)'
2.	Nupe Tako	(tsó)	
3.	Gwari	səɬji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ə-sepia	
5.	Gade	à-fu	

PEB *tu

6.	Ebira Okene	tú	'blow (of wind)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tú	

PYIG. fé 'blow (of wind, with mouth)' (AK. C.S. 63)

PE. phuphu 'blow (with mouth)' (EL. C.S. 179)

C.S. 38

PN *tiu

'to die'

1.	Nupe	tsu	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsutsu	
3.	Gwari	(fi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-tʃú	
5.	Gade	tʃi	

PEB *su

'to die'

6.	Ebira Okene	sú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	sú	

PYIG ku 'die' (AK. C.S. 286)

PE. ghu 'die' (EL. C.S. 88)

PB. -kú- 'die' (Gt. C.S. 1249)

PWS. kù, kùé, kùí 'sterben, toten' (West. pp.237-8; Yor. and Ig. p.c.)

C.S. 39

PN *CV-kiukuNu

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------------------------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | tsúkù | 'bone' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-súkù | |
| 3. | Gwari | a-súkù | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | tʃúŋ ^w ù | |
| 5. | Gade | gu-k'ík ^w ù | |

PEB * -tʃ uku

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | é-tʃúku | 'bone' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | a-tʃókù | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | o-tʃókú | |

PYIG V-k'íkù 'bone' (AK. C.S. 302)

PB. kúpà 'bone' (Gt. C.S. 1273)

PWS. -kù, -kúp-, kúá 'knochen' (West. p. 238; Yor.)

C.S. 40

PN *ci

'descend'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | tʃi | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tsí | |
| 3. | Gwari | (ká)ʃi | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | ʃ'ɪʒi | |
| 5. | Gade | ʃi | |

PEB *tʃi

'descend'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-----|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | tʃi | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | tʃi | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | tʃi | |

C.S. 41

PN *V-cigbàNa

'tree'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----------------------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | tʃigbā | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tsigbò | |
| 3. | Gwari | a-ʃiŋ ^w ā | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | tʃim ^w ā | |
| 5. | Gade | ù-kí | |

	PEB *ɔ-tʃi	
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-tʃi 'tree'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-tʃi
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃi

PN reconstruction here is slightly different from that in C.S. 41. -Na at the end of this reconstruction is suspected to be a suffix meaning 'big' cf. Yoruba *nla* 'big'. Only in PEB is the reconstruction for 'tree' and 'stick' identical.

PYIG.	e-gi (i-) 'tree, firewood'	(AK. C.S. 305)
PE.	U-thaNi (I-) 'tree'	(EI. C.S. 188)
PB.	-kúnj 'firewood'	(GL. C.S. 1218)
PWS.	-gi, -gíl- (-git-) 'Baum'	(West. p.222-3; Yor. and Ig. p.c.)

C.S. 42

	PN *cigbiɔ	'stick'
1.	Nupe	tʃigba
2.	Nupe Tako	tsʃgbò
3.	Gwari	búsi
4.	Gwari Yamma	buti
5.	Gade	(ú-rúgbo)
	PEB *ɔ-tʃi	'stick'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-tʃi
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-tʃi
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	ɔ-tʃi

Forms in 3 and 4 are believed to have undergone metathesis.

C.S. 43

	PN *tsie	'shoot'
1.	Nupe	tʃé
2.	Nupe Tako	tsé
3.	Gwari	ʃé
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃówó
5.	Gade	tʃé
	PEB *tʃe	'shoot'
6.	Ebira Okene	(ha)

7. Ebira Kwotto tje
8. Etuno (Igarra) tje

PYIG. la 'shoot (arrow, catapult)' (AK. C.S. 78)
PYIG. jii /yii/ 'shoot (gun)' (AK. C.S. 265)
PB. -tá 'bow' (Gl. CS. 1631)
PWS. -tá- 'schiessen, Geschoss, Bogen' (West. pp.280-1; Yor.)

C.S. 44

PN *cie

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-----------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | tjé - je' | 'throw' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tsé | |
| 3. | Gwari | j'é | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | tjówó | |
| 5. | Gade | tjé | |

PEB *ne

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|---------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ne | 'throw' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ne | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ne | |

PYIG. so 'throw' (AK. C.S. 135)
PYOR. jù 'throw' (AK. C.S. 253)
PE. ca 'shoot, hit' (EL. C.S. 23)

C.S. 45

PN *si

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | ʃi | 'buy' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | ʃi | |
| 3. | Gwari | si | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | si | |
| 5. | Gade | si | |

PEB *ʃi

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hi | 'buy' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hi | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ʃi | |

PYIG. rà /là/ 'buy' (AK. C.S. 160)
PE. de 'buy' (EL. C.S. 73)
PB. -dând- 'buy' (Gl. CS. 490)
PWS. la, (lia, lua) 'kaufen' (West. p. 248; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 46

PN *a -za

1.	Nupe	e-za	'person'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-za	
3.	Gwari	a-za	
4.	Gwari Yamma	zàngg'ò	
5.	Gade	(ù-ní)	
	PEB	* a -za	
6.	Ebira Okene	ò -za	'person'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò -za	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò -za	

PYIG. a-ní /òlí (é-) (AK. C.S.216)

C.S. 47

PN *V-zu

			'beans'
1.	Nupe	e-zo	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-zo	
3.	Gwari	u-zu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(kapá)	
5.	Gade	(ń -kapa)	
	PEB *é-za		'beans'
6.	Ebira Okene	é-za	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	é-za	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	é-za	

PYIG. é-gwa /é-guà/ 'beans' (AK. C.S. 317)

Forms in 4 and 5 are considered to be innovations since they differ completely from the PN and PEB forms.

C.S. 48.

PN *lhuN- (rdl.)

'cotton/thread'

1.	Nupe	lulufuka
2.	Nupe Tako	lulu
3.	Gwari	lúlu
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɔwūfu
5.	Gade	(gèjè)

	PEB *o-wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	o-ú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-wú	'cotton/thread'
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-wú	
PE.	O-dhudhu (I-)	'cotton'	(EL. C.S. 69)

C.S. 49

	PN *		
1.	Nupe	lèmú	'orange'
2.	Nupe Tako	lèmú	
3.	Gwari	dzəmuyi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	rèmuuri	
5.	Gade	ù-lémú	
	PEB *		
6.	Ebira Okene	o-ròmí	'orange'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-lèmí	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-ròmí	

No reconstruction is made here since the item is borrowed from Hausa.

C.S. 50

	PN *ə-bui		'dog'
1.	Nupe	(e-ŋgi)	
2.	Nupe Tako	(i-ŋi)	
3.	Gwari	ə-muí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-mui	
5.	Gade	gə-biki	
	PEB *ire-zi		'dog'
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-zi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(a-bjá)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ire-zi	

The Ebira Kwotto form [abjá] is suspected to be cognate with Yoruba [adzá]

'dog'. This implies that two forms for 'dog' exist side by side in Ebiroid as in PN.

PE A-bhua 'dog' (EL. C.S. 12)

C.S. 51

PN *CV-zia

1.	Nupe	é-zi	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-zi	'egg'
3.	Gwari	ə-zi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è-zi	
5.	Gade	ŋ -zè	
		PEB *a-dzè	
6.	Ebira Okene	a-dzè	'egg'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	adzè	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-dzè	

PYIG	ɛ-g'ɪ	'egg'	(AK. C.S. 328)
PE	dhi-kiNa	'egg'	(EL. C.S. 112)
PB	gè	'egg'	(Gt. C.S. 79)
	gí	'egg'	(Gt. C.S. 809)
PBC	-kiŋ/-tiŋ (i-/a-)	'egg'	(DeW. p. 54)
PBK	-k-ŋ-	'egg'	(PBK. 8)

C.S. 52

PN * o-zi- (rdl.)

1.	Nupe	zik ^o	'black'
2.	Nupe Tako	zik ^o	
3.	Gwari	zijiɓiji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	dzidzi	
5.	Gade	(punu)	
		PEB *dziko (rdl.)	
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-dz'ódzi	'black'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-dzi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ó-dz'ódzi	

PYIG	dū	'be black'	(AK. C.S. 119)
PE	bi	'be black'	(EL. C.S. 21)

C.S. 53.

PN *ə-ja

1.	Nupe	e-ja	'year'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ja	
3.	Gwari	ə-já	

4.	Gwari Yamma	e-jé	
5.	Gade	ù-je	
	PEB *(ira)-je		
6.	Ebira Okene	ira-jé	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ji	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ira-jé	

'year'

PYIG. ɔ-dū 'year' (AK. C.S. 115)
 PE. U-kpe (A-) 'year' (EL. C.S. 133)

C.S. 54

PN *je-

1.	Nupe	jéle.	
2.	Nupe Tako	jéle	
3.	Gwari	jezihi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(mi)jézi	
5.	Gade	(ù-g ^w ɔ)	

'in-law'

PEB *ɔ-je

6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-jé	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-jé	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-jéé	

'in-law'

C.S. 55

PN *ɔ-ja

1.	Nupe	è-ja	
2.	Nupe Tako	e-ja	
3.	Gwari	à-ja	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(ù-fá)	

'buffalo'

PEB *ɛ-ja

6.	Ebira Okene	é-ja	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-ja	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɛ-ja	

'buffalo'

PYIG. ɛ-fá 'buffalo (bushcow) (AK. C.S. 72)

C.S. 56

PN *wi

1.	Nupe	ji	
2.	Nupe Tako	ji	

'steal'

3.	Gwari	w ^ɔ ɟ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	w ^ɔ ɟ	
5.	Gade	ɟi	
	PEB *ɟi		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɟi	'steal'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɟi	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	ɟi	
PYIG	ɟi 'steal'	(AK. C.S. 238)	
PE.	o-ɟi (A-) 'thief'	(EL. C.S. 67)	
PB.	-yib- 'steal'	(Gt. C.S. 1988)	
	-yib- 'steal'	(Gt. C.S. 2020)	

C.S. 57

	PN *e-wie		
1.	Nupe	è-ɟè	'eye'
2.	Nupe Tako	à-ɟe	
3.	Gwari	e-w ^ɔ ɟ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-w ^ɔ ɟ	
5.	Gade	(japí)	
	PEB *e-ɟi		
6.	Ebira Okene	e-i	'eye'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-ɟi	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	e-i	
PYIG	e-ɟú 'eye'	(AK. C.S. 252)	
PE.	dhl-dhu 'eye'	(EL. C.S. 71)	

C.S. 58

	PN *ɟiNkɔN		'tooth'
1.	Nupe	ɟiḱā	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ɟikɔ	
3.	Gwari	ɟiḱā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɟigā	
5.	Gade	riɟi	
	PEB *a-ɟi		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ɟi	'tooth'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ɟi	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	a-ɟi	

PYIG e-ɟū /e-yī/ 'tooth' (AK. C.S. 263)
 PE dhl-kuN (A-) 'tooth' (EL. C.S. 118)
 PWS. -ni,-nín- 'sahn' (West. pp. 267-8; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 59.

		PN *ji-	
1.	Nupe	jigidi	
2.	Nupe Tako	jigidi	'sun/sunshine'
3.	Gwari	ɲip-éi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	wlāŋgó	
5.	Gade	(ù-zù)	
		PEB *ɔ-ji	
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ji	'sun/ sunshine'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-ji	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ɔ-ji	

PYIG o-rū /o-l'ū / 'sun' (AK. C.S. 192)

PS. ʏfi 'Sonne, Gestirn' (West. p. 194 no. 312; Yor.)

C.S. 60

		PN *jiNKo	
1.	Nupe	jiwo	'female'
2.	Nupe Tako	jiwó	
3.	Gwari	ɲik*ózá	ɲik*ó + ɔ-za female + person
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲik*ózá	ɲik*o + zāŋg*ó female + person
5.	Gade	ɲí nē(ni)	
		PEB *ɔ-jeŋe	
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔɲéŋe	'female'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔɲije	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ɔjéŋe	

The form in 3 and 4 are contracted from the nouns: female and person. See C.S. 46 for reconstruction of 'person'. The form in 7 is considered older. It seems like a derived word from Yoruba words [eni] 'person' + [je] 'lay'. The forms in 6 and 8 are similar to the Nupoid forms.

		PN *jɔNkpa		'iron (metal)'
1.	Nupe	ɲāŋkpa		
2.	Nupe Tako	ɲāŋkpa		

3. Gwari (sũŋkɔ̃á)
 4. Gwari Yamma jajjá
 5. Gade (gá-tʃi)

PEB *ɔ-ɲise

6. Ebira Okene è-ɲise
 7. Ebira Kwotto e-ɲise
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) e-ɲise

'iron (metal)'

PYIG. u-ñ (i-) 'iron (metal)' (AK. C.S. 177)

C.S. 62 PN *jiNiko

1. Nupe ɲizáɟi
 2. Nupe Tako nzádʒi
 3. Gwari ɲik^wózá
 4. Gwari Yamma ɲik^wózá
 5. Gade ɲinèni

'woman'

PEB *ɔ-ɲene

6. Ebira Okene ð-ɲéne
 7. Ebira Kwotto ɔ-nijé
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) ð-ɲéne

'woman'

PYIG. o-bírí /o-bíl' T 'woman, female' (AK. C.S. 1b)

C.S. 63 PN *jiəN (rdl.)

1. Nupe ɲāɲā
 2. Nupe Tako ɲīɲā
 3. Gwari ɲāɲā
 4. Gwari Yamma ɲāɲā
 5. Gade (zimú)

'dance (v.)'

PEB *ɲeze

6. Ebira Okene ɲéze
 7. Ebira Kwotto ɲéze
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) ɲéze

'dance(v.)'

PYIG. jó 'dance v.' (AK. C.S. 248)

C.S. 64

PN *ə-die

'wine/beer (general word)'

1. Nupe e-g'e
 2. Nupe Tako i-ze

	Gwari	ɔ-dʒe	
3.	Gwari Yamma	e-d'e	
4.	Gade	bà-ʒe	
5.	PEB *e-tʃe		
6.	Ebira Okene	è-tʃè	'wine/beer (general word)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-tʃè	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	è-tʃè	

PYIG. ɔ-tʃi 'wine, beer (general word)' (AK. C.S. 91)
 PWS. tá (+nasal) 'zu Ende sei' (West. p. ; Yor.)

C.S. 65	PN *V-ku			
1.	Nupe	e-k ^w ú		'corpse'
2.	Nupe Tako	í-ku		
3.	Gwari	(zàfí)	two morphemes:	eza + fi
				'person' 'die'
4.	Gwari Yamma	zàtʃú		eza + tʃu
				'person' 'die'
5.	Gade	gi-tʃi		
	PEB *o-ku			'corpse'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-kú		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-kú		
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	o-kú		

PYIG ɔ-kú 'corpse' (AK. C.S. 286a)
 deverbal noun from 'die'
 PE O-dhimhi (A-) 'corpse' (EL. C.S. 64)
 PB -kú 'dead person' (Gt. C.S. 1247)

C.S. 66	PN *ka(ra)(pu)			'crab'
1.	Nupe	kara		
2.	Nupe Tako	a-kára		
3.	Gwari	kapú		
4.	Gwari Yamma	kapú		
5.	Gade	(rɪ-tʃene)		
	PEB *V-kakara			'crab'
6.	Ebira Okene	ù-kákàrà		

7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-kákàrá
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ó-kákara
PYIG.	a-kiàrà/akiàl'á /	'crab'
PB.	-káda	'crab'
PWS.	-ka-, -ka-	'Krabbe'

(AK. C.S. 300)
(Gl. C.S. 981)
(West. p. 230, Yor.)

C.S. 67 PN *piə

1.	Nupe	(ká)	'wring (clothes)
2.	Nupe Tako	(kɔ)	
3.	Gwari	pí (ja)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	pí	
5.	Gade	tse	

PEB *kama

6.	Ebira Okene	kámá	'wring (clothes)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(pìrí)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	kámá	

PYIG. fū 'wring (clothes), squeeze'
PE. mi 'wring (clothes)'

(AK. C.S. 73)
(EL. C.S. 144)

C.S. 68 PN *giə Na

1.	Nupe	gǎ	'divide' (share out)
2.	Nupe Tako	gó	
3.	Gwari	gɲǎ	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gɲǎ	
5.	Gade	(zà)	

PEB *ga

6.	Ebira Okene	gà	'divide (share out)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	gà	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	gà	

PYIG. kpī 'divide, share' (AK. C.S. 348)

C.S. 69 PN *go

1.	Nupe	g ^w o	'grind'
2.	Nupe Tako	g ^w o	
3.	Gwari	g ^w o	
4.	Gwari Yamma	g ^w o	
5.	Gade	k ^w o	

PEB *ku

6.	Ebira Okene	ku(sá)	'grind'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	kù	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	kù	
PYIG.	gù 'pound (in mortar)	(AK. C.S. 307)	
	lù 'grind'	(AK. C.S. 207)	
PE	lù 'grind'	(EL. C.S. 140)	

C.S. 70

PN

1.	Nupe	e-ga	'guest (stranger)
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ga	
3.	Gwari	(zìgbejì)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(gjerì)	
5.	Gade	(ù-ní zà)	

PEB*ɔ-zɔga

6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-zɔga	'guest (stranger)
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-zɔga	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɔ-zɔga	

C.S. 71

PN *V-kpa

1.	Nupe	e-kpa	'snail'
2.	Nupe Tako	à-kpāṅkúrú	
3.	Gwari	ɔ-ká	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɔ-ka	
5.	Gade	ú-kpa	

PEB * -kɔkɔrɪ

6.	Ebira Okene	ú-kákórɪ	'snail'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ɪrɛ-kpá)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	à-kí kórɪ	

PYIG. u-gbī (ɪ-) 'snail' (AK. C.S. 363)

C.S. 72

PN *ə-kpɔNi

1.	Nupe	kpomi	'okro'
2.	Nupe Tako	à-kpɔm(i)	
3.	Gwari	à-kpɔmí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ò-kpɔmí	

	Gade	(ri-k ^w oibi)	
5.	PEB *ε-kpɛfu		
	Ebira Okene	e-péhu	'okro'
6.	Ebira Kwotto	è-kpè	
7.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-péfú	
8.			

C.S. 73.

	PN *CV-gbɔgbɔ		
1.	Nupe	gbèrè	'root'
2.	Nupe Tako	gbèrè	
3.	Gwari	à-gbeg'è	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gbèr'è	
5.	Gade	tó-gbògbò	

PEB *ε -kpa

6.	Ebira Okene	è-pɔtʃi	epa + ɔtʃi Body + stick/tree	'root'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-kpá		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	e-pà		

cf. Yoruba 'gbòngbò 'root'

C.S. 74

	PN *-gbhuɔpiNi		'left'
1.	Nupe	g ^w ápì	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-gɔpi	
3.	Gwari	bwápmi	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bwápmí	
5.	Gade	(gà-pèrè)	

PEB *u-bɔfa

6.	Ebira Okene	u-vóhà	'left'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-bóha	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-vófa	

PYIG. o-si 'left (hand side)' (AK. C.S. 130)

C.S. 75

	PN *-gbhuɔ-		'right (side)'
1.	Nupe	a-g ^w alò	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-gɔlò	
3.	Gwari	bwaizè	

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------------|----------------|
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bwarɪdʒlɛ | |
| 5. | Gade | (gá-rí'rí) | |
| | PEB *-bɔɪ | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-vɔ́ŋ | 'right (side)' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-bɔ́ŋ | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | u-v ɔ́ŋ | |

PYIG ɔ-tu 'right (hand side)' (AK. C.S. 94)

C.S. 76

PN *CV-gbhɔɔ-

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------------------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-g ^w a | 'hand' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-gɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | o-bwá | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | wagmá | |
| 5. | Gade | gu-b ^w o | |

PEB *u-bɔ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-vɔ́ | 'hand' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-bɔ́ | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | u-vɔ́ | |

PYIG ɔ-b'ɔ 'hand' (AK. C.S. 31)

PE. ghU-ɔɔ (A-) 'hand' (EL. C.S. 17)

PB. -bókó 'arm' (Gt. C.S. 158)

PWS. -búá, -búák- 'oberarm' (West. p. 212)

C.S. 77 PN *wu

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | wu | 'kill' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | wu | |
| 3. | Gwari | wu | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | wú | |
| 5. | Gade | wú | |
| | PEB *wu 'kill' | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | wu | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | wu | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | wu | |

PYIG. lú 'beat (person, drum)' (AK. C.S. 210)

PE. gbeGi 'beat, kill' (EL. C.S. 90)

C.S. 78

PN *wu

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | wo | |
| | Nupe Tako | wo | 'hear' |
| 2. | Gwari | wo | |
| 3. | Gwari Yamma | háwô | |
| 4. | Gade | wu | |

PEB *wu

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|--------|
| 5. | Ebira Okene | wú | 'hear' |
| 6. | Ebira Kwotto | wú | |
| 7. | Etuno (Igarra) | wú | |

PYIG. gbá

'hear' (AK. C.S. 360)

PE chuanha, chianhi

'hear' (EL. C.S. 48)

C.S. 79

PN *wo

- | | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|-----------------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | woro | | 'new' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | woro | | |
| 3. | Gwari | weiwei | (wo)we+i (rdl.) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | wowe | | |
| 5. | Gade | (pɪpa) | | |

PEB *ɔ-wɔwɔ

- | | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-wɔwá | | 'new' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɔ-wɔ:wá | | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ɔ-wɔwá | | |

PYIG. -tū 'be new (rdl.)' (AK. C.S. 95)

PE. pha 'be new' (EL. C.S. 174)

-gbɔ 'newness' (EL. C.S. 93)

C.S. 80

PN *kawia

'dry'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------------------------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | wo | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | wí'wɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | kawí | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | a-k ^w okawu | |
| 5. | Gade | (kikéré) | |

PEB *ɔ-we

'dry'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | wu | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ó-wejí | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ɔ-wèŋwá | |

PYIG. gbe
PE ka
'become dry' (of water, cloth etc.) (AK. C.S. 356)
'dry' (EL. C.S. 103)

C.S. 81
PN * CV-wa

1.	Nupe	e-wa	
	Nupe Tako	i-wa	'snake'
2.	Gwari	o-wa	
3.	Gwari Yamma	o-wa	
4.	Gade	gù-wá	
5.	PEB	* e-wu	
6.	Ebira Okene	e-u	'snake'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-wu	
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	(i-setfi)	

C.S. 82

PN *- niàN

1.	Nupe	wó +nā	gbo + enā	'hot (as fire)'
			strong + fire	
2.	Nupe Tako	wó +nò	gbo + inā	
			strong + fire	
3.	Gwari	zì +nā'	zì +anā	
			strong + fire	
4.	Gwari Yamma	gḡū +nā	gḡū + nā	
			strong + fire	
5.	Gade	ḡa+gi-wa	< ḡa + giwa	

PEB *ḡ^wura

6.	Ebira Okene	ḡ ^w urá	< ḡ ^w u + ira 'dry fire'	'hot (as fire)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ḡ ^w urá	< ḡ ^w u + ira	
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	ḡ ^w ùra	< ḡ ^w u + ira	

PYIG. ta 'be hot as pepper'

(AK. C.S. 79)

Cf. Yoruba gbóná 'be hot'

C.S. 83

PN *

'swell (of

boil)

1.	Nupe	wù
2.	Nupe Tako	ḡ ^w ū

3.	Gwari	(sū)	
4.	Gwari Yamma		(a-si)
5.	Gade	(yi)	
	PEB	*wū	
6.	Ebira Okene	wū	'swell(of boil)
7.	Ebira Kwotto	wū	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)		wū

C.S. 84 PN *pa

1.	Nupe	pa	'to tie (rope)'
2.	Nupe Tako	pa	
3.	Gwari	pa	
4.	Gwari Yamma	pa	
5.	Gade	(kʲɛ)	
	PEB	*sū	
6.	Ebira Okene	sū	'to tie (rope)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sū	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	sū	

PYIG so 'tie (rope, animal etc) (AK. C.S. 136)
 PE fadhı 'tie (bundle); make (rope) (EL. C.S. 77)

C.S. 85

PN *pa 'remember'

1.	Nupe	pa	
2.	Nupe Tako	pa	
3.	Gwari	pá	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(mukpéyelo)	
5.	Gade	(tɛ)	
	PEB	*tamaji	'remember'
6.	Ebira Okene	támái	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	támaji	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	támái	

C.S. 86

PN *a-bia 'knife'

1.	Nupe	e-bi	
2.	Nupe Tako	è-bi	
3.	Gwari	a-be	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-be	

5.	Gade	u-ba	
	PEB *u-fu ₃		
6.	Ebira Okene	ù-h ^w ɔ	'knife'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-hɔ	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ù-fɔ	

PYIG. ɔ-be 'knife' (AK. C.S. 6a)

C.S. 87

	PN *ba		
1.	Nupe	bà	'count'
2.	Nupe Tako	bà	
3.	Gwari	bà	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bà	
5.	Gade	(zà)	
	PEB *-ka		
6.	Ebira Okene	kà	'count'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(zi)kà	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	kà	

The PEB stem *ka, is related to the PYIG stem for 'count' and 'recount'
 PYIG ka 'count' (AK. C.S. 275)
 cf. kà 'recount, tell, say, gossip' (AK. C.S. 276)
 PWS. bà, bàl- 'sahlen' (West. p. 204)?

C.S. 88

	PN *gbuodɪNko		'thigh'
1.	Nupe	gbòko	
2.	Nupe Tako	buzik ^w o	
3.	Gwari	bùzik ^w ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bwòzìngwó	
5.	Gade	gwògji	
	PEB *u-siji		'thigh'
6.	Ebira Okene	u-sí	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-siji	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	u-sí	

PYIG u-tiã (i-) 'thigh' (AK. C.S. 97)

C.S. 89

PN *6a

1.	Nupe	bā	'break (pot, calabash)'
2.	Nupe Tako	(lā)	
3.	Gwari	bāja	
4.	Gwari Yamma		
5.	Gade	(tʃikā)	
	PEB *tʃaka		
6.	Ebira Okene	tʃaká	'break (pot, calabash)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tʃaká	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	sáká	

Cf. Yoruba là 'split'

PYIG. f5 'break (pot, calabash etc.)' (AK. C.S. 67)

C.S. 90

PN *ǝ-mɪ

1.	Nupe	e-mi	'oil'
2.	Nupe Tako	(inzini)	
3.	Gwari	ǝ-mí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ǝ-mí	
5.	Gade	(bà-nɪ)	
	PEB *a-ŋ ^w é		'oil'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ŋ ^w é	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ŋ ^w é	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-ŋ ^w é	

PE. A-bhidhi (l-) 'oil' (EL. C.S. 8)

C.S. 91

PN *matiaN

1.	Nupe	mátsa	'laugh v.'
2.	Nupe Tako	mótsɔ	
3.	Gwari	masā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	matsā	
5.	Gade	(tʃɪ tùm ^w ó)	
	PEB *ɲɪ (rdl.)		'laugh v.'

- | | | | |
|------|----------------|----------------|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | nijī | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | nūjī | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | nūjī | |
| PYIG | ri /li 'laugh' | (AK. C.S. 172) | |
| PE | ghia (gbai?) | (EL. C.S. 92) | |

C.S. 92

PN * mɔ

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------|------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | mā | 'sweet, (tasty)' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | mɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | (ndá) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (dá) | |
| 5. | Gade | munu | |

PEB *jine

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|-----------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hiné | 'sweet (tasty)' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hiné | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | jine | |

C.S. 93

PN *mɛNdeN

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-----------|-------------|
| 1. | Nupe | mādā | 'hunger n.' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | mɔdɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | (mí kɛŋŋ) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (mí ŋwŋ) | |
| 5. | Gade | ŋ-mé | |

PEB *u- ŋwe

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------|---------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | u-ŋwe | 'hunger (n.)' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-ŋwe | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | u-ŋwe | |

PYIG. e-bi 'hunger' (AK. C.S. 3)

C.S. 94

PN *

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|-----------------|
| | | | 'wash (things)' |
| 1. | Nupe | fō | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | fo | |
| 3. | Gwari | (zā) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (dzidá) | |
| 5. | Gade | (nijī) | |

		PEB *jina	
6.	Ebira Okene	jina	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	jina	'wash (things)'
8.	Etuno (Igarra)		
		ji na	

C.S. 95		PN *	
1.	Nupe	fafa	
2.	Nupe Tako	fafa	'dawn'
3.	Gwari	(labmi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(gezū)	
5.	Gade	(gegigi)	
		PEB *	
6.	Ebira Okene	(é-túh ^w eí)	'dawn'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(i-dzeí bobo)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	(ò-nénévíri)	

C.S. 96		PN *CV-tiuko	
1.	Nupe	e-ti	'head'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ti	
3.	Gwari	túk ^w ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	túg ^w ó	
5.	Gade	ru-tu	

		PEB *ire-su	'head'
6.	Ebira Okene	ire-sú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	e-sú	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ire-sú	

- PYIG. o-d'i 'head' (AK. C.S. 121)
- PE U-chiamhi (A-) 'head' (EL. C.S. 42)
- PB. -tu 'head' (Gt. C.S. 1808)
- Pl. tifi 'head' (Wil.)

C.S. 97		PN *tu	'vomit'
1.	Nupe	tu	
2.	Nupe Tako	tú	
3.	Gwari	tu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tú	
5.	Gade	(gwò)	
		PEB *huere	'vomit'

6	Ebira Okene	hèrè	
7	Ebira Kwotto	hwèrè	
8	Etunọ (Igarra)	(kàrènu) v.	(irèn) n.

PYIG sè 'vomit', precipitate' (AK. p.s. 139)
 PE. kpa 'vomit' (EL. C.S. 128)

C.S. 98

	PN *e-tuNu	(rdl.)	
1.	Nupe	e-tū	'work' n
2.	Nupe Tako	i -tū	
3.	Gwari	tnutnù	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tnùtnù	
5.	Gade	(gà-time)	

PEB *-kórɔ

6.	Ebira Okene	u-kórɔ	'work n.'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-kórɔ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-kórɔ	

PYIG. u-cé 'work (n.)' (AK. C.S. 229)

C.S. 99

	PN *tsiNi		'plait (hair)'
1.	Nupe	ti	
2.	Nupe Tako	ti	
3.	Gwari	kɲí	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kɲí	
5.	Gade	(m ^w ɔ)	

PEB *za

6.	Ebira Okene	(gú)	'plait (hair)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	zá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(và)	

PYIG. bā 'plait' (hair, rope) (AK. C.S. 109)

dí 'plait' (hair, rope) (AK. C.S. 23)

PE. dí 'tie (rope)' (EL. C.S. 56)

PB. -dít- 'tie a knot' (Gt. C.S. 629)

C.S. 100

PN *CV-da

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|-----------|
| 1. | Nupe | gada | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | (mátsi) | 'matchet' |
| 3. | Gwari | à-da' | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | ò-dá | |
| 5. | Gade | à-ndá | |

PEB *tokofi

- | | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|-----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (o-h ^w óbáñi) | ò-h ^w + óbáñi | 'matchet' |
| | | | 'knife' 'big' | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | tókòfi | | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | (ò-pija) | | |
| | cf. Yoruba | à-dá | 'matchet' | |

C.S. 101 PN *da-

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------------|------------|
| 1. | Nupe | dà | '(be) wet' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | dá | |
| 3. | Gwari | (búdó) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | dafi | |
| 5. | Gade | (u-mòzokwò) | |

PEB *o-fuefu

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-----------|------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (e-nejì) | '(be) wet' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | o-hwehùrú | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ó-fófú | |

PYIG -tu 'be wet, cold' (AK. C.S. 96)

Igala ridòdò

C.S. 102 PN *

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | è-dā | 'bat' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | à-dó | |
| 3. | Gwari | (vi-ja) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (zupa) | |
| 5. | Gade | - | |

PEB *arí-ga

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | arí-ga | 'bat' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | irú-ga | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | arí-ga | |

C.S. 103

PN *a-diaNsu

'fear n.'

1.	Nupe	dāsū	
2.	Nupe Tako	dòsu	
3.	Gwari	à-dnā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è-dnā	
5.	Gade	(ñ-zìzè)	
	PEB *a-ŋwajɪ		
6.	Ebira Okene	à-ŋwāhi	'fear n.'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ŋwāhi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	a-ŋwajɪ	
	PYIG. à-rū	'fear (n.)'	(AK. C.S. 190)
	PE. U-piN	'fear (n.)'	(EL. C.S. 169)

C.S. 104

PN *diəziəN

1.	Nupe	dazā	'walk v.'
2.	Nupe Tako	dɪ'zò	
3.	Gwari	zāzā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	dàzā	
5.	Gade	(zu)	
	PEB *zuse		
6.	Ebira Okene	zuse	'walk v.'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	zuse	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	zuse (use (n.))	
	PYIG. rɪ/ɪ/	'walk v.'	(AK. C.S. 178)
	PE. khiNa	'walk, go'	(EL. C.S. 121)

C.S. 105

PN *-n-dache

'hunter'

1.	Nupe	n-datʃe	< nda + etse /tʃe father shoot /throw
2.	Nupe Tako	ñ-də'tsé	
3.	Gwari	(nagbeyi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(bóúfè)	
5.	Gade	(a-zunu)	
	PEB *o-(zu)gbe		
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-zùbè	'hunter'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-zùgbèi	

8. Etunõ (Igarra) ð-bè

C.S. 106

PN *tiu-

1. Nupe (dag^wa) < da + eg^wa 'walk' 'hand' 'push'

2. Nupe Tako (dag^wo) < da + ago 'walk' 'hand'

3. Gwari tjaðwaja < tje + oðwa + ja 'throw' 'hand' 'away'

4. Gwari Yamma tjuja < tje + uja 'throw' 'away'

5. Gade tju
PEB *tuuvõ

'push'

6. Ebira Okene tuuvõ < tu + uvõ 'send' 'hand'

7. Ebira Kwotto (gbubõ) < gbe+ ubõ 'hand'

8. Etunõ (Igarra) tuuvõ < tu + uvõ 'send' 'hand'

PYIG. ti 'push'

(AK. C.S. 89)

Igala kécè < ka ... ècè

Ife Togo télè (Arm.a)

C.S. 107

PN *diuNa

'burn (tr.)'

1. Nupe dinã

2. Nupe Tako dinõ

3. Gwari dnãdnã

4. Gwari Yamma (á-gì)nã

5. Gade du

PEB *rira

'burn (tr.)'

6. Ebira Okene ri

7. Ebira Kwotto rira

8. Etunõ (Igarra) rira

PYIG. jó 'burn (trans.)' (AK. C.S. 247)

PE. tuchi 'burn (trans.)' (EL. C.S. 185)

C.S. 108

PN *

1.	Nupe	dī	'pull'
2.	Nupe Tako	dī	
3.	Gwari	(gŋī)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(gŋī)	
5.	Gade	(kúkwo)	
	PEB*tura		
6.	Ebira Okene	tùrà	'pull'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	tùrà	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	tùrà	

C.S. 109

PN *CV-zīNi-

1.	Nupe	(dīnī)	'housefly'
2.	Nupe Tako	(ā-ndīnī)	
3.	Gwari	bùzùk ^w ó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bùzùg ^w ò	
5.	Gade	gù-ǰī	
	PEB *i-si-		'housefly'
6.	Ebira Okene	ì-sì	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ì-sikpá	
8.	Ẹtunọ (Igarra)	ì-sì	

PYIG V-cīcī 'housefly' (AK. C.S. 232)

PE. A-khīNa (I-) 'housefly' (EL. C.S. 120)

PBC -zin (i-/i-) 'fly' (DeW. p. 55)

PB. -ǰī 'fly' (Gt. C.S. 819)

C.S. 110

PN *- du

			'cook'
1.	Nupe	du	
2.	Nupe Tako	du	
3.	Gwari	(na) du	
4.	Gwari Yamma		
5.	Gade	(nū) ~ (sa)	
	PEB *fū		'cook'
6.	Ebira Okene	hú for solids; ne me (for liquids)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hú " " ne " "	

8.	Etuno (Igarra)	fù	
PYIG	si	'cook'	(AK. C.S. 127)
PYIS	se	'cook'	(AK. C.S. 127)
PLN	si	'cook'	(Wil. 56)

C.S. 111

PN *

1.	Nupe	è-dù	'sea'
2.	Nupe Tako	è-dù	
3.	Gwari	(à-là)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(sugwó)	
5.	Gade	(u-zò)	
	PEB *ire-fu		
6.	Ebira Okene	ìrè-hù	'sea'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	è-hù	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ìrè-fù	

C.S. 112

PN *

1.	Nupe	dùkù	'(water) pot'
2.	Nupe Tako	dùkù(nùḡwā)	
3.	Gwari	(nùḡwāfjakḡū)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	džúmúù	
5.	Gade	(gì-yákpà)	
	PEB *i-noko		'(water) pot'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-nókó ~ u-rùkù	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-nókó	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	u-nókó , ò-džĩ	

C.S. 113

PN *V-doko

1.	Nupe	dòkò	'horse'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-dòk ^w ò	
3.	Gwari	dok ^w ò	
4.	Gwari Yamma	dog ^w ò	
5.	Gade	(ù-vakà)	
	PEB *V-baŋta		'horse'
6.	Ebira Okene	u-mántà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-bátà	

B. Etuno (Igarra) ò-vurata

C.S. 114
PN *

- | | | | |
|-----------|----------------|----------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | dontfi | 'mortar' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | dotsi | |
| 3. | Gwari | (gɔ̃jɔ̃) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (gɔ̃jɔ̃) | |
| 5. | Gade | (gòtu) | |
| PEB *i-ne | | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | i-nè | 'mortar' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | i-nè | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | i-nè | |

C.S. 115 PN *nuNwɔN

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | nũŋ ^w ã | 'water' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | nũŋ ^w ɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | nũŋ ^w ɔ | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | nũŋ ^w ɔ | |
| 5. | Gade | (ù-zɔ) | |

PEB *e-ji

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|---------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | e-ji | 'water' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | e-ji | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | e-ji | |

PYIG. o-mĩ 'water' (AK. C.S. 52)

PE. A-mɪN (I-) 'water' (EL. C.S. 146)

Pl. fèDijĩ 'water' (PBK 42)

PBK. -bh-dh-ŋ 'water' (PBK. 42)

C.S. 116

PN *a-na

'goat'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | nãŋgi | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-nõ | |
| 3. | Gwari | à-nã | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | è-nã | |
| 5. | Gade | (fubu) | |

PEB *e-bu

'goat'

6.	Ebira Okene	ε-vú
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-bú
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-vú

PYIG. ɔ-búko	'he goat'	(AK. C.S. 19)
PYIG. ε-b'ó	'she goat'	(AK. C.S. 32)
PE E-bhui (I-)	'goat'	(EL. C.S. 13)
PB. -búđi	'goat'	(Gt. C.S. 185)
PBC. -bwoni (I- / I-)		(DeW. p. 55)

C.S. 117

PN *nəNkpiaN

1.	Nupe	nāmpá	< ɔ-nā + e-pa 'animal' + 'skin'	'leopard'
2.	Nupe Tako	nāpá		
3.	Gwari	nakp̄mī		
4.	Gwari Yamma	_____		
5.	Gade	(fū-zè)		

PEB *ε-zu

6.	Ebira Okene	ε-zu		'leopard'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ù-dòmì)		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ε-zu		

PE E-kpɛN (I-) 'leopard' (EL. C.S. 135)

C.S. 118

PN *nanɔ

1.	Nupe	nānā		'dream v.'
2.	Nupe Tako	nánō		
3.	Gwari	nāná		
4.	Gwari Yamma	nānā		
5.	Gade	(kurubāna)		

PEB *rura

6.	Ebira Okene	rura		'dream v.'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	rúrá		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	rura		

PYIG. lá 'dream v.' (AK. C.S. 202)

PB. -dāād- 'lie down' (Gl. CS. 454)
 -daad- 'pass the night' (Gl. CS. 456)
 cf. Cama. lá rina / dá ādā/ 'sleep' (Maddieson 1974)

C.S. 119

PN *nókó-

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|------------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | naka | 'body' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | nókotsigbà | |
| 3. | Gwari | najī | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (pātā) | |
| 5. | Gade | (i-wu) | |

PEB *ε-ηυ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------------------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ε-ηυ | 'body' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ε-ηυ | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ε-ηυ ~ εη ^w υ | |

PYIG. V- ra /M'a/ 'body' (AK. C.S. 158)

C.S. 120

PN*

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | nākā | 'meat' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | nókā | |
| 3. | Gwari | (ā-bu) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (búda) | |
| 5. | Gade | (fūtjī) | |

PEB

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | * u-ye | 'meat' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | u-ye | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | u-ye | |

C.S. 121

PN*

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | nāvo | 'refuse' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | nòvo | |
| 3. | Gwari | (fiwo) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | — | |
| 5. | Gade | (g ³ ε) | |

PEB *ji

- | | | | |
|----|--------------|----|----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ji | 'refuse' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | jī | |

8. Etuno (Igarra) ji

C.S. 122

PN *e-niaN

1.	Nupe	e-ni	'soup'
2.	Nupe Tako	e-ni	
3.	Gwari	e-ji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-ji	
5.	Gade	i-ne	

PEB *ε-kpε

6.	Ebira Okene	è-pè	'soup'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(o-bo)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	è-pè	

C.S. 123

PN *a-nieN-

1.	Nupe	e-ni	'song'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ni	
3.	Gwari	a-ji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	jik ^w o	
5.	Gade	à-je	

PEB *a-fε

6.	Ebira Okene	a-hé	'song'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-hé	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-fé	

PYIG. e-ri /e'l'i/ (AK. C.S. 175)

PE. l-yodho 'song' (EL. C.S. 206)

C.S. 124

PN *-daNa-

1.	Nupe	tsudā	'fear' v.
2.	Nupe Tako	tsudò	
3.	Gwari	dnàwó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	è- dnà	
5.	Gade	(n - zizè)	

PEB * a- η^w aji

6.	Ebira Okene	à-ηwahĩ	'fear'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ηwahĩ	

8. Ètunọ (Igarra) à-ṅwàjì
 PYIG. à-rù 'fear n.' (AK. C.S. 190)
 Cf. Yoruba. i-dāwo 'test'

C.S. 125

PN *CV-tiuNu

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | gútsù | 'five' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | gútsù | |
| 3. | Gwari | ṅ-tnú | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (ṅákṅú) | |
| 5. | Gade | t-tó | |

PEB *ε-ʃɪ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | è-hì | 'five' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | è-hì | |
| 8. | Ètunọ (Igarra) | ε-ʃɪ | |

PYIG. à-rūā /al'ū/ 'five' (AK. C.S. 195)
 PE. ii-chiNānhi 'five' (EL. C.S. 43)
 PJ. ton (i-) 'five' (Sh. pp. 60-1)
 PB. -cáánò 'five' (Gt. C.S. 275)
 PBK. -T-ṅ-nh-

C.S. 126

PN *o-tiu

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----------|--------------|
| 1. | Nupe | o-tsu | 'king/chief' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | o-tsu | |
| 3. | Gwari | e-tsu | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | o-tʃu | |
| 5. | Gade | (u-gomə) | |

PEB *o-ʃinóʃɪ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----------|--------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | o-hinóʃɪ | 'king/chief' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | o-hinóʃɪ | |
| 8. | Ètunọ (Igarra) | o-ʃinóʃɪ | |

PE. O-via (l-) 'five' (EL. C.S. 195)

C.S. 127

PN *cigbɔN-

1.	Nupe	tʃigbɔ	
2.	Nupe Tako	tsigbɔnɔgú	'firewood'
3.	Gwari	ʃiŋ ^w á	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tʃimwaná	
5.	Gade	(i-wu)	

PEB *ɔ-ku

6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ku	'firewood'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-kó	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ɔ-ku	

PYIG. e-gi (i-) 'tree, firewood'

(AK. C.S. 305)

PBC. kwoni (bu-ŋ-) 'firewood'

(DeW. p. 57)

PWS. -gí, -gíl- (-git-) 'Baum'

(West. pp. 222-3; Yor. and Igala p.c.)

C.S. 128

PN *cigbe

1.	Nupe	tʃigbé	'medicine (charm)'
2.	Nupe Tako	tsigbé	
3.	Gwari	ʃi'gbé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(amùsùŋkpi)	
5.	Gade	—	

PEB *ira-fɔnɔ

6.	Ebira Okene	à-hònò	'medicine (charm)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ɛ-tʃikpà)	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ìrà-fɔnò	

PYIG. o-gū 'medicine'

(AK. C.S. 311)

C.S. 129

PN *tiaNtia

1.	Nupe	tʃi'ntara	'tail'
2.	Nupe Tako	tsità	
3.	Gwari	sási	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ténti'	
5.	Gade	(u-p ^w ɔ)	

PEB *o-mu-

tail'

6.	Ebira Okene	ò-mùtá
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-mù
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-mù

Forms in 3 and 4 have undergone metathesis.

C.S. 130

		PN *V-ti	
1.	Nupe	e-tʃi	'yam'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-tsi	
3.	Gwari	(jǎmá)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɔ-tʃi	
5.	Gade	(gɪ-zè)	
		PEB *E-NU	
6.	Ebira Okene	ɛ-nu	'yam'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-nu	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(é-vina)	

PYIG. u-cū (i-) 'yam' (AK. C.S. 236)
 PWS. -ki, -ku 'Jams' (West. p. 233; Yor. and Okp.)

C.S. 131

		PN *e-tsi	'twenty'
1.	Nupe	e-ʃi	
2.	Nupe Tako	e-tsi	
3.	Gwari	—	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(wó)ʃi	
5.	Gade	(à-zaàvâ)	
		PEB *o-fu	'twenty'
6.	Ebira Okene	o-hú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-hú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-fú	

PYIG. o-gū 'twenty' (AK. C.S. 308)
 PE. U-gheGi 'twenty' (EL. C.S. 86)
 PE. I-və 'twenty' (EL. C.S. 194)

C.S. 132

		PN *tse	'be full'
1.	Nupe	ʃe	

	Nupe Tako	tse	
2	Gwari	(nūnūji)	
3	Gwari Yamma	(ā-nū)	
4	Gade	(rere)	
5	PEB *V-fi		
	Ebira Okene	o-hihi	'be full'
6	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
7	Etuno (Igarra)	fi	
8			

3 and 4 have different forms for the lexical item. This is one innovation that distinguishes the two speech forms as a unit under PN.

PYIG. kū 'be full' (AK. C.S. 291)
 PE. vuNu 'be full' (EL. C.S. 198)

C.S. 133

	PN *		'red'
1	Nupe	dzúru	
2	Nupe Tako	dzúru	
3	Gwari	(bjeĩ bjeĩ)	
4	Gwari Yamma	(k'ári)	
5	Gade	(zi)	
	PEB *o-vivi		'red'
6	Ebira Okene	ó-ví vi	
7	Ebira Kwotto	(o-zá ɲà)	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-vívi	

C.S. 134

	PN *		'sow (seeds in holes)'
1	Nupe	dzò / gbi	
2	Nupe Tako	dzò	
3	Gwari	(bjè)	
4	Gwari Yamma	(mágjé)	
5	Gade	(zi)	
	PEB *tʃire		'sow (seeds in holes)'
6	Ebira Okene	tʃire	
7	Ebira Kwotto	(tú)	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	tʃirè	

C.S. 135

PN *

1	Nupe	e-dzò	'seed'
2	Nupe Tako	i-zò	
3	Gwari	(ə-náb'ɛ)	
4	Gwari Yamma	(o-náb'è)	
5	Gade	(i-bek'ɔ)	
	PEB *V-tutu		'seed'
6	Ebira Okene	è-tutu	
7	Ebira Kwotto	ò-tùtu	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	è-tùtù	

C.S. 136

PN *

			'play games'
1	Nupe	dzòdzò	
2	Nupe Tako	zazó	
3	Gwari	(fwāwje)	
4	Gwari Yamma	(obwwa)	
5	Gade	(vutùva)	
	PEB *maahɛ		'play games'
6	Ebira Okene	ma:hè	
7	Ebira Kwotto	(ɲuhùkú)	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	(mirèɲf'ɲí)	

C.S. 137

PN *CV-gieNiko

			'market'
1	Nupe	(dzukó)	
2	Nupe Tako	(duk'ó)	
3	Gwari	gɲɪg'ó	
4	Gwari Yamma	gɲɪg'ó	
5	Gade	gi-g'ɛ	
	PEB *o-fu		'market'
6	Ebira Okene	ò-hù	
7	Ebira Kwotto	ò-hù	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-fù	

PYIG. a-jà 'market place' (AK. C.S. 245)

PE. A-ki (I-) 'market'
 PWS. gi, gia- 'kaufen'

(EL. C.S. 109)
 (West. pp. 214-5; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 138

PN *V-səN-

1.	Nupe	e-sā	'salt'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-sə	
3.	Gwari	sāŋkpeje	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(o-nū)	
5.	Gade	(u-katsi)	

PEB *a-nə

6.	Ebira Okene	a-nə	'salt'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-nə	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	a-nə	

PYIG.	o-b'ù	'salt'	(AK. C.S. 39)
PB.	-nyù	'salt'	(Gt. CS. 1396)
	-yínò	'salt'	(Gt. CS. 2072)
	-yínyù	'salt'	(Gt. CS. 2080)
PWS.	(m)-ba-	'salz'	(West. p. 204)
PJ.	ŋwa	'salt'	(Sh. p. 171)

C.S. 139

PN *siəkəji

			'God'
1.	Nupe	sòko	
2.	Nupe Tako	sòko	
3.	Gwari	fek*oji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(tʃwafɛ)	
5.	Gade	síkapa	

PEB *i-ʃinɛgba

			'God'
6.	Ebira Okene	i-hínébà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ì-hìnégbā	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	(o-ʃomo:fi)	

C.S. 140

PN *zuN-

			'rainy season'
1.	Nupe	zuzuka	
2.	Nupe Tako	zuzu	

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------------------------|--|
| 3. | Gwari | (viŋiik ^w ó) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | zòŋg ^w ó | |
| 5. | Gade | (gù-gu) | |
| | PEB *ire-su | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ìrè-sù | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ìrè-sù | |
| 8. | Ètunọ (Igarra) | ìrè-sù | |

'rainy season'

C.S. 141

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------------------|--|
| | PN * | | |
| 1. | Nupe | zū | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | zū | |
| 3. | Gwari | (bmàya) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | | |
| 5. | Gade | (tʃika; kje, mí) | |
| | PEB *tʃe | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | tʃé | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | tʃé | |
| 8. | Ètunọ (Igarra) | tʃé | |

'break (stick)'

'break (stick)'

C.S. 142

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-----------------|--|
| | PN * | | |
| 1. | Nupe | è-zūzì kò | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | zòŋkara | |
| 3. | Gwari | (nākāvunu) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (nāgā) | |
| 5. | Gade | (gù-dùndù) | |
| | PEB *a-remi | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | á-rémi | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (a-gí gí ní bí) | |
| 8. | Ètunọ (Igarra) | á-rémi | |

'charcoal'

'charcoal'

C.S. 143 PN *zo

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | zó | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | zo | |
| 3. | Gwari | zo | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | á-zuo | |
| 5. | Gade | (bjé) | |

'finish (intr.)'

	PEB *ta		
6.	Ebira Okene	tá	'finish (intr.)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(mèhu)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	tá	
PYIG	kpaVd'i	'end v. be finished'	
PYIG	tā	'end v. be finished (intransitive)'	(AK. C.S. 343)
PE	pu	'be finished, end'	(AK. C.S. 92)
PWS	kuá	'beenden'	(EL. C.S. 170)
			(West. p. 240)

C.S. 144

	PN *(e)-bhu-		
1.	Nupe	ruŋmgbá	'dust'
2.	Nupe Tako	è-rúŋmgbá	
3.	Gwari	a-bútukū	
4.	Gwari Yamma	bùreketé	
5.	Gade	(gu-riri)	
	PEB *e-dudu		
6.	Ebira Okene	è-dùdù	'dust'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(è-bùtù)	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	è-dùdù	
PE	-fu-	'sand, dust'	(EL. C.S. 19)

C.S. 145

	PN *		'fifty'
1.	Nupe	ā-ràtā	
2.	Nupe Tako	á-rátà	
3.	Gwari	(jīitnu)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(jīitnu)	
5.	Gade	(kùrī)	
	PEB *e- bareu		'fifty'
6.	Ebira Okene	e-varēu	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(i-hw)ebareú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(e-bèr)èvatùrèu	

C.S. 146

	PN *-luki		'bird'
1.	Nupe	e-lúgi	
2.	Nupe Tako	a-lú	
3.	Gwari	ə-lú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-lú	
5.	Gade	gú-nakjì	

	PEB *i-nomi		
6.	Ebira Okene	i-nomi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-nómi	'bird'
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	u-nómi	

PYIG. e-we 'bird' (AK. C.S. 44)
 PE. A-pi (i-) 'bird' (EL. C.S. 168)

C.S. 147

	PN *lɔ-		
1.	Nupe	lò	'untie'
2.	Nupe Tako	lò	
3.	Gwari	lèja	
4.	Gwari Yamma		
5.	Gade	(bana)	

	PEB *ɲua-		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɲwà	'untie'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɲwàri	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɲwàra	

PYIG tú 'untie' (AK. C.S. 86)
 PE thaN 'untie' (EL. C.S. 187)
 PLN. tɔ (Wil.)

C.S. 148

	PN *lo		'go' v.
1.	Nupe	lo	
2.	Nupe Tako	(túg ^w o)	
3.	Gwari	lo	
4.	Gwari Yamma	lo	
5.	Gade	(gɛ)	

	PEB *na		'go' v.
6.	Ebira Okene	ná:	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	nâ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ná	

PYOR lɔ 'go v.' (AK. C.S. 206)
 cf Cama lò/đo 'go' (Maddieson '74)

PE khiNa 'walk, go' (EL C.S. 121)

C.S. 149

PN *la

1.	Nupe	la	
2.	Nupe Tako	-	'take (one thing)'
3.	Gwari	lá	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(g ^w o)	
5.	Gade	(sú)	
	PEB	*si	
6.	Ebira Okene	si	'take (one thing)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	si	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	si	

PYIG. mū 'take (one thing) catch, seize, hold)'

PE da 'take (some thing)'

PWS. mu, mua- 'greifen, fangen'

(AK C.S. 59)

(EL C.S. 50)

(West. p 258; Yor. and Okp.)

C.S. 150

PN *

1.	Nupe	lág ^w oto	'touch (with hand)
2.	Nupe Tako	lágoto	
3.	Gwari	gḡwato	
4.	Gwari Yamma	tobwá	
5.	Gade	(dà)	
	PEB	*(yubɔ) kani	'touch (with hand)
6.	Ebira Okene	kàjǐ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(yúbó)kàñi	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	kani	

C.S. 151

PN *le

1.	Nupe	lètjǐ	'lie down'
2.	Nupe Tako	le	
3.	Gwari	(jaǝǐ)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(jǎtǝire)	
5.	Gade	nénè, i	
	PEB	*futu	'lie down'
6.	Ebira Okene	hùtú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hùtú	

8. Etuno (Igarra) [ute

C.S. 152

PN *lhelhe

- | | | | | | |
|----|----------------|----------------------------------|--|------------|---------------|
| 1. | Nupe | lele | | | 'sleep(v.)' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | lile | | | |
| 3. | Gwari | ŋ ^w ag ^l e | | | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | jer ^l e | | | |
| 5. | Gade | (bā-ná) | | | |
| | | PEB *suara | | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | swará < sù + ará | | | 'sleep(v.)' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | sará | | (~ sùhufú) | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | sará | | | |

PYIG. sù 'sleep'

(AK. C.S. 145)

PE U-bhichiN(a) (or. bhichir ?) 'sleep (v.)' (EL. C.S. 9)

C.S. 153

PN *lhu

'beat (person)'

- | | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--|--|
| 1. | Nupe | wu | | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | lu | | |
| 3. | Gwari | lu | | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | lu | | |
| 5. | Gade | ru | | |
| | | PEB *tu | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | tú | | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (jísá) | | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | tú | | |

'beat (person)'

PYIG. lù 'beat (person, drum)' (PYIG. C.S. 210)

PE. gbeGi 'beat, kill' (PE. C.S. 90)

PLN. lu 'fight' (Wil.50)

C.S. 154

PN *lu

'weave' v.

- | | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--|--|
| 1. | Nupe | lu | | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | lu | | |
| 3. | Gwari | lu | | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | lú | | |
| 5. | Gade | rú | | |
| | | PEB *jɪ | | |

'weave'

6.	Ebira Okene	hi	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	ji	
	pyIG. nu /ghū 'weave'		(AK. C.S. 331)
	PE do 'weave'		(EL. C.S. 58)

C.S. 155

	PN *		
1.	Nupe	nī	'beat (drum)'
2.	Nupe Tako	li	
3.	Gwari	(jè)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	-	
5.	Gade	(gí)	
	PEB	* fu	'beat(drum)'
6.	Ebira Okene	hú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hú	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	fú	

C.S. 156

	PN *			
1.	Nupe	nīkí		'fall' v.
2.	Nupe Tako	lètjím		
3.	Gwari	(káya)		
4.	Gwari Yamma	(wákàyà)		
5.	Gade	(pírí)		
	PEB	*sèdu		'fall' v.
6.	Ebira Okene	hǐédó		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(kwété)	< ku +	été + ground
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	sédú		

C.S. 157

	PN *nuN			'extinguish'
1.	Nupe	nū		
2.	Nupe Tako	nū		
3.	Gwari	ŋ ^w ū		
4.	Gwari Yamma	-		
5.	Gade	(rì)		'extinguish'
	PEB *mí			
6.	Ebira Okene	mí		

7. Ebira Kwotto mī
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) mīó

PYIG. rú /l'ú / 'destroy, exterminate'
 PE. puN 'extinguish' (AK. C.S. 187)
 (EL. C.S. 172)

C.S. 158 PN *zi

1. Nupe dʒí 'make'
 2. Nupe Tako ʒí
 3. Gwari ʒí
 4. Gwari Yamma (sú)
 5. Gade (mɛ)

PEB *mɛ

6. Ebira Okene mɛ 'make'
 7. Ebira Kwotto mɛ
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) mɛ

PYIG. ce 'make, do'
 PE. di 'tie rope' (AK. C.S. 227)
 PE. fadhí 'tie (bundle); make (rope)' (EL. C.S. 56)
 PWS. kia 'machen' (EL. C.S. 56)
 (West. p. 233-4)

C.S. 159

PN *

1. Nupe dʒika 'bag'
 2. Nupe Tako ʒika
 3. Gwari (gumá)
 4. Gwari Yamma
 5. Gade (kapwú)

PEB *a-mpo

6. Ebira Okene à-mpú 'bag'
 7. Ebira Kwotto (à-díko)
 8. Etunọ (Igarra) à-m̀pò

C.S. 160

PN *e-die

1. Nupe e-dʒè 'food'
 2. Nupe Tako i-ʒè
 3. Gwari (nagʒi)
 4. Gwari Yamma e-dʒe
 5. Gade (gi-já)

PEB *i-sɔŋ

	Ebira Okene	i-sá	
6.	Ebira Kwotto	i-sɔŋ	'food'
7.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	i-sɔŋ	
8.			

C.S. 161

PN *a-zi

1.	Nupe	e-zi	'town'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-zi	
3.	Gwari	a-zi jako	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-zi	
5.	Gade	(i-ré)	

PEB *ire-kura

6.	Ebira Okene	è-kùrà	'town'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	u-ráda	
8.	Etunɔ (Igarra)	ire-kùrà	

C.S. 162

PN *zi-

1.	Nupe	zì	'return (intr.)'
2.	Nupe Tako	(dà)zi	
3.	Gwari	ziji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(dʒeʒèkpézi)	
5.	Gade	(kórègi)	

PEB *babe

6.	Ebira Okene	vávè	'return (intr.)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	bà(hama)bé	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	và	

C.S. 163

PN *je-

1.	Nupe	jébó	'to like'
2.	Nupe Tako	jébó	
3.	Gwari	jě	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	jé	'to like'

PEB *sire

6.	Ebira Okene	si	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	sireji	

8. Etuno (Igarra) sió ~ siréáni

C.S. 164

PN *CV-je

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | (sunnā) | 'name' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | (sunnā) | |
| 3. | Gwari | e-je | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | e-je | |
| 5. | Gade | ñ-je' | |

PEB *ire-fa

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ire-fa' | 'name' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ire-fa' | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ire-fà | |

Forms in 1 and 2 are borrowed from Hausa language.

PE. dhl-ni (A-) 'name' (EL. C.S. 157)

C.S. 165

PN *V-bhuə

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--------|
| 1. | Nupe | (è-jè) | 'nose' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | (i-jè) | |
| 3. | Gwari | ù-bwà | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | o-bwa | |
| 5. | Gade | gu-rúfè | |

PEB *a-fɪ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|--------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ǎ-h'ɪ | 'nose' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | à-hɪ | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | à-fɪfɪ | |

PYIG. i-ŋmu 'nose' (AK. C.S. 369)

PE. l-chuəNi; -chuveNi (A-) 'nose' (EL. C.S.49)

PS. bɸu 'Loch, Nasenloch' (West. p. 123no. 62; Yor.)

PWS.-nwu- (ta), -nyu- (ta) 'Nase' (West. pp. 272-3; Yor. and Ig.)

PLN. i-mi 'nose' (Wil.)

C.S. 166 PN * 'night'

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-----------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | jèfɪ | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | jèfɪ | |
| 3. | Gwari | (súkwó) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (tʃóɲgwó) | |

5.	Gade	(ù-tù)	
	PEB	* ira-fu	
6.	Ebira Okene	irá-fù	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ira-fu	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	irà-fu	

'night'

C.S. 167

	PN *		
1.	Nupe	jèk ^w ò	
2.	Nupe Tako	jèk ^w ò	
3.	Gwari	(fuyí fuyí)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(á-bàse)	
5.	Gade	(teteɛ)	
	PEB * V-fuefu		
6.	Ebira Okene	hu' (néneɛ)	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hwéhùrú	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	o-fúofú	

'cold (v.)'

'cold (v.)'

C.S. 168

	PN *e-ja		
1.	Nupe	e-ja	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ja	
3.	Gwari	e-janũ ^w ájá	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-janũ ^w ájá	
5.	Gade	(gú-kpá)	
	PEB *ε-kpa		
6.	Ebira Okene	è-pà	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-kpa	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	(ó-kó)	

'boat (canoe)'

'boat (canoe)'

Only the form in 8 is cognate with the Yoruba and PE forms. It may have been borrowed.

cf. Yoruba ɔ-kò 'vehicle'

PE. U-kɔ (l-) 'boat canoe; mortar' (EL. C.S. 116)

C.S. 169

	PN *		
1.	Nupe	è-ja	
2.	Nupe Tako	è-já	
3.	Gwari	(núkwó)	

'friend'

4.	Gwari Yamma	(nùkwódò)	
5.	Gade	(-róòrò)	
	PEB * ɔ-ta		
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-tá	'friend'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-tá	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ò-tá	

C.S. 170

	PN * ji		
1.	Nupe	ji	'call v.'
2.	Nupe Tako	ji	
3.	Gwari	ji	
4.	Gwari Yamma	zi	
5.	Gade	(vurà)	
	PEB * ʃɪ		
6.	Ebira Okene	hi	'call v.'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hi	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ʃiá	

PYIG. kpè 'call, summon' (AK. C.S. 338)
 PLN. kpə 'call, summon' (Wil.42)

C.S. 171

	PN *V-wiji			'guinea corn'
1.	Nupe	e-ji		
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ji		
3.	Gwari	á-wʲí		
4.	Gwari Yamma	ò-wʲí		
5.	Gade	(gù-tfú)		
	PEB *a-ku			'guinea corn'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-kú		
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-kú		
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	à-kú		

C.S. 172

	PN *wia			'look for'
1.	Nupe	wáza		
2.	Nupe Tako	wáza		
3.	Gwari	wʲèkà		

- 4. Gwari Yamma w.l̩e
- 5. Gade (dejapú)
- PEB *si
- 6. Ebira Okene si
- 7. Ebira Kwotto si
- 8. Etun̩o (Igarra) si
- cf. Yoruba wa 'look for'

C.S. 173

PN*

- 1. Nupe j̩aka 'pepper'
- 2. Nupe Tako a-jikp̩o
- 3. Gwari n̩angb̩a
- 4. Gwari Yamma d̩z̩agb̩a
- 5. Gade ú-kp̩okp̩o
- PEB * a-kp̩okp̩o
- 6. Ebira Okene á-k̩ok̩o 'pepper'
- 7. Ebira Kwotto a-kp̩okp̩o
- 8. Etun̩o (Igarra) a-p̩okp̩o

C.S. 174 PN *V-ji̩Nk̩oN

- 1. Nupe n̩ĩk̩ā 'fish'
- 2. Nupe Tako n̩ik̩o
- 3. Gwari ə-bj̩ǎ
- 4. Gwari Yamma (f̩ewò)
- 5. Gade (rú-gbetù)
- PEB *i-sepi 'fish'
- 6. Ebira Okene (l-vòvò)
- 7. Ebira Kwotto u-n̩i
- 8. Etun̩o (Igarra) i-séj̩n̩ĩ < isá + ep̩ĩ
'thing' + 'water'

PYIG. ε-ja 'fish' (AK. C.S. 242)

PJ. gyá (ki-/i-) 'fish' (West. pp. 163-4)

C.S. 175

PN *ji̩Ni -

'wife'

- 1. Nupe n̩ĩm̩ĩ
- 2. Nupe Tako n̩ĩm̩ĩ
- 3. Gwari n̩ĩk̩"ó

4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲĩg ^o	
5.	Gade	ɲine	
	PEB *u-sɪ		
6.	Ebira Okene	ò-se'	'wife'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò-sɪ'	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ò-sé	

C.S. 176

	PN *V-ɲN		
1.	Nupe	e-ɲā	'thing'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-ɲō	
3.	Gwari	ə-ɲā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲā̀dò	
5.	Gade	(ù-be)	
	PEB *ɪ-sa		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɪ-sá	'thing'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-sá	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	i-sá	

PE -mhinhi 'thing, something' (EL. C.S. 153)

C.S. 177

	PN *		
1.	Nupe	kan	'farm'
2.	Nupe Tako	káñ	
3.	Gwari	(ù-fā)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(ù-fwà)	
5.	Gade	(u-nɔ)	
	PEB *ɪra-rɛ		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-rɛ'	'farm'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-rɛ'	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɪra-rɛ'	

C.S. 178

	PN *		
1.	Nupe	kàsà	'crocodile'
2.	Nupe Tako	kàsà	
3.	Gwari	(à-w ^ɔ i)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(nakakpa)	
5.	Gade	(u-fuku)	

	PEB	*a-gugu	
6.	Ebira Okene	à-gugu	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(à-pè)	'crocodile'
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	à-gùgù	

C.S. 179

	PN	*a-kià	
1.	Nupe	e-kā	'thorn(s)'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-kò	
3.	Gwari	à-kḡā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ò-kḡā	
5.	Gade	(kúkùbàni) (i-)	
	PEB	*i-kehi	
6.	Ebira Okene	i-kehi	'thorn(s)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	i-ke'jī	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	i-kei	

PYIG. à-gù 'thorn, prickle' (AK. C.S. 306a)
Igalà i-kéké

C.S. 180

	PN	*kuti	
1.	Nupe	kúti	'fetish (juju)'
2.	Nupe Tako	kúti	
3.	Gwari	—	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kutjī	
5.	Gade	(ʒiʒi)	

	PEB	*ira-fìnò	
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ví	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ʒiʒi)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ìrà-fìnò	'medicine, charm'

PYIG. ò-gù 'medicine' (AK. C.S. 311)

C.S. 181

	PN	*à-kòNò	
1.	Nupe	kānā	'monkey'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-kōnō	
3.	Gwari	à-kḡā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(nákpá)	
5.	Gade	(fù-ka)	

	PEB *ɔ-ntʃerɛ		
6.	Ebira Okene	ɔ-ntʃerɛ	'monkey'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-n'ʃerɛ	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-ntʃerɛ	

C.S. 182

	PN *kɔNa		
1.	Nupe	kā	'fry'
2.	Nupe Tako	kɔ	
3.	Gwari	kɲā	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kɲā	
5.	Gade	kénè	
	PEB *wara		
6.	Ebira Okene	wara	'fry'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	wara	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	wàrà	

PYIG. dī 'fry (in oil)' (AK. C.S. 110)

C.S. 183

	PN *kuNu		'sell'
1.	Nupe	k ^w ú	
2.	Nupe Tako	k ^w ú	
3.	Gwari	kɲú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kɲú	
5.	Gade	(zɪnɛ)	
	PEB *na		'sell'
6.	Ebira Okene	na	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	na'	
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	na	

PYIG. ta 'sell' (AK. C.S. 82)

PE. deGr 'sell' (EL. C.S. 55)

PB. -tég- 'sell' (Gt. C.S. 1697)

PWS. ta- 'kaufen, verkaufen' (West. p.284; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 184

PN *ko + ani 'sing'

		'sing' + 'song'	
1.	Nupe	koni	
2.	Nupe Tako	k ^w ani	'sing song'
3.	Gwari	kwani	
4.	Gwari Yamma	k ^w oni	
5.	Gade	ka, aje	
	PEB *dʒi-	(v.) + aje (n.)	
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒahe < dʒi + ahe	'sing'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hahe < hi + ahe	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	dʒaʃe < dʒi + aʃe	

cf Yor. kari < ko + ori 'sing song'
 PE.cu 'sing' (EL. C.S. 31)

C.S. 185

		PN *CV-ka-	
1.	Nupe	k ^w oro	'navel'
2.	Nupe Tako	k ^w oro	
3.	Gwari	kɔpu	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kàpú	
5.	Gade	(kú)-pómpo	
		PEB *ira- dʒe	
6.	Ebira Okene	ira-dʒé	'navel'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	à-ndʒé	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	ira-dʒe	

PYIG. u-do (i-) 'navel, umbilical cord' (AK. p.s. 107)
 PE. U-khəN (I-) 'navel' (EL. C.S. 119)

C.S. 186

		PN *kaba	'maize'
1.	Nupe	kaba	
2.	Nupe Tako	kàba	
3.	Gwari	(jàw ^ɔ i)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	kàmbà (~ ew ^ɔ e)	
5.	Gade	(gú)-tsúmpwá	
		PEB *a-kpa(kpa)	'maize'
6.	Ebira Okene	à-pá pá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a:kpa	
8.	Etunṣo (Igarra)	à-pápà	

C.S. 187

PN *V-kiNi

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|--------------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | kī | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tjīm | 'ground' |
| 3. | Gwari | à-kŋí | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | | |
| 5. | Gade | (fízá) è-kŋí | |

PEB *E-tE

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|------|----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | e-té | 'ground' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | e-té | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | e-té | |
- PE. U-to (A-) 'ground' (EL. C.S. 181)

C.S. 188

PN *kiN

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | ki | 'sew' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | tji | |
| 3. | Gwari | tji | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (lú) | |
| 5. | Gade | (kwó) | |

PEB *ge

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|----|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | gé | 'sew' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | gé | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | gé | |

PYIG. rā 'sew with thread' (AK. C.S. 179)

Igala gá

C.S. 189

PN *V-kiNi

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|----------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | e-kī | 'needle' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | à-tjī | |
| 3. | Gwari | à-tjī | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | è-kŋī | |
| 5. | Gade | (ú-géza) | |

PEB *ɔ-rɪhɪ

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-rɪ hɪ | 'needle' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɔ-rɪhɪ | |
| 8. | Etunọ (Igarra) | ɔ-rɪhɪ | |
- cf. Yoruba o-kinī 'needle'

C.S. 190 PN *

1.	Nupe	k'ata			'donkey'
2.	Nupe Tako	ketekete	(Yor)		
3.	Gwari	3atfi	(Yor)		
4.	Gwari Yamma	d3àki	(Hausa)		
5.	Gade	(zanki)	(Hausa)		

PEB *

6.	Ebira Okene	ira-kumi			'donkey'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(ketekete)			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	kétékété	'donkey'	ira-kumi	'camel'

C.S. 191

PN *guNu

1.	Nupe	gū			'climb'
2.	Nupe Tako	g ^w u			
3.	Gwari	gṅú			
4.	Gwari Yamma	gṅū			
5.	Gade	g ^w o			

PEB *fīre

6.	Ebira Okene	hīre			'climb'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hīrè			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	fīre			

PYIG. gū 'climb, mount' (AK. C.S. 310)

C.S. 192

PN *

1.	Nupe	gùlu			'vulture'
2.	Nupe Tako	āṅgùlú			
3.	Gwari	gùlu			
4.	Gwari Yamma	gùlu			
5.	Gade	gùnúbje			

PEB * u-gba

6.	Ebira Okene	ù-bà			'vulture'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ù-gbà			
8.	Etunọ (Igarra)	ù-bà			

C.S. 193

	PN *guzija		
1.	Nupe	guʒa	
2.	Nupe Tako	guz'a	'groundnut'
3.	Gwari	(gbògbè)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(gbègbè)	
5.	Gade	guʒija	
	PEB *V-kusije		
6.	Ebira Okene	(e-tʃupá)	'groundnut'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-gúzija	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	e-kúfájé	

C.S. 194

	PN *e-gbhə		
1.	Nupe	e-g ^w o'	'grass'
2.	Nupe Tako	i-g ^w ó	
3.	Gwari	gbógbè	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(sájgo)	
5.	Gade	(à-bí)	
	PEB *a-bɪ		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ví	'grass'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-bí	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	a-ví	

The similarity observed between 5 and PEB suggests that i the parent.
 Cf. Yoruba igbó 'grass'

C.S. 195

	PN *CV-ko		'word'
1.	Nupe	e-gā	
2.	Nupe Tako	i-gò	
3.	Gwari	(bada)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(betá)	
5.	Gade	ɾi-ka'	
	PEB *ɪrɛ-ʃɪ		'word'
6.	Ebira Okene	ɪrɛ-ɪ	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-ʃɪ	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ɪrɛ-ɪ	

PYIG. ɔ-rò /ɔl'ò / 'word, matter' (AK. C.S. 167)

C.S. 196

PN *gɔN

1	Nupe	gā	'surpass'
2	Nupe Tako	gɔ	
3	Gwari	dù gɔ̃	
4	Gwari Yamma	—	
5	Gade	(pé)	
	PEB *funa		
6	Ebira Okene	huna	'surpass'
7	Ebira Kwotto		
8	Etuno (Igarra)	funa	

C.S. 197

PN *gogɔN

1	Nupe	g ^w ògā	'pass by'
2	Nupe Tako	g ^w ògɔ	
3	Gwari	(dùja)	
4	Gwari Yamma	(wádùja)	
5	Gade	(k ^j é)	
	PEB *pa(ra)fu		'pass by'
6	Ebira Okene	pàràhu	
7	Ebira Kwotto	béhu	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	pàràfú	

C.S. 198

PN *gi

1	Nupe	gí	'eat'
2	Nupe Tako	dʒí	
3	Gwari	g ^j í	
4	Gwari Yamma	gí	
5	Gade	(rɪ)	
	PEB *rɪ		'eat'
6	Ebira Okene	rí	
7	Ebira Kwotto	rí	
8	Etuno (Igarra)	rí	

PYIG. je

'eat'

(AK. C.S. 240)

PE. dhl

'eat'

(EL. C.S. 65)

PJ. dyl 'to eat'
 PWS. li, lià 'essen'
 PLN. di 'eat'

(Sh. pp. 90-1)
 (West. p.250-1; Yor. and Okp.)
 (Wil. 14)

C.S. 199

PN *e-gbhi

1.	Nupe	e-gi (ʒi)	'child(ren)'
2.	Nupe Tako	ɾ-dʒi (ʒi)	
3.	Gwari	e-bí (a-)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	e-bí (a-)	
5.	Gade	ù-bí (ba-)	
	PEB *o-zi		
6.	Ebira Okene	o-zi (e-)	'child(ren)'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	o-zi (-ni)	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	o-zi (e-)	

C.S. 200 PN *

1.	Nupe	gí	'bite'
2.	Nupe Tako	bagí	
3.	Gwari	(sá:)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(sá)	
5.	Gade	(tsigárú)	
	PEB *dʒɪrɛrɛ		'bite'
6.	Ebira Okene	dʒɪrɛrú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(dàrí)	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	dʒɪrɛrú	

C.S. 201

PN *V-gie

1.	Nupe	e-g'la	'blood'
2.	Nupe Tako	a-ʒè	
3.	Gwari	(a-mi)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	é-g'lá	
5.	Gade	(bà-ji)	
	PEB *a-ɲa		'blood'
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ɲá	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	a-ɲa	
8.	Ètuno (Igarra)	a-ɲá	

FYIG. ð-bjè ðbrè/ 'blood'
 PE. U-ɣt-ɣia (A-) 'blood'
 PS. ɣia 'Blut'
 PWS. -ɣia 'Blut'

(AK. C.S. 25)
 (EL. C.S. 101)
 (West. p. 135 no. 109; Yor. p.c.)
 (West. p. 215; Yor. p.c.)

C.S. 202

PN * -giNtara

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------------|----------|
| 1. | Nupe | g̃intara | 'tongue' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | á-g̃in tara | |
| 3. | Gwari | ɣĩtala | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | mintá | |
| 5. | Gade | (gá-kòre) | |

PEB *ira-rè

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------|----------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ìrà-rè | 'tongue' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ìrà-rè | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | ìrà-rè | |

PYIG. u-b'á (t-) 'tongue'

(AK. C.S. 36)

PE. U-dhamhi 'tongue'

(EL. C.S. 63)

PBC. -lemi (li-u-) 'tongue'

(DeW. p. 54)

PWK. -dh-mh- 'tongue'

(PBK. 39)

PP. dyam 'tongue'

(PBK. 39)

C.S. 203

PN *kpe

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------|--------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | kpe | 'to cover (a pot)' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | kpe | |
| 3. | Gwari | (kwajá) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | kpéré | |
| 5. | Gade | (kúru) | |

PEB *kuoku

'to cover (a pot)'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------------------|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | k ^w oku | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | _____ | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | k ^w ókú: | |

PYIG. dé 'cover, put on (head, pot)' (AK. C.S. 99)

C.S. 204

PN *kpe

'know'

- | | | |
|----|-----------|-----|
| 1. | Nupe | kpe |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | kpe |
| 3. | Gwari | kpé |

4.	Gwari Yamma	kpéjájé	
5.	Gade	kpu	
	PEB *jé		
6.	Ebira Okene	jé	'know'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	jé	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	jé	

PYIG. mā 'know' (AK. C.S. 57)
 PE. nhinha, nhiacha (EL. C.S. 165)
 PLN. ònā 'know' (Wil. 9)

C.S. 205

	PN *kpe		
1.	Nupe	kpī	'learn'
2.	Nupe Tako	kpí	
3.	Gwari	kpéjé	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(mutúmú)	
5.	Gade	(tsene)	
	PEB *kɔsɛ		
6.	Ebira Okene	kɔsɛ	'learn'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	kɔsɛ	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	kɔswɛ	

PYIG. kɔ 'learn, teach' (AK. C.S. 278)
 PE. ma- 'learn' (EL. C.S. 142)

C.S. 206

	PN *		'neck'
1.	Nupe	kpàtsū	
2.	Nupe Tako	kpatsū	
3.	Gwari	(bəge)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(o-tʃa)	
5.	Gade	(u-tó)	
	PEB *ɔ-gbɛ		
6.	Ebira Okene	(ɔ-rakɔ)	'neck'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-gbɛ	
8.	Ètunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-bɛ	

C.S. 207

	PN *		'two hundred'
1.	Nupe	kpákpó	
2.	Nupe Tako	kpákó	

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------|---------------|
| 3. | Gwari | (tãgɪ gwába) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (derɪpaba) | |
| 5. | Gade | (kurɪɪno) | |
| | PEB * | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɪrɛ-ká | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɪ-hwɛ̀ɔ | 'two hundred' |
| 8. | Etunɔ (Igarra) | | |

C.S. 208

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|--------------|-------|
| | PN | *CV -gbakhuN | |
| 1. | Nupe | e-gbà | 'axe' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | a-gbà | |
| 3. | Gwari | gbakɪ̀ | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | gbakɪ̀wɪ̀ | |
| 5. | Gade | du-gbà | |
| | PEB * | *ira-ga | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɪrà-gà | 'axe' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɪrà-gà | |
| 8. | Etunɔ (Igarra) | ɪrà-gà | |

PYIG. e-dū 'axe' (AK. C.S. 117)

PYOR -ké 'axe' (AK. C.S. 272)

PE. A-juəNi (I-) 'axe' (EL. C.S. 102)

C.S. 209

- | | | | | |
|----|----------------|----------|--|-------------------------|
| | PN | * | | 'belly (ext./stomach)' |
| 1. | Nupe | gbàkó | | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | gbàkó | | |
| 3. | Gwari | (núbwo) | | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (mɪɪga) | | |
| 5. | Gade | (gɪ-ne) | | |
| | PEB * | ɪ-ne | | 'belly (ext / stomach)' |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (ɪrɛ-ká) | | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | ɪ-ne' | | |
| 8. | Etunɔ (Igarra) | ɪ-ne' | | |

C.S. 210

- | | | | | |
|----|------|------|--|-------|
| | PN | *gba | | 'dig' |
| 1. | Nupe | gbà | | |

2	Nupe Tako	gbá
3	Gwari	(jì)
4	Gwari Yamma	(jì)
5	Gade	gbá
	PEB *gba	
6	Ebira Okene	(tʃi)
7	Ebira Kwotto	gbá
8	Ẹ̀tunọ̀ (Igarra)	bá

PYIG. gwà/guà	'dig'	(AK. C.S. 316)
PE. toN	'dig'	(EL. C.S. 182)
PLN. gwu	'dig'	(Wil.33)

C.S. 211

	PN *		'thirty'
1.	Nupe	gbāwo	
2.	Nupe Tako	gbòwó	
3.	Gwari	(jɪˀta)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(wogata)	
5.	Gade	(kátsei)	
	PEB *o-furèwu		'thirty'
6.	Ebira Okene	o- hùrèwú	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ò- hurèwú	
8.	Ẹ̀tunọ̀ (Igarra)	ò- furèu	

C.S. 212

	PN *gbigòN		'ask'
1.	Nupe	gbīgā	
2.	Nupe Tako	gbigò	
3.	Gwari	já	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(bi...rge) ('to know how')	
	PEB *fusetʃe		'ask'
6.	Ebira Okene	-hùsè	
7.	Ebira Kwotto	hùretʃé	
8.	Ẹ̀tunọ̀ (Igarra)	fò ~ fùswè	

PYIG. bí	'ask (question)	(AK. C.S. 2)
PE. bhianha	'ask'	(EL. C.S. 7)

PE. na 'ask, question'
 PWS. bi- (bifid) 'fragen'
 Pl. bi 'ask'

(EL. C.S. 162)
 (West. p. 208, Yor. and Okp.)
 (Wil.)

C.S. 213

PN *gbhiti

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-----------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | gbitji | |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | bitsi | 'run' |
| 3. | Gwari | busi | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | buti | |
| 5. | Gade | (tsaakji) | |

PEB *zuetji

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|---------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | zwetji | 'run' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (detji) | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | zwe | |

PYIG. sa 'run (a race)' (AK. 134)

C.S. 214

PN *gbhia

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------------------------|---------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | gbè ~ bè | 'blow (with mouth)' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | bè | |
| 3. | Gwari | (sufi) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | bia | |
| 5. | Gade | (re afu, su, wu) 'blow' | |

PEB

*kuahı

'blow (with mouth)'

- | | | | |
|----|----------------|-------------|--|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | (tu) | |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | kwahı | |
| 8. | Etuno (Igarra) | kwahı, jafe | |

PYIG. fe 'blow (of wind, with mouth)' (AK. C.S. 63)

PE. phupho 'blow (with mouth)' (EL. C.S. 179)

PWS. -pap, -pep- 'wind' (West. p. 274 ; Yor.)

PB. -peepè 'wind' (Gl. C.S. 1491)

PB. -pèpè 'wind' (Gl. C.S. 1493)

C.S. 215

PN *gbhia

'good'

- | | | | |
|----|------|------------------|--|
| 1. | Nupe | g ^j e | |
|----|------|------------------|--|

2.	Nupe Tako	gb'je
3.	Gwari	b'já
4.	Gwari Yamma	b'já
5.	Gade	jeje
	PEB *-zoza	
6.	Ebira Okene	ó-zózà
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(wúsà)
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	zózà

'good'

PE. chiamhi 'be good' (EL. C.S. 41)

C.S. 216

PN *gbhokana

1.	Nupe	gbóká
2.	Nupe Tako	gbóká
3.	Gwari	(kárá)
4.	Gwari Yamma	wógāná
5.	Gade	(pantɪ)

'strong'

PEB *u-kata

6.	Ebira Okene	u-kata
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(púŋkpahɪ)
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	kátá

'strong'

cf. Yoruba gbókeke 'very strong'

C.S. 217

PN *V-nɔwu

'smoke'

1.	Nupe	e-nāwú < ena + awu	'fire' + 'robe/gown'
2.	Nupe Tako	ɪ-nōwú < inō + awu	
3.	Gwari	a-wú	
4.	Gwari Yamma	o-wú	
5.	Gade	a-mú	

PEB *are-ji

'smoke'

6.	Ebira Okene	áré-ji
7.	Ebira Kwotto	aré-ji
8.	Ètunò (Igarra)	aré-ji

C.S. 218

PN *wa

1.	Nupe	wá	'want, desire'
2.	Nupe Tako	wá	
3.	Gwari	(jé)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	—	
5.	Gade	(jé)	
	PEB *si		
6.	Ebira Okene	si	'want, desire'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	si	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	si	

PYIG fe 'want(desire)' (AK. C.S. 62)

C.S. 219

PN * CV-wo

1.	Nupe	gúwo	'ten'
2.	Nupe Tako	guwo	
3.	Gwari	ñ-wó	
4.	Gwari Yamma	ɲiawo	
5.	Gade	ú-bwó	
	PEB *ε-wu		
6.	Ebira Okene	ε-u	'ten'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	ε-wú	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	ε-wú	

PYIG. è-gwá /ε-guá/ 'ten' (AK. C.S. 313)

PE. gbeNi 'ten' (EL. C.S. 91)

PWS. -guá 'Zehn' (West. p. 225-6; Yor. and Ig.)

C.S. 220

PN * V-wu

			'robe/gown/smock'
1.	Nupe	e-wó	
2.	Nupe Tako	à-wúbàdǔjǐ	
3.	Gwari	(dǔékǔpé)	
4.	Gwari Yamma	(è-djelugwe)	
5.	Gade	tégwo	
	PEB *a-ruǔbǎjǐ		
6.	Ebira Okene	a-ruǔbǎjǐ	'robe/gown/smock'
7.	Ebira Kwotto	(i-tógbe)	
8.	Etuno (Igarra)	à-rù	

PYIG. à-wù 'gown, robe' (AK. C.S. 50)

C.S. 221

PN *wɔN

- | | | | |
|----|-----------------|----------------------|---------|
| 1. | Nupe | ŋ ^w ã | 'catch' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | ŋ ^w ɔ | |
| 3. | Gwari | ŋ ^w á | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | ŋ ^w ã | |
| 5. | Gade | m ^w ɔ | |
| | PEB *za | | |
| 6. | Ebira Okene | za | 'catch' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | zá | |
| 8. | Etunṣo (Igarra) | za, g ^w ɔ | |

PYIG. mū 'take (one thing), catch, seize hold' (AK. C.S. 59)

PE. mu 'catch hold(in hand)'

PWS. mu, mua- 'greifen, fangen'

PLN. wnu 'catch'

(EL. C.S. 149)

(West. p.258 ; Yor. and Okp.)

(Wil. 68)

C.S. 222

PN*

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|---------------------|-------|
| 1. | Nupe | ŋ ^w atsi | 'big' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | jédāntsi | |
| 3. | Gwari | (dnagbájñi) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (mwárie) | |
| 5. | Gade | --- | |

PEB *ɔbani

- | | | | |
|----|-----------------|---------|-------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | ɔ-bani | 'big' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | (ɔ-iza) | |
| 8. | Etunṣo (Igarra) | ɔ-báni | |

C.S. 223

PN*

- | | | | |
|----|-------------|-------------|---------------------|
| 1. | Nupe | fù | 'wash body'/'bathe' |
| 2. | Nupe Tako | fù | |
| 3. | Gwari | (tná) | |
| 4. | Gwari Yamma | (džiakpaka) | |
| 5. | Gade | (su) | |

PEB *fueɲi

- | | | | |
|----|--------------|-------|---------------------|
| 6. | Ebira Okene | hwéɲi | 'wash body'/'bathe' |
| 7. | Ebira Kwotto | hweɲi | |

8. Etuno (Igarra) fweji

C.S 224

PN*

1. Nupe (só)

2. Nupe Tako - 'bury'

3. Gwari bí

4. Gwari Yamma bí

5. Gade pú

PEB *ne

6. Ebira Okene ne

7. Ebira Kwotto - 'bury'

8. Etuno (Igarra) nē

C.S 225

PN*

1. Nupe (eji) 'feather'

2. Nupe Tako (àkàlú)

3. Gwari bminà

4. Gwari Yamma binà

5. Gade (ùge')

PEB *asise

6. Ebira Okene asise 'feather'

7. Ebira Kwotto ---

8. Etuno (Igarra) asisé

C.S. 226

PN* già

1. Nupe (lájà) 'give'

2. Nupe Tako (lájà)

3. Gwari gâ

4. Gwari Yamma gimi

5. Gade g³i

PEB *si

6. Ebira Okene sí 'give'

7. Ebira Kwotto (dô)

8. Etuno (Igarra) sjóm

PE. na 'give' (EL C.S. 155)

C.S. 227

PN*		
1. Nupe	(guru)	
2. Nupe Tako	(tsátsá)	'horn'
3. Gwari	mwaji	
4. Gwari Yamma	mwarí	
5. Gade	---	
PEB *ɔpáɲi ?		
6. Ebira Okene	ɔpáɲi	'horn'
7. Ebira Kwotto	(ɔkáhu)	
8. Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔpáɲi	

C.S. 228

PN * V-tiji		
1. Nupe	tiji	'hair'
2. Nupe Tako	aí	
3. Gwari	eji, túkwòɲí	
4. Gwari Yamma	eji	
5. Gade	tiji	
PEB * ɛ-ji		
6. Ebira Okene	ɛ-í	'hair'
7. Ebira Kwotto	ɛ-ji	
8. Etunọ (Igarra)	ɛ-ji	

PYIG. u-rū /ul'ū/ (r-) 'hair' (AK. C.S. 183)

PE. U-tuN (l-) 'hair' (EL. C.S. 186)

C.S. 229

PN *fu		
1. Nupe	fù	'jump'
2. Nupe Tako	fù	
3. Gwari	(jàgà)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(wátafù)	
5. Gade	furu	
PEB *dʒi		
6. Ebira Okene	dʒiriga	'jump'
7. Ebira Kwotto	---	
8. Etunọ (Igarra)	dʒi	

C.S. 230

	PN*	
1. Nupe		
2. Nupe Tako		'knee'
3. Gwari	(avukpa)	
4. Gwari Yamma	nikütukwó	
5. Gade	kukú	

	PEB *i-duŋku	
6. Ebira Okene	idūŋkú	'knee'
7. Ebira Kwotto	idèhéku	
8. Etunọ (Igarra)	idūŋkú	

C.S. 231

	PN* wuNakpa	
1. Nupe	ŋ ^w ūkpá	'long'
2. Nupe Tako	(gbòrò)	
3. Gwari	(daləbji)	
4. Gwari Yamma	m ^w ákpa	
5. Gade	---	

	PEB *ɔ-gɔdɔ	
6. Ebira Okene	ɔ-gɔdɔ	'long'
7. Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-gɔdɔ	
8. Etunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-gɔdɔ	

Yoruba gū 'be long'
 PE. dedhi 'be long (of stick)' (EL. C.S. 53)

C.S. 232

	PN*	'mountain'
1. Nupe	páti	
2. Nupe Tako	páti	
3. Gwari	(əpé)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(kukú)	
5. Gade	(rūgwò)	

	PEB *a-taba	'mountain'
6. Ebira Okene	ataba	
7. Ebira Kwotto	àtábà	
8. Etunọ (Igarra)	(iresúfá)	

C.S. 233	PN *gbaghi	'man'
1. Nupe	bági	
2. Nupe Tako	bádʒi	

3. Gwari	zānugbáji	
4. Gwari Yamma	(mísa)	
5. Gade	(úròòrò)	
	PEB *ɔ-nɔru	
6. Ebira Okene	ɔ-nɔrú	'man'
7. Ebira Kwotto	ɔ-nɔrú	
8. Ètunọ (Igarra)	ɔ-nɔrú	
PYIG. ɔ-kɔ	'husband (male)	(AK. C.S. 283)
PE. O-chi- (I-)	'husband'	(EL. C.S. 44)

C.S. 234	PN* e-mi	'mouth'
1. Nupe	emi	
2. Nupe Tako	am(i)	
3. Gwari	(ágbè)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(egbè)	
5. Gade	(gànú)	
	PEB *ire-nu	
6. Ebira Okene	ire-nu	'mouth'
7. Ebira Kwotto	irè-nù	
8. Ètunọ (Igarra)	iré-nú	

C.S. 235	PN *e-gbhɔ	'rope'
1. Nupe	égbá	
2. Nupe Tako	àgbɔ	
3. Gwari	(òŋ ^w ŭ)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(oŋ ^w ŭ)	
5. Gade	(ùrí)	
	PEB *o-rukpa	
6. Ebira Okene	orukpa	'rope'
7. Ebira Kwotto	-----	
8. Ètunọ (Igarra)	(obó)	

PYIG. V-kū 'rope (general)' (AK. C.S. 296)
 PE. U-dhuNi, -dhiNi 'rope' (EL. C.S. 70)
 PB. -dí 'string' (Gt. CS. 592)
 PWS. (West. p. ; Yor.)
 Pl. dígí 'rope' (Wil.)

C.S. 236	PN*	'road'
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1. Nupe	ekó	
2. Nupe Tako	yèk*ó	
3. Gwari	(zòkwó)	
4. Gwari Yamma	(zògwo)	
5. Gade	(tùwóji)	
	PEB *o-ze	
6. Ebira Okene	òzè	'road'
7. Ebira Kwotto	òzi	
8. Ètunọ (Igarra)	òzè	

C.S. 237

	PN *fedu	
1. Nupe	fédú	'sit down'
2. Nupe Tako	fédù	
3. Gwari	àsəsè	
4. Gwari Yamma	(jà:so)	
5. Gade	(dèndè)	
	PEB *jatu	
6. Ebira Okene	jaátù	'sit down'
7. Ebira Kwotto	jatù	
8. Ètunọ (Igarra)	jà:tù	

C.S. 238

	PN *fiífi	'small'
1. Nupe	(gbàgbà)	
2. Nupe Tako	(tʃiíndʒi)	
3. Gwari	fiífi	
4. Gwari Yamma	biri	
5. Gade	bibi	
	PEB *kiiki	'small'
6. Ebira Okene	kíiki	
7. Ebira Kwotto	----	
8. Ètunọ (Igarra)	----	

C.S. 239

	PN *giə	'say (something)'
1. Nupe	gā	
2. Nupe Tako	gə	
3. Gwari	(da)	

- | | | |
|-------------------|--------------|-------------------|
| 4. Gwari Yamma | (m̄gadabofá) | |
| 5. Gade | gè | |
| | PEB *kare | |
| 6. Ebira Okene | kà | 'say (something)' |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | òkikà | |
| 8. Etunọ (Igarra) | kàre | |

PYIS. gwí /guĩ/	'say something'	(AK. C.S. 321)
PE ta	'say, tell'	(EL. C.S. 180)
weGi	'say (to someone)'	(EL. C.S. 202)

- | | | | |
|-------------------|--------------|--|--------|
| C.S. 240 | PN* | | 'star' |
| 1. Nupe | ets* aɲgĩ | | |
| 2. Nupe Tako | (iɲògbāndzi) | | |
| 3. Gwari | ((à)kpási) | | |
| 4. Gwari Yamma | (kúdu) | | |
| 5. Gade | --- | | |
| | PEB *ɔ-zòmí | | 'star' |
| 6. Ebira Okene | ù-zòmì | | |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | ò-tàùráru | | |
| 8. Etunọ (Igarra) | ù-zòmì | | |

- | | | | |
|-------------------|--------------|--|--------|
| C.S. 241 | PN* d̄zikana | | 'sand' |
| 1. upe | d̄zikànà | | |
| 2. Nupe Tako | āɲkòṅṅ | | |
| 3. Gwari | amúí | | |
| 4. Gwari Yamma | muḥd̄ziā | | |
| 5. Gade | ----- | | |
| | PEB *a-r̄ɛ | | 'sand' |
| 6. Ebira Okene | àrè | | |
| 7. Ebira Kwotto | --- | | |
| 8. Etunọ (Igarra) | (ezi) | | |

- | | | | |
|--------------|---------------|--|----------|
| C.S. 242 | PN* minikini | | 'saliva' |
| 1. Nupe | mit̄jini, ébi | | |
| 2. Nupe Tako | ansiní | | |
| 3. Gwari | a-kjĩ | | |

4. Gwari Yamma	míntí	
5. Gade	(k ^ɔ)k ^ɔ ɛ	
	PEB *a-tɛ	
6. Ebira Okene	a-tɛ	'saliva'
7. Ebira Kwotto	--	
8. Etunò (Igarra)	a-tɛ	

PYIG. i-15	'saliva'	(AK. C.S. 93)
PE. A-biaNi(I-)	'saliva'	(EL. C.S. 29)
PB. -tai	'Spittle'	(Meussen 1973)
PBK. -T-ɲ-	'saliva'	(PBK 30)
PWS. -tá-	'speichel'	(West. p. 282; Yor.)
PBC. -ntáti (ma-)	'saliva'	(DeW. p. 58)
PS. tá	'speichel'	(West. p. 187 no. 282; Yor.)

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Send	tuNu	C.S. 24	tu
Sea		C.S. 111	ire-fu
Seed		C.S. 135	V-tutu
Sell	kuNu	C.S. 183	na
Sew	kiN	C.S. 188	ge
Share out (see divide)			
Shoe	CV-dabua	C.S. 31	i-dava
Shoot	tsie	C.S. 43	tje
Sing	ko+ani	C.S. 184	dzi
Sit down	fedu	C.S. 237	jatu
Skin	a-pa	C.S. 3	u-kpa
Sleep	ihelhe	C.S. 152	suara
Small	ɛifi	C.S. 238	kiiki
Smoke	V-nɔwu	C.S. 217	are-ji

Snail	V-kpa	C.S. 71	-kokoŋi
Snake	CV-wa	C.S. 81	e-wu
Song	a-niaN	C.S. 123	a-fe
Soup	e-niaN	C.S. 122	e-kpe
Sow (seeds in holes)		C.S. 134	tfire
Steal	wi	C.S. 56	ji
Stick	cigbia	C.S. 42	a-tfi
Stomach (see belly)			
Stone	o-kuta	C.S. 28	ire-ta
Stranger (see guest)			
Strong	gbhokana	C.S. 216	u-kata
Sun/Sunshine	ji	C.S. 59	a-ji
Surpass	gɔN	C.S. 196	funa
Swallow	miNi	C.S. 2	mune
Swell (of boil)		C.S. 83	wu
Sweep	fiN-	C.S. 18	ji
Sweet	mɔNu	C.S. 92	jine
T			
Tail	tiaNtia	C.S. 129	o-mu
Take (one thing)	la	C.S. 149	si
Ten	CV-wo	C.S. 219	e-wu
Thigh	gbuodiNko	C.S. 88	u-siji
Thing	V-joN	C.S. 176	i-sa
Thirty		C.S. 211	o-furewu
Thorn	a-kia	C.S. 179	i-kehi
Three	gu-ta	C.S. 29	e-ta
Throw	cie	C.S. 44	ne
Tie	pa	C.S. 84	su
Tongue	a-giNtara	C.S. 202	ira-re
Tooth	jiNkoN	C.S. 58	a-ji
Touch (with hand)	lagboto	C.S. 150	(yuba) kani
Town	a-zi	C.S. 161	ire-kura
Tree	V-cigboNa	C.S. 41	a-tfi
Twenty	e-tsi	C.S. 131	o-fu
Two	gu-ba	C.S. 13	e-ba
Two hundred		C.S. 207	(-)

U

Untie	la	C.S. 147	ɔwa
V			
Vomit	tu	C.S. 97	huɛɛ
Vulture	(V)-gulu	C.S. 192	u-ɔba
W			
Walk	ɔiaziN	C.S. 104	zusi
Want (see desire)			
Wash (things)		C.S. 94	ɔina
Water	nuNɔ ^h a	C.S. 115	e-ɔi
Water pot	ɔiukhuN	C.S. 112	i-nɔkɔ
'We'			
Weave v.	lu	C.S. 154	ʃi
Wet	da	C.S. 101	o-fuefu
White	bu	C.S. 11	ɔ-bu
Wife	ɔiNi	C.S. 175	u-si
Wind	-phe	C.S. 21	a-je
Wine/beer (general word)	ɔ-die	C.S. 64	e-tje
Woman	ɔiNiko	C.S. 62	ɔɔɛɛ
Word	CV-kɔ	C.S. 195	iɛ-ɔi
Work n.	e-tuNu	C.S. 98	-kɔɔ
Wring (clothes)	ɔiɔ	C.S. 67	kama
Y			
Yam	V-ti	C.S. 130	ɛ-nu
Year	ɔ-ja	C.S. 53	iɔa-je
'You'			

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1

Bennett and Sterk (1977) wordlist of 87 items.

Animal	chin/jaw	eye	heart/liver	mountain	see	
Arrow	come	father	honey/bee	mouth	shoulder	two
Back	crocodile	fire	house	name	six	urine
Belly	dance	fish	hunger	neck	skin	war
Bird	day	five	husband	night	slave	water
Black	die	four	iron	nose	snake	white
Blood	dog	go	kill	oil/fat	stone	wife
Body	dream	goat/ he-goat	king/chief	one	sun	woman
Bone	drink	guest	leaf	person	ten	yam
Bow	ear	hair	leg/foot	rain	three	year
Buy	earth	hand/arm	man	red	tongue	
Chicken/cock	eat	head	moon	river	tooth	
Child	egg	hear	mother	saliva	tree	

Appendix II

The revised Swadesh 100-word-list employed in the lexicostatistical study in this work is presented in this appendix. The original Swadesh 100-word-list is also presented here for quick identification of the eliminated and the substituted item. The revision was done in 1975 in the Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages, U.I.

The Revised Swadesh 100 word-list

1. I
2. You (sg.)
3. we
4. You pl.
5. three
6. four
7. five
8. Child
9. Navel
10. Roast
11. One
12. Two
13. Big
14. Long
15. Small

Swadesh 100 word-list

- I
- thou
- we
- this
- that
- who
- what
- Not
- All
- Many
- One
- Two
- Big
- Long
- Small

16. Woman
17. Man
18. Person
19. Fish
20. Bird
21. Dog
22. Goat
23. Tree
24. Seed
25. Leaf
26. Root
27. Housefly
28. Skin
29. Meat
30. Blood
31. Bone
32. Fat
33. Egg
34. Horn
35. Tail
36. Feather
37. Hair
38. Head
39. Ear
40. Eye
41. Nose
42. Mouth
43. Tooth
44. Tongue
45. Nail (finger, toe)
46. Leg
47. Knee
48. Hand
49. Belly
50. Neck
51. Breast(s)
52. Heart
53. Swallow
54. Drink

Woman
Man
Person
Fish
Bird
Dog
Louse
Tree
Seed
Leaf
Roof
Bark
Skin
Flesh
Blood
Bone
Grease
Egg
Horn
Tail
Feather
Hair
Head
Ear
Eye
Nose
Mouth
Tooth
Tongue
Nail
Foot
Knee
Hand
Belly
Neck
Breast(s)
Heart
Liver
Drink

55. Eat
 56. Bite
 57. See
 58. Hear
 59. Know
 60. Sleep
 61. Die
 62. Kill
 63. Bathe
 64. Jump
 65. Walk
 66. Come
 67. Lie down
 68. Sit down
 69. Blow
 70. Give
 71. Say (something)
 72. Sun
 73. Moon
 74. Star
 75. Water
 76. Steal
 77. Stone
 78. Sand
 79. Ground
 80. Rope
 81. Smoke
 82. Fire
 83. Ashes
 84. Saliva
 85. Road
 86. Mountain
 87. Red
 88. Give birth
 89. Bury
 90. White
 91. Black
 92. Night
 93. Hot
 94. Cold
 95. Full
 96. New
 97. Good
 98. Fowl (chicken)
 99. Dry
 100. Name

Eat
 Bite
 See
 Hear
 Know
 Sleep
 Die
 Kill
 Swim
 Fly
 Walk
 Come
 Lie
 Sit
 Stand
 Give
 Say
 Sun
 Moon
 Star
 Water
 Rain
 Stone
 Sand
 Earth
 Cloud
 Smoke
 Fire
 Ash
 Burn
 Path
 Mountain
 Red
 Green
 Yellow
 White
 Black
 Night
 Hot
 Cold
 Full
 New
 Good
 Round
 Dry
 Name